
'CAN WE SEE OUR VOICES?'

A child rights-based participatory study with young children and participatory action research with Early Childhood practitioners exploring their perspectives and lived experiences of Nature under Article 29 1 (e) of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child.

A thesis submitted by
Muireann Ranta
socialCORE
Faculty of Humanities & Business

To the South East Technological University (SETU)

In fulfilment of the Requirements for the
Degree of Doctor of Philosophy

Supervisors: Dr Sheila Long, Dr Niamh McCrea and Dr Lillian Byrne, South East Technological University (SETU), Ireland.

External examiner: Professor Kay Tisdall, University of Edinburgh, Scotland.

Internal examiner: Dr Dawn Murphy, South East Technological University (SETU), Ireland.

Submitted to the South East Technological University (SETU),

September 2024

Declaration of Authorship

I, Muireann Ranta, declare that this thesis entitled, *'Can we see our voices' - A child rights-based participatory study with young children and participatory action research with Early Childhood practitioners exploring their perspectives and lived experiences of Nature under Article 29 1 (e) of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child* which is being presented to the Southeast Technological University in Carlow as part of the fulfilment for the Doctor of Philosophy degree, is an authentic representation of my research work. The contents of this research thesis have not been previously submitted to any other university or institution for the purpose of obtaining any other academic degree.

Signed:

Date:

23/5/25

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I want to express my deepest gratitude to all the research participants who generously shared their time and expertise for this study. Your contributions have been invaluable and significantly enriched the research in a way I never imagined. I would also like to extend a special thanks to the research site owner and the early childhood practitioners for their insights into the crucial role of the early childhood pedagogical skillset in a child rights approach.

Next, thanks to my three supervisors for each of their roles in my research journey. To Dr. Sheila Long, my co-pilot in and out of child rights bunny holes for the first two years. Dr. Niamh McCrea, who has given me the confidence to believe in my own expertise and tirelessly supported me in having it heard. And to Dr. Lillian Byrne and her guidance in getting the whole thing ‘finally over the line’. To all my colleagues and friends at SETU for letting me burn your ears and being so generous with your time and resources, that helped untie the many knots in my head over the years. A particular thanks to Madie Doyle in the Research Office and the SETU Carlow Helpdesk, who got me out of countless pickles. To the OMEP Ireland Committee and many colleagues from the ECEC sector for having such faith in me.

To my parents, Mary and Pat Cantwell, my sister Aoife, my little family Jaakko, Lily-Mary, Paddy, Georgie-Buttons, Nelly-Belly, and The Cat Family, all of my extended family, friends, and neighbours, particularly the Old Leighlin Mothers and Others gang. It has been a long road full of bumps and detours. Thank you for your unwavering support, love, and laughter.

Away with the birds,

By M. Ranta.

The song thrush starts,
as if you sent her,
to gently draw me,
from the pain.
Stay in the moment.
It works.

My littlest friend, the wren,
with your perfectly-portioned
tail and beak.
You make me smile.

As for you, cheeky chaffinch,
I didn't recognise you,
but I am happy,
that you are here.

Now, not to be missed,
my lifelong friend,
and head gardener,
dearest robin,
pipes up with her,
familiar song.

And then, on cue,
the softest crow,
from across the field.
Pheasant's instant comfort.
And again.
There you are,
and there you will be,
my longest love,

I will always find you with the birds.

I dedicate this thesis to my Daddy, my longest love and forever companion of wonder.

Table of Contents

Declaration of Authorship	1
Acknowledgements.....	2
Table of Contents.....	4
List of Figures.....	8
List of Tables	10
List of Acronyms	12
Abstract	14
Chapter 1. Introduction	16
1.1. Introduction.	16
1.2. Research justification.	17
1.3. Transformative child rights paradigm	18
1.4. A note on ontology and epistemology.....	19
1.5. Who is the researcher?.....	21
1.6. Methodological focus	22
1.7. Chapter outline	23
1.8. Research scope	27
1.8. A note on terminology.....	28
Chapter 2. Setting the context: The climate crisis through a child rights lens.....	29
2.1. Introduction.	29
2.2. How does the climate crisis impact children’s lives?.....	29
2.3. Where are children’s rights violated, and how could the CRC inform climate action?	30
2.4. Revisioning rights.....	45
Chapter 3. Examining policy and curriculum for rights-based ESD in ECEC.....	50
3.1. Introduction.	50
3.2. International legal and policy context for rights-based ESD in early childhood education and care	50
3.3. National legal and policy context for rights-based ESD	53
3.4. An analysis of national strategies for ESD in early childhood.....	57
3.5. The limited place of ESD in ECEC policy in Ireland.....	62
3.6. A child rights-based curriculum for learning in, through, about and for Nature for early childhood.	65
3.7. International curricula and legislation	78
3.8. The updated curriculum framework	83

Chapter 4: Literature Review: Learning in, through, about and for Nature under Article 29 1 (e).	85
4.1. Introduction	85
4.2. Nature learning and how children as learners are viewed in early education theory.	85
4.3. The developmental view.....	86
4.4. The democratic view	87
4.5. Other synergies for rights-based ESD in early childhood theory	88
4.6. Varying names for education for sustainable development.....	89
4.7. Defining sustainability in education	89
4.8. Approaches to ESD in early childhood education.....	90
4.9. Positioning the learner - the young child in ESD	93
4.10. Contextual starting points for ESD.....	94
4.11. Communitarian citizenship learning.....	95
4.12. Participation and democracy	96
4.13. The role of the ECEC practitioner as a duty bearer under Article 29 1 (e).	98
4.14. What is needed to support ECEC practitioners under Article 29 1 (e).....	100
4.15. A long-term sustained change	102
4.16. Conceptual Frameworks for the Study.	104
Chapter 5. Stage 1: Child rights-based participatory methodology.	106
5.1. Introduction	106
5.2. Ontological and Epistemological positions.	106
5.3. Child rights-based participatory research.	107
5.4. The principles of rights-based research participation.....	109
5.5. Implementing child rights-based research with young children in a local context .	113
5.6. Implementing ethical principles	113
5.7. Overview of research phases	117
5.8. Reflexivity and its role within this methodology	118
5.9. Informed consent process	123
5.10. Reflexive thematic analysis approach	123
5.11. Researcher’s positionality.....	124
5.12 Coding system for stage one and rigour.	124
Chapter 6. Stage 1: Designing a child rights-based participatory methodology with young children.....	127
6.1. Introduction	127
6.2. Recruitment process	127

6.3. CRAG research methods evaluations	130
6.4. Introducing a new research method: the influence of the CRAG.....	137
6.5. CRAG guidance in understanding the cultural context for research design.....	140
6.6. Audience and influence at a local level	141
6.7. An influential change in roles.....	143
6.8. External audience and influence.....	147
6.9. Data analysis process designed with the CRAG for phase 2.....	150
6.10. A stepped data analysis process.....	152
Chapter 7 Stage 2: Audience and influence: A participatory action research approach with ECEC practitioners.....	167
7.1. Introduction	167
7.2. Rationale for using PAR for stage two.....	167
7.3. What is participatory action research methodology?	169
7.4. Fundamental principles of participatory methodology.....	171
7.5. Rigour and tensions in balancing participatory principles	178
7.6. Challenges in implementing change.....	179
7.7. Data analysis approach for stage two	179
Chapter 8: Young children’s own perspectives and lived experiences of Nature under Article 29 1 (e).	182
8.1 Introduction.	182
8.2. First Connections.....	182
8.3. Learning in Nature – making Nature connections more democratic in Nature and with peers.....	184
8.4. The responsive adult – a companion in wonder	187
8.5. Learning for Nature	193
8.6. Conclusion	200
Chapter 9: Towards a child's rights-based approach to ESD/CCE in ECEC.....	201
9.1. Introduction	201
9.2. Free-flowing participation	201
9.3. The child’s clock.	203
9.4. Verbal/Nonverbal participation.	207
9.5. Relational participation.....	210
9.6. Children’s own engagement with research tools.....	214
9.7. Participation that respects local culture	219
9.8. Respecting children’s terminology.....	223
9.9. Making Space for ‘Unicorn Moments’.....	224

9.10. Children are their own experts.....	224
9.11. No rebuke	227
9.12. Child-initiated elements.....	231
9.13. Conclusion.....	235
Chapter 10. Building the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate child rights-based ESD into early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e).	236
10.1. Introduction	236
10.2. Participants’ existing knowledge of, and resources for, a child rights ESD approach.....	236
10.3. Paradigms of pedagogy	242
10.4. Practitioners’ capacity to enact change.	247
10.5. Conclusion.....	256
Chapter 11. Conclusion.....	257
11.1. Introduction	257
11.2. Research contributions	260
11.3. Concluding remarks.....	266
Reference List	267
Appendix A. Ethical approval by Research Ethics Committee, Institute of Technology, Carlow.	291
Appendix B. Gatekeeper Information Evening Presentation (April 2019).	292
Appendix C. Gatekeeper’s Letter (April 2019).....	297
Appendix D. Research Flier and Poster for CRAG recruitment (April 2019).....	301
Appendix E. Storybook Information & Consent Material for CRAG members and families (May 2019)	303
Appendix F. Research Information Storybook & Consent Material for Research Participants and Families (September 2019).....	313
Appendix G. Research Update Information Letter for CRAG members and families (September 2019)	320
Appendix H: Recruitment Letter for Adult Participants	322
Appendix I: Recruitment Letter for Identified Listener	325
Appendix J: Original Overview of Research Plan & Proposed Phase Content (April 2019).....	327
Appendix K: Field Reflective Notes and CRAG Feedback from Workshop 1.....	329
Appendix L: Reflexive Fieldnotes and CRAG guidance from Workshop 2 – Research Methods (May 28 th)	331
Appendix M: Reflexive Fieldnotes and CRAG guidance from Workshop 3 – Research Methods (2 sessions June 12 th & June 21 st).....	333

Appendix N: Story used with CRAG members to explore research understanding and evaluate story telling as research method.	337
Appendix O: CRAG members and families’ information newsletter for phase 2.....	339
Appendix P: Email to CRAG members and families for further informed consent.....	340
Appendix Q. Information Blurb on PAR study- How can we hear your voices?	342
Appendix R. Informed Consent Material	343
Appendix S: Protocol for Shared Drive.....	347
Appendix T: Suggested Outline of content for ESD module.	348
Appendix U: The Children's Nature Book ...(attached as a separate document)	
Appendix V: Study's Submission for the Aistear Updating Consultation Process.... (attached as a separate document)	

List of Figures.

Figure 1.1: Overview of the methodology chapters.....	pg. 24.
Figure 2.1: Top 10 countries where children are most at risk from the climate crisis.....	pg. 30.
Figure 2.2: Expanded rights framework	pg. 45.
Figure 3.1: Cross Government action plan for participation	pg. 55.
Figure 3.2: Action steps by the Irish government to support climate awareness.....	pg. 56.
Figure 3.3: Major issues impacting children and young people in Ireland.....	pg. 57.
Figure 4.1: Strategies for achieving systems change.....	pg.103.
Figure 5.1: Hart’s Ladder of participation	pg. 109.
Figure 5.2: Hierarchy of children’s research participation rights, showing its relationship to Hart’s ladder of participation	pg.110.
Figure 5.3: Conceptualising Article 12	pg. 111.
Figure 5.4: The participants’ Hedgehog cake for our ‘research party’.....	pg. 117.
Figure 5.5: Visual overview of research phases	pg. 118.
Figure 5.6: Reflexivity thought process.....	pg. 119.
Figure 5.7: The early childhood rights-based research reinforcing cycle	pg.121.
Figure 5.8: Interwoven elements of meaningful participation at the local context.....	pg.122.
Figure 5.9: Overview of second stage coding for stage one.....	pg.125.
Figure 6.1: Research Storybook and props.....	pg.129.
Figure 6.2: Extract of reflective field notes from Workshop 1 (May 15th) & Informal Session (May 24 th)	pg. 131.
Figure 6.3: Power balance checklist visual – Workshop 1	pg. 132.
Figure 6.4: Extract (a)from reflective field notes Workshop 2	pg. 133.
Figure 6.5: Extract (b) from reflective field notes from Workshop 2	pg. 136.
Figure 6.6: Extract (a) from reflective notes from Workshop 3	pg. 137.
Figure 6.7: Extract (b) from reflective notes from Workshop 3	pg. 138.
Figure 6.8: Hazel the Hedgehog and the research basket	pg. 141.
Figure 6.9: The Lundy model revised with CRAG guidance.....	pg. 143.
Figure 6.10: Extract (c) from reflective field notes Workshop 3	pg. 143.
Figure 6.11: CRAG Information Insects/Animals Workshop Session 1.....	pg. 145.
Figure 6.12: CRAG Information Waste Management Workshop Session 3	pg. 145.
Figure 6.13: Extract of relational support with ‘familiar adult’ in scaffolding capacity to form and express views.....	pg. 146.
Figure 6.14: Photo Walls used in the data analysis process with the CRAG.....	pg. 151.
Figure 6.15: Starting the data analysis process	pg.152.
Figure 6.16: A stepped process for data analysis with CRAG.....	pg. 153.
Figure 6.17: CRAG’s own perspectives of Nature	pg. 153.
Figure 6.18: <i>A spider with no body</i> (CMG1)	pg. 154.
Figure 6.19: <i>I know spiders have eight legs, but I gave mine 10. This is pink and has red, and the rest is blue. This is a tarantula</i> (CMG2)	pg. 154.
Figure 6.20: Extract highlighting capacity building opportunity.....	pg. 155.
Figure 6.21: Spiders following capacity building support (CMG2)	pg. 155.
Figure 6.22: View expressed about Spiders following capacity building support (CMG2)	pg. 155.
Figure 6.23: <i>Like a circle but squiggly for the spikes</i> (CMB2)	pg. 156.
Figure 6.24: Hedgehog (CMB2)	pg. 157.
Figure 6.25: A perspective expressed about hedgehogs (CMB2)	pg. 157.
Figure 6.26: Mine	pg. 158.
Figure 6.27: Ownership of ideas (a)	pg. 158.
Figure 6.28: Ownership of ideas (b)	pg. 159.
Figure 6.29: Establishing their own involvement.	pg. 159.
Figure 6.30: Establishing their own and others’ involvement.	pg. 159.
Figure 6.31: Insect poster	pg. 160.
Figure 6.32: Insect house	pg. 160.
Figure 6.33: Group interpretation of their insect hunt	pg.160.
Figure 6.34: Horse chestnuts and pinecones	pg.161.
Figure 6.35: Collecting stuff	pg.161.
Figure 6.36: Group interpretation of the Nature game.....	pg. 161.
Figure 6.37: Tree planting (a)	pg. 162.
Figure 6.38: Tree planting (b)	pg. 162.

Figure 6.39: CRAG group interpretation on tree planting	pg. 162.
Figure 6.40: CRAG interpretation on birdfeeder	pg. 163.
Figure 6.41: Birdfeeder	pg. 163.
Figure 6.42.: Flowerbed.....	pg.163.
Figure 6.43: CRAG group interpretation of flowerbed	pg. 163.
Figure 6.44: Feedback of research from families (a)	pg. 165.
Figure 6.45: Feedback of research from families (b)	pg. 165.
Figure 6.46: Feedback of research from families (c)	pg. 165.
Figure 6.47: Feedback of research from families (d)	pg. 165.
Figure 6.48: Feedback of research from families (e)	pg. 165.
Figure 7.1: Overview of the coding process for stage two.....	pg.181.
Figure 8.1: Magic Nature Bag with artefacts and Hazel the Hedgehog	pg. 182.
Figure 8.2. The broken stone or acorn	pg. 183.
Figure 8.3. My hat	pg. 186.
Figure 8.4. Connections with hat and horse chestnuts.....	pg. 186.
Figure 8.5: Place-based insect poster	pg.190.
Figure 8.6: Crocus.....	pg. 191.
Figure 8.7: A horse chestnut	pg. 194.
Figure 8.8: Transporting a slug on a leaf.....	pg.197.
Figure 8.9: Flower bed	pg. 198.
Figure 9.1: Moving like a slug.....	pg. 207.
Figure 9.2: Peanut Butter	pg. 211.
Figure 9.3: The Magic Nature Bag.....	pg. 216.
Figure 9.4: Research tools for exploring birds and making birdfeeders.....	pg. 217.
Figure 9.5: Goldfinch.....	pg. 220.
Figure 9.6: Sandpit.....	pg. 221.
Figure 9.7: Outdoor designs with clouds and flowers.....	pg. 225.
Figure 9.8: A giant minion.....	pg. 225.
Figure 9.9: Just Hazel.....	pg. 227.
Figure 9.10: Roby the Rob ..Roby the Ribs.....	pg. 227.
Figure 9.11: Seashell.....	pg. 229.
Figure 9.12: Tools for bird care activity	pg.231.
Figure 9.13: Lily Lily Lil.....	pg.232.
Figure 9.14: Goldfinch not fish.....	pg.232.
Figure 9.15: Child-initiated elements.....	pg.234.
Figure 11.1: Respecting children’s Nature connections to inform a child rights-based education approach under Article 29 1 (e).	pg.259.
Figure 11.2: Expanded Rights Framework	pg. 262.
Figure 11.3: The Lundy model revised with CRAG guidance.....	pg. 263.
Figure 11.4: Ongoing reflexivity tool to support a child rights-based participatory approach.....	pg.264.

List of Tables.

Table 5.1: Identification codes used in the study.....	pg. 115.
Table 5.2: Initial coding system for stage one	pg.125.
Table 6.1: Overview of research workshop sessions for Phase 2.....	pg. 150.
Table 7.1: Details of participants for Iteration 2	pg.168.
Table 7.2: PAR Workshop Sessions Schedule	pg.169.
Table 7.3: Overview of PAR Workshop Session 1	pg.170.
Table 7.4: Overview of PAR Workshop Session 2	pg. 171.
Table 7.5: Overview of PAR Workshop Session 3	pg. 175.
Table 7.6: Overview of PAR Workshop Session 4	pg. 176.
Table 7.7: Initial coding system for stage two.	pg. 180.
Table 7.8: Overview of second stage coding for stage two.....	pg. 180.
Table 8.1: Connections with artefacts.....	pg. 183.
Table 8.2: Connections with Figure 8.2	pg. 183.
Table 8.3: Connection with the seashell	pg.184.
Table 8.4: Connection with a horse chestnut	pg.184.
Table 8.5: Connections with the seashell in a peer group	pg. 185.
Table 8.6: Further connections with the seashell in the peer group.....	pg.185.
Table 8.7: Connection with Nature through imaginary play	pg.186.
Table 8.8: Horse chestnuts and pinecones (a)	pg. 186.
Table 8.9: Horse chestnuts and pinecones (b).....	pg. 186.
Table 8.10: Connection with Nature through imaginary play.....	pg. 187.
Table 8.11: Exploring with magnifying glasses.....	pg. 188.
Table 8.12: Connection with a magnifying glass and supportive adult	pg.188.
Table 8.13: Seasons and hibernating -sharing their own Nature knowledge.	pg. 188.
Table 8.14: Connections with slug (a)	pg.189.
Table 8.15: Connections with slug (b)	pg. 189.
Table 8.16: Connections with a centipede	pg. 191.
Table 8.17: Extending own ideas with adult support (a).....	pg. 191.
Table 8.18: Extending own ideas with adult support (b).....	pg. 192
Table 8.19: Connecting with horse chestnuts (a).....	pg. 194.
Table 8.20: Connecting with horse chestnuts (b).....	pg. 194
Table 8.21: Changing to pro-environment behaviours with adult support (a)	pg. 195.
Table 8.22: Changing to pro-environmental behaviours with adult support (b).....	pg. 196.
Table 8.23: Changing to pro-environmental behaviours with adult support (c).....	pg. 197.
Table 8.24: Participant explains how they will change their behaviour to be more respectful of Nature.pg.198.	
Table 9.1: Defining their own participatory rights when introduced to research (a)	pg. 202.
Table 9.2: Defining their own participatory rights when introduced to research (b)	pg. 202.
Table 9.3: Participants' decision-making in participation	pg. 203.
Table 9.4: Deciding the research agenda.....	pg. 205.
Table 9.5: Non-verbal/quieter participation (a)	pg. 208.
Table 9.6: Non-verbal/quieter participation (b)	pg. 208.
Table 9.7: Non-verbal/quieter participation with support of ECEC practitioner.....	pg. 208.
Table 9.8: Rapport building to support quieter participation (a).....	pg. 209.
Table 9.9: Rapport building to support quieter participation (b).....	pg. 209.
Table 9.10: Rapport building to support quieter participation (c).....	pg. 210.
Table 9.11: Rapport building to support quieter participation (d).....	pg. 210.
Table 9.12: Example of rapport creating safe research space (a).....	pg. 211.
Table 9.13: Example of rapport creating safe research space (b).....	pg. 211.
Table 9.14: Conversation styles with the research space (a).....	pg. 212.
Table 9.15: Conversation styles with the research space (b).....	pg. 213.
Table 9.16: Participation elicited with the support of an ECEC practitioner.....	pg. 214.
Table 9.17: Own engagement with research tools.....	pg. 215.
Table 9.18: Giving participants the space and time to engage in their own way with research tools (a)...pg.218.	
Table 9.19: Giving participants the space and time to engage in their own way with research tools (b)...pg.219.	
Table 9.20: Participant's own perspectives on a goldfinch.....	pg.220.
Table 9.21: Participant's own stories influencing discussion topics	pg. 221.

Table 9.22: Space to share participants' chosen topics of discussion (a).....	pg.221.
Table 9.23: Space to share participants' chosen topics of discussion (b).....	pg. 222.
Table 9.24: Participants own terminology (a).....	pg. 223.
Table 9.25: Participants' own terminology (b).....	pg. 223.
Table 9.26: Participants' own terminology (c).....	pg. 223.
Table 9.27: Listening with no rebuke during our native bird story	pg. 228.
Table 9.28: Replacing adult with child agenda	pg. 229.
Table 9.29: Complexities of 'unicorn moments' and giving them a space to support participatory rights authentically.....	pg. 230.
Table 9.30: Examples of unicorn moments.....	pg. 232.
Table 9.31: Replacing adult with child agenda.....	pg. 233.
Table 10.1: Supporting participatory rights in practice	pg. 239.
Table 10.2: Example of contradictory language used to discuss children's rights-based practice.....	pg. 241.
Table 10.3: Contradictory practice to balance child rights.....	pg. 241.
Table 10.4: The importance of listening.....	pg.243.
Table 10.5: Listening out for children's interests	pg.244.
Table 10.6: Children's interests and practitioner's own agenda.....	pg. 245.
Table 10.7: Participant reflecting in their own rights-based approach (a).....	pg. 245.
Table 10.8: Participant reflecting in their own rights-based approach (b).....	pg. 246.
Table 10.9: Example of support (or lack of) to implement sustainability practices.....	pg. 247.
Table 10.10: Whole setting support for sustainability practices.....	pg. 248.
Table 10.11: Participant's suggestion to enact whole system changes.....	pg.248.
Table 10.12: Ambivalence in suggestion to enact system change.....	pg. 248.
Table 10.13: Suggestion to enact whole system change.....	pg.249.
Table 10.14: Practitioner's description of their learning in the research process	pg. 250.
Table 10.15: Participant's enjoyment of their research participation.....	pg. 251.
Table 10.16: Learning from someone who is passionate about the subject	pg. 252.
Table 10.17: Suggestion of content for ESD module for ECEC practitioners	pg. 253.
Table 10.18: The science of implementing child rights.....	pg. 258.

Acronyms

BOBF - Better Outcomes Brighter Futures

CCE – Climate Change Education.

CRAG – Children’s Research Advisory Group

CRC – Convention on the Rights of the Child

DCEDIY – Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth.

DCYA – Department of Children and Youth Affairs

ECEC – Early Childhood Education and Care.

ESD – Education for Sustainable Development.

PAR – Participatory Action Research

GARN – Global Alliance for the Rights of Nature

GOI – Government of Ireland

IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

SDG – Sustainable Development Goals

UDHR - Universal Declaration of Human Rights

UNCRC – United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child.

UNDESD - United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development

UNDRIP - United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples

UNESCO - United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

UNICEF – United Nations International Children’s Emergency Fund

UNGA – United Nations General Assembly

UNMD- United Nations Millennium Declaration

WHO – World Health Organization

Abstract

The climate crisis is a child rights crisis, with young and future generations of children most at risk (UNICEF, 2018; UNGA, 2018; Daly, 2023). This thesis intersects child rights-based research, early childhood pedagogy, education for sustainable development (ESD) and climate change (CCE) and involves two research stages. I worked with young children (2-5 years old) in their early childhood setting in Ireland for stage one and with a group of early childhood education and care (ECEC) practitioners using an online platform for stage two. Article 29 1 (e) stipulates children's educational right to develop respect for the natural environment under the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC, 1989). My three research aims were:

1. to explore young children's own perspectives and lived experiences of Nature,
2. to develop a child rights-based research methodology with young children to support their participation in developing an ESD approach under Article 29 1 (e), and,
3. to build the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate child rights-based ESD into early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e).

Despite a growth in child rights literature (Lundy, 2007; Alderson, 2008; 2012; Lundy et al., 2011, 2012; Shier, 2016; Tisdall; 2015; 2017; Collins et al., 2020) and more recently that which includes early childhood (Mayne et al., 2016,2017. 2018, Wall et al., 2019) child rights-based research with young children remains in its infancy. Robson (2016) and Lundy and Martinez Sainz's (2018) also call for a less 'top-down', policy-to-practice approach to children's education and participatory rights and for greater attention to children's living realities. By providing a detailed outline of how I engaged in rights-based research in a local context in stage one, my research participants and I contribute to a 'bottoms up' rights-based approach for this early age. Findings showed that children define their own relationship with Nature and make their own connections with it. In claiming their right to education about Nature and taking part in research about matters that affect them, they also establish their own definitions of participation.

A participatory action research (PAR) approach with ECEC practitioners was used for stage 2 as a means of audience and influence for the children's research contributions (Lundy, 2007). A number of key findings were identified for developing a rights-based ESD approach. Firstly, to establish an authentic child rights education approach, it is necessary to gain an understanding and respect for the local culture of an educational context as the starting point. Secondly, following an exploration of the role of language and balancing rights when seeking to create a rights-respecting culture, I identified a shortfall with certain 'non-rights language' being used. This highlights the necessity for the UNCRC to be explicitly linked to national ECEC policies, frameworks and training. Furthermore, the research found that the capacity to make the changes necessary in everyday practice for more sustainable behaviours varied.

Participants agreed that a lack of time and resources, such as more 'hands', hindered a rights-based approach. Findings also demonstrated how pedagogical concepts in early childhood theory can be misinterpreted and that the different ways practitioners understand these principles can also be barriers to capacity building. From examining the role of reflection and demonstrating that regardless of each setting's current sustainable practices and ESD, ongoing opportunities for reflection on practice were key to integrating a child-rights-based approach under Article 29 1 (e). Finally, by analysing different forms of sustainability leadership, my findings show that transformative leadership is needed to change mindset and behaviours for effective climate action, both in policy and practice.

Chapter 1. Introduction

1.1. Introduction.

The extent and magnitude of the triple planetary crisis, comprising the climate emergency, the collapse of biodiversity and pervasive pollution, is an urgent and systemic threat to children's rights globally.

(UNCRC 2023, p.1).

This thesis sits at the intersection of child rights-based research, early childhood pedagogy, education for sustainable development (ESD) and climate change (CCE) and has three research aims:

Research Aims

- To explore with young children their own perspectives and lived experiences of Nature under Article 29 1 (e) of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child.
- To develop a child rights-based research methodology with young children to support their participation in developing an Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) approach in early childhood under Article 29 1 (e).
- To build the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate child rights-based ESD into early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e).

The objectives of the study were:

Research Objectives

- To analyse the pedagogical synergies between ECEC and ESD.
- To evaluate how ECEC pedagogy, articulated in Ireland's national early childhood curriculum framework, Aistear can contribute to developing a child rights-based ESD approach under Article 29 1 (e).
- To identify ways of promoting authentic learner participation among young children under Article 29 1 (e).
- To explore the ECEC practitioners' skillset and evaluate its contribution to eliciting learner participation to realise Article 29 1 (e).
- To examine if and how an overall rights-respecting culture can contribute to a more effective child rights-based ESD approach.

The study involved two stages. I worked with two groups of young children (2-5 years old and 19 in total) in their early childhood setting in Ireland for stage one. This process took 9 months and included 11 one-hour research sessions both in and outdoors with a varied number of participants. For stage two, my participants were a group of early childhood education and care (ECEC) practitioners recruited nationally. I used an online platform with them to facilitate 6 one-hour research workshop sessions.

1.2. Research justification.

Children bear the most significant burden of climate change, as they are more vulnerable than adults to disease, extreme weather events or food insecurity, and because the planet itself is becoming unsafe (UNICEF, 2021). Furthermore, environmental harm has severe consequences for children under the age of 5. Their vulnerability to pollution and other hazards makes them more susceptible to health issues and even death. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA), environmental risks contributed to 1.5 million deaths of children under 5 in 2015, and many of these deaths could have been prevented with reduced exposure to environmental dangers. This makes the climate crisis a child rights crisis (UNICEF: 2021, UNCRC, 2023).

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC, 1989) is a legally binding agreement that establishes the fundamental rights of all children. Taking force in 1990, it encompasses various civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights. Under the CRC, a child is defined as any human being below the age of eighteen unless the law applicable to them grants them the status of majority earlier. Article 29 1 (e) of the CRC enshrines the right of all children to receive an education that develops respect for Nature as follows:

Article 29

1. States Parties agree that the education of the child shall be directed to:

(a) The development of the child's personality, talents, and mental and physical abilities to their fullest potential;

(b) The development of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, and for the principles enshrined in the Charter of the United Nations;

(c) The development of respect for the child's parents, his or her own cultural identity, language, and values, for the national values of the country in which the child is

living, the country from which he or she may originate, and for civilizations different from his or her own;

(d) The preparation of the child for responsible life in a free society, in the spirit of understanding, peace, tolerance, equality of sexes, and friendship among all peoples, ethnic, national, and religious groups and persons of indigenous origin;

(e) The development of respect for the natural environment.

2. No part of the present article or article 28 shall be construed so as to interfere with the liberty of individuals and bodies to establish and direct educational institutions, subject always to the observance of the principle set forth in paragraph 1 of the present article and to the requirements that the education given in such institutions shall conform to such minimum standards as may be laid down by the State.

(UNCRC, 1989, p.9).

Education has been pinpointed as the tool needed to bring about the necessary changes in human behaviour and attitudes to combat this climate crisis (UNDP, 2015). Nevertheless, Waldron, Mallon, Barry and Martínez Sainz (2020) have also identified resistance at both a political and societal level to climate change education in Ireland. At least from an ECEC perspective, a firm governmental commitment in the form of resources and training of educators is yet to happen in Ireland. *General Comment 26* (UNCRC, 2023, p.1) also highlights the role of child human rights defenders as ‘agents of change’ who ‘have made historic contributions to human rights and environmental protection’. In addition, the general comment calls for a child rights approach to environmental protection and more transformative education approaches for climate action. Taking on these last three points, this study is underpinned by a transformative child rights paradigm to examine with young children and ECEC practitioners how to develop a transformative ‘bottom-up’ child rights-based ESD approach for the ECEC sector.

1.3. Transformative child rights paradigm

Research with children as participants was influenced by the arrival of the UNCRC in 1989. The entitlements to education, health and well-being, and civil and political rights for children, acted as a catalyst for the more widespread acceptance of the child as a rights holder and expert in their own lifestyles, experiences, relationships, and matters affecting them (Lundy, 2007; Alderson, 2008, 2012). Bessell (2015) describes the CRC as the blueprint for the ethical treatment of all children in research. Lundy and McEvoy (2011) describe a varied relationship between children and research, including research that *relates to* children’s

rights, research that is *about* children's rights, research that is participatory, and research that is both participatory and specifically guided by CRC standards.

While some argue that protection concerns, developmental incompetence, and limited life experience render research with young children complex, it is still a legal imperative under the CRC, which accords children participatory rights to be involved in research concerning matters relative to them (Lundy, 2007; Harcourt & Conroy, 2011; Lundy et al., 2011, 2012). Alderson (2008) points out that it is not the lack of competency in children themselves that hinders their participation in research, but rather adult attitudes, traditional developmental views, or misplaced protection concerns. A key feature of research influenced by the CRC is the view of babies and young children as essential stakeholders and sophisticated thinkers. It holds that they can contribute knowledge, expertise and opinions missed by traditional research when adequate opportunities are provided for them to do so (Harcourt & Conroy, 2005; Clark & Moss, 2005; Christensen & James, 2008).

However, although participation is one of the guiding principles underpinning the CRC, it also presents significant challenges (UNICEF, 2014; Mayne et al., 2018). This is because a young child's potential as a competent, contributing participant requires clear commitment, respect, and effective means to be fully supported. *General Comment No. 7* specifies this by highlighting the need for more rights-based research to highlight the value of theory and evidence from young children's participation in developing early childhood policies, practices, and education (UN, 2005). This further justifies the transformative child rights paradigm applied to this study and the insights it brings to child rights discourse and practice from young children's perspectives.

1.4. A note on ontology and epistemology.

As the previous section clarifies, a transformative child rights paradigm carries clear epistemological and ontological commitments. Ontologically, it views the child as an active social agent with rights and a constructor of knowledge rather than the passive property of adults. Active rights holders must be consulted and contribute to any matter that affects their lives, including their education (UNCRC, 1989). This implies an epistemology which looks to work with young children and minimise power inequalities between them and the researcher. Edwards (2010) describes the early childhood world as 'a living mess' interwoven with complex webs of dialogue and interaction. In addition, given the dependent nature of

young children on other ‘more capable humans’, there is a distinct adult/child power dynamic within early childhood realities (Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2015; 2018; 2019; Leonard, 2016). Kucharczyk and Hanna (2020) argue that understanding generational power dynamics is crucial to avoid misrepresenting or limiting young children's voices and perspectives. Still, this understanding greatly depends on individuals’ thoughts and beliefs (Mukhles M. Al-Ababhneh, 2020). Democratic and development views of children and how their positioning in educational settings can devalue their capacity to construct knowledge is discussed further in Chapter 4. I balance the power in this research space by using methods that respectfully gain access to the children’s worlds and include them in all aspects of the research process, described in detail in Chapters 5 and 6.

Knowledge is constructed through interactions between humans and the world. hooks (1994) describes knowledge as a field in which we must all work, connecting ideas learned in university settings and those learned in life practices. Dismantling or reclaiming more subjugated knowledge opens a path for revisioning and including other expertise. Burr (2015) discusses that a person’s perception of what is true to them is a result of social processes rather than objective observation. I am researching within the world of early childhood, recognising that there is no universal early childhood experience. As outlined above, I defend an epistemological position that takes children's role as knowledge creators seriously (Mukhles M. Al-Ababhneh, 2020). That said, as described by Thomas (2021), while childhoods are socially constructed, I recognise that this is on a foundation of reality determined by biological differences related to age. However, I also demonstrate in this study that I did not understand all of the children’s contributions, and their sense of reality sometimes differed from mine. This notion is introduced in Chapter 5 during the methodology design phase and throughout the findings chapters (Chapters 8-10). For these reasons, I have concluded that a critical realist ontological approach is most salient to the research approach (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009; Byrne, 2021).

Critical realism (CR) is a recent philosophical trend (Zhang, 2022). Its distinct feature is ontological realism, which asserts a transcendental reality that Archer et al. (2016) explain operates independent of our knowledge of it and does not wholly answer to empirical examination. It has been described as a third-way alternative paradigm to forms of positivism and to the solid interpretive turn that focuses on ‘hermeneutics and description at the cost of

causation' (Zhang, 2022, p.16). These realities must also be examined for constructing new knowledge, challenging structures and how that all relates to a transformative rights-based approach (Freire, 2000; Mertens, 2007).

1.5. Who is the researcher?

My earliest childhood memories of connecting with Nature were to try to pull the seeds off long grasses with one hand and then scatter them out to feed my imaginary chickens. I also became quite an intricate cake decorator using those seeds, a collection of wildflower petals and builder's sand, which I sold from various pop-up businesses. On beach trips, I spent many moments sifting dry beach sand through my fingers to get just one single particle by itself and wonder at its size and existence. With over 20 years of experience in ECEC practice, heavily influenced by seven in Finland, a country renowned for its Nature connecting culture, I advocate for children to explore freely in natural environments. I advocate for the magnitude of learning and enjoyment that these first-hand experiences can offer, which includes developing a respect for the natural world. I believe that to learn democratically about Nature, every child as a rights holder must be in Nature and have regular access to local green areas within their own education settings and community (Chawla, 1998; Mannion, 2007; Davies, 2009; Ross & Mannion, 2012; Chawla & Rivkin, 2014; Mackey, 2014). Ultimately, my own affinity for Nature and experiencing how young children engage with it has led me to carry out this work.

Finally, from my early childhood studies, I discovered the theory of knowledge from the early childhood theorist Jerome Bruner regularly aligned with my own practice experiences, such as beginning with the young child's interests and learning styles for holistic and meaningful learning experiences. I have also found Bruner's writing both accessible and relatable to my reflective thought process. For this reason, I refer to several of Bruner's key theoretical concepts (spiral curriculum, community of learning and 'discovery learning') in the thesis to highlight the synergies between ECEC and ESD pedagogy from a practice based perspective.

1.6. Methodological focus

Stage one followed the rights-based participatory research *Lundy Model* (2007), which conceptualises Article 12 of the CRC when working with children to further their right to participation:

Article 12

1. States Parties shall assure to the child who is capable of forming his or her own views the right to express those views freely in all matters affecting the child, the views of the child being given due weight in accordance with the age and maturity of the child.
2. For this purpose, the child shall, in particular be provided the opportunity to be heard in any judicial and administrative proceedings affecting the child, either directly, or through a representative or an appropriate body, in a manner consistent with the procedural rules of national law.

(UNCRC, 1989, p.4).

A rights-based research approach with children must have certain features (Tisdall, 2015). From the outset, the researcher must clearly understand what the CRC means for researching with children (Mayne et al., 2018). Their attitudes and perspectives towards young children, whether they view them as objects to be studied (which is not a rights-based approach) or as competent individuals capable of playing an interactive role in research, greatly influence the decisions made during the initial planning of the study (Mayne & Howitt, 2015; Mayne et al., 2018). Despite the clear paradigm shift in positioning children as participants with their own perspectives and experiences to offer, these can still be limited to shaping research questions and agendas set by adults and, therefore, cannot be clearly located in a rights-based realm (Lundy, 2007; Roberts, 2008; Lundy & McEvoy, 2012).

Participatory research with children and the principles of children's rights emerged around the same time and have many similarities. However, there are also notable methodological differences between participatory research and a child rights-based research approach (CRA) (Bessell, 2015). Chapters 5 and 6 give an account of how the methodological journey for stage one was analysed and applied to the child rights-based research approach designed with the participating children.

For children’s participatory rights to be fully realised, their perspectives must also be listened to and considered in decision-making about any matters that will affect them (UNCRC, 1989; UN, 2009; DCEDIY, 2021). This was the rationale for applying a participatory action research (PAR) approach with ECEC practitioners to listen to the children’s contributions for stage two. A PAR approach is described by Machin-Mastromatteo and Tarango (2019) as a participatory and mainly qualitative methodology whereby the researcher implements several actions to gain insight into participants' practices, views, and behaviours. This knowledge is, in turn, used to empower them to make changes to improve their situations through their own reflection and actions. Cornwall and Jewkes (1995, p.1667) describe this as ‘a process of sequential reflection and action, carried out with and by local people rather than on them’. My approach aimed to present the children’s contributions to the practitioners and explore them further in developing a transformational child rights-based ESD approach for early childhood. Chapter 7 gives a detailed account of how the approach was developed with the participants.

1.7. Chapter outline

The thesis begins with an extensive literature review in chapters 2-4. Chapter 2 sets the context by discussing how the climate crisis impacts children’s lives and explains why it is a child rights crisis. The chapter also highlights the obligations of the ratified States to ensure that any decisions taken on climate action do not negatively impact the rights of children or future generations (UNGA, 2018; Daly, 2023). I conclude with a discussion on the critiques of the Convention and the necessity to reframe rights for the type of action needed to combat the crisis (Davies, 2014). Chapter 3 concentrates on policy and curriculum for supporting a child rights-based approach to ESD in early childhood. It begins with examining the international legal and policy context before providing a detailed analysis of national policy for children and ESD. This leads to an overall discussion on the ambiguity surrounding the value of ECEC for ESD promotion within Irish State policy. The second section provides a curriculum analysis from a national perspective and then an international one. It concludes with a discussion on the recent updating process of the national curriculum framework (NCCA, 2024) and its relevance for embedding transformative ESD.

Chapter 4 reviews literature and research on learning in, through, about and for Nature under Article 29 1 (e). I begin with an analysis of how Nature learning and young children as

learners have been considered in early childhood pedagogies and examine the pedagogical synergies between ESD and ECEC. The second section explores ESD in early childhood research and the complexities surrounding sustainability as a concept. This involves a discussion of its various definitions and learning approaches, including an analysis of collaborative, participatory projects. The final section discusses the ECEC practitioner's duty-bearer role and how the perceived complexities of sustainability can act as a barrier to effective ESD implementation in early childhood. I also review transformative research studies in this section and changes in initial teacher training programmes, including specific content on leadership skills for effective sustainability.

Figure 1.1: Overview of the methodology chapters.

Chapters 5-7 are the methodology chapters (Figure 1.1). Chapter 5 begins by exploring child rights-based participatory research and its principles. I then discuss implementing the

approach with young children and the ethical considerations involved. I examine the central role of reflexivity within the methodology and the informed consent process. The chapter concludes by explaining the data analysis approach and coding system used for stage one.

Chapter 6 gives an account of the young children's involvement in the design of the methodology. This includes the recruitment of a research advisory group and their evaluation of some traditional research methods used with young children. There is also an account of a change in research roles and an adjustment to the *Lundy Model* to suit the local context informed by this advisory group. The chapter concludes with a discussion of data analysis with the children. In particular, I describe how there was, at times, a crossover between the data collection and data analysis processes which, while complex to follow, was respectful of authentic child participation. In this concluding section, I also discuss several process orientated findings from the analysis stage with the CRAG. They are placed in this chapter rather than the main findings chapters as they were initial findings from a small group of children used to inform an inclusive rights-based research approach for all participating children at the local context.

Chapter 7 concentrates on the participatory action research (PAR) approach I chose to use with the ECEC practitioners and the rationale behind that. I describe the fundamental principles of a PAR approach and how they were considered while working with this particular group. This is continued by a short discussion on tensions I experienced while following these principles and an examination of where the overall 'action' was in the approach.

The thesis has generated three types of findings,

- 1) process-orientated findings described in the final data analysis section of Chapter 6 and in my reflections on a methodology that could be useful to other transformative child rights researchers discussed in Chapters 8 and 9,
- 2) children's perspectives on Nature and participation in Chapters 8 and 9, and,
- 3) findings from the PAR sessions in stage 2 discussed in Chapter 10.

Chapter 8 addresses the first research aim of exploring young children's own perspectives of Nature under Article 29 1 (e). I begin by exploring how the young participants made their first Nature connections. This gave insight into how learning in or through Nature offers a more democratic approach to ESD in that it provides an opportunity for child-driven curricula. I continue by analysing how a responsive adult engages with these Nature connections as starting points for learning about sustainability, which can further a child rights approach. Doing so demonstrates how we can holistically transfer from the 'in' or 'through' to the 'about' Nature learning. The final section identifies where, in the data collection phase, opportunities to extend this to learning 'for' Nature could be seen that were both authentic and participant-driven.

Chapter 9 addresses the second aim of developing a child rights-based research methodology with young children to support their participation in developing an ESD approach. This chapter begins with a section that analyses six ways in which children enjoyed their participatory rights (free-flowing participation, the child's clock, verbal/non-verbal participation, relational participation, children's engagement with research tools and participation that respects local culture). It continues with a discussion on children's own terminology and the necessity to respect both that and many other aspects of their lives. This is followed by a second section that I have entitled 'Making space for unicorn moments', which came about as the participants led me to understand the relational aspect of supporting authentic child-rights approaches.

Chapter 10 analyses the findings from stage two under the third research aim, which looks at building the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate child rights-based ESD into their settings. Its first key finding is that while practitioners have their own existing knowledge of ECEC and ESD pedagogical synergies, some interpretations of these in practice are problematic from a child rights-based education approach. That said, the participants also gave insights into how child rights are interdependent and leads to my second finding that they often need to be 'balanced' for authentic enjoyment in practice and context. This is discussed under the themes of 'practitioner existing knowledge' and 'paradigms of pedagogy'. My final finding is that with all the will in the world and commitment to promoting sustainability with young children, practitioners themselves are often limited in

their capacity to make changes for the transformative approach needed for ‘whole system changes’. This can be because of a lack of time and resources or commitment to sustainability at management level or amongst co-workers. Participants provided several suggestions to support sector changes. This is analysed in the final theme of the capacity to enact change. The chapter concludes with a discussion on creating a transformative child rights approach for ESD with insights from the participants that they believe would further empower them in their duty-bearing roles under Article 29 1 (e). The discussion ends with an argument for a transformative leadership approach for effective change for climate action.

Chapter 11 ends the thesis with a discussion of the research contributions. It concludes that the thesis demonstrates that given the right elements, young children as rights holders can and should be partners in ESD curriculum making. By actively working towards a rights-respecting culture in early childhood, we can empower young children to become active, engaged, and contributing social actors in their own lives and communities. Additionally, in order to build the capacity of ECEC practitioners, further development is required in training, resources, and the type of leadership required to enact whole system change for effective transformative rights-based ESD approaches under Article 29 1 (e). It concludes by recommending further studies in settings of disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds and/or with limited daily access to the natural environment to gain insight on how children in such spaces can also fully enjoy their education and participatory rights under the CRC.

1.8. Research scope

With the arrival of Covid 19, data analysis and dissemination of findings with the children were impacted. Notably, we were to have a book launch for the children’s own publication, *The Children’s Nature Book*, which included a party for their families, ECEC practitioners and some local representatives. The online alternative did not fully support the children to enjoy their participatory rights as they had defined them. Furthermore, I was also limited in my contact with their families and, therefore, essential data for the analysis process with the children themselves.

Four participants withdrew for stage two, which limited the diversity of settings represented during the PAR approach. That said, these participants withdrew mainly because of time

restrictions, which gave insight into barriers surrounding effective ESD approaches. Furthermore, because these workshops were online, my understanding of the local culture was limited, which impacted the form of practical guidance I could give the ECEC practitioners on developing a rights-based ESD approach authentic to them. This, however, also gave insight into the form of learning (mentorship/on-site visits) that the participants considered valuable to developing that same approach, which is explored further in Chapter 10.

1.8. A note on terminology

A survey carried out in 2023 by *PEMI* (Professional Educators and Managers Ireland) identified that *Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC)* is the preferred name for Ireland's early childhood education sector. The Irish government, in contrast, uses the name *Early Learning and Care (ELC)*, which was adopted in 2019 without consultation with stakeholders (GOI, 2022). This continues to be a matter of ongoing dispute. For this thesis, I have chosen to use ECEC. In addition, ambiguity surrounds the naming of early childhood professionals and terms such as *educator*, *practitioner* and *teacher* are all used intermittently. Considering the highly specialised skillset such professionals use to fulfil the responsibilities of care and education in their role, I choose to identify as an ECEC practitioner and will use this term throughout the thesis.

A special UN report, *Harmony with Nature* (2019, p. 1), highlights humankind's evolving consciousness of our relationship with the natural environment and the "urgency to protect Mother Earth and to transition to an Earth-centred paradigm in furthering the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development." In the context of this paradigm, Nature or Mother Earth is not an object or property but a subject of law, with legal personhood, with Nature written throughout with a capital N. To that end, I have also capitalised the term Nature, and present it as a proper noun throughout the thesis to respectfully reflect its equal and interdependent standing with human species.

Chapter 2. Setting the context: The climate crisis through a child rights lens.

2.1. Introduction.

In the context of the climate crisis, it is crucial to recognise that it is also a child rights crisis (UNICEF, 2021; Daly, 2023). A child as a rights holder is not just a notion. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) serves as a legal imperative for States Parties to ensure that all children within their countries have their rights realised and enjoyed. In this chapter, I discuss how the climate crisis impacts children's lives. I continue this by analysing the CRC to reveal potential child rights violations and to explore how it could be used to better inform climate action. I also highlight the obligations of ratified States in ensuring that any decisions taken on climate action do not negatively impact the rights of children or future generations (UNGA, 2018). As a global challenge, addressing climate change requires comprehensive and transformative approaches that prioritise sustainable practices and protect the rights of present and future generations (Daly, 2023). In the final section, I focus on the Convention's critiques and the necessity to reframe rights for the type of action needed to combat the crisis (Davies, 2014).

2.2. How does the climate crisis impact children's lives?

Children bear the most significant burden of climate change, as they are more vulnerable than adults to disease, extreme weather events or food insecurity, and because the planet itself is becoming unsafe (UNICEF, 2021). Environmental harm has severe consequences for children under the age of 5. Their vulnerability to pollution and other hazards makes them more susceptible to health issues and even death. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA), environmental risks contributed to 1.5 million deaths of children under 5 in 2015, and many of these deaths could have been prevented with reduced exposure to environmental dangers (UNGA, 2018). Key environmental risks affecting young children include air pollution, water contamination, chemical exposure, climate change impacts, and vector-borne diseases. Reducing these risks can significantly improve child health and well-being (UNGA, 2018).

UNICEF's *Children's Climate Risk Index* (2021, p.2) reveals that 1 billion children – or half the world's child population - are at 'extremely high risk' of the impacts of climate change. The *Children's Climate Risk Index* (2021) ranks countries based on how vulnerable children

are to environmental stresses and extreme weather. For example, it finds children in Central Africa, Chad, Nigeria, Guinea, and Guinea Bissau most at risk (see Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Top 10 countries where children are most at risk from the climate crisis.

CCRI RANK	COUNTRY	CLIMATE AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS		CHILD VULNERABILITY		CHILDREN'S CLIMATE RISK INDEX	
		Score	Indicator	Score	Indicator	Score	Indicator
1	Central African Republic	6.7	●	9.8	●	8.7	●
2	Chad	7.0	●	9.4	●	8.5	●
2	Nigeria	8.8	●	8.1	●	8.5	●
4	Guinea	7.7	●	8.9	●	8.4	●
4	Guinea-Bissau	6.4	●	9.5	●	8.4	●
4	Somalia	7.0	●	9.3	●	8.4	●
7	Niger	7.3	●	8.9	●	8.2	●
7	South Sudan	6.8	●	9.2	●	8.2	●
9	Democratic Republic of the Congo	7.2	●	8.6	●	8.0	●
10	Angola	6.5	●	8.9	●	7.9	●
10	Cameroon	7.8	●	7.9	●	7.9	●
10	Madagascar	7.8	●	7.9	●	7.9	●
10	Mozambique	7.5	●	8.2	●	7.9	●

(UNICEF, 2021, p.14).

Notably, these same countries are also among those least responsible for creating the climate crisis (33 extremely high-risk countries collectively emit just 9% of global CO2 emissions in contrast to the ten highest emitting countries, which account for nearly 70%) (UNICEF, 2021, p.20). Almost every living child is now exposed to at least one environmental hazard, such as heatwaves, cyclones, air pollution, flooding and water scarcity. Furthermore, UNICEF (2021, p.23) highlights that approximately one-third of all children (850 million) are exposed to four or more of these stresses and describes the climate crisis as ‘the defining human and child’s rights challenge of this generation’. Aside from the environmental hazards affecting children’s access to essential services (health, nutrition, education and social protection), the lack of access reduces their adaptive capacity, increasing their vulnerability further.

2.3. Where are children’s rights violated, and how could the CRC inform climate action?

Although rights are understood as interrelated and interconnected (Long, 2019; Mitchell et al., 2023), it can be argued that there are at least ten articles relevant to how the climate crisis is violating children’s rights (UNGA, 2018; UNICEF, 2021). Most notable is Article 24,

which is the right to health and is most often referred to on account of the health risks of the climate crisis described above. Articles 2, 3, 5, 6, 12, 16, 28, 29 and 42 can also be considered, which I will now discuss in turn. It is important to note that given the complex, diverse nature of individual children's realities, violations under other articles also occur (UNCRC, 2023). Therefore, this analysis is by no means an exhaustive list.

2.3.1. Article 24, the right to health.

The CRC requires its Parties to ensure full implementation of children's right to health, explicitly as follows:

Article 24,

2. States Parties shall pursue full implementation of this right and, in particular, shall take appropriate measures:

- (a) To diminish infant and child mortality;
- (b) To ensure the provision of necessary medical assistance and health care to all children with emphasis on the development of primary health care;
- (c) To combat disease and malnutrition, including within the framework of primary health care, through, inter alia, the application of readily available technology and through the provision of adequate nutritious foods and clean drinking-water, taking into consideration the dangers and risks of environmental pollution;
- (d) To ensure appropriate pre-natal and post-natal health care for mothers;
- (e) To ensure that all segments of society, in particular parents and children, are informed, have access to education and are supported in the use of basic knowledge of child health and nutrition, the advantages of breastfeeding, hygiene and environmental sanitation and the prevention of accidents;
- (f) To develop preventive health care, guidance for parents and family planning education and services.

(UNCRC, 1989, p.7).

The specifics of Article 24 clearly outline States Parties' responsibilities for children's rights to health, nutrition and safety from environmental dangers. *General Comment 26* also points out that the right to health is dependent on and indispensable to the enjoyment of many other rights (UNCRC, 2023). The comment also highlights how climate change, pollution and toxic substances represent critical drivers of the alarming loss in biodiversity on which human health depends. In addition, the comment also raises concerns about children's current and anticipated psychosocial and mental health conditions caused by environmental harm, including climate change-related events. The UN's Human Rights Council¹ has also

¹ The Human Rights Council is an inter-governmental body within the United Nations system responsible for the promotion and protection of all human rights

recognised children’s vulnerability to climate change and highlighted violations, including physical and mental health, access to education, adequate food and housing and safe drinking water and sanitation (UNGA, 2018). The Council have also expressed their concerns about how climate change affects some children more than others, including children with disabilities, children seeking refuge, those living in poverty and Indigenous children.

2.3.2. *Article 2 – Non-Discrimination.*

To ensure equality and non-discrimination in our children’s lives, the CRC directs as follows:

Article 2

1. States Parties shall respect and ensure the rights set forth in the present Convention to each child within their jurisdiction without discrimination of any kind, irrespective of the child's or his or her parent's or legal guardian's race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national, ethnic, or social origin, property, disability, birth or other status.

2. States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that the child is protected against all forms of discrimination or punishment on the basis of the status, activities, expressed opinions, or beliefs of the child's parents, legal guardians, or family members

(UNCRC, 1989, p.2).

However, inequalities such as extreme poverty, hunger, disease, violence, and illiteracy are very much part of millions of children’s lives, and therefore, their rights under Article 2 are being violated (Croft, 2017; Lundy & Martínez Sainz, 2018). The language within Article 2 has been critiqued on the basis that it does not explicitly name Indigenous, gender variant or non-binary children, as well as girls and children who are homeless, as marginalised groups (Freeman, 2012). However, the Committee has interpreted the expression of ‘other status’ to include sexual orientation and gender identity.

General Comment No 26 (2023) also highlights that:

A. Right to non-discrimination (art. 2)

14. ... ‘Children in general, and certain groups of children in particular, face heightened barriers to the enjoyment of their rights, due to multiple and intersecting forms of discrimination; such grounds include those specifically prohibited under article 2 of the Convention and the “other status” referred to in the article’.

(UNCRC, 2023, p.3).

The General Comment continues by naming those groups who are discriminatorily affected by the impact of environmental harm as:

‘Indigenous children, children belonging to minority groups, children with disabilities and children living in disaster-prone or climate-vulnerable environments’

(UNCRC, 2023, p.3).

2.3.3. *Article 3 - Best interests of the child.*

The principle of the best interests of the child is a foundational element of the CRC and is also identified as one of the four general principles as follows:

Article 3

1. In all actions concerning children, whether undertaken by public or private social welfare institutions, courts of law, administrative authorities or legislative bodies, the best interests of the child shall be a primary consideration.

2. States Parties undertake to ensure the child such protection and care as is necessary for his or her well-being, taking into account the rights and duties of his or her parents, legal guardians, or other individuals legally responsible for him or her, and, to this end, shall take all appropriate legislative and administrative measures.

3. States Parties shall ensure that the institutions, services and facilities responsible for the care or protection of children shall conform with the standards established by competent authorities, particularly in the areas of safety, health, in the number and suitability of their staff, as well as competent supervision

(UNCRC, 1989, p.2).

Arguably, Article 3 should be considered the foundation for protecting children's rights in environmental matters. It directs State Parties to prioritise the child's best interests in decision-making processes related to environmental harm. By doing so, policymakers can develop effective and responsible approaches to safeguard children's well-being and ensure a sustainable future. General Comment 26 furthers this with the following recommendation:

A. Best interests of the child (art. 3)

16. ... ‘Where an environmental decision may have a significant impact on children, conducting a more detailed procedure to assess and determine children’s best interests that provides opportunities for their effective and meaningful participation, is appropriate’ (UNCRC, 2023, p.3).

Zermaetten (2010) claims it needs to be seen as a rule of procedure or a step to be integrated into the decision-making process concerning matters that affect a child. Its purpose is to assess the potential impact that a decision will have on the child involved. In this context,

Article 3 serves as a guide to ensure that children's rights and well-being are considered during decision-making processes that directly concern them. However, the impact of this could be positive or negative if based upon the recognition that an adult is only in a position to make decisions on behalf of a child because of their 'lack of experience and judgement'. Peleg (2013) argues this to be disrespectful of child agency and contrary to the view of the competent contributing young global citizen. Likewise, Archard (2002) questions how this adult will be considered an expert in a particular child's life and whether the terms of the trust bestowed upon that adult are sufficiently clear. Archard (2002) argues that it is not a question of interests but choice - how can the adult know what the child would choose if they could, and how can that be evident?

Eekelaar (2017) discusses the 'indeterminacy of the principle', which refers to the difficulty of predicting the future effects of present decisions on a child. Each child has unique social experiences, making objectively assessing their interests challenging. In 2023, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) claimed that human demands are exhausting the planet's resources and putting the lives of future generations at risk. Given this context it is clear that it is in the best interests of young children to take action, acquire new skills, and change behaviours to address and mitigate the climate crisis. Daly (2023) states that the best interest principle has enormous potential for environmental litigation. She argues that it is essential to emphasise the link that children of this generation have with the future one and those yet to be born. Specific attention must be given to the overlapping interests of both groups of children to give their rights the status they deserve in the context of a climate crisis (UNCRC, 2023).

A child rights-based approach advocates for involving children in decision-making processes that affect them, considering their best interests, and protecting their rights. While encouraging children to take part in actions that address environmental issues is essential for fostering a sense of responsibility and empowerment, it should be done in a manner that respects their rights. In practical terms, this means engaging children in age-appropriate and meaningful ways, providing them with education and awareness about environmental challenges, and encouraging their participation in activities that promote sustainable practices without compromising their well-being or infringing upon their rights. From a best interests

perspective, the balance is achieved by recognising children as active agents in building a sustainable future while safeguarding their rights and ensuring that adults bear the primary responsibility for addressing the root causes of the climate crisis (UNCRC, 2023).

The first Special Rapporteur report (2013) on human rights issues concerning the enjoyment of a safe and healthy environment stated that human rights and the environment are interdependent. Equally, a clean and sustainable environment is necessary to fully enjoy many human rights, including the rights to life, health, clean food and water. Still, rights to information, participation, and remedy are vital for protecting the planet.

2.3.4. Article 5 – Right to guidance.

In choosing to express a view (or not) on a matter affecting them, Lundy et al. (2011;2012) underline the necessity of supporting the young child to form a view through building capacities. This means informing children about such matters using strategies that are respectful, inclusive, and safe from rebuke and that offer the opportunity to form and express ideas in a manner meaningful to them if they choose to do so (Lundy, 2007). This can be seen under Article 5 as follows:

Article 5

States Parties shall respect the responsibilities, rights and duties of parents or, where applicable, the members of the extended family or community as provided for by local custom, legal guardians or other persons legally responsible for the child, to provide, in a manner consistent with the evolving capacities of the child, appropriate direction and guidance in the exercise by the child of the rights recognised in the present Convention.

(UNCRC, 1989, p.2).

The article is distinctive in giving the primary responsibilities to parents. The Committee on the Rights of the Child identified many gaps in information on the effects of exposure to environmental harm. Much more must be done to make data publicly available and accessible to children (UNCRC, 2016). Not having this data and mechanisms to protect children adequately points to a violation under Article 5.

Any decision-making relating to the environment must be assessed in line with how it would impact the enjoyment of children's rights (Byrne & Lundy, 2019; UNGA, 2018). This is particularly relevant to ESD in early childhood because there is a common perception that the young child is not competent enough to understand or engage with complex environmental issues (Mackey, 2012; 2014). Whether or not an educator holds this perception is irrelevant under Article 5. There is a duty that strategies are created to provide every child with the necessary guidance to enjoy their right to a healthy environment. (Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; Davies, 2009, 2014; Duhn, 2012).

2.3.5. Article 6 – Life, survival, and development.

The development of children is intertwined with the environment in which they live (CRC, 2023). The CRC stipulates the protection of eight areas of child development (physical, mental, moral, social, cultural, spiritual, personality and talent) under a collection of articles (18, 23, 27, 29 and 32) and an overall right to life, survival, and development under the following:

Article 6

1. States Parties recognize that every child has the inherent right to life.
2. States Parties shall ensure to the maximum extent possible the survival and development of the child

(UNCRC, 1989, p. 3).

General Comment 5 (2003) reinforces the significance of protecting the rights to life, survival, and development as one of the critical principles of CRC. Environmental harm directly threatens children's life, health, and development rights. Denying them access to essential resources such as food, housing, water, sanitation, and clean air violates their right to an adequate standard of living. Exposure to harmful chemicals, waste, and loss of biodiversity not only hinders a child's rights but also impacts their overall development throughout their lives. Moreover, access to a safe and healthy environment is crucial for children's opportunities for play and leisure, as highlighted by the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) in 2018. Therefore, ensuring a clean and sustainable environment is essential for protecting children's rights to life, health, development, and a fulfilling childhood experience.

Peleg (2013) argues that the child's right to development under Article 6 has been approached as adult-centred, hindering child agency. This perspective is related to the belief that the complexity and potential distress of the climate crisis might lead adults to shield children from engaging with the topic. However, Peleg contends that restricting children's learning and engagement based on predetermined developmental stages and adult perspectives inhibits their ability to develop their agency. This issue also resonates with the NCCA report (2018), which analysed Ireland's early childhood curriculum framework *Aistear's* potential linkage to promoting ESD. The report used predefined adult-defined competencies or age-appropriateness indicators. However, relying on these criteria limits children's agency in defining their competency in environmental issues and sustainability. Peleg's argument emphasises the importance of recognising and respecting children's agency in addressing complex global challenges like the climate crisis. Children should have opportunities to engage with these topics at their own pace and in a manner that allows them to develop their understanding and capacity for action rather than being restricted by adult-centric perspectives. Encouraging child agency in education and environmental initiatives can empower children to actively participate in creating a sustainable future. Peleg (2013) also discusses the 'human beings' conception, which encompasses the view of children as beings in their own right and not comparative to adults. This conception positions the child as a rights holder, capable of building their own life rather than having it made for them.

2.3.6. Article 12 – the right to participate and be heard.

Lundy (2007) has described Article 12 - the content of which I outlined under the *Methodological focus* section in Chapter 1 - as the most contentious provision from a theoretical and legal perspective. Lundy also claims that Article 12 can only be fully understood when considered in connection with the other provisions of the CRC, namely Article 2, Article 3, Article 5 and Article 13- the right to information and Article 19 - the right to be safe (Lundy, 2007; Lundy et al., 2011; 2012). This interconnected understanding of Article 12 forms the basis of *the Lundy Model*, a rights-based model of participation, which seeks to empower children's right to participate and is discussed in detail in Chapter 5 forms the basis of this thesis. It encourages the meaningful involvement of children in decision-making processes, especially in matters that directly affect them.

The Convention's *General Comment No. 7 (2005) Implementing child rights in early childhood* reinforces this view by highlighting that the CRC requires recognising even the youngest children as individuals with their own rights, concerns, and contributions. This reaffirms the importance of considering children as participating members of families, communities, and societies and respecting their right to be heard and valued. This view was further strengthened in the development of a specific *General Comment No 12 (2009), The Right of the Child to be Heard*, highlighting the importance of Article 12 by stating:

The right of all children to be heard and taken seriously constitutes one of the fundamental values of the Convention. The Committee on the Rights of the Child (the Committee) has identified article 12 as one of the four general principles of the Convention, the others being the right to non-discrimination, the right to life and development, and the primary consideration of the child's best interests, which highlights the fact that this article establishes not only a right in itself but should also be considered in the interpretation and implementation of all other rights

(UNCRC, 2009, p.5).

General Comment No 12 (2009) explains participation as 'a process, not as an individual one-off event' (UNCRC, 2009, p.29). It also states that:

'children's views have to be treated with respect and they should be provided with opportunities to initiate ideas and activities. Adults working with children should acknowledge, respect and build on good examples of children's participation, for instance, in their contributions to the family, school, culture and the work environment. They also need an understanding of the socio-economic, environmental and cultural context of children's lives'.

(UNCRC, 2009, p.29).

Gillet-Swan and Sargent (2019) define participation as voice, inclusive practice, actions and processes that embrace children's perspectives while actively engaging with them on matters that affect them. Yet, this is not universally accepted, and significant inconsistencies in what constitutes effective and authentic participation in education sectors remain (Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2015; 2018; 2019 Robson; 2016). On one end of the spectrum is tokenistic or tick-box consultation with children, whose participation is superficial and lacks meaningful engagement. On the other end, there is high-level shared or child-led decision-making participation, as described by Hart (1992) and Mackler and Groundwater-Smith (2015),

which allows for transformative learning experiences. Despite such transformative participation being claimed to enhance children's development, strategic action remains scarce to authentically embed young children's voices in daily education experiences. Gillet-Swan and Sargent (2015; 2019) have highlighted this lack of progress in fully integrating children's perspectives into educational practices.

General Comment 26 (UNCRC, 2023) underlines that children identify environmental issues as highly important to their lives. The comment continues by emphasising that children's voices are a powerful global force which adds relevant perspectives to decision-making on climate matters at all levels. Furthermore, the Committee recommends proactively seeking children's views on such issues. Therefore, child participation in developing sustainable practices should recognise the child as a current social actor and rights holder. To be more effective, it should consider the interdependence between child participation, sociocultural environments, and children's lived realities, as suggested by Horgan et al. (2017), Martínez Sainz (2018), and Moody and Darbellay (2019). Leonard (2016) introduces the concept of "generagency," which discusses agency in terms of inter- and intra-generational relationships. It also highlights the structural inequalities in these relationships and how power dynamics affect children's realities. Understanding these generational power dynamics is crucial to avoid misrepresenting or limiting young children's voices and perspectives. Considering the interplay between child participation, sociocultural contexts, and power dynamics, the discourse on authentic child participation in climate action can be enriched, as proposed by Kucharczyk and Hanna (2020). This approach can empower children to actively engage in climate action and contribute meaningfully to shaping sustainable practices and policies. *General Comment 26* also emphasises the need to engage with additional support and unique strategies to empower disadvantaged children to exercise their right to be heard. Notably, the development of this comment involved a substantial amount of consultation with children. However, the participation of young children in the consultation was less visible. In the future, however, this could be more effectively supported by the right to guidance under Article 5 and the right to information under Article 13.

2.3.7. Article 13 – the right to information.

As described above, a need for more robust information on the level of environmental harm for children was highlighted at the general day of discussion in 2016. *General Comment 26* also emphasises that the right to information about environmental issues is fundamental. It is stipulated as follows under the CRC:

Article 13

1. The child shall have the right to freedom of expression; this right shall include freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas of all kinds, regardless of frontiers, either orally, in writing or print, in the form of art, or through any other media of the child's choice.
2. The exercise of this right may be subject to certain restrictions, but these shall only be such as are provided by law and are necessary:
 - (a) For respect of the rights or reputations of others; or
 - (b) For the protection of national security or of public order (ordre public), or of public health or morals.

(UNCRC, 1989, p.4).

The first report from the Special Rapporteur (2013) highlighted that access to environmental information had two dimensions. Firstly, State Parties are responsible for regularly collecting, updating and disseminating all information relevant to the climate crisis, and secondly, this information must be timely and accessible to all people. As highlighted already under Article 5, this information must also be accessible and appropriate to children and, when necessary, used in line with the right to guidance to ensure that children are fully informed on matters that affect them. Making information accessible to children as part of their education is further stipulated in Article 28, discussed next. In an Irish context, governmental policy has significantly progressed in determining what is meant (and what is not) by child participation. Taking the time and space to share information to support children in forming views is heavily underlined (DCEDIY, 2021). In addition, the Rapporteur Report (2013) emphasises that environmental education should begin early in any child's educational process (UNGA, 2018).

That said, children who have exercised their right to freedom of expression and engaged in protests on environmental matters under Article 13 have often faced threats and other forms of reprisal (UNCRC, 2023). In addition to the right to information, *General Comment 26* also recommends that state actors such as teachers receive training on children's civil and political

rights, including measures to ensure children can enjoy them safely. Moreover, the Committee underlines that States must recognise that children’s civil and political engagement is a positive means to hear and include their contributions to climate action (UNCRC, 2023).

2.3.8. Articles 28 and 29 – the right to education.

General Comment 26 (2023, p.9) underlines that education is ‘one of the cornerstones of a child rights-based approach to the environment’. Children have also highlighted that education protects their rights and increases their preparedness for environmental damage (UNCRC, 2023). Children’s education rights are stipulated under Articles 28 and 29 as follows:

Article 28

1. States Parties recognize the right of the child to education, and to achieve this right progressively and based on equal opportunity, they shall, in particular:

- (a) Make primary education compulsory and available free to all;
- (b) Encourage the development of different forms of secondary education, including general and vocational education, make them available and accessible to every child, and take appropriate measures such as the introduction of free education and offering financial assistance in case of need;
- (c) Make higher education accessible to all on the basis of capacity by every appropriate means;
- (d) Make educational and vocational information and guidance available and accessible to all children;
- (e) Take measures to encourage regular attendance at schools and the reduction of drop-out rates.

2. States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that school discipline is administered in a manner consistent with the child's human dignity and in conformity with the present Convention.

3. States Parties shall promote and encourage international cooperation in matters relating to education, in particular with a view to contributing to the elimination of ignorance and illiteracy throughout the world and facilitating access to scientific and technical knowledge and modern teaching methods. In this regard, a particular account shall be taken of the needs of developing countries.

Article 29

1. States Parties agree that the education of the child shall be directed to:

- (a) The development of the child’s personality, talents, and mental and physical abilities to their fullest potential;

- (b) The development of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, and for the principles enshrined in the Charter of the United Nations;
- (c) The development of respect for the child's parents, his or her own cultural identity, language, and values, for the national values of the country in which the child is living, the country from which he or she may originate, and for civilizations different from his or her own;
- (d) The preparation of the child for responsible life in a free society, in the spirit of understanding, peace, tolerance, equality of sexes, and friendship among all peoples, ethnic, national, and religious groups and persons of indigenous origin;
- (e) The development of respect for the natural environment

2. No part of the present article or article 28 shall be construed so as to interfere with the liberty of individuals and bodies to establish and direct educational institutions, subject always to the observance of the principle set forth in paragraph 1 of the present article and to the requirements that the education given in such institutions shall conform to such minimum standards as may be laid down by the State.

(UNCRC, 1989, p.8-9).

The right to develop respect for the natural environment is explicit in Article 29 1 (e). It is important to first discuss what is meant by 'the natural environment' in order to provide a working definition for this thesis.

Hartig *et al.* (2014, p. 208.) suggest a natural environment involves 'the physical features and processes of nonhuman origin that people ordinarily can perceive, including the 'living nature' of flora and fauna, together with still and running water, qualities of air and weather, and the landscapes that comprise these and show the influence of geological processes'. The natural environment comprises land-based ecosystems, such as grasslands and forests, aquatic ecosystems, including rivers and wetlands, and coastal and marine ecosystems, including mangroves and seagrass meadows. Ecosystems include animals and plants, and the interactions they have with each other and their physical environment. From a Western perspective, the natural environment is often considered separate from human actions (Cutter-McKenzie & Rousell, 2019; UNICEF, 2021). Indigenous people believe these two concepts are not separate (Shava, 2013), but rather intertwined, with this relationship creating the cultural landscapes and processes we see today. Likewise, Osgood (2022; 2025) describes this as 'multispecies flourishing' as a means to support young children's understanding of their interdependent part of the natural world and a flattening of hierarchies.

The natural environment system spans public and private land, and there are no clear boundaries between where it ends and other systems begin. This is important to consider when thinking about access to the natural environment and how that looks in the context of young children's lives. While some children may have rich access to large green areas, those living in built-up inner-city areas may experience it in other, less obvious ways (Osgood, 2025), such as through weather elements, sightings of flora and fauna, gardening projects, and/or exposure to media and technology. I have therefore chosen to use the term Nature (which, as described in Chapter 1, is presented as a proper noun to reflect its equal standing with the human species) as a means to better reflect the diversity in such experiences and enjoyment of this right.

Additionally, *General Comment 1 (2001) Article 29 (1): The aims of education* outline that education should promote and protect the core value of the CRC, namely the human dignity of each child and their equal rights without discrimination. Furthermore, education must be child-centred, child-friendly and empowering by providing every child with life skills that strengthen their capacity to enjoy their full range of rights. Every child is entitled to live in a society where rights and values are embedded in daily life and experiences (Lundy & Martínez Sainz, 2018). *General Comment 26 (2023, p.9)* also describes a rights-based environmental education as 'transformative, inclusive, child-friendly and empowering'. Life skills must go beyond literacy and numeracy, including making well-balanced decisions, critical thinking, conflict resolution, and developing healthy social relationships and civic responsibility.

Education should go beyond the one-way transmission of knowledge and position learners as competent to contribute to the world. This further highlights identifiable legal and theoretical foundations to support children's rights as active and contributing citizens for climate action. *General Comment 1 (2001)* also outlines that education must link issues of environment and sustainable development with socio-economic, socio-cultural and demographic issues, which echoes the pillars of ESD (Sirjai-Blatchford, 2009). *General Comment 26* furthers this by stating that education must also acknowledge the close interrelationship between respect for the natural environment and other ethical values enshrined in Article 29 (1). The Committee also emphasises that this respect is being promoted at home, in schools, and within the

community, actively involving children in local and global ESD projects (CRC, 2001). This provides further legal underpinnings for the young child's agency as a contributing citizen (Mac Naughton, Hughes & Smith, 2008; Dunn, 2012; Hägglund & Johansson, 2014).

A final aspect of Article 29 (1) and the aims of education that align with ESD for effective climate action is the young child's right to learn about human rights and ethical values (Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008). *General Comments 1 (2001)* and *26 (2023)* emphasise the importance of providing education that fosters an understanding and appreciation of the values outlined in Article 29 (1), including respect for differences, both within the educational environment and through teaching approaches. However, integrating such values effectively requires ensuring that those responsible for supporting and promoting them are adequately convinced and trained to do so (Lundy, 2007; Jerome, Emerson, Lundy & Orr, 2015; Jerome, 2018; Lundy & Martínez Sainz; Long, 2019). Therefore, the committee emphasises the necessity of pre-service and in-service training programmes for teachers, educational administrators, and all involved in child education to promote the human values stated under Article 29(1). As will be highlighted in the following policy chapter, this becomes crucial in addressing the lack of ESD training for ECEC practitioners in Ireland. The responsibility for the provision of child rights education is dealt with under Article 42 as follows:

Article 42

States Parties undertake to make the principles and provisions of the Convention widely known, by appropriate and active means, to adults and children alike.

(UNCRC, 1989, p.12).

By providing proper training and support, educators can effectively integrate human rights and ethical values into the education of young children, thereby contributing to their holistic development and fostering a culture of sustainability. Davies (2014) argues that the Convention itself is not enough to ensure sustainable development for the 21st century. As such, she calls for an overall revision of rights to better understand what is needed regarding human and non-human rights for more effective climate action.

2.4. Revisioning rights

Reynaert, Bourverne-De Bie and Vandeveldel (2012), Robson (2016), and Lundy and Martínez Sainz (2018) believe that a ‘top-down’ policy to practice approach to implementing children’s rights is restrictive and argue for its reframing to better serve children’s living realities. Moody and Darbellay (2019) build on this and emphasise the need for interdisciplinary collaboration to provide more innovative solutions for children to enjoy their rights more effectively. Davies (2014) argues that it is time for an overall revision of rights and justice to meet humanity's current challenges. To that end, she provides an expanded rights-based framework to support a more harmonious way of life for both human and non-human species. This *Expanded Rights Framework* can be seen in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Expanded Rights Framework

(Davies, 2014).

The framework incorporates five dimensions that encompass various environmental, social, and cultural perspectives. The approach positions early childhood education at the forefront of addressing and meeting sustainability demands. Davies (2014) argues that integrating these dimensions through holistic and transformative learning experiences in early childhood education can significantly shape environmentally conscious and sustainable citizenship.

Dimension 1 of the framework emphasises the foundational importance and interconnectedness of all the articles of CRC under the four guiding principles: survival and development, protection, participation, and best interests. The previous section provided a thorough examination of this dimension. **Dimension 2** calls for expanding and reconceptualising children's agentic participation rights. Davies (2014) argues that the CRC needs clarity on the various forms of active participation that children can engage in. Arguably, there has since been significant work in developing this discourse, such as *The Participation Framework* (DCEDIY, 2021), discussed in the following chapter. By recognising and nurturing young children's agency, the framework promotes meaningful and authentic participation, allowing them to actively contribute to their learning and development.

Dimension 3 acknowledges the importance of collective rights and aims to address global challenges with collective origins. These challenges include human migrations, food and water security, overuse of non-renewable energy, biodiversity loss, and species decline. As these issues are complex and require collaborative responses at local, national, and international levels, the framework emphasises the need for collective action to address them effectively. Davies (2014) highlights that existing human rights treaties often reflect an individualistic concept of human rights and may not adequately support conditions conducive to a shared existence of marginalised groups, including children, women, people experiencing poverty, people with disabilities, and indigenous people (Boyd, 2010). Climate change likely disproportionately affects indigenous communities despite their low ecological footprints (Cutter-McKenzie & Rousell, 2019; UNICEF, 2021). Shava (2013) stresses the importance of advocating for and recognising the value of indigenous traditions and knowledge and including indigenous voices in ESD scholarship.

The United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP), established and approved in 2007, is a significant step. Still, there has been criticism for perceiving indigenous knowledge as merely valuable for being extracted and universalised. Instead, what is needed is a revitalisation of the indigenous concept of 'self of place' (discussed in Chapter 3) or the development of shared connectedness with people living in the same geography. This approach would encompass a shared responsibility for both the human and

non-human worlds, promoting a deeper understanding and appreciation of the interconnectedness of all life (Shava, 2013). By recognising collective rights, the framework seeks to create a more inclusive and sustainable world that addresses the needs of all individuals and communities, including the most vulnerable and marginalised.

Dimension 4 recognises intergenerational rights. An extension of collective rights is intergenerational rights. One generation using resources to the extent that it leaves the planet unable to meet the needs of future generations is a matter of justice (Davies, 2014). Although the next generation does not exist, they will need resources such as clean air and water for survival. Beder (2012) claims that as a group of people, the next generation have collective rights and that we must fulfil them. Daly (2023) discusses the paradox of intergenerationality and highlights that the relationships between intergenerational equity, children's rights, and those yet to be born are difficult to elaborate on. She criticises the lack of clarity in *General Comment 26* on intergenerational justice and how it relates to children's rights (Daly, 2023). Human rights, intergenerational rights and children's rights are all being employed to tackle the climate crisis legally. Daly (2023) argues that invoking the principle of best interest (discussed in section 2.3.3) should be a key component of the principle of intergenerational equity and a bridge between the interests of those in the present and in the future.

Dimension 5 recognises biocentric/ecocentric rights. Biocentrism considers humans one of many biological species and places inherent value on non-human organisms. Ecocentrism furthers this concept to include the value of the planet's non-living systems and the reliance on the entire ecosystem. Davies (2014) advocates for the rights of Nature, seeking to establish legal standing for the natural environment and treat all beings, human and non-human, as equals to secure an everyday and sustainable existence. The rights of Nature have gained traction in recent years. Rather than treating it as property under the law, the rights of Nature acknowledge that Nature, in all its life forms and cycles, has the right to exist.

The Global Alliance for the Rights of Nature (GARN) is a global network of organisations and individuals committed to universally adopting and implementing legal systems that

recognise the rights of Nature. Countries that have now legally recognised the rights of Nature include Ecuador, New Zealand, Colombia, Australia, the United States, Bangladesh, and India. While this has yet to become the case in Ireland, the recently published *Report of the Citizens Assembly on Biodiversity Loss* (2023) also highlights the need for Nature to become a legal entity and enforceable rights in the same way companies have rights. The report also outlined that having a law would not be enough, with Nature rights needing to be enforced and appropriately governed.

Along with expanding rights, Davies (2014) suggests considering the four pillars of The Earth Charter: ‘respect and care for the community of life’, ‘ecological integrity’, ‘social and economic justice’, and ‘democracy, non-violence and peace’ as starting points for integrating a reconceptualised rights-based framework for learning for sustainability. The Earth Charter is a document crafted by visionaries in 2000 to drive a global movement towards a more just, sustainable and peaceful world. Crowell (2017) believes its values must be central to any ESD curriculum. Learners should have the opportunities to establish a relationship with Nature while learning about it, and having positive learning experiences is more likely to make a difference in attitudes and pro-environmental behaviours.

The first two dimensions align with this thesis's conceptual framework, which focuses on the perspectives of young children and ECEC practitioners. To make a meaningful contribution under Article 29 1 (e), it is essential to rethink current early years teaching and expand it to include eco-sociocultural approaches that acknowledge and respect the rights and inherent values of humans and nonhumans. This shift in pedagogy emphasises the interconnectedness of all living beings and the environment, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation for the natural world. Transformative learning is crucial in enabling young children to become change agents for sustainability. By empowering them to shape a sustainable future, transformative learning offers practical insights into how traditional social pedagogy can evolve into rights-based pedagogy. This approach not only focuses on academic knowledge but also values other expertise. It instils a sense of responsibility and agency in young learners, motivating them to advocate for environmental conservation and social justice

(Davies, 2014; Robson, 2016). To that end, the following chapter examines both education policy and curriculum for ESD in early childhood.

Chapter 3. Examining policy and curriculum for rights-based ESD in ECEC.

3.1. Introduction.

This chapter concentrates on policy and curriculum for supporting a child rights-based approach to education for sustainable development in early childhood. It begins with examining international legal and policy context before providing a detailed analysis of national policy for children and ESD. This leads to an overall discussion on the ambiguity surrounding the value of ECEC for ESD promotion within Irish government policy. The second section provides a curriculum analysis from a national perspective and then an international one. I explore where both Nature learning, care for the environment and child rights are supported in the national curriculum framework. I also highlight where vagueness can be identified surrounding some key sustainable concepts, which could lead to misinterpretation in practice. This is continued by examining how ESD is embedded at an international curriculum level. The section concludes with a discussion on the recent updating process of the national curriculum (NCCA, 2024), how it reflects the current ESD in ECEC research and where it still falls short under the UNCRC.

3.2. International legal and policy context for rights-based ESD in early childhood education and care

As described in detail in the previous chapter, the CRC is a legally binding agreement that establishes the fundamental rights of all children. Taking force in 1990, it encompasses various civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights. Under the CRC, a child is defined as any human being below the age of eighteen unless the law applicable to them grants them the status of majority earlier. Article 29 1 (e) of the CRC enshrines the right of all children to receive an education that develops respect for Nature as follows:

Article 29

1. States Parties agree that the education of the child shall be directed to:
 - (e) The development of respect for the natural environment.

(UNCRC, 1989, p.9).

The UNESCO² report *Educating for a Sustainable Future* (1997) underlined education as the most effective means to achieve sustainable development. The United Nations Millennium Declaration (UNMD) was signed in 2000, committing world leaders to achieve eight goals relating to global growth by 2015, including environmental sustainability and universal primary education. Since the World Summit on Sustainable Development³ in 2002, the role of education in achieving harmonious, sustainable living and promoting pro-environmental behaviours has been widely recognised. The United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (DESD)⁴ (2005-2014) resulted in an overall education goal that:

integrates values, activities, principles, that are inherently linked to sustainable development into all forms of education and learning and help usher in a change in attitudes, behaviours, and values to ensure a more sustainable future in social, environmental and economic terms.

(UNESCO, 2007, p.5).

The integral position of early education and care (ECEC) in promoting ESD was initially stated in *The Contribution of Early Childhood Education to a Sustainable Society* (UNESCO, 2008) and subsequently in the OMEP *Education for Sustainable Development in the Early Years* reports (Siraj-Blatchford, Smith, and Pramling Samuelsson, 2010). OMEP, The World Organisation for Early Childhood Education (OMEP), is an NGO founded in 1948 and operating in more than 60 countries that works to defend the Human Rights of girls and boys from when they are born until they are eight years of age (early childhood). The reports emphasise the importance of recognising young children as rights holders in their education spaces and implementing the CRC. They also define sustainability as an evolving concept as various sustainability concerns are experienced by children worldwide. As such, a deep understanding of local cultural contexts is essential for effective and respectful ESD application. During the DESD (2005-2014), the OMEP World Project *Early Childhood*

² UNESCO - The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) is a specialised agency of the United Nations (UN) that promotes world peace and security through international cooperation in education, arts, sciences and culture.

³ The World Summit on Sustainable Development 2002 took place in South Africa from 26 August to 4 September 2002. 190 countries pledged their commitment to achieve a significant reduction in the current rate of biodiversity loss at global, regional and local levels by 2010

⁴ The Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (DESD) 2005–2014 was an Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) initiative of the United Nations.

*Education for Sustainability (2009-2015)*⁵ examined an awareness of the sector's role in ESD promotion with a particular focus on taking a child-oriented perspective (Engdahl, 2015). The report indicated that young children possess substantial knowledge about Nature and environmental issues and an understanding of individual responsibilities for sustainability. Findings also highlighted that adults frequently underestimate young children's competencies in this regard. As part of the research, OMEP introduced *The Environmental Rating Scale for Sustainable Development in Early Childhood (ERS-SDES)* in 2013 to further assess ESD curricula development for the sector. Over the last decade, there has been an increased interest in how ESD can be enhanced from early childhood. However, ESD educational provision in this sector remains fragmented within and between countries worldwide (Siraj-Blatchford & Pramling Samuelsson, 2015).

In 2002, leaders of 189 countries committed to achieving a set of eight measurable goals, termed the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), that ranged from halving extreme poverty and hunger to promoting gender equality and reducing child mortality by the target date of 2015. They were not achieved. Child rights violations from extreme poverty, hunger, disease, violence, illiteracy, environmental degradation, and overall discrimination remain a feature of many children's lives (Lundy & Martínez Sainz, 2018). In 2015, all UN member states adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.⁶ From a rights perspective, the goals are explicitly grounded in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)⁷ and international human rights treaties, including the CRC. However, while the SDGs serve as a 'crucial contemporary impetus' for child rights discourses and, if implemented effectively, could result in the advancement of rights, its associated implementation processes also pose child rights challenges (Nolan, 2020, p.14). Firstly, the SDGs are not legally enforceable, nor is the CRC fully integrated into them. Secondly, Nolan and McGrath (2016) question the narrowness of the indicators to monitor the implementation of the SDGs and ensure accountability, which they describe as neither child rights sensitive nor child rights compliant. They call for qualitative measures in

⁵ The OMEP research comprised four studies drawn from 28 participating countries, involved more than 44,330 children aged from birth to 8 years, as well as 13,225 teachers. These participants were from various early childhood educational contexts.

⁶ The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was launched by a UN Summit in New York on 25-27 September 2015 and is aimed at ending poverty in all its forms. The UN 2030 Agenda envisages "a world of universal respect for human rights and human dignity, the rule of law, justice, equality and non-discrimination.

⁷ The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) is an international document adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1948 that enshrines the rights and freedoms of all human beings.

addition to quantitative ones to provide a broader scope for assessing implementation. Finally, while child participation is an element of the work of the United Nations High-Level Panel Forum on Sustainable Development (HLPF), which is charged with reviewing the 2030 Agenda at global level, there are limitations to its meaningful implementation in this context. Notably, the parameters of the body responsible for managing child participation, the United Nations Major Group for Children and Youth (MGCYP), are unclear and problematic under Article 12. Particularly concerning from an early childhood rights perspective is the MCCYP's scope, which applies to people under 30 and not children under 18, leading to uncertainty about how different age groups will be involved and prioritised (Nolan, 2020).

3.3. National legal and policy context for rights-based ESD

Ireland has been experiencing a policy hiatus with its frameworks for children and young children. The current national policy framework for children and young people: *Young Ireland: National Policy Framework for Children and Young People 2023-2028* was published in November 2023 and replaces *Better Outcomes Brighter Futures (BOBF) (2015-2020)*, which was expected to expire in 2020. BOBF contained five outcomes, two of which contain aims relevant to ESD:

Outcome 1: Active and healthy, physical and mental wellbeing.

Children and young people are or have...

1.4. enjoying play, recreation, sport, arts, culture, and nature.

(DCYA, 2014, p.47).

Outcome 5: Connected, respected and contributing to their world.

Children and young people are or have...

5.1. a sense of own identity, free from discrimination.

5.3. civically engaged, socially and environmentally conscious.

5.4. aware of their rights, responsible and respectful of the law.

(DCYA, 2014, p.97).

The policy was rights-informed and referenced the CRC throughout, with specific articles being cited under the framework's proposed outcomes. Particular to Article 29 1 (e) and ESD promotion is the following under *Outcome 2: Achieving full potential in learning and development*,

Achievement of Outcome 2 will further Ireland’s implementation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child.

Article 29: Education should be directed at developing the child’s personality and talents; fostering respect for human rights; own cultural, national values; and the environment.

(DCYA, 2014, p. 62).

Young Ireland: National Policy Framework for Children and Young People 2023-2028 has kept the same five outcomes with a specified priority of *Participation in Democracy* under *Outcome 5*. The policy addresses the Concluding Observations following Ireland’s fifth and report submissions to the UN on child rights and highlights that this new framework should be ‘developed with the meaningful participation of children, and encompass all areas covered by the Convention’ (DCEDIY, 2023, p.vi-vii).

The participation of children and young children is discussed in section three, entitled *Enabling Environment*. In 2015, the Irish government published the first *National Strategy on Children and Young People’s Participation in Decision-Making* for 2015 to 2020 (DCEDIY, 2015). It was a whole-of-government strategy, with the department taking responsibility for policy leadership and support and has since been replaced by *The Participation Framework – The National Framework for Children and Young People’s Participation in Decision-Making* (DCEDIY, 2021) discussed further below. Participation is described as ‘involvement in decision-making processes in everyday settings such as classrooms, childcare settings, healthcare, and out-of-school settings’ (DCEDIY, 2023, p.24). With such an emphasis on child and youth participation, a detailed *Cross Government Action Plan for Participation* is to be developed to progress the following high-level actions (Figure 3.1). Actions such as embedding the voice of children and young people in decision-making and the development of policy, legislation, education and research and building capacity to support this are both highlighted. From a child rights perspective, this is particularly relevant to involving young children in developing meaningful ESD.

Specific to ESD and the overall climate crisis and in contrast to *Better Outcomes Brighter Futures (BOBF) (2015-2020)*, Article 29 1 (e) has not been referenced. The policy is underpinned by the SDGs as mentioned above and does discuss *General Comment No. 26 (2023) on children’s rights and the environment, with a special focus on climate change*.

Figure 3.1: Cross-Government Action Plan for Participation

ACTION 1 PARTICIPATION

NO.	OWNER	ACTION	TIMELINE
1.1	All Departments	Embed the voice of children and young people in decision-making and the development of policy, legislation and research.	2023-2028
1.2	Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth	Build capacity through the provision of training, education, resources and supports.	2023-2028
1.3	Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth working with the Department of Rural and Community Development; Local Authorities; Department of Education	Embed the voice of children and young people in their communities.	2023-2028
1.4	Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth working with the Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, the Gaeltacht, Sport and Media; Department of Education; Coimisiún na Meán	Embed the voice of children and young people in decision-making in education, health and social services, legal processes, and online.	2023-2028
1.5	Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth	Promote the voice of children and young people in decision-making in their homes.	2023-2028

(DCEDIY, 2023, p.25).

The State’s obligations to urgently implement legislative and administrative measures and ‘to guarantee that children are able to exercise their rights in mitigating the impacts of climate change’ (DCEDIY, 2023, p.115) are highlighted. In addition, while not explicitly citing a child rights-based approach to ESD, the policy does state:

Government is seeking to engage, enable and empower young people through a two-way dialogue leading to the co-creation of climate actions that are meaningful, inclusive, accessible, and fair.

(DCEDIY, 2023, p.115).

Figure 3.2 gives an overview of agreed actions to be taken by different governmental departments to support climate awareness.

Figure 3.2: Action Steps by the Irish government to support climate awareness.

NO.	OWNER	ACTION	TIMELINE
67.1	Department of the Environment, Climate, and Communications	Acknowledge the leadership role of children and young people in advocating for climate policy, and ensure all of society, including parents, also contribute to these efforts.	2023
67.2	Department of the Environment, Climate, and Communications; Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth	Promote climate literacy among parents.	2024-2028
67.3	Department of the Environment, Climate, and Communications; Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth	Provide information for children on the relative impact of pro-environment actions and pro-environment policies, and behaviours which have a negative impact on the climate, mindful of the relative impact individual action can have on climate breakdown.	2024

(DCEDIY, 2023, p.115).

New in this policy is a section on ‘spotlights’, described as ‘areas which require action across Government’ and ‘a concerted effort over a specified period of time to generate the necessary momentum for change’ (DCEDIY, 2023, p.42). Current spotlights have been identified as child and youth poverty, mental health and well-being for children and young people, and disability services. In addition to these spotlights, the policy also names the following nine ‘major issues impacting children and young people’ (Figure 3.3); ‘play and recreation’, ‘education reform’, ‘inclusion in education’, ‘youth and family justice’, ‘foster care, care and aftercare’, ‘child protection’, ‘access to housing’, ‘access to further and higher education, including apprenticeships, for disadvantaged cohorts’ and the ‘digital environment’ (DCEDIY, 2023, p.6).

Although the policy references *General Comment 26*, which outlines in detail how much children are and will be impacted by the climate crisis, it has not been identified as a pending spotlight or made the above list. It also cites the latest national ESD strategy and highlights a cross-government action (Action 39, p.84) to ensure that ‘all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development’ (DCECIY, 2023). The following section examines this in further detail.

Figure 3.3: Major issues impacting children and young people in Ireland.

(DCEDIY, 2023, p.6).

3.4. An analysis of national strategies for ESD in early childhood

The Irish government has published two national strategies on ESD: *The National Strategy on Education for Sustainable Development (2014 -2020)* and *ESD to 2030: Second National Strategy on Education for Sustainable Development*, published in 2022. The second strategy comes with an implementation plan for 2022-2026. It outlines this under five priority action areas: (i) advancing policy, (ii) transforming learning environments, (iii) building capacities of educators, (iv) empowering and mobilising young people and (v) accelerating local and community level actions (GOI, 2022). At first glance, these objectives are transformative of ESD promotion; however, the following analysis highlights their shortcomings for the ECEC sector.

3.4.1. Advancing policy

The *National Strategy on Education for Sustainable Development (2014-2020)* reaffirmed the need for ESD in the curriculum from preschool to senior cycle, empowering children to become informed, active citizens in sustaining our environment. With specific reference to the ECEC sector, *Priority Action 3.3.1* of the strategy states:

This is particularly important given the potential for this sector to foster principles of sustainable development in young children when they are first learning to make sense of the world in which they live. Recognition of the importance of the early years' sector to promoting ESD is still in its infancy internationally (UNESCO, 2012, 34, 37). There is an opportunity therefore for Ireland to be in the forefront in this regard given the existing emphasis on ESD in *Aistear* and *Síolta*

(DES, 2014, p.12).

What is notable about this statement is that the government considered it a national opportunity to be 'in the forefront' of promoting ESD in early childhood as far back as 2014. However, the strategy did not explicitly mention Article 29 1 (e) nor the Convention, thereby lessening its potential impact. The valuable role of ECEC in ESD promotion is less apparent in the second national strategy, which instead emphasises ESD as lifelong learning (GOI, 2022). It does refer to the CRC in terms of a general comment on children's rights and the environment and the importance of human rights education in ESD. Other than that, no explicit references are made to Article 29 1 (e) (GOI, 2022).

Ireland's duty-bearing role as a State party under the CRC is also not evident under the new strategy (GOI, 2022). Byrne and Lundy (2019) argue that evaluating the impact of a strategy on child rights is a crucial step towards advancing effective policy development. This point was also recently made in the UN's Concluding Observations on Ireland's fifth and sixth report submissions on child rights. The Committee recommended establishing "systematic child-rights impact assessment procedures for national and subnational legislation and policies related to children" (UN, 2023, p.2).

3.4.2. Transforming learning environments

Under the priority area of transforming learning environments, the second ESD national strategy, *ESD to 2030*, contains an action (2.1a, p.6) to develop leadership skills for ESD promotion in primary, secondary and third levels. However, early education and care is not mentioned. Its omission as a transformative learning environment is significant, particularly when the priority seeks to explore ESD pedagogies and place-based learning, which reflect early childhood pedagogy (Siraj-Blatchford & Samuelsson, 2015) and existing practitioner skill sets, as I will later argue.

The implementation plan for the second strategy also aims to ensure high-quality resources for ESD with an action (2.5a, p.9) to carry out a cyclical review to ensure they are up-to-date, meaningful, appropriate, and easily accessible (GOI, 2022). Specific to the ECEC sector is an action (2.5h, p.9) to develop resources to support outdoor play in early childhood settings. Under the same priority, there is an action (2.6h, p.10) to increase educational programmes to raise awareness of biodiversity and climate change across primary, post-primary, and third-level sectors. A follow-up action (2.6g, p.10) to this is to increase visits to primary schools through the *Heritage in Schools*⁸ programme, which includes education on biodiversity. However, this commitment is not extended to the ECEC sector. Developing resources to support outdoor play in the ECEC but excluding the sector from these biodiversity programmes could be considered a missed opportunity. Indeed, from a child rights perspective, this violates Article 29 1 (e), Article 2 regarding age discrimination and Article 12 regarding participatory rights. Remarkably, these violations were already identified within the first strategy (DES, 2018).

3.4.3. *Building capacities of educators*

The same implementation plan's third priority is to build educators' capacities with an action to support ESD preservice training and CPD opportunities for the ECEC sector (3.1a, p. 12). Teachers in primary schools will also be encouraged to engage with ESD learning opportunities, including 'summer courses' for primary teachers and via the Teacher Refund of Fees Scheme⁹ (GOI, 2022, p.12). Whether these learning opportunities for the ECEC sector will also be reimbursed is unclear. Under the same priority, there is also an action under capacity building (3.1f) that 'all Higher Education institutions providing accredited programs of initial teacher education shall ensure that ESD and GCE are included as core elements underpinning all aspects of primary and post-programmes' (GOI, 2022, p.12). Accredited programmes of early education and care were not included. This exclusion and the fact that resources (learning materials, expert visits, free teacher training) remain more readily available for primary, secondary, and third-level education directly point to further inequalities between the different educational sectors. The obligation of ensuring ECEC is

⁸ The Heritage in Schools Scheme provides a panel of Heritage Specialists who visit primary schools to help children and their teachers learn about and appreciate their local heritage. The Scheme supports the stated aims and objectives of the Social, Scientific and Environmental Education (SESE) curriculum and provides an additional educational tool and resource for teachers.

⁹ Teacher Fee Refund Scheme provides funding to teachers towards the cost of course participation and examination fees on successful completion of professional development courses.

included in all relevant policy frameworks associated with ESD is underscored by *General Comment No. 7* from the CRC, which directed State Parties:

To contribute to the realisation of rights for all young children through formulation and promotion of comprehensive policies, laws, programmes, practices, professional training, and research specifically focused on rights in early childhood.

(CRC, 2006, p.2).

Equally significant and as highlighted above is Article 2 of the CRC and every child's right to non-discrimination, which is being violated by young children not having access to the same ESD resources afforded to other children because of their age. *General Comment No. 7* further underlines state duties for the realisation of rights in early childhood by stating:

Young children are especially at risk of discrimination because they are relatively powerless and depend on others for the realisation of their rights.

(CRC, 2006, p.5).

The State's duty to protect children from discrimination was also outlined in BOBF, under *Outcome 5 Connected, Respected and Contributing* where all children and young people 'are free from discrimination' (DCYA, 2014, p.6). Likewise, *Young Ireland: National Policy Framework for Children and Young People 2023-2028* discusses addressing discrimination as 'everyone's business' (p.vii.). In addition, it states that the children and young people consulted in its development also highlighted discrimination as a worrying issue.

3.4.4. Empowering and mobilising young people

In terms of consultation, the Irish government is currently developing a dialogue strategy as part of a national *Climate Action Plan (2021)* that aims to ensure: 'all voices will be heard in a fair and equal manner'. The plan provides details for taking decisive action to achieve a 51% reduction in overall greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 and setting Ireland on a path to reach net-zero emissions by no later than 2050, as set out in the Climate Act 2021¹⁰. As mentioned above, another important development to support departments, agencies and

¹⁰ An Act to provide for the approval of plans by the Government in relation to climate change for the purpose of pursuing the transition to a climate resilient, biodiversity rich and climate neutral economy by no later than the end of the year 2050.

organisations to improve their practice in listening to children and young people and involving them in consultation was the launch of the second national participation strategy *The Participation Framework* from the Department for Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth (DCEDIY) in 2021. As with the first strategy, it is underpinned by the CRC and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) and commits to: ‘listening to children and young people and giving them a voice in decision-making’ (DCEDIY 2021, p. 17). *ESD to 2030* also emphasises children’s participatory rights and highlights ‘a need for mechanisms to ensure the voices of children ... are heard clearly and consistently in furthering the ESD agenda’ (GOI, 2022, p. 16). It acknowledges that the commitment to collaborate with children in the original national ESD strategy did not progress for ‘a number of reasons’ and reaffirms this as an impending action (DES, 2014, p.18).

Under the priority action of empowering and mobilising young people, there is an objective (*Priority 4.1*, p.24) to recognise young people as critical contributors to sustainability and ensure their involvement in policies and programmes on ESD. The follow-on actions include providing opportunities for student engagement, such as further promoting student councils in primary schools and child and student voices as part of curriculum processes. This section’s language needs to be revised from a child rights perspective. Firstly, if the term young people is intended to include young children (which is not clarified in the strategy), it is unclear why the term ‘child and student voice’ has been introduced in subsequent actions (GOI, p.14). This could imply an omission of young children’s involvement in ESD policies under the first priority, particularly when promoting student councils in primary schools, not primary schools and early childhood settings is being recommended. Concerning ESD, there was a consultation with children from both primary and post-primary schools following the recommendations of *The National Strategy of the Inclusion of Children’s Voice*¹¹ to inform future policy in 2016. The Department of Education (DES), in collaboration with a dedicated Citizen Participation Unit of the Department of Children and Youth Affairs (DCYA) at that time, developed a child-friendly definition of ESD:

Education for Sustainable Development means what you learn in school to make the world a fairer and better place for everyone (DES, 2016, p.2).

¹¹The strategy focuses on the everyday lives of children and young people and the places and spaces in which they are entitled to have a voice in decisions that affect their lives, including in community, education, health and well-being, and legal settings .

During the consultation, it was found that participants had a strong desire to understand their own and other's rights. This highlights the importance of including human rights education in future ESD policy development. It should, however, also be noted that early education participants were not consulted in this initiative. The ambiguity surrounding the extent to which the Irish government values early childhood for ESD promotion warrants a section of its own.

3.5. The limited place of ESD in ECEC policy in Ireland

The previous section has identified a number of areas whereby the early education and care sector has been considered less favourably in state policy. The limited place for the ECEC sector in relation to ESD can also be identified in the *National Strategy for Early Years-First Five (2019-2028)*. This is a whole-of-government strategy to improve the lives of babies, young children and their families. It is a ten-year plan to help make sure all children have positive early experiences and get a great start in life (GOI, 2019). The strategy states that the recommendations of the CRC inform it and link to specific articles in its text. However, as previously highlighted, without the explicit language of articles, child rights can be diluted or misinterpreted (Jerome, 2018; Lundy & Martínez Sainz, 2018; Long, 2019; Nolan, 2020). This is evident in how Article 29 is summarised within the strategy:

Aims of education

Education should develop children's personalities, talents and mental and physical abilities to their fullest potential and develop respect for human rights, for the child's parents, for cultural identity, language, and values. Education should provide children with the tools to live a full and responsible life within society.

Summary of Article 29 of the UNCRC (DCYA, 2019, p.88)

This summary omits the respect for the natural environment despite the government's ongoing expressed commitment to ESD since 2014. These education aims are cited under *Objective 8* of the strategy, which states:

Babies and young children have access to safe, high-quality, developmentally appropriate, integrated ELC (Early Learning and Care) (and school-age childcare), which reflects diversity of need.

(DCYA, 2019, p. 94).

A broader policy context is included under the same objective as:

ELC is also recognised as integral to the achievement of global development in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 2015.

(DCYA, 2019, p.94).

However, there is no reference to ESD promotion under *Objective 8*. The strategy has not provided any clear commitment to the state's duty under Article 29 1 (e), and the following is the only reference to ESD promotion within the 196-page document:

it is important to promote greater use by children of the outdoors and natural environment, including supporting children's learning about the natural world.

(DCYA, 2019, p.81).

While the strategy emphasises the increase of investment in the provision of ECEC, Ireland was placed in the bottom third of OECD countries for affordable childcare in a recent report by UNICEF (Gromada & Richardson, 2021). Taking note of the earlier international guidance of a strong interconnection between investment in early education and building a sustainable society (UNESCO, 2008; Siraj-Blatchford et al., 2010; Engdahl, 2015), this itself paints a dark picture of the value of ECEC as an education sector and its role in ESD promotion at the governmental level. Indeed, this low-level investment also infringes on Article 4 of the CRC, which directs as follows:

States Parties shall undertake all appropriate legislative, administrative, and other measures for the implementation of the rights recognized in the present Convention. With regard to economic, social and cultural rights, States Parties shall undertake such measures to the maximum extent of their available resources and, where needed, within the framework of international co-operation.

(UNCRC, 1989, p.2).

The previous Programme for Government *Our Shared Future* (2020) discussed the government's commitment to the early education and care sector as follows:

... we recognise the value of Early Education and Childcare for children and we will introduce a long-term sustainable funding model that promotes quality, better outcomes for children and makes a career in childcare more attractive.

(PfG, 2020, p. 93).

The current Programme for Government *Securing Ireland's Future (2025)* describes early childhood as:

a time of great opportunity to shape a child's development and build a secure foundation for their future.

(PfG, 2025, p.62).

Particular to ESD promotion within the Programme for Government (2020) are the following:

Continue funding for the Child Care Law Reporting Project. We will publish and implement a successor to Better Outcomes, Brighter Futures: The National Policy Framework for Children and Young People and will develop mechanisms, through a new youth strategy, for the voice and views of young people to be part of decision-making at community, county and national levels.

(PfG, 2020, p.94).

A similar commitment to child participation can be identified in *Securing Our Future* as:

We will continue to support the work of the Ombudsman for Children and ensure that the voices of children and young people are reflected in the development of policies that affect them.

(PfG, 2025, p.62).

The promotion of education on biodiversity is discussed in *Our Shared Future* as follows:

Promote biodiversity initiatives across primary, post-primary and third-level sectors, and ensure that schools, colleges and universities across the country play an active role in providing areas to promote biodiversity.

(PfG, 2020, p.42).

The current Programme of Government (2025) places more emphasis on supporting sustainable living, reducing emissions, and committing to the Sustainable Development Goals (UN, 2015). Surprisingly, while there is also discussion on protecting and promoting our natural heritage, education on biodiversity or, indeed, sustainable development is not addressed within the current Programme of Government (2025).

Looking at this from the perspective of participatory rights, creating a strategy for involving young people in decision-making seems like a positive step. However, there are some issues with using the term 'young people' since it does not clarify how different age groups will be

involved and prioritised. This is somewhat addressed in the 2025 Programme by adding the term ‘children’. Definitions of these terms are required to avoid misrepresentation.

This lack of clarity is similar to the problems with child participation in monitoring SDGs, as pointed out by Nolan (2020). In addition, as already noted in the implementation plan for the second ESD strategy, the omission of the early education sector from biodiversity initiatives is at odds with Article 2 and Article 29 1 (e). This could well be considered an example of a ‘chicken soup’ approach to child rights, as noted by Sloth Nielsen (1996) in Lundy and Martínez Sainz (2018). Lundy and Martínez Sainz argue that despite the international ratification of the CRC, children's educational experiences in every country often fall short of legal requirements. In the case of Article 29 1 (e) in ECEC, while the national policies and strategies use the right language, the reality of young children's education and their right to respect the natural environment tells a different story (Waldron et al., 2020).

3.6. A child rights-based curriculum for learning in, through, about and for Nature for early childhood.

Davies and Elliot (2014) highlight that translating ESD to ECEC is challenging and requires responsive and sensitive pedagogy. They also argue that ESD is wider than environmental education and extends beyond simply exploring nature outdoors. Creating a curriculum for effective, sustainable learning in ECEC requires an approach that includes young children’s perspectives and participation. Learner participation in education is defined as all the ways in which learners engage in practices and dialogue with their educators to create positive learning outcomes and changes (Education Scotland, 2018). It is a fundamental component of ESD that emphasises empowerment and agency for active citizenship, human rights, and societal change (Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; Davis & Elliot, 2014; Phillips, 2014; Hägglund & Johansson, 2014). Consequently, this principle also points to possible synergies between a rights-based education and ESD. A rights pedagogy can be established by recognising and implementing children's rights within education, especially the right to have their voices heard and be involved in decision-making processes. This approach can empower young children, enabling them to engage in meaningful learning experiences and foster a sense of agency and autonomy in shaping their own educational journey (Education Scotland,

2018). As a result, children's enjoyment of their rights and active participation in shaping a sustainable future can be realised.

The UNESCO report (2008) on the role of early education for sustainability emphasises the significance of adequately implementing the CRC as a foundational framework while conceptualising and designing an ESD approach in early childhood. Pramling Samuelson and Kaga (2008) highlight actively listening as a crucial aspect of ESD in considering children's ideas to shape content and learning approaches that promote action for sustainability. In addition, Grindheim, Bakken, Hiis Hauge and Presthus Heggen (2019) call for space for 'subjectification', where learners can come forward with something new. They argue that while early childhood pedagogy has a long tradition of supporting children to gain knowledge and to learn how to participate and socialise, learning to go against the grain and disrupt existing practices and culture is less common. Exactly what will happen in the future about the climate crisis remains unknown, but there is no doubt that what we have been doing to date has contributed to it. For this reason, Grindheim et al. (2019) maintain that now more than ever, our educational spaces need learners to challenge our 'common ways of facilitating thought and action' (p.380). In practical terms, this means moving from learning in, through and about Nature to learning for Nature.

Pramling Samuelsson and Kaga (2008) and Davies and Elliot (2014) argue that both ECEC and ESD pedagogies share a commitment to 'connecting with Nature', experiential learning, curiosity and critical thinking, democracy and participation and the classroom as a community (2014). Several analyses have been done on ESD in the ECEC curriculum. To begin, Jóhannesson, Norðdahl, Óskarsdóttir, Pálsdóttir, and Pétursdóttir (2011) developed a 'curriculum key' to analyse the Icelandic curriculum and possible links to ESD principles. In addition, Ärlmalm-Hagsér and Davies (2014) examined Sweden and Australia's early years' national curricula under the lens of four aspects: 'inclusion of sustainability concepts', 'recognition of human place and environmental stewardship', 'critical thinking for sustainability' and 'reference to children as active agents and participating citizens'. Similarly, Weldemariam et al. (2017) provide a critical cross-national analysis of sustainability concepts within five early childhood curricula from Australia, Sweden,

Norway, England, and the USA. In this study, researchers concentrated on aspects of ‘sustainability presence’, ‘views of the child, human-environment relationship’ and ‘philosophical/theoretical underpinnings on ideas expressed about sustainability’. Unlike Ärlemalm-Hagsér and Davies (2014), who concentrated on the explicit inclusion of sustainability concepts, Weldemariam et al. (2017) examine both the explicit and implicitly embedded concepts.

I will now extend an analysis of this theme by examining (i) Aistear - the national early childhood curriculum framework in Ireland (NCCA, 2009, 2024); (ii) the Aistear/Síolta Practice Guide (2015, 2019) – an updated supporting guide informed by both Aistear and Síolta, the National Quality Framework for Early Childhood (CECDE, 2006); and (iii) documents produced by the national early years’ inspectorate, namely, the Preschool Regulations (2016) and the Quality and Regulatory Framework (QRF) (2018). Aistear (2024, p. 12), originally published in 2009, has now been updated and claims ‘how babies, toddlers and young children should learn through the development of a rights-based, emergent and inquiry-based curriculum’. As highlighted in the policy review section, there is tension surrounding child rights being misinterpreted and diluted when not used explicitly. My analysis will, therefore, also explore this tension under the subheadings of the ESD/ECEC pedagogical synergies mentioned above.

3.6.1. Connecting with Nature

Educational literature suggests that early childhood is a crucial time to cultivate a harmonious connection with Nature. Carson (1956) describes this as laying the groundwork for aligning human activity with Nature. Chawla (1998) and Chawla and Rivkin (2014) build upon this idea, asserting that positive Nature experiences during childhood lead to a lifelong interest in environmental conservation. Exploring Nature freely allows young children to understand the natural changes and rhythms over time, developing a first-hand appreciation for the cycles of life and the elements of Earth that sustain human existence.

The literature also highlights the significance of extended free play and direct sensory experiences in Nature for children's learning about their environment. While books and digital technologies can represent Nature, they cannot fully replicate the depth and detail of

biodiverse encounters that allow children to explore and think in meaningful ways for themselves. A lack of access to the natural world that limits essential developmental foundations under Article 29 1 (e) emphasises the crucial need for learning in Nature to foster rights-based ESD (Chawla, 1998; Chawla & Rivkin, 2014).

Aistear (NCCA, 2024, p. 20) discusses practitioners embracing ‘possibilities in the local environment through a sense of *ómós áite* (value of place) and place-based learning’ and place an emphasis on *dúlra* (nature), natural spaces, provocations, and resources.’ Connecting with the natural environment is consistent in Aistear under the theme of *Exploring and Thinking*, as follows:

Aim 1: Babies, toddlers and young children will learn about and make sense of the world around them.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Recognise their connection to and responsibility for the environment and their community and come to know and respect local people flora and fauna.

(NCCA, 2024, p. 29).

This is furthered as follows:

Aim 3: Babies, toddlers and young children will learn about and make sense of the world around them.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Feel a connection and sense of *ómós áite* (value of place) by being present in *dúlra* (nature) and *súgragh* (play), merging with local heritage in coming to know the environment in a deeper sense through the seasons.

Learn about life on land and life in water through experiencing, discovering, questioning, engaging, investigating and using digital technologies, where developmentally appropriate, and use books to research and extend knowledge about our planet.

(NCCA, 2024, p.29).

While there is an evident recognition for learning to care and respect the planet and its inhabitants, there is no explicit link to the young child’s right to an education that develops a respect for the natural environment under Article 29 1 (e) (NCCA, 2024).

Daily access to the outdoor environment is specified under the Preschool Regulations (2016) and the Quality Framework (QRF) as follows:

Regulation 19 Facilities for Rest and Play

Access to outdoor play

Services who registered a premises **on or after 30 June 2016**, and those who moved premises **on or after 30 June 2016** require a suitable, safe, and secure outdoor space on the premises that is accessible to the children on a daily basis.

For services registered **before 30 June 2016**: Where access to outdoor space is provided on the premises, it is suitable, safe and secure. Where access is provided off the premises, the outdoor space is suitable. Children access the outdoor space on a daily basis unless otherwise advised following a risk assessment by the service.

(TUSLA, 2018, p.49).

The Aistear/Síolta practice guide under the pillar *Creating and Using the Learning Environment* also highlights: ‘the importance of daily outdoor experiences in all-weather types’ (p.145) and describes the natural world: ‘as a foundation for creativity, play and sensory stimulation’ (p.145). Learning resources such as video casts are also provided to support the creation of outdoor areas offering rich early-year experiences for babies and young children, including a connection and love for Nature (NCCA, 2015; Farrell & Daly, 2023). However, while the connection to Nature has been highlighted from a rights-based perspective, access to Nature as an education entitlement framed under Article 29 1 (e) is again missing. Notably, the practice guide is to be updated to align with *Aistear* (2024), allowing hopefully further underpinning of this through a child-rights lens.

Connecting with and/or appreciating Nature and caring for others is also implied under the *Well-being* theme of Aistear, as follows:

Aim 3: Babies, toddlers and young children will be creative, spiritual and compassionate.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Enhance their spirituality through nurturing their sense of *ionadh* (wonder), awe, stillness and gratitude and through respecting ethnicity, culture, traditions, festivals, rituals and *dúlra* (nature).

(NCCA, 2024, p.23).

It also vaguely features under the *Communicating* theme:

Aim 3: Babies, toddlers and young children will broaden their understanding of the world by making sense of their world through emergent literacy and numeracy experiences.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Experience an inclusive, print-rich environment to promote emergent literacy and numeracy and learn the value of books and digital technologies, where developmentally appropriate, as a source of information to learn about the world.

(NCCA, 2024, p. 27).

And more explicitly, under the theme of *Identity and Belonging*:

Aim 2: Babies, toddlers and young children will have a sense of group identity with *cairdre* (friends), peers, educators, their family and community.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

See themselves as part of the community by coming to know the features and people of the locality, to know their responsibility to care for and look after the environment and know *meitheal* (community spirit of coming together) in their lives.

(NCCA, 2024, p. 25).

Portraying young children as responsible for caring for the planet can be considered ethically problematic (Davies, 2014). Instead, it is necessary to present the complexities of sustainability in a way that allows children to build their capacities to form and express their views and take meaningful action rather than burdening them with a problem they are solely responsible for (Pramling Samuelsson, 2011; Spiteri, 2021). Weldemariam et al. (2017) argue for a more inclusive approach that explicitly considers the connection with Nature and sustainable living, treating humans, non-human beings, and other species as equal members of a shared world. This perspective emphasises the importance of promoting environmental care and action while also recognising all living beings' interconnectedness and shared responsibility for the planet's well-being. This can be implicitly identified within the updated *Aistear*'s (NCCA, 2024, p. 9) vision of ensuring that all young children 'can thrive and

flourish and contribute to a more sustainable world by caring for themselves, others and the environment’.

3.6.2. *Experiential learning*

Luff (2018) describes experiential learning in early childhood as fundamental for a child to process and construct their own ideas. Dewey and Bruner also highlight the significance of building knowledge in a social and cultural context, which provides opportunities for young children to develop new insights and concepts to support their learning (Follari, 2011). In the context of ESD for young children, this involves extending the learning environment to include experiences in Nature to fulfil the stipulations of Article 29 1 (e) (Davies, 2015). Gilbert, Fuller, Palmer and Rose (2014) and Sundberg and Ottander (2014) stress the importance of enabling environments and supportive interactions that ignite curiosity in young children. These factors significantly influence their present and future beliefs, values and behaviours, particularly regarding respect for Nature and sustainable living. Linking these ecological concepts more explicitly with the theme of *Exploring and Thinking* in Aistear demonstrates how providing experiential Nature-based learning opportunities for young children can promote meaningful engagement to foster a deeper sense of care and responsibility towards the environment as I have highlighted in the previous section (NCCA, 2024).

Providing opportunities for experiential learning is discussed in the Aistear/Síolta (2015, 2019) practice guide as follows: ‘sensory exploration to help babies develop ideas about the world’ (p.45): ‘experience the effect of water on different materials, sand, stones, soil and ice’ (p.47) or: ‘noting the life-cycle of a frog through regular visits to the nearby pond’ (p.51). This emphasis on inquiry-based learning demonstrates how Aistear is consistent with ESD principles (Luff, 2018; Farrell & Daly, 2023; NCCA, 2024).

Additionally, Davies (2015) and Luff (2018) highlight the significance of recognising and building on children's interests to provide a democratic physical and social environment where young children can actively explore, experiment, and critically engage with sustainability questions relevant to their daily lives. By focusing on children's own interests as holistic starting points for ESD, educators can create meaningful learning experiences that

allow children to understand and address sustainability issues within their own context. Rather than overwhelming young children with complex and often daunting global sustainable issues, they can gradually engage with relevant aspects in a way that respects their rights to enjoy their education while connecting it to real-life moments (Weldemariam et al., 2017; Lundy & Martínez Sainz, 2018).

3.6.3. *Curiosity and critical thinking*

According to Dewey, curiosity and critical thought are most effective when initiated by the young child and supported by skilled adults through questioning and probing (Follari, 2011). This process allows children to construct meaning actively. They develop the necessary dispositions to address current climate challenges as they move from initial curiosity about the physical environment to sustained and systematic problem-solving (Luff, 2018). The ‘in’, ‘through’, and ‘about’ aspects of learning are grounded in constructivist theory. The ‘for’ aspect offers the potential for a transformative model to empower learners to actively shape their understanding and take meaningful action for a sustainable future (Burns, Diamond-Vaught & Bauman, 2015).

Learning ‘in’, ‘through’, and ‘about’ Nature without incorporating learning ‘for’ Nature may lead to fear or anxiety in young children, particularly given the stark reality surrounding the lack of action (Croft, 2017). The ‘for’ aspect provides opportunities for problem-solving and positive action, allowing children to take meaningful steps towards addressing environmental challenges. Combining all four elements, ‘in’, ‘through’, ‘about’, and ‘for’, supports the perspective that humans need to work interdependently with Nature to ensure a sustainable future (Cutter-MacKenzie et al., 2014; Davies, 2009, 2014, 2015; Elliot, 2014). Learning ‘for’ Nature is best linked to the following aims and learning goals of the *Exploring and Thinking* theme of Aistear:

Aim 2: Babies, toddlers and young children will develop and use skills and strategies for observing, questioning, investigating, understanding, negotiating and problem-solving and come to see themselves as explorers and thinkers.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Make connections and associations between new learning and what they already know, having the time and space to explore and develop theories about how the world works.

Explore a variety of resources, provocations, open-ended and natural materials, as well as digital technologies where developmentally appropriate, to investigate, to research and to find out about the world around them.

Collaborate and play with others to share interests, to learn about the past, the present and the future, to solve problems, to be creative and to think logically.

(NCCA, 2024, p. 29).

Aim 4: Babies, toddlers and young children will have positive attitudes towards learning and develop dispositions like independence, curiosity, *spraíúlacht* (playfulness), perseverance, resilience, *muinín* (confidence), resourcefulness and risk-taking.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Demonstrate growing *muinín* (confidence) in being able to do things for themselves, seeing themselves as agentic learners who are open to new ideas and experiences.

Develop higher-order thinking skills such as problem-solving, predicting, analysing, questioning and justifying through *súgradh* (play) and playful explorations.

Think together to build meaning and understanding as well as being *fiosrach* (curious) about how to use letters, words, sentences, numbers, signs, pictures, colour and shapes to give and record information, to describe and to make sense of their own and others' experiences through play and hands-on experiences.

(NCCA, 2024, p. 29).

In addition, the Aistear/Síolta Guide provides suggestions for resources to include open-ended loose parts, recyclables and natural materials and for the inclusion of a water-saving facility during outdoor play as well as opportunities to plant and harvest a setting's own produce (NCCA, 2015, 2019; Farrell & Daly, 2023).

3.6.4. *Democracy and participation*

A fourth principle of ESD that relates to the 'learning for' element of Article 29 1 (e) is the young child's agency to act as a contributing social citizen and rights holder both locally and globally (Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; Davis & Elliot, 2014; Phillips, 2014; Hägglund & Johansson, 2014). Democracy and participation is put forward in Aistear (2024) as portraying babies, toddlers and young children to be competent, confident and agentic global citizens:

‘Being agentic means they have voice and influence and that they can make choices about and in their learning... They can experience democracy by having their voice heard and respected by educators who support active participation’

(NCCA, 2024, p. 16).

It can also be identified to varying degrees under all four themes in Aistear and the Aistear/Síolta practice guide as follows:

Well-being

Aim 1: Babies, toddlers and young children will be strong psychologically and socially.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Be empowered to communicate their feelings and emotions to make sense of life experiences, to cope with challenges and to learn to co-regulate and self-regulate.

Aim 4: Babies, toddlers and young children will be agentic global citizens and have positive outlooks on learning and on life.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Demonstrate agency and express choices, preferences and make decisions for themselves and their communities whilst respecting diversity, equity and inclusion.

Explore and identify their place in the world, and be empowered to live sustainably as agentic, respectful, caring and compassionate global citizens with rights and emerging responsibilities.

(NCCA, 2024, p. 23).

Identity and Belonging

Aim 3: Babies, toddlers and young children will express their rights and will be supported to develop an understanding and regard for the identity, rights and views of others.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Know there is a space where they can be at ease, communicate their views and feel confident that their voice, in their varying forms, is heard and responded to in all matters affecting them.

Develop a sense of social justice and fairness, be aware of and respect their own and others' needs, rights and feelings while also developing the skills of co-operation, responsibility, negotiation, problem-solving and conflict resolution.

(NCCA, 2024, p. 25).

Communicating

Aim 1: Babies, toddlers and young children will use multiple ways of communicating.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Be agentic communicators who influence and initiate interactions, *cómhra* (conversations) and decisions.

Share, recognise, understand, interpret and respond to the many ways humans communicate including but not limited to vocalisations, facial expressions, gestures, body language and Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC).

Combine different communication strategies to express choices, ideas, feelings and opinions, to listen and to learn to respect the choices, ideas, feelings and opinions of others.

(NCCA, 2024, p. 27).

Exploring and Thinking

Aim 3: Babies, toddlers and young children will have positive attitudes towards learning and develop dispositions like independence, curiosity, *spraíúlacht* (playfulness), perseverance, resilience, *muinín* (confidence), resourcefulness and risk-taking.

Through nurturing relationships within a supportive environment, babies, toddlers and young children will:

Demonstrate growing *muinín* (confidence) in being able to do things for themselves, seeing themselves as agentic learners who are open to new ideas and experiences.

Develop higher-order thinking skills such as problem-solving, predicting, analysing, questioning and justifying through *súgradh* (play) and playful explorations.

Think together to build meaning and understanding as well as being *fiosrach* (curious) about how to use letters, words, sentences, numbers, signs, pictures, colour and shapes to give and record information, to describe and to make sense of their own and others' experiences through play and hands-on experiences.

(NCCA, 2024, p. 29).

The text in all four themes emphasises supporting children to make their own decisions and choices in their learning. This strong underpinning of democratic education and ensuring children feel listened and respectfully responded to points to ample opportunity for furthering rights pedagogy in practice (Moss, 2016; Robson, 2016; Clark, 2017; 2020; Jerome, 2018; Lyndon et al., 2019). In addition, this is further supported in the Aistear/Síolta practice guide, which references Articles 3 and 12 of the CRC as ‘especially relevant for early childhood’ (NCCA, 2015, p. 35).

Involving children in decisions that affect them is further implied in: ‘having their opinions and choices respected, viewing them as citizens with rights and responsibilities free from any form of discrimination’ (NCCA, 2015, p. 35). The practice guide describes the ECEC practitioner’s ‘interpretation’ of the ‘young child’s rights as having important implications for the curriculum’ (NCCA, 2015, p. 35) and a ‘recognition of the child’s individuality, strengths, rights and needs as citizens are central and contribute to a quality early childhood experience where an understanding of equality, rights and responsibilities is promoted’ (NCCA, 2015, p.75). However, the deficit in this guidance lies in how children’s rights are interpreted. The CRC has a total of 54 articles, not just two. As all rights are interrelated and interconnected, all 54 articles are relevant for early childhood and all stages of childhood (Long, 2019; Mitchell et al., 2023). This point will hopefully be addressed as the practice guide is currently being updated.

Furthermore, while Aistear has provided the young child with a curricular entitlement to participation, the use of the terminology ‘voice’ and ‘choice’ does not recognise the full complexity of the CRC and what that means for participative decision-making (Jerome et al., 2015; Long, 2019; Mitchell et al., 2023). For example, using the word ‘voice’ could inadvertently exclude nonverbal participation. Notably, this point has been addressed well in the update with emphasis now placed on communication through multimodal forms as described under the aims of the *Communicating* theme above (NCCA, 2024). Equally, how a child’s ‘choice’ is determined, for example, whether it is the adult or the child deciding what there is to choose, will limit what is meant by children fully participating in their learning environments (DCEDIY, 2021).

3.6.5. *The classroom as a community*

McDonald (2015) claims that ‘communitarian citizenship learning’, alongside a ‘living curriculum’ - a curriculum that has the ability to change with the needs of the learners and circumstances, supports the young child's understanding of environmental sustainability. Communitarian citizenship learning refers to the idea that there should be a connection between an individual and their wider community that values learning to work together for the greater good. This is done through modelling processes and planning experiences that provoke thought and learning about children’s daily lives and community (the ECEC setting). Underpinned by Bruner’s socio-cultural theory of learning and supported by the democratic and dialogic nature of rights pedagogy, a communitarian approach can authentically engage the young child’s capacity as a contributing social actor (Bruner, 1961, 1996; McDonald, 2015). Phillips (2014) and Cutter-MacKenzie et al. (2014, 2019) argue that purposeful group action toward citizenship, underpinned by a sense of community responsibility, can cultivate a transformational shift in promoting the young child’s social agency. The update described in the previous section clearly emphasises young children’s agency and their global citizen role. This approach can also be linked to some of the aims and learning goals of the *Well-being, Identity and Belonging* and *Exploring and Thinking* themes in Aistear above that emphasise children’s overall contributing social agency. Notably, the theme of *Identity and Belonging* highlights the necessity of supporting a sense of group identity, being part of the community and learning about *meitheal* (community spirit of coming together) in their lives (NCCA, 2024, p.25).

Phillips (2014), Mackey (2014), Robson (2016) and Martínez Sainz (2018) claim that although young children have restricted access to civic institutions and political participation in the broader sense, opportunities to engage in active communitarian citizenship can develop capacities to be local and global community contributors through transformative, empowering and meaningful pedagogy. However, there is no explicit reference in Aistear to the young child’s right to know about social and environmental issues and to participate in action and possible solutions (Mackey, 2014). Therefore, while local context is essential in supporting young children’s agency, Mackey (2014) contends that a shift to rights pedagogy is limited if there is no explicit acknowledgement of its legal imperative within the curriculum.

Additionally, while Aistear places emphasis on a sense of *ómós áite* (value of place), the overall concept needed further discussion in its role under Article 29 1 (e). For example, Ross and Mannion (2012) underline the significance of place or dwelling in curriculum making and its impact on the individual learner. They argue that learning is an attunement process, where meanings are derived from individuals' relationships and connections with the world around them. These relationships extend beyond the social sphere and include connections with Nature, materials, and the context of a specific place. The Maori view also highlights the importance of understanding relationships between people and Nature (Vincent-Snow, 2017). Lived embodied experiences in places offer profound meanings to individuals, fostering a deeper sense of belonging and connection to the world they inhabit by embracing the significance of place and the relationships it entails. From this perspective, a 'sense of place' is when a learner can envelop their genetic sense of being part of Nature and meaningfully and actively inhabit the natural environment in harmony with all other species in that place. This also relates to the post-humanist philosophy of living in a common world and links to Davies's (2014) ecocentric lens of rights pedagogy. Weldemariam et al. (2017) argue that there is a need to widen the scope of ESD with different perspectives that shift sustainability in ECEC beyond anthropocentrism.¹² That said, engaging with this definition of a 'sense of place' requires regular access to places that are bountiful with Nature as the starting point.

3.7. International curricula and legislation

Te Whāriki, which is the bicultural early childhood curriculum of Aotearoa/New Zealand influenced by Maori knowledge, supports the young child's connection to and interdependence with the land (Vincent-Snow, 2017). Comparatively, Aistear can be likened to Te Whāriki in how it has positioned pro-environmental learning (Farrell & Daly, 2023). It also has no explicit mandatory links to sustainability but rather provides implicit aspirational guidance to ECEC practitioners to include a holistic ESD approach in their curricula (Croft, 2017; Weldemariam et al., 2017). Notably, New Zealand has recently established an 'Enviro-kindy' movement, a subset of Enviro-schools¹³ for early years settings. As highlighted in the policy review section, its equivalent programme in Ireland, Green Schools, has yet to roll out a specific programme for the early years sector.

¹² Anthropocentrism means regarding humankind as the central or most important element of existence.

¹³ Enviro-schools is an environmental action-based programme where settings can commit to a long-term sustainability journey.

The curricula frameworks from the USA and England do not explicitly mention sustainability. However, Weldemariam et al. (2017) identified implicit references in both frameworks that still require the educator or setting to use their own understanding and value of sustainable living to promote ESD. This indicates that while sustainability might not be directly addressed, elements within the curricula can be interpreted to incorporate sustainable practices. Moreover, the study by Weldemariam et al. (2017) also highlighted that environmental sustainability was more visibly addressed in early childhood curricula than sustainability's social-cultural and economic dimensions. This suggests that while environmental aspects were more prominent, other crucial dimensions of sustainability, such as social and economic considerations, might be overlooked or given less emphasis. Their findings identify Australia and Norway as the two countries addressing sustainability more explicitly. For example, the Australian Early Years Learning Framework, *Belonging, Being and Becoming*, describes multiple pillars of sustainability and a need to adopt a broader definition that:

helps to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

(AGDE, 2022, p.18).

Further to this is an emphasis placed on the interdependent relationship between child and Nature where ECEC practitioners are encouraged to support children:

to develop appreciation of the natural world, understand our impact on the natural world, and the interdependence between people, animals, plants, lands and waters.

(AGDE, 2022, p.18).

Likewise, the Australian curriculum recognises the culture and traditions of its Aboriginal Indigenous people in residing harmoniously with Nature (AGDE, 2022). It also emphasises the type of 'sense of place' learning described in the previous section (3.6.5.) that encourages a more common world philosophy of living respectfully with non-human species as well (Weldemariam et al., 2017). In addition, the curriculum recognises that ESD must go beyond Nature and that young children must be supported to engage with concepts such as 'social justice, fairness, sharing, democracy and citizenship' (AGDE, 2022, p.18). The National

Quality Standard (NQS) (ACECQA, 2023)¹⁴ for Australia makes explicit reference to sustainable practices as a requirement for accreditation as follows:

Element 3.2.3 Environmentally Responsible

The service cares for the environment and supports children to become environmentally responsible.

(ACECQA, 2023, p. 208).

Significantly, the Australian early years framework also emphasises the importance of ‘intentional teaching’ or learning with intentionality. This is best described as when an educator extends learning using intentional strategies such as asking questions and holistically introducing new ideas. Broström, Johansson, Sandberg, and Frøkjær (2014) argue that ‘intentional teaching’ is controversial in contemporary early years practice due to historical associations with rote learning and adult instruction. This has led to a preference for uninterrupted learning through free play. Elliot and Davies (2009) suggest that this view has contributed to the reluctance of some early childhood education practitioners to embrace ESD pedagogy fully. However, while learning in and through Nature is foundational for developing sensitivity towards the natural world, scholars such as Moore et al. (2014), Elliott (2014), and Ernst et al. (2021) recognise that it is not enough to merely develop conceptions of the environment and understanding of sustainability issues. Instead, what is also required is intentional science teaching which is proposed by Sundberg and Ottander (2014) as also foundational for empowering young children to engage with ESD principles. They advocate for a change in views on science, Nature, and pedagogy, calling for a shift towards science inquiry in early childhood education practice. This intentional and inquiry-based approach to teaching science can help cultivate a deeper connection with Nature and foster a sense of agency and responsibility in young learners towards environmental and sustainability issues.

From an Irish perspective, there is a notable correlation between ‘intentional teaching’ and the emphasis on fostering an inquiry-based emergent curriculum approach within the Aistear/Síolta Practice Guide (NCCA, 2015, 2019). However, its effectiveness in promoting democratic pedagogy depends on how it is considered and conceptualised in practice. If educators embrace and implement inquiry-based learning in a way that values children's

¹⁴ The National Quality Standard (NQS) (ACECQA, 2023) is the Australian equivalent to Ireland’s national early years’ quality inspectorate

voices, agency, and active participation, it can create a conducive environment for democratic pedagogy. This approach allows children to explore their interests, ask questions, and engage in meaningful learning experiences that promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills. On the other hand, if inquiry-based pedagogy is interpreted in a more controlled or directive manner, it may not fully support democratic principles. Educators must ensure that inquiry-based learning aligns with democratic values, empowering children as active participants in their learning journey and fostering a sense of ownership over their education. By doing so, early childhood education can play a crucial role in cultivating democratic citizenship from an early age discussed in the Norwegian curriculum as:

The kindergarten has to promote democracy, diversity, mutual respect, equality, sustainable development, life skills and health.

(Ministry of Education and Research, 2017, p.7).

In addition, the Norwegian curriculum also states that:

The kindergarten has an important task to promote values, attitudes and practices for more sustainable societies the kindergarten shall contribute to giving children an understanding that [any] actions have consequences in future.

(Ministry of Education and Research, 2017, p.10-11).

Sweden also updated their early years' curriculum in 2018 to be more explicit about the democratic forms that education should undertake:

Education should be undertaken in democratic forms and lay the foundation for a growing interest and responsibility among children for active participation in civic life and for sustainable development – not only economic, but also social and environmental. Both long-term and global future perspectives should be made explicit in education.

(Curriculum for the Preschool—Lpfö 18, 2019., p.5).

This is furthered by the goals of the curriculum as follows:

The preschool should provide each child with the conditions to develop

- respect and understanding of the equal value of all people and human rights, and
- a growing responsibility for and interest in sustainable development and active participation in society.

(Curriculum for the Preschool—Lpfö 18, 2019., p.13).

Scotland has made significant strides in integrating children's rights and ESD by incorporating learning for sustainability as an entitlement for all learners within their national curriculum framework, *Curriculum for Excellence*¹⁵ (Education Scotland, 2019). The Scottish national *Learning for Sustainability Action Plan* aims to adopt a holistic ESD approach that involves entire schools and their local communities (Education, Scotland, 2019). The approach also encompasses critical concepts such as global citizenship, sustainable development education, and outdoor learning to create transformative learning experiences. By engaging students in learning experiences that promote a deeper understanding of sustainability, global interconnectedness, and environmental stewardship, Scotland is fostering a generation of well-equipped learners to contribute positively to the well-being of local and international communities. The emphasis on whole-school and community involvement also underscores the importance of collaboration and partnership among various stakeholders, including educators, students, parents, and community members. This collective effort ensures that sustainability principles are embedded in multiple aspects of the educational journey, reinforcing the commitment to fostering environmentally and socially responsible citizens. Such an approach more readily aligns with the ripple effect of local to the global context and ESD's social, political and cultural dimensions (Duhn, 2012). Scotland's approach to learning for sustainability demonstrates how educational policies and practices can be aligned to promote rights-based transformative learning experiences and contribute to developing a more sustainable and just society.

Integrating human rights principles, including those outlined in the CRC, into the curriculum provides a solid legal framework to protect and fulfil children's rights. This acknowledgement reinforces the importance of promoting children's rights and can empower educators to advocate for resources where all children's rights are respected and upheld. The above analysis demonstrates that learning to care for Nature and the potential to develop it to synergise with ESD principles is evident in the national curriculum framework Aistear (French & McKenna, 2022). Skehill and Daly (2023, p. 192-193) argue that Aistear is 'very innovative in its focus on active citizenship, caring for the environment, and the creation of a fairer, more socially just and sustainable environment'. However, without the explicit reference to being entitled to an ESD approach under Article 29 1 (e), its promotion remains dependent

¹⁵ The Curriculum for Excellence or CfE is the national curriculum of Scotland for children and young people from the ages of 3-18.

on practitioners' interpretation and commitment to sustainability. (Sjoberg & Schreiner, 2006; Sageidet; 2014; Inoue, O'Gorman and Davies, 2016, Collins & Garrity: 2023). Additionally, by embracing the significance of a 'sense of place' and the relationships it entails, educators can create more meaningful and relevant learning experiences that honour learners' diverse perspectives and connections with their environment.

3.8. The updated curriculum framework

French and McKenna (2022) argued for an updating of Aistear, where sustainability is interwoven throughout and explicit emphasis is placed on the agentic role of young children. Skehill and Daly (2023) describe three phases of the first consultation for updating Aistear: a literature review focusing on the framework's themes (French & McKenna, 2022), consultation with young children (O'Toole, Walsh, Kerrins, Doherty, Forde, Kelleher, McCartney, Stafford, Stokes, Matson & Mooney, 2023) and engagement with stakeholders (NCCA, 2023). The importance of embedding SDGs, child rights and citizenship and access to Nature were highlighted as key areas for ESD (NCCA, 2023). The consultation also highlighted ECEC's pedagogical advantages and the importance of creating time and space for young children to develop relationships with each other and their local environment, as foundational for implementing ESD in practice. From the previous sections, it is evident that significant progress has been made towards positioning children as contributing social agents with rights and the importance of connecting with Nature and developing a respect for it and others in it. However, sustainability as a whole concept that includes a political pillar is not adequately discussed (UNESCO, 2010; Weldemariam et al., 2017; Skehill & Daly, 2023). The update does place value on respecting children's participation; however, recognising that young children already have their own Nature expertise and respecting that as a means to support authentic ESD learning is missed. This would have further strengthened the overall discussion on the importance of child agency, citizenship and child rights, which have been identified as underpinnings for the update. If not addressed, this would result in a missed opportunity to further young children's enjoyment of Article 29 1 (e). Indeed, Article 29 1 (e) itself is not explicitly referenced which is at odds with claiming a framework to be both rights-informed and adhering to rights-based processes in creating and updating it (Farrell & Daly, 2023; O'Toole et al., 2023).

In this chapter, I sought to examine policy and curriculum in support of a child rights approach for ESD in early childhood. My analysis demonstrates that despite significant

progress internationally, an ambiguity surrounding the value of ECEC for ESD promotion can be identified in Irish policy. The newly updated ECEC curriculum framework is underdeveloped about some key sustainable concepts. Subsequently, while synergies with ESD can be pinpointed within the framework's aims and learning goals, much more explicit integration of child rights is needed to ensure a full realisation of education and participatory rights under Article 29 1 (e). The following chapter provides a review of current ESD research in ECEC.

Chapter 4: Literature Review: Learning in, through, about and for Nature under Article 29 1 (e).

4.1. Introduction

This chapter examines the education and research literature relevant to a child rights-based ESD approach in ECEC. The first section analyses how Nature learning and young children as learners have been considered in early childhood pedagogies. I also examine the synergies between ESD and ECEC to identify early educational theorists' recognition of learning for sustainability. The second section explores ESD in early childhood research and the complexities surrounding sustainability as a concept. This involves a discussion of its various definitions and learning approaches, including an analysis of collaborative, participatory projects. The third section discusses the ECEC practitioner's duty-bearer role and how the perceived complexities of sustainability can act as a barrier to effective ESD implementation in early childhood. It also analyses the role of attitudes towards sustainability and the existing skillset of the ECEC practitioner in promoting Article 29 1 (e) and overall rights pedagogy in early childhood. Transformative research studies are reviewed in the final section, suggesting changes in initial teacher training programmes, including specific content on leadership skills for effective sustainability. I conclude with a discussion on transformative learning to provide a working definition for the thesis.

4.2. Nature learning and how children as learners are viewed in early education theory.

In the sixteenth century, early education aimed to instil values of hard work and strong moral character based on religious beliefs and trade skills for future adulthood. Learning in Nature was highly valued within the Global North for fostering children's growth (Follari, 2011). Moving towards the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, early childhood theorists like Rousseau, Pestalozzi, Owens, and Froebel emphasised active learning and hands-on experiences in the natural environment. Froebel likened young children to tender seedlings and saw early years teachers as caring gardeners, nurturing a harmonious learning environment rather than emphasising academic instruction (Follari, 2011). Froebel's idea of 'kindergarten' established a conceptual relationship between Nature and early education, influencing much of Western ECEC philosophy (Duhn, 2012; Urban, 2016).

Throughout the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, this promotion of Nature as a learning environment continued. Hall advocated for children to spend more time outdoors, as the

classroom environment was seen to cause anxiety and push them to grow prematurely (Follari, 2011). From the early 1900s to the mid-century, there was a surge of outdoor play and open-air nurseries in the United Kingdom, including those established by the McMillan sisters in Peckham in 1914 and the Chelsea Open Air School supported by Susan Isaacs in 1928 (Barratt, Barratt-Hacking, & Black, 2014).

4.3. The developmental view

While recognising Nature as a site for active and first-hand experiential learning for the young child remained steady as early education theories grew, the developmental theories of educational thinkers such as Dewey (1859 -1952), Piaget (1896-1980), Vygotsky (1986-1934) and Bruner (1915-2016), were also highly influential in emerging early childhood learning pedagogies (Follari, 2011; Zanatta & Long, 2021). Jerome (2018) points out that how we view children as learners greatly influences our teaching practices in response to the changing world. In early education, Penn (2008) claims that young children's learning is often viewed through a developmental lens. In particular, Piaget's theory features heavily in contemporary child development studies. Penn (2008) points out that versions of his theories remain foundational for the developmental image of the young child. Piaget focused on how children acquired logic and knowledge at specific stages, which needed to be adequately developed before proceeding to the next for effective learning (Follari, 2011). He also challenged the prevailing didactic teaching style by advocating for children to take charge of their thinking process.

Piaget emphasised the importance of a well-resourced classroom where children could experiment and explore how things worked, guided by the teacher. This theoretical support for learning through play was highly influential in early education. According to Piaget's approach, children develop their conceptual ideas or schemas through hands-on experiences. These ideas were continually redefined and reconceptualised over time, allowing children to progress at their own pace (Penn, 2008; Follari, 2011). Acknowledging that children learn at their own pace with their unique ideas is also a fundamental aspect of rights-based education (Clark, 2020). However, it is important to note that Piaget's dataset was limited to observations from his own children and was presented based on a generalised 'typical child'.

which does not exist (Pramling Samuelsson, 2011). Both Penn (2008) and Pramling Samuelsson (2011) argue that Piaget overlooked the significance of context and relationships in shaping individual children's development. Instead, he focused on overarching epistemological theories of how and when knowledge is acquired by children in general. The demands of their times significantly influenced educational theorists, and Piaget's developmental theories were instrumental in advancing an understanding of logical thinking. For example, they influenced both Vygotsky's (Abtahi, 2017) theory of the 'More Knowledgeable Other' (MKO) and Bruner's (1960) 'community of learning', identifying the essential role of adults in supporting education that values children's interests and individual learning pace.

4.4. The democratic view

As discussed in the previous policy chapter, education is tasked with making necessary changes to address this crisis and promote sustainable development (UNDP, 2015). This calls for a re-evaluation of education and an overall shift towards rights-based pedagogy to make it more democratic (Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; Davies, 2009, 2014, 2015; Pramling-Samuelsson, 2011; Ernst et al., 2021). Boyd (2018) argues that while traditional developmental theories often imply a passive learning stance of sitting, listening, and responding, there is at least some recognition of children's potential to co-construct their learning and development. Thus, the idea of viewing young children as critical agents of change is not limited to contemporary perspectives but can be traced back to the pedagogies of influential figures in early education. Both Montessori (1870-1952) and Steiner (1861-1925) supported the development of caring, compassionate critical thinkers. They envisioned independent, capable, and active children, not merely passive recipients of information (Pramling Samuelsson, 2011; Boyd, 2018).

ESD is rooted in principles of critical inquiry, empowerment, participation, democratic decision-making, and taking action to support sustainable living (Davies, 2009, 2015). In the context of ESD, Edwards (2015) emphasises that how children are viewed within the educational system and society at large impacts their ability to become ecologically engaged individuals. Montessori (1946/1947) echoed this sentiment, describing education as a radical

means to transform society. She cautioned against considering the child as subordinate or weak but as relatively robust, with their own potential to problem solve and think critically.

Dewey (1859-1952) also contributed to the foundation of a democratic view of education. Luff (2018) identifies five essential elements of ESD rooted in Deweyan theory, which were used as subheadings in the curriculum analysis section 3.6 of the previous chapter. These elements include *experiential learning, fostering curiosity and critical thinking, experiencing Nature, promoting democracy and participation in the classroom, and treating the classroom as a community*. Dewey emphasised positive growth and advocated for a learning environment that allowed young children to reconstruct and apply their own theories. His concept of reflective thought as a meaning-making process aligns with the ESD principle of critical inquiry, enabling learners to discuss issues and take action. This perspective is particularly relevant to the young child's learning connections as a starting point for rights-respecting ESD (Davies, 2015; Boyd, 2018; Luff, 2018).

4.5. Other synergies for rights-based ESD in early childhood theory

Both Steiner and Montessori emphasised the young child's connection with Nature and advocated for an 'unhurried approach' to education without imposing milestones or undue assessments (Boyd, 2018). Steiner described the child as a whole, perceiving everything, including their surroundings, as interconnected - part of Nature itself (Steiner, 1924). This aligns with the post-humanistic common world's perspective, nurturing the idea that young children belong to and are interrelated with Nature. Common worlds take account of children's relations with all the others in their worlds – including the more-than-human others (Shava, 2013; Barrable, 2019; Ernst et al., 2021). He integrated sustainable living into daily activities such as communal cooking, gardening, and laundry, fostering sustainable thinking through practices like harvesting only what is necessary, recycling, reusing, regenerating, and minimising waste (Boyd, 2018).

Montessori also viewed practical life learning experiences as essential values of humanity (Montessori, 2013). In her prepared learning environment, the garden played a vital role, and experiences in Nature were recognised as nourishing the 'absorbent mind' of the young child.

The Montessori directrice (teacher) was instructed to follow the child's thoughts and questions and be wary not to categorise them as sensitive or complex topics. Instead, they were encouraged to meet the child's inquiries and respond to them intellectually and honestly, akin to Bruner's approach (Bruner, 1961; Montessori, 2013). Korczak, a humanitarian child pedagogue, also stressed the importance of allowing young children to view the world through various lenses. This perspective remains relevant today, especially in the context of the climate emergency that surrounds young children. It is crucial for supportive adults to sensitively help children construct meaning from such experiences, as they may otherwise potentially lead to upset or anxiety (Siraj-Blatchford et al., 2010; Davies & Elliot, 2014; Duhn, 2012).

The purpose of this section was to highlight the role of Nature as a learning companion for young children in early education thinking. In addition, I also examined how children are viewed as learners and its relevance to rights-based education. I have identified a line of theoretical thought between early education and ESD pedagogies from the earliest theorists of the sixteenth century to the modern day. This body of theory underscores the pedagogical advantages within ECEC for realising Article 29 1 (e) (Pramling-Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; Siraj-Blatchford et al., 2010; Pramling-Samuelsson, 2011; Davies & Elliot, 2014).

4.6. Varying names for education for sustainable development.

Research relevant to Article 29 1 (e) falls under environmental education, education for sustainability, and education for sustainable development. The terms used vary across countries, with Europe using 'education for sustainable development (ESD),' Japan and the United States using 'environmental education (EE),' and Australia and New Zealand adopting 'education for sustainability (EfS)' (Innoue, O'Gorman & Davies, 2016). A newer subfield called 'early childhood education for sustainability (ECEfS)' has emerged. This diversity illustrates that sustainability is a complex concept understood differently by governments, researchers, and the general public, as well as across regions and nations. Thus, it is crucial to examine the term 'sustainability' itself and the role of education in its development.

4.7. Defining sustainability in education

The concept of sustainability is dynamic and value-laden, with various interpretations. ESD should be seen as an ongoing learning process rather than a fixed outcome. It is essential to

recognise the contextual nature of ESD due to the diverse sustainability concerns in developing and developed countries (Pramling-Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; Siraj-Blatchford et al., 2010; Pramling-Samuelsson, 2011). For example, in developing countries, ESD is more oriented towards supporting and empowering families and communities to address basic needs like sanitation, nutrition, healthcare, and protection. In contrast, policy and practice in developed countries are more likely to emphasise ESD regarding curriculum content, teacher education, and best practices in educational settings, an approach which nonetheless neglects the ongoing existence of poverty here in Ireland for example. It is, therefore, essential not to assume that every person in developed countries is enjoying equal human rights (CRA, 2021, 2022).

The Brundtland Commission Report, *Our Common Future* (1987), commissioned by the United Nations, defines sustainable development as meeting the present needs without compromising future generations' ability to meet them. The United Nations Millennium Declaration (UNMD) (2000) emphasises the importance of prudence, ensuring that we meet the current generation's basic human needs in a way that does not harm the planet's life-sustaining systems for future generations. This illustrates that sustainability encompasses multiple generations (Daly, 2023), with both local and global perspectives, and requires individual involvement and responsibility (Earth Charter, 2000; Pramling-Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008).

4.8. Approaches to ESD in early childhood education

As described in the previous policy section 3.2, the UNESCO report *Educating for a Sustainable Future* (1997) asserts that education is humanity's most powerful tool for sustainable development. This assertion was reinforced during the United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (UNDESD) from 2005 to 2014. The current United Nations Sustainable Development Agenda (2015-2030) maintains a solid commitment to education for sustainable development, as exemplified in Education Goal Target 4.7:

By 2030, ensure all learners acquire knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including among others through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development. (UNDP, 2015, p.17).

Hedelfalk et al. (2015) highlight the significance of early childhood in cultivating lifelong learning skills and instilling values, attitudes, and behaviours that support effective ESD. However, they note that definitions of ESD in early education vary in theory and in practice. For instance, Priest (1989) views environmental education in early childhood as interconnected relationships between natural resources, people, and society. Davies (2009) defines it as an education that occurs in, through, about, and for the environment. Meanwhile, Hedelfalk et al. (2015) present the following two definitions of how ESD should be approached:

1. a threefold approach to education, based on questions concerning, as Davies describes, education about, in and for the environment.
2. an approach to education that includes three interrelated dimensions (economic, social and environment) (p. 978).

4.8.1. An education approach about, in and for the environment.

Education about, in, and for the environment in early childhood has been called science-based knowledge or environmental education (EE). It involves young children exploring and learning about various environmental sustainability issues, such as waste disposal, water consumption, biodiversity, and energy conservation (Hedelfalk et al., 2015). This approach aims to instil environmental awareness and understanding in young learners, fostering a sense of responsibility towards the planet from an early age. Activities that involve the natural environment have deep roots in Nordic early childhood education and care (ECEC) traditions (Engdahl & Ärlemalm-Hagsér, 2014).

Spending time outdoors and in Nature aligns with an inquiry-based emergent curriculum approach in early education described in the previous curriculum section 3.6, where children are encouraged to engage in activities or projects driven by their own interests (Stacey, 2014). This encompasses the ‘in’ and ‘about’ aspects of education. Moreover, the ‘for’ element of the definition comes into play by encouraging active participation in making sustainable choices or systems for protecting and preserving the environment. This holistic approach involves learning about and in the environment and then taking active steps towards working for its sustainability (Davies, 2009, 2014). By combining these elements, early childhood education plays a crucial role in instilling environmental consciousness and promoting sustainable practices from an early age.

4.8.2. An education approach with interrelated dimensions

UNESCO (2010) describe the interdependent pillars or systems of sustainability as natural, social and cultural, economic and political (also referred to as good governance) (Grindheim et al., 2019). In her work, Phillips (2014) explains how the Earth has an ecosystem, a natural system of resources which supports life. To manage coexistence, humans constructed social, cultural and economic systems required to control or divide labour, property ownership, and trading. In turn, political systems were developed to legislate policies and decisions on how the social and cultural and economic systems use the natural system of resources. Therefore, we, as human inhabitants, are embedded in these interrelated systems.

Sustainability issues are connected to society, human action, and a shared environmental, social, economic, and political responsibility (Phillips, 2014; Grindheim et al., 2019). Accordingly, for young children to be fully engaged in ESD, Ji and Stuhmcke (2014) argue that they must have opportunities to participate in transformative education, that is, in education which fosters their capacities to understand and act across all these systems. Alongside protecting the environment, being empowered with social capabilities such as engaging in critical thinking and participating in democratic decision-making processes offers a more profound definition of sustainability by integrating broader issues of community life and citizenship into our learning spaces (Edwards & Cutter-Mackenzie, 2011; Duhn, 2012; Mackey, 2012; Sundberg & Ottander, 2014).

4.8.3 The post-humanist approach.

A third approach takes a post-humanist perspective and looks to base its pedagogical framework around the relationships between human and non-human Nature (Barrable, 2019; Ernst et al., 2021). This approach moves from the view of non-human Nature as merely an instrument or a learning environment in early childhood towards an eco-centric orientation, emphasising that children are part of Nature (Earth Charter, 2000; Croft, 2017; Barrable, 2019). Barrable (2019) calls for a ‘pedagogy of connectedness’ in the early years to support the young child in developing empathy and compassion towards non-human Nature and subsequent responsible environmental behaviour (REB). This is still in keeping with Davies’s (2009) approach of ‘in, through, about and for’ Nature while also emphasising a need for the young child to form a deep affective connection with Nature to motivate pro-environmental

and sustainable behaviours (Davies, 2009; Barrable, 2019; 2020; Mullenbach, Andrejewski and Mowen, 2019).

Giving young children the platform and adult support to be in Nature and establish their own connections or interests with it supports opportunities to engage in their own authentic sustainability participation (Davies, 2010, 2014; Anderson & Gullberg, 2012). This also supports opportunities for scientific inquiry and intentional teaching to extend to deeper dimensions of learning for Nature (Siraj-Blatchford, 2011; Engdahl & Ärlemalm-Hagsér, 2014; Cutter-MacKenzie, Edwards, Moore, and Boyd, 2014). Arguably, whichever definition or approach is considered, the principles of ESD in early childhood, namely the ethical positioning of the young child, contextual starting points, democracy, participation, and communitarian citizenship learning, should remain steadfast.

4.9. Positioning the learner - the young child in ESD

Carson (1956) describes early childhood as the time to ‘prepare the soil’ for the harmonious alignment of human activity in Nature. Carson also claims that children play an intrinsic role in halting environmental damage. However, to overburden a child as the ‘redemptive vehicle’ in curing the ills of the world is unethical (Dahlberg & Petrie, 2002). Davies and Elliot (2014) argue that children should not be viewed as ‘saviours for sustainability’, here to repair the environmental damage that adults have caused. Instead, ESD in the early years should promote an approach where young children are authentically involved in areas that interest them and are supported by ECEC practitioners to explore these interests through curricula and pedagogies (Duhn, 2012; Kahrman-Pamuk, 2019).

Positioning young children as thinkers, problem-solvers, and rights-holders challenges traditional learning. It opens the doors to transformational possibilities for them to develop their own perspectives and make meaningful responses to issues that surround them (Davies, 2014; 2015; Hirst, 2019; Mackey, 2012; 2014). McDonald (2015) describes this type of learning as starting in a local context, where young children are involved in projects exploring solutions for living systems, such as a setting’s waste management, food production or water usage system.

4.10. Contextual starting points for ESD

As outlined in the definitions of ESD, sustainable development is an evolving process with room for many different starting points depending on the context, interests, knowledge base, and resources of those involved (Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008). Pedagogies of child-led project-based learning are standard practices in early childhood, giving early education a pedagogical advantage for this kind of transformative approach to ESD learning (Davies et al., 2011). Transformative participatory projects are initiated based on the children's knowledge, interests and feelings and a 'curriculum web'¹⁶ is developed through discussions between children and adults to ensure meaningful learning experiences (Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; Davies et al., 2011; Ji & Stuhmcke, 2014). *The Musim Stream Project* in South Korea and *The Rainforest Project* in Australia are examples of transformative participatory projects where young children develop problem-solving and community leadership skills by studying local environmental issues.

In *The Musim Stream Project*, the children engaged in various activities to learn about otters and their habitats. They watched informative videos, went otter tracking with an expert, and expressed their perspectives through artwork, letters to the animals, and an otter song, emphasising care for the planet. During their research, they discovered the absence of otter information on existing bio maps and created a child-friendly map with illustrations and locations of animals and plants along the stream. The children submitted this map as a proposal to the Cheongju City Hall for inclusion in local information guides. They also extended their work to the local community by organising an event advocating otter protection, performing their otter songs, distributing informative materials, and sharing hand-drawn otter pictures (Ji & Stuhmcke, 2014).

In the Brisbane *Rainforest Project*, the children's interest was sparked by a collage shared by one child, leading to the creation of a three-dimensional rainforest model. The teacher facilitated learning through picture books with environmental themes and Nature hunts, promoting respect for biodiversity. The children also developed an interest in recycling and conservation within their own environments, establishing rules to prevent water pollution and protect wildlife, showing their commitment to environmental stewardship (Ji & Stuhmcke,

¹⁶ A 'curriculum web' starts with the central theme that goes in the middle of the web. The theme serves as the starting point for sub-themes and lesson plans in the web.

2014). To teach other people ways to care about the earth, a book titled *Ways to Act for the Environment* was published as a project output. The book included children's drawings and learnings and was distributed to local families or families of children participating in the project.

The studies identified the value of a transformative participatory project approach with young children to support authentic learning for sustainability. Two distinct and meaningful ESD projects were developed by engaging with children's connections to Nature and utilising appropriate pedagogy. These projects exemplify active co-construction of learning and active participation in creating positive change (Katz & Chard, 2000). Moreover, the children's involvement in local contexts had broader impacts, contributing to their identity as global social actors (Vaealiki & Mackey, 2008; Duhn, 2012; Phillips, 2014; Tisdall, 2015; LeBorgne & Tisdall, 2017). Davies (2008) considers these learner-initiated projects representative of small wins that can lay the foundation for new ways of thinking and lead to pro-environmental behaviours that extend beyond the local level, creating positive ripple effects.

4.11. Communitarian citizenship learning

Children often experience moments of enthusiasm for active citizenship but encounter social, political and civic barriers that limit their participation and empowerment (Lundy, 2007; Lundy & McEvoy, 2011). As Philips (2014) emphasises, ESD in early childhood can offer civic inclusion opportunities. She advocates for a communitarian approach, where children engage in purposeful group action with a sense of community responsibility. This approach, exemplified in the *Musim Stream project's* efforts to protect endangered species, can lead to a transformative shift in promoting young children's social agency (Ji & Stuhmcke, 2014).

In her research on young children's active citizenship, Phillips (2014) employs a living theory'¹⁷ of social injustice storytelling with the children. She highlights that while young children desire to contribute to society, the traditional role of pretend or imaginary play in early education may limit their opportunities for real-life meaning-making. Building on this communitarian approach, MacDonald (2015) proposes a 'living curriculum' – one that has

¹⁷ A living-educational-theory (often abbreviated to living-theory or living theory in the literature) is a term Whitehead (1989) coined to mean a valid, values-based explanation created by a practitioner-researcher of their educational influence in their own learning, the learning of others and the learning of the social formations they live and work in.

the ability to change with the needs of the learners and circumstances - based on four learning capacities: love and belonging, living systems, origins, relationship and care, and respect for environment and boundaries. MacDonald suggests that these capacities can be realised through reciprocal, collaborative and intellectually engaging conversations between adults and children, leading to active learning opportunities.

In MacDonald's study, the learning environment included four possible learning areas: the forest, the setting's building and grounds, gardening, and composting and recycling. The pedagogy was project-based, similar to those mentioned above, and an emphasis was placed on respect for multiple perspectives and diversity in constructing knowledge. The projects included learning about living systems to better understand the impact of human actions and subsequent care of resources, e.g. waste and heating systems, gardening, and compost systems. The democratic and dialogic nature of the adult/child relationship also promoted social sustainability and authentic engagement of the young child's capacity as a contributing social actor. MacDonald (2015) emphasises how active, dialogical educational programmes concerning social and political responsibility used to integrate ESD can cultivate opportunities for critical awareness and promote a learning environment to engage young children to question practices impacting sustainable development. It is this aspect of participation and democracy that warrants further exploration in shedding light on the realisation of a child rights-based ESD approach.

4.12. Participation and democracy

According to Pramling Samuelsson and Kaga (2008), the fundamental tenets of ESD in early childhood are centred around viewing the child as a rights holder, fostering meaningful dialogue and engagement with children, and promoting respect and appreciation for diverse contributions. By integrating these interconnected elements, learning spaces can advance democracy and rights-based pedagogy (Martínez Sainz, 2018; Grindheim et al., 2019). As discussed earlier, involving young children in authentic, real-life experiences and encouraging them to make meaningful contributions nurtures their competencies to take action. This active involvement is crucial in enabling their role as contributing citizens (Vaealiki & Mackey, 2008; Mackey, 2012, 2014). The concepts of agency and autonomy are integral to active child participation. How adults respond to and understand active child participation plays a crucial role in supporting agency and autonomy (Mannion, 2007; Shier,

2016; 2019; Horgan et al., 2017). While implementing 'living curriculum' projects in learning spaces is beneficial, establishing a rights-respecting culture, where children's voices are heard and where they are involved in decision-making, truly fosters democratic learning. This approach ensures that children have a genuine sense of participation and influence in their educational experiences.

Clark (2020) emphasises the importance of 'slow pedagogy,' which involves slowing down and actively listening to children. This approach helps adults gain a better understanding of children's contributions to their own learning. By valuing children's contributions as knowledge in early years' practice, educators can enhance their skill sets and support a culture of slow pedagogy. Jerome (2018), Lyndon, Bertram, Brown, and Pascal (2019), and Clark (2020) all point out that the prevalent 'measurement culture' in early years learning has marginalised listening to children in favour of lengthy quantitative processes to record and monitor learning. Similar to Nolan and McGrath's (2016) critique of the narrowness of the SDG indicators outlined in the policy overview section, this measurement-oriented approach neglects many aspects of young children's perspectives and experiences. In contrast, it is creating a 'counter-culture' to democratic learning (Moss, 2016; Clark, 2017, 2020; Jerome, 2018; Lyndon et al., 2019).

Elliot (2014) argues that addressing sustainability issues in early childhood education requires more than just 'access to rocks' or natural outdoor spaces. Through two-year-long critical participatory action research case studies, Elliot found that aside from collaborative projects described in the previous section, proactive responses from ECEC practitioners and families were also crucial in promoting effective ESD. Regardless of the amenities available, how ESD was implemented within the settings significantly influenced changes (or not) in behaviour towards more sustainable practices. Effective ESD goes beyond the physical environment and relies on proactive efforts to drive sustainable change in behaviour and practices. Sirjai-Blatchford et al. (2010) described this as a departure from mere 'how to do' guidelines for ESD in the early years, emphasising the need for transformative pathways aligned with the broader concept of sustainability. This type of transformative approach can further the possibilities for developing rights-respecting education spaces when we acknowledge and advocate for the young child as a rights holder and contributing social actor

in their everyday lives (Hägglund & Johansson, 2014; Tisdall, 2015; LeBorgne & Tisdall, 2017; Lundy & Martínez Sainz, 2018).

4.13. The role of the ECEC practitioner as a duty bearer under Article 29 1 (e).

Gilbert et al. (2014) stress the importance of creating ‘professional capital’ to promote advocacy for young children's potential to contribute meaningfully to a sustainable society. Elliot and Davies (2009) and Cutter-Mackenzie and Rousell (2019) note that ESD is often considered too complex to integrate into early childhood. This final section unpacks that contention and explores the evolving concept of sustainability and its relevance to ECEC practice. It examines theories by Bruner, such as ‘the spiral curriculum’ and ‘discovery learning’ and how they can be applied to promote ESD using an ECEC practitioner’s skillset. This is continued by analysing the role and implications of practitioners’ own beliefs and attitudes towards sustainability principles. The next discussion offers insight into studies that have considered transformational pedagogy with practitioners in early childhood and its significance in promoting ESD in early childhood settings. I conclude by providing a working definition for ‘transformative learning’ for the thesis.

4.13.1. Linking Bruner with ESD.

For Bruner (1961), the purpose of education was not simply imparting knowledge or facts. Instead, it involves acknowledging children as thinkers and respecting their thoughts and ideas. Educators are encouraged to understand the thought process behind a child's thinking and provide support (scaffolding) to help them construct their own understanding of the world. One of Bruner's key contributions is ‘the spiral curriculum’, where information is organised so that complex ideas are presented at a level suitable for the learner and revisited and expanded upon as their thinking develops. Bruner also believed that learning was not simply about mastering facts and techniques, but rather the methods and structure of how knowledge is transferred is also relevant. His ‘discovery learning theory’ is an inquiry-based, constructivist learning theory that takes place in problem-solving situations where the learner draws on past experiences and existing knowledge to discover facts, relationships, and new ideas to be learned (Bruner, 1961).

These concepts are relevant for an authentic ESD approach in early childhood. By engaging young learners in intellectually honest ways and gradually deepening their understanding of

sustainable development, ‘the spiral curriculum’ can effectively promote environmentally responsible thinking and action from an early age (Elliot & Davies, 2009; Cutter-Mackenzie & Rousell, 2019; Bord & Samuelsson, 2022). Indeed, Bruner (1961; 1996) emphasised the importance of starting the learning process by connecting with a young child's own perspectives and lived experiences related to a subject. By doing so, children are encouraged to explore and discover their own ideas, thoughts, and meaningful constructs about the topic. This learner-centred approach recognises the significance of a child's existing knowledge as a foundation for building new understanding. By building upon what children already know and find meaningful, educators can facilitate more effective and engaging learning experiences, fostering a deeper and more personal connection to the subject matter.

Bruner's constructivist learning theory also highlights the significance of responsive scaffolding and supportive interactions to facilitate learning. The concept of ‘discovery learning’ implies that children are constructing their own knowledge, and the role of the teacher is not to teach through rote learning but rather to present the information or material and facilitate the learner to connect their own relationships with the same. In the context of ESD, recognising a young child's connection with sustainable practices, such as discovering a worm or responsibly disposing of a food wrapper, can serve as a solid starting point for promoting sustainable attitudes and behaviours. By valuing their perspectives and making them central to the learning process, an authentic rights pedagogy can be promoted within an ESD approach. This approach empowers children to become active participants in their education and fosters a sense of agency and responsibility towards sustainability from a young age (Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2015; 2019; Martínez Sainz, 2018; Jerome; 2018 Clark, 2020).

4.13.2. The importance of practitioners’ values and beliefs to support ESD.

Practitioners’ own values and beliefs of sustainability also play a role in how effective any approach to ESD will be. Saigedet (2014) argues that the personal motivations and value orientation of young children and their preschool teachers toward sustainable living play a pivotal role in shaping behaviours and effectively developing sustainable practices.

Understanding and fostering these motivations and values are crucial in promoting ESD among young children and educators. Saigedet (2014) claims that while a range of studies demonstrate the importance of outdoor education and sustainable practices, placing value on

being outdoors does not automatically translate to placing value on sustainable living. For example, Nordic countries share many elements that can be considered in line with sustainable living, such as appreciating regular outdoor activity, sustainable production and consumption and welfare models based on core values of equality. Yet, significantly, the high living standards of these countries also promote large ecological footprints, which are far more significant than many other parts of the world (WWF, 2018).

Innoue et al. (2016) argue that the multiple definitions of sustainability, described in section 4.6, can lead to misuse and reduced impact due to different interpretations by governments, researchers, the public, and across regions and nations. In their collaborative research study on Australian and Japanese ECEC practitioners' views on ESD, findings indicated that neither group had well-developed ideas or practices supporting sustainability with young children (Innoue, O’Gorman, Davies, 2016). Their study showed that learning opportunities in Nature were well-established in both countries. However, it also revealed that learning in Nature was primarily implemented for child development purposes, social learning, and sensory awareness rather than focusing on sustainability outcomes (Innoue, 2014; Innoue et al., 2016). It could therefore be argued that while curricula frameworks and guidelines point to the importance of learning for Nature as outlined in the previous chapter, that alone is insufficient in supporting ECEC practitioners in their role as duty bearers to develop more effective learning under Article 29 1 (e) (Dyment, Davis, Nailon, Emery, Getenet, McCrea & Hill, 2014; Innoue et al, 2016; Cutter-MacKenzie & Rousell, 2019; Bord & Samuelsson, 2022).

4.14. What is needed to support ECEC practitioners under Article 29 1 (e).

The UNESCO report *The UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (DESD 2005–2014): The First Two Years* considered the role of the teacher to be a critical factor for advancing ESD. There has been a notable push to embed learning for sustainability into curricula, as analysed in the previous chapter. In addition, governments have also funded initiatives to provide resources and training in the area. For example, the Norwegian government have funded and cooperated with several non-governmental organisations such as *Eco-Agents*¹⁸ and the *Green Children’s Cities*.¹⁹ Within these initiatives, kindergartens can

¹⁸ Eco-agents is a Norwegian member-based environmental organisation for children.

involve themselves in projects focused on everyday sustainable practices. Settings work towards achieving the international environmental green flag certification for early childhood services associated with the eco-school movement established by *The Foundation for Environmental Education* (FEE).²⁰

Many Norwegian municipalities have also made green flag participation compulsory (Saigedet, 2014). Interestingly, while families and ECEC practitioners have positively received such projects, one-third of settings still required stimulus in the form of a compulsory programme and guidance. The practitioners were not intrinsically driven to engage in ESD without external incentives or directives. To address this, a professional network of sustainability officers was created to provide guidance and develop competencies. Saigedet (2014) discovered that when ECEC practitioners initially engaged in sustainability projects, received expert guidance, and had access to resources, they changed their attitudes and competencies in integrating ESD pedagogy. This would, therefore, suggest that with the right support, practitioners can be empowered to embrace sustainable practices and effectively incorporate ESD principles into their educational approach.

Dyment et al. (2014) carried out a study to measure the impact of professional development on ECEC practitioners in terms of confidence, understanding and knowledge of ESD. Findings suggested that a lack of professional development may cause practitioners to be, as indicated earlier, overwhelmed and/or confused by ESD topics. This can result in questioning their competencies to understand and embed such concepts in an intellectually honest manner for the young child. Furthermore, Dyment et al. (2014) describe professional development approaches that disseminate knowledge in a top-down manner as often insufficient for changing teaching practices. In contrast, their study outlined the importance of empowering practitioners by connecting their existing skillset and new knowledge (Dyment, 2014; Robson, 2016; Lyndon et al., 2019). The potential of such an approach was illustrated in my analysis in the previous section, which linked ESD with Bruner's theory. Sirjai-Blatchford et al. (2010) consider that promoting this pedagogical advantage and enhancing the connections

¹⁹ Green Children's Cities is a campaign involving children and their cities to respond to climate change by providing resources, partnerships, and a platform to take climate action.

²⁰ The Foundation for Environmental Education (FEE) is one of the world's largest environmental education organisations, with over 100 member organisations in 81 countries.

between ECEC and ESD approaches can be highly beneficial. Additionally, by developing and utilising resources specific to the early years' context, ECEC practitioners can effectively integrate sustainable principles into their educational practices.

Feriver, Teksöz, Olgan and Reid (2016) argue that implementing systems-wide preservice and in-service practitioner training is also vital. Such training equips skilled ECEC practitioners with the knowledge, skills, and tools necessary to support young children as duty bearers under Article 29 1 (e). However, Ferreira, Ryan and Davies (2015) outline how difficult it is to change teaching and remind us that the push to ensure ESD becomes a constituent part of pre-service training has been ongoing for the last 30 years. Contextual constraints and constant changes in policy requirements in pre-service education have resulted in fragmented and poorly executed projects that have negatively impacted the enthusiasm to engage in further initiatives for change (Ferreira et al., 2015; Moss, 2016; Clark, 2020). Ferreira et al. (2015) also describe a conservatism now exacerbated by neoliberal imperatives at third level, which focus more on student outcomes in literacy and numeracy. Leadership capacities are increasingly recognised as necessary in the transition to sustainability more generally and must be explicitly developed if ESD is to become embedded in preservice education. However, Ferreira et al. (2015) also warn that being a leader in an academic area that involves pre-service teacher training does not automatically equate to the leadership knowledge or skills required to initiate and enact the systems-wide change for effective ESD.

4.15. A long-term sustained change

Ferreira et al. (2015) highlight the importance of having a common vision for change widely shared throughout a system to bring about long-term sustained change. When it comes to effecting change in pre-service ECEC practitioner training, it requires efforts by various stakeholders, including training institutes, universities, government agencies, statutory authorities, and early years' settings (Moody & Darbellay, 2019). Collaboration and coordination among these entities are essential to achieve meaningful and lasting transformation in the ECEC system. It calls for a collective effort to align goals, strategies, and approaches towards promoting ESD in pre-service training for ECEC practitioners. Having a shared vision and working together ensures a more comprehensive and impactful integration of sustainability principles into early childhood education, leading to a more

environmentally conscious and socially responsible generation. Ferreira et al. (2015) propose a three-part process for sustaining change alongside possible strategies to help achieve this, as outlined in Figure 4.1.

While such practitioner training has historically been rooted in hierarchical and authoritarian cultures expressed through top-down decision-making and policy processes, Ferreira et al. (2015) call for a transformative ‘bottom-up’ network leadership approach. This would give the opportunity to all those involved in an organisation to contribute to learning meaningful to them.

Figure 4.1: Strategies for achieving systems change (adapted from Ferreira & Ryan, 2012) (Ferreira et al, 2015)

Focus	Possible Strategies
Working with Pre-Service Teacher Education Systems	Identify the system and its components (the individual organizations that are involved in the system)
	Delineate system boundaries in order to understand what can and cannot be influenced and changed
	Map and understand the nature of the relationships between system components (for example, client, competitor, or resource provider)
	Identify and involve hubs or change agents with disproportionate influence within and across the system to provide points of leverage for desired change
Working with People	Build a common vision amongst all stakeholders for the change that is to be achieved, in ways that develop ownership of that change
	Use action research processes to build participants’ capacities for change and to continuously monitor and adapt change strategies
Working for Change	Develop effective communication strategies across the system to support coordinated and strategic approaches aligned to the collaborative vision for change, not only amongst active change agents, but also more broadly amongst system members.
	Continuously evaluate and monitor the change processes at all system levels and across all participants
	Celebrate successful incremental changes

Using Mezirow’s ‘transformative learning theory’ (1997), Feriver et al. (2016) presented research participants (24 ECEC practitioners) with ‘disorienting dilemmas’ - described as information or scenarios presented to a person that cause them to question their existing practices or assumptions and often used in transformative learning, to challenge their thinking surrounding sustainability. Mezirow’s theory holds that learners who get new information also evaluate their past ideas and understanding and shift their views through critical reflection as they obtain new information. In this case, dilemmas included analysing

sustainability situations, including participants' own consumption patterns and ecological footprint and their impact on the planet. The research also included peer discussion and guidance from a more knowledgeable mentor in sustainability that supported participants in recognising and voicing their disorientation. Similarly, their disorientation was used to explore new roles, relationships and actions through examples of how to change behaviours and attitudes in real-life situations and in their settings that were attainable in a local context but could have a ripple effect globally (Feriver et al., 2016). Indeed, the learning process described is empowering, as it involves breaking down perceived complex ideas and challenging uninformed assumptions. This approach helps ECEC practitioners better understand sustainability issues and how to incorporate sustainable practices into their educational settings. It encourages critical thinking and fosters a sense of agency and ownership among practitioners, empowering them to take meaningful actions towards promoting sustainable behaviours and values among young children. Providing accessible knowledge, resources, and support enables a transformation in thinking and practice (Ferreira et al., 2015; Feriver et al., 2016; Robson, 2016; Moody & Darbellay, 2019). This approach recognises that sustainability education is not a one-size-fits-all approach; instead, it should be tailored to meet the needs and interests of the participants.

4.16. Conceptual Frameworks for the Study.

As outlined in my introductory chapter, I proposed to work with young children as active researchers and research participants to explore their perspectives, lived experiences, and legitimate right to an education under Article 29 1 (e). These perspectives were, in turn, shared with ECEC practitioners to gain further insight from both groups of stakeholders to bring about the sustained changes needed in values, teacher education, practices and resources for the successful implementation of authentic ESD approaches under the CRC. Involving children, ECEC practitioners, and families in the process provides an opportunity for active participation and ownership in the learning journey. Ultimately, such a 'bottom-up' participatory approach to ESD can lead to more profound and sustainable changes in attitudes and behaviours, as it empowers those involved to take ownership of sustainability principles and practices in a way that is relevant and meaningful to them. It is this same transformative idea which gave rise to the rationale of this research study.

I described Davies (2014) *Expanded Rights Framework* and its five dimensions, that she argues essential for effective ESD in Chapter 2. This study is conceptually underpinned by

the framework's second dimension. **Dimension 2** calls for expanding and reconceptualising children's agentic participation rights and clarity on the various forms of active participation that children can engage in. By recognising and nurturing young children's agency, the framework promotes meaningful and authentic participation, allowing them to actively contribute to their learning and development. The study uses the same definition of 'agency' from the updated Aistear (2024, p.30), respecting their right to 'make choices about and in their learning'. Additionally, the study acknowledges the participants' influence on relationships, decisions and the working of the shared research space under Article 12.

In terms of 'transformative learning' and as described in the previous section, I take it to mean education that brings about change, be that change in understanding, value, attitude, behaviours or a combination of any for a common good (Mezirow, 1997). In this case, that common good would be for more sustainable, harmonious living for this and the next generations (Earth Charter, 2000; Davies, 2014; UNICEF, 2018; UNGA, 2018; Daly, 2023; UNCRC 1989, 2023). The following three chapters sheds further light on these concepts and discusses the methodologies used in these processes.

Chapter 5. Stage 1: Child rights-based participatory methodology.

5.1. Introduction

There are three methods chapters in this thesis. This chapter is divided into two sections to demonstrate how the methodological journey for stage one was analysed and applied to support the study's chosen child rights-based research approach. Key to this chapter's discussion will be the centrality of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), with section one offering an analysis of child rights-based participatory research. This is followed by a broad review of key contributing literature on rights-based participation models and a more detailed discussion of the main hallmarks of child rights-based research. Section two discusses the ethical considerations and strategies that were informed by the Children's Research Advisory Group (CRAG). This discussion will also include an account of the study's limitations. The study's second aim was to develop a child rights-based research methodology with young children. Their contributions to this will be discussed separately as a finding in Chapter 8. The final section gives an account of the data analysis process for this stage and my initial coding system.

5.2. Ontological and Epistemological positions.

Ontology is the term philosophers use for the ideas or assumptions we hold about the world around us (Mukherji & Albon, 2018). Our assumptions on how things are inevitably influence the decisions we make in our research processes and the ways we go about finding the truth or knowledge about our research questions (Cohen, Mannion & Morrison, 2011; Robert-Holmes, 2014). Mukherji & Albon (2018) describe epistemology as the method we use to find out about the world around us. Cohen et al. (2011, p.3) define it as 'ways of researching and enquiring into the nature of reality and the nature of things'. Or more simply put, epistemology answers the questions 'what do you know?' and 'how do you know it?' (Mukherji & Albon, 2018).

To recap, the research aims of this study were:

Aims

- To explore with young children their own perspectives and lived experiences of Nature under Article 29 1 (e) of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child.
- To develop a child rights-based research methodology with young children to support their participation in developing an Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) approach in early childhood under Article 29 1 (e).

- To build the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate child rights-based ESD into early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e).

As this methodology chapter will illuminate, and in keeping with the transformative child rights paradigm, this thesis defends an epistemological position that all children are knowledge creators. Their perspectives and lived experiences of Nature are valued and will be used as described above to construct knowledge that will contribute to education and participatory rights under Article 29 1 (e). As described in the introduction chapter, early childhood is a messy place (Edwards, 2010). Young children's views are expressed in a busy social world where thousands of things go on simultaneously. There is constantly a shifting network of complex interactions between children and adults, which can provide both constraints and possibilities for interpretation (Edwards, 2010). A clear adult/child power dynamic is therefore necessary to keep some kind of order. However, being aware of this dynamic and balancing it was pertinent to ensuring authentic child participation and real-life matters were heard. Not all, and indeed very few, research methods can stand up to the type of rigour needed for a true representation of young children's views (Shier, 2019). This justifies choosing a research methodology that supported the participants themselves to make decisions and contribute to the research process. The following section gives an account of child rights-based participatory research methodology designed with the children and its alignment with the study's ontological and epistemological positions. The second section of this chapter discusses the extent to which the research approach was applied and how it was supported by ongoing reflexivity to promote child rights-based participatory research at a local level.

5.3. Child rights-based participatory research.

A rights-based research approach with children must have certain features (Tisdall, 2015). From the outset, the researcher is required to clearly understand what the CRC means for researching with children (Mayne et al., 2018). Their attitudes and perspectives towards young children, whether they view them as objects to be studied or as competent individuals capable of playing an interactive role in research, greatly influence the decisions made during the initial planning of the study (Mayne & Howitt, 2015; Mayne et al., 2018). Despite the clear paradigm shift in positioning children as participants with their own perspectives and experiences to offer, these can still be limited to shaping research questions and agendas set

by adults and, therefore, cannot be clearly located in a rights-based realm (Lundy, 2007; Roberts, 2008; Lundy & McEvoy, 2012). Participatory research with children and the principles of children's rights emerged around the same time and have many similarities. However, there are also notable methodological differences between participatory research and a child rights-based research approach (CRA) (Bessell, 2015).

Two different strands of child rights-based research have been identified. The first is from Ennew and Plateau (2004, p.29.), who put forward a combination of specific articles (Article 3.3, 12.1, 13.1., and 36) and five fundamental principles to ensure children are 'properly' involved in research (i) it is respectful to children in their research roles, (ii) it is ethical, (iii) it is scientifically valid using systematic methods that can be replicated, (iv) it involves rigorous analysis and (v) it prioritises local knowledge. The second strand is found in Lundy and colleagues' work, drawing its conceptual framing from international human rights research approaches. There are three core principles to this rights-based approach: (i) that the study should further advance the realisation of rights, (ii) that children's rights standards should guide all research stages, and (iii) the analysis should support the development of the capacity of duty bearers to meet obligations and of children as rights-holders to claim their rights (Lundy and McEvoy, 2011, 2012). Research aims and processes must be informed, comply with all CRC standards, and be grounded in children's dignity, profound moral respect, and entitlements as bearers of human rights. In particular, the best interests (Article 3.1), views of the child (Article 12) and freedom of expression (Article 13) are viewed as central to this approach. It is this articulation that informs the methodology for stage one.

A distinctive feature of Lundy et al.'s approach is the use of a Children's Research Advisory Group (CRAG) in their research (Lundy & McEvoy, 2009, 2012; Lundy et al., 2011). CRAG members are invited to take an advisory role to inform the thinking of the adult researcher by providing input on each research stage. Their role can include advice on formulating research questions, suitable research methods, design of data collection instruments, analysis and interpretation of findings and dissemination. A second feature of the approach is building children's capacities to engage in research activity. This is particularly important for the CRAG to support their roles as researchers in specific research tasks and to support them in

formulating their own ideas and expressing views on matters affecting them. (Abebe & Bessell, 2014; Bessell, 2015).

5.4. The principles of rights-based research participation

The principle of participation has been conceived in several ways. *General Comment 12 on the Right to be Heard* (2009) highlights the primacy of Article 12 and the principle of participation. Alderson (2008; 2012) considers participation to be a broad concept of taking part, being consulted, and being involved in decision-making. Hart (1992) describes it as a skill cultivated from involvement in meaningful engagement, where children are intrinsically motivated and experience a sense of ownership. Experiences of authentic participation also build confidence and competence, but what is meant by meaningful engagement is critical (Mayne, 2018). Fler and Pramling (2015) argue that young children’s competencies are only revealed when experiences or engagement make sense, enabling them to relate to particular issues. Meaningful participation is, therefore, more than taking part. It is a cumulative process that needs space, the right resources and time for understanding and planning (Groundwater-Smith, Dockett & Bottrell, 2015).

One well-known way of representing meaningful participation is Hart’s *Ladder of Participation* (1992), which offers levels of participation as an effective visual to understand the difference between tokenistic and meaningful participation (see Figure 5.1.):

Figure 5.1: Hart’s Ladder of Participation (Hart, 1992).

Groundwater-Smith et al. (2015) describe the first three levels of Hart’s ladder as preparatory stages, which may lead to higher levels of participation. Shier (2001) believes that a minimum level of 4 is required, where children’s participatory rights are ‘somewhat considered’. Mannion (2007) and Horgan et al. (2017) argue that while agency and autonomy are fundamental concepts of active child participation, adults’ understanding of and response to these concepts is critical in ensuring they are supported. How the research agenda is determined, who is given the power to speak, who listens and who takes action is crucial to meaningful participation. Mayne et al. (2018) offer a hierarchical table (Figure 5.2.) that demonstrates how four elements of participation: (i) information, (ii) understanding, (iii) voice and (iv) influence, play a unique role in the way children’s rights to research participation are played out in practice.

Figure 5.2: Hierarchy of children’s research participation rights, showing its relationship to Hart’s ladder of participation (Mayne et al., 2018).

Hart’s Ladder of Participation		Hierarchy of children’s research participation rights					
Rung on Hart’s ladder	Hart’s participation categories	Level Descriptors	Participation rights				
			Information provided to the child: Information	Appropriate to the child’s capacities: Understanding	Express views and relate experiences: Voice	Carries weight in decision-making processes: Influence	
Rights-based Participation	8	Child-initiated and directed, shared decisions with adults	Child-initiated and directed with significant influence, decisions shared with adults. Child’s voice having greatest influence with adults overseeing.	Information created by children	Understanding greater than adults’	Voice equal to that of adults	Significant influence
	7	Child-initiated and directed	Child-initiated and directed, but facilitated by adults. Significant scope for child voice and influence.	Information greater than adults’	Understanding equal to that of adults	Significant voice	Selected influence
	6	Adult-initiated, shared decisions with children	Adult-initiated and scaffolded, decisions shared with children. Selected scope for child voice with scaffolded influence.	Information equal to that of adults	Significant understanding	Selected voice	Scaffolded influence
	5	Consulted and informed	Consulted, informed with understanding, and heard. Volunteers with a measure of voice and influence.	Significant information	Selected understanding	Scaffolded voice	Restricted opportunities for influence
	4	Assigned but informed	Assigned, informed with understanding. Volunteers but restricted to a practical yet symbolic role	Selected information	Scaffolded understanding	Restricted opportunities for voice	Negligible influence
Non-participation	3	Tokenism	Assigned, somewhat informed. May offer opinions but no action is taken	Scaffolded information	Restricted opportunities for understanding	Negligible voice	No influence
	2	Decoration	Assigned, largely unaware, not consulted	Restricted opportunities for information	Negligible understanding	No voice	No influence
	1	Manipulation	Assigned, unaware, possibly misled to facilitate involvement	Negligible information	No understanding	No voice	No influence

They describe participatory rights as complex and reiterate the above factors when seeking to ensure that young children enjoy their full rights as research participants. Young children’s

active involvement as co-researchers or research participants should allow for an empowerment effect that should not be a side effect of research. How children’s social agency is respected and strengthened in the study itself should be used to assess the importance of social research (Kellet, 2010; Shier, 2015). While children are recognised as experts in their own lives with the competence to communicate a unique insight into their experiences, they are also competent researchers when given the opportunity to learn more about a topic and deepen their existing knowledge (Shier, 2016, 2019; Huser et al., 2022). Scaffolding this sense of empowerment, emancipation or ‘protagonismo infantil’ as children take action and research essential issues is fundamental in strengthening children’s overall transformative agency (Shier, 2016).

Lundy (2007) provides a rights-based model, *the Lundy Model*, for participation with children. It conceptualises Article 12 of the CRC when working with children to further their right to participation (see Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3: Conceptualising Article 12 (Lundy, 2007)

The model consists of four elements (space, voice, audience, and influence) required to realise participatory rights fully. A safe space without fear of reproach or reprimand is essential for children (Space). Allowing them first to consider if a matter affects them and then to offer a platform to express, or not, in a manner appropriate to them (Voice and Audience). The space must be inclusive to all children. That still only provides a platform for the expression of a view. Lundy argues that the complete legal imperative of Article 12 and the principle of participation is the weight or consideration given to that view that will evaluate the compliance of that right (Influence) (Lundy, 2007).

As discussed above, a rights-based approach also needs supportive strategies such as building capacities to help the young child form a view. Information is a precondition for forming a view; therefore, Article 13 and the young child's right to information should also be considered when exploring children's perspectives. Lundy contends that Article 12 can only be fully understood when considered in connection with the other provisions of the CRC, namely Article 2 - Non-Discrimination, Article 3 - Best Interests, Article 5 - Right to Guidance, Article 13 - Right to Information and Article 19 – Right to be Safe (Ennew & Plateau, 2004; Lundy, 2007; Bae, 2010; Lundy et al. 2011, 2012).

Despite the growing salience of Article 12 and researchers becoming more aware of the necessity to examine how they position the children in their research, Mayne et al. (2018) note that there has been limited practical guidance in the holistic design of a rights-based research approach. This is further underlined by the limited guidelines on CRA ethics for researchers. To fill this gap, Mayne et al. (2016, 2017, 2018) have designed a framework that supports researchers in keeping track of their rights compliance for the entire research process. Drawing on contemporary rights-based theory, they offer five key considerations when designing a rights-based research approach.

Firstly, children must be provided with information on the context and purpose of the research. Secondly, the researcher must understand and respect how they choose to participate and their participatory rights. Thirdly, an interactive narrative can empower children to become part of the research story, while fourthly, a multi-layered understanding

process is needed to support the complexities of children's rights. Fifthly, there should be opportunities for families and practitioners to consolidate the young children's understanding of the research and what is asked of them in terms of participation (Mayne et al. 2016, 2017, 2018). In addition to this, *the Participation Framework* (DCEDIY, 2021) mentioned in the previous chapter also now provides a practical child participation toolkit based on the *Lundy Model* to support child rights-based approaches.

5.5. Implementing child rights-based research with young children in a local context

Having set out the broad principles of a child rights-based research approach, I will now explain how these were applied pragmatically in my own study. I worked with two groups of children, one (CRAG members) to advise on the research process and the other (research participants) to collect data relating to their experiences of Nature using various creative methods. Their recruitment is discussed in the following chapter. Notably, a role change in the project's second phase resulted in an amalgamation of these two groups, which will be explained later.

5.6. Implementing ethical principles

5.6.1. Respect for children

While the study observed formal institutional ethics procedures by the Institute of Technology²¹, Carlow's Research Ethics Committee (Appendix A), I also wish to discuss them through a child rights paradigm. The CRC is described as the blueprint for the ethical treatment of all children in research (Bessell, 2015). It is based on principles of dignity, deep moral respect, and the rightful entitlements of children. This study's primary framework revolves around valuing children as authorities in their own lives, including their educational choices and participation rights. Furthermore, each child is seen as a subject developing in the context of their own families and communities, which are culturally situated as part of wider societies. No child was treated with any prejudice or excluded because of their identity. All participants involved in the processes were treated fairly, sensitively, with dignity and without prejudice, and respectful of age, religion, language, disability, health condition, gender identity, sexuality, race, ethnicity, class, national origin, culture, social, economic or domestic status.

²¹ The Institute of Technology Carlow changed to the South East Technological University Ireland in 2022.

5.6.2. *Participatory ethics*

All participants in the research process were viewed as subjects, not objects, with rights to participate in the research activity, either directly or indirectly, actively or passively or indeed not at all. The project also acknowledged the rights of others to hold values, attitudes and opinions that differed from mine. Considering the adult/child dynamic in eliciting these perspectives, I also strived to minimise bias of any kind and committed to strategies that distributed power among all participants, supporting all involved to actively participate in the research process and contribute equally as they freely chose. A particular bias that I needed to watch was that of judgement on my part regarding some contributions discussed in chapter 9.

Kiili and Moilanen (2019) point out that the diversity of definitions, models and approaches to child participation can cause challenges for researchers. Indeed, this was the case for me, particularly regarding who decided the participants' involvement in the project and where they could effectively see their influence on decisions. Houghton (2015) argues that children's participation is typically absent when research ethics are under consideration or, at the very least, Powell et al. (2016) consider that the approaches to realising children's involvement in research ethics remain underdeveloped. Kiili and Moilanen (2019) describe 'adult-centred procedural ethics' derived historically from biomedical research as problematic, when rigidly applied to social science research where the practice is more subjective, person bound and contextual. They would undoubtedly cause contention through a child rights lens without additional strategies to support a different ethical research practice. From this perspective, attention must also be given to ethical considerations that may arise that have not been considered in more procedural ethics processes, such as the participation of assenting children whose families had not consented (Skånfors, 2009). The recruitment section in Chapter 8 (8.2) and the informed consent process section below (5.9) offer insight into how I applied such attention to develop strategies that I considered more in keeping with a child rights-centric participatory approach (Collins et al., 2020; Huser et al., 2022).

5.6.3. *Knowing from multiple perspectives.*

I aspire to construct new innovative knowledge with my participants that will contribute to rights-based research and education under Article 29 1 (e) and challenge existing orthodoxies and assumptions. In doing so, it is also essential that I recognise the valuable contribution of knowledge thus far from such works and disciplines in furthering both my thoughts and

discussions. Of equal importance, I also recognise that the perspectives of both the young participants and CRAG members and their own definitions of rights are at the forefront of this research journey. For this matter, an ethic of respect for knowledge from multiple perspectives, including participants, families, gatekeepers, ECEC practitioners, policymakers, and various research disciplines, underpins the study throughout.

5.6.4. Confidentiality, anonymity, and data protection

The right to privacy was upheld for the entire project. *The European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (2016)* guided confidentiality, anonymity, and data safeguarding methods. Audio recordings were taken during each research session with a hand-held audio recorder, which I transcribed using Microsoft Word, stored electronically, and protected with a password. Both groups of children were introduced to the audio recorder before its usage, and time was given to explore how it worked. Children were asked for their assent before the recorder was turned on, and time was spent in the sessions to explore it again when the participants wished. The write-up omits names or other personal information. Recordings were then deleted from the audio recording device. Ownership rights of the children's creations and research materials were a particular ethical concern raised by the CRAG and remained an essential aspect for the duration of the research. For example, it was important for some participants to take home their creations to their families. Photographic images were used only to capture ideas and activities; no identifiable pictures of children are used in this thesis. I also used a system of coding to highlight each participant's role in the findings chapter as follows (Table 5.1):

Table 5.1: Identification codes used in the study.

Code	Description
CMG (number)	CRAG Member girl (number)
CMB (number)	CRAG Member boy (number)
G (number)	Girl Research Participant (number)
B (number)	Boy Research Participant (number)
**	** non-consent
AR	Adult Researcher
EP (number)	ECEC practitioner (number)

5.6.5. Child protection

I underlined to all stakeholders involved that confidentiality was limited should information be disclosed that caused concern for the protection and welfare of any young child. In such an event, I would follow the guidance of *Children First: National Guidance for the Protection and Welfare of Children (DCYA, 2017)* and refer to the designated liaison person in the setting. I was also fully Garda Vetted before the study commenced.

5.6.6. Emotional support/no harm

All necessary steps must be taken to reduce the sense of intrusion, pressure, or stress from participation in the research. Equally, researchers must immediately desist from any actions that may cause distress to participants. Of relevance to this study was the emphasis and time allocated before processes started to build rapport and trust between myself, the gatekeeper, the families, the ECEC practitioners and the children (Huser et al., 2022). I ensured that at least one other ECEC practitioner was always present to support the children further during the workshop sessions. That practitioner was made aware of any ethical considerations that may have arose with my guidance. I intentionally did this with the understanding that such adults were more familiar to the participants and, therefore, had better insight into individual personalities and needs. This would provide emotional support and an extra strategy for encouraging participation, which I may not have considered otherwise. It proved to be very effective in ensuring inclusivity in the project, which will be described in more detail in Chapter 9.

5.6.7. Integrity and transparency

This project's ethical guidelines were also outlined in all communication with the research site owner and the children's families. This included making research actions transparent and documented fully, with data and methods open for external scrutiny and critical review. However, as a child rights-based approach, I also needed to ensure that the same ethical guidelines were evident in the young participants' research processes. Central to bringing ethical practice to the daily research space was the role of reflexivity, which is discussed further in its own section.

5.6.8. Regular feedback and dissemination

With a rights-based approach, the participants and their families had the right to hear regular feedback, progress, and project outcomes. Input with the participants took the form of

dialogue, listening and eliciting the children's ideas and views as they were expressed in an ongoing nature within the research space. Feedback was somewhat limited after the workshop sessions as it was also going home time and the setting used this time to discuss their own matters with the children's families. For this purpose, I set up a weekly online research feedback blog where the children and families were invited to read an account of the activities that took place that week and also further avail of the online resources I used that were of interest to the participants. Feedback was also given through emails via the gatekeeper and then directly from myself when data collection on site ended. The participants were also presented with their version of the study, *The Children's Nature Book* (attached as separate appendix U) It was conceptualised through work with the CRAG members and discussed in detail in the next chapter. It is important to note that the COVID-19 global pandemic outbreak meant that a public launch of the book with families was managed virtually. A copy of the book with a personalised note from myself was posted, and a small number of families provided feedback via email from the participants to me. Thankfully, we managed to hold our own private 'end of research party' with a customised cake (Figure 5.4) requested by the participants and the opportunity to take home and keep some research tools for themselves (magnifying glass and customised insect and bird poster). A full copy of this thesis and any further updates/progress are available for the children and their families.

Figure 5.4: The participants' Hedgehog cake for our 'research party'.

5.7. Overview of research phases

The initial plan for the research was as follows (Figure 5.5):

Phase 1 (Apr–Jun 2019) – Recruitment and research design with CRAG members comprising children aged 3-5.

Phase 2 (Oct-Dec 2019) - Data collection with research participants comprising children aged 2-3.

- Data analysis with CRAG members
- Semi-structured interviews with adult participants.

Phase 3 (Spring - 2020) - Dissemination of findings with CRAG members and identified listeners.

In keeping with Lundy et al. (2011, 2012), the procedure for Phase 1 was recruitment and three research design interactive workshops with the CRAG members and I, the adult researcher, to explore research methods and their suitability for the data collection phase (Phase 2) with the research participants. The concept was to create a research toolkit similar to aspects of the Mosaic approach²² (Clarke & Moss, 2005). This consisted of various participatory methods that the CRAG members had evaluated and considered most salient for this research context.

Figure 5.5: Visual overview of research phases

5.8. Reflexivity and its role within this methodology

Reflective pedagogy is taking the time to consider, review, and reevaluate teaching practices as an overall ongoing process to inform both provision and practice. It has been heavily

²² The Mosaic approach is a multi-method approach in which children's own photographs, tours, maps, and other contributions can be joined to talking and observing to gain a deeper understanding of children's perspectives on different matters.

promoted in *Síolta, Aistear* and *the Aistear Síolta Practice Guide* (CECDE, 2006; NCCA, 2009; NCCA, 2015). I was unaware of how essential reflexivity as an ongoing process would be in supporting the research approach as I described in section 5.2. Nor did I realise that it would be the most helpful tool in developing my confidence to keep the research grounded in the participants’ perspectives. The purpose of this section is first to identify the layers of reflection I needed to consider, which became an ethical checklist of sorts as I grappled with ensuring a rights-based approach was upheld. It also details how I did it practically within the everyday busy realities of early childhood (Edwards, 2010; Alderson & Morrow, 2011; Alderson, 2012; Cook, 2021).

5.8.1. Ethical radar

Merely following research ethical principles is not enough when researching with young children. Skånfors (2009, p. 16) describes an ‘ethical radar’ as the need for ‘the researcher to be observant of children’s actions and understand these not only in terms of the collection of data but also in the context of the impact of the research process on their worlds, rather than just relying on children’s initial verbal acceptance or consent given by parents’. Researchers must be on high alert throughout the process to deal with the complexities of daily early childhood business. Figure 5.6 demonstrates how I applied reflexivity.

Figure 5.6: Reflexivity thought process

The radar was on full alert while I was on-site working alongside the children or, as Schön (1991) describes as ‘in action’ during the research workshops and later again as ‘on action’ when considering by myself what took place during the workshops.

5.8.2. *The Role of Understanding*

This study recognises multiple realities and understandings regarding how young children engage with Nature. Bruner (1996) argues that how any one of us understands anything can only really be understood by us. He describes an intersubjective space between individuals in which they negotiate new meanings. Engaging in this space to establish what is being understood by everyone is pivotal for supporting learning and capacity building (Huser et al., 2022). Mayne et al.’s (2017) *Early Childhood Rights-Based Research Reinforcing Cycle* (Figure 5.7.) proved helpful in monitoring what the young participants and I understood. The value of this cyclical model is that it represents how the quality of overall child participation stems from the quality of the strategies used to establish how understanding has been achieved. It is an ongoing process throughout the research stages that continually facilitates the young child’s evolving capacity to form views when they are provided with information in a manner meaningful to them. This, in turn, empowers them to participate and supports their sense of agency; such is the true essence of the CRC principles (Lundy et al., 2011, 2012; Mayne et al., 2015, 2016, 2017). The quality of understanding cannot be underestimated and requires a consistent reflective role from the adult researcher to monitor how the information is received. To support a researcher in establishing what is being understood by their participants, Mayne et al. (2017) offer three simple questions to consider:

1. Can the child’s understanding be applied in other situations?
2. What actions is the child taking from their understanding?
3. How confident are they in responding to the information?

All three questions informed my thought process. However, it was the third question in particular that I found very helpful because confidence levels indicate good understanding and were readily notable amongst these participants. Confidence pays dividends in the quality of participation and in supporting children’s capacities to express their views (Lundy et al., 2011, 2012; Shier, 2016; Mayne et al., 2017).

Aside from putting some time between the workshop sessions for reflexivity, I also got into the habit of repeating back to the participants their exact words as I heard them. I had several

purposes for this: firstly, to fulfil my listening role as their audience under Article 12; secondly, to actively demonstrate to them that I had understood and to check if that was correct; and thirdly, for the participants to reflect on their ideas as they heard them back. Such practice is common among ECEC practitioners and resonates comfortably with our relational listening pedagogies (Lyndon et al., 2019; Clark, 2020). Indeed, as with reflective pedagogy, it was this practice and the participants’ response to hearing back their ideas that highlighted the overlap between ECEC practitioners’ pedagogical concepts and skillset and child rights-based participatory methodology.

Pedagogy and listening are closely linked and, slowing down, or as Clark (2020) describes it, ‘slow pedagogy’, supported me in incorporating forms of knowledge from the young participants within the research space. As explored, this ongoing process of assessing the understanding on both sides also fed into the quality of participation, keeping it meaningful and from the children’s perspectives (Lyndon et al., 2019). This finely-grained listening that the CRAG members enjoyed also reflected elements of the *Lundy model*, particularly ‘audience’ and ‘influence’ that worked in their research space, which will be explored in detail in Chapter 8 (Mayne et al., 2018).

Figure 5.7: The Early Childhood Rights-Based Research Reinforcing Cycle (Mayne et al., 2017)

5.8.3. Meaningful participation

The quality of participation also stems from the quality of informing the child. This means keeping the child fully informed in an authentic manner of what is happening or what is intended throughout the stages. It is an ongoing process that facilitates the young child's evolving capacity to form views when provided with meaningful information. The CRAG members and research participants defined many of their variations of participatory rights, which will be presented separately in the findings chapter to minimise repetition. Figure 5.8. offers an overview highlighting the number of these definitions and their interwoven nature (Mayne et al., 2018). In the first section of this chapter, I focussed on the different meanings and models of child research participation. Having knowledge of these models helped to influence my reflexivity in this role and craft a model of participation that best aligned with the CRAG members' definition of what is meaningful and authentic.

Figure 5.8: Interwoven elements of meaningful participation in the local context.

For example, their process of negotiating assent/dissent throughout the stages can best be described as an extension of the existing culture, gentle and non-invasive in its approach.

5.9. Informed consent process

Cocks (2006) in Mayne et al. (2016) describe three components necessary for meaningful informed consent: information provided by the researcher, the children's understanding of the research and what it means to be involved, and the child's response to the information provided. I have explained my research information materials (available in Appendices B - I) throughout the previous sections. I have also explained how applying a cyclical ongoing process was necessary to assess what was being understood by participants (child and adult alike). However, it was not until I met with each participant's response to the research information at any given moment that I could understand their participatory rights and stand by a consent process that I considered rights-based (Huser et al., 2022). It was during Phase 1 that the CRAG members advised me on how this should look (elements of which can already be seen in my narrative of workshop one and the mistakes I made with the toolkit described in the following chapter). The free-flowing culture of the local context, where children moved as they pleased within and between indoor and outdoor spaces, supported their own decision-making in whether to take part or not (Huser et al., 2022). Negotiations before the sessions started were not captured through audio recording but often included exploring research tools before any participatory decisions were made. This can be likened to what Mayne et al. (2016) describe as an interactive narrative approach where research information is communicated, and individual support can assist participants' understanding and responses. In the earlier stages of the project, this was a messy approach. My organisational skills were undoubtedly tested by the influx of questions and switches in participant numbers. However, as an ECEC practitioner, I am used to mess. With the support of the more familiar adults, namely the site's practitioners, we facilitated a relational assent negotiation process that was respectful of the participants' own culture with autonomous, self-determined choices (Huser et al., 2022). Further examples of what was negotiated are explored in the findings chapters. For now, it is essential to underline the involvement of the CRAG members and their guidance in informing the assent process. Chapter 7 explores more of their advice on how we extended the 'audience' and 'influence' elements of the Lundy model of research participation within the research context (Lundy, 2007).

5.10. Reflexive thematic analysis approach

This study used Braun and Clarke's (2006, 2013, 2020) reflexive thematic analysis approach to interpret data for stage one. I considered a reflexive thematic analysis approach most salient in terms of its flexibility and the fact that it does not require particular theoretical and

technological knowledge for its application. This made it more open for reflection and change of thought process, which, as described above, was fundamental in keeping abreast with the complexities and evolving nature of ECEC realities (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2013, 2020). I used its constructionist and contextualised approach to acknowledge the diversity and individual nature of how the young participants made their own meaning and experiences of the research question and participation. A reflexive thematic approach also aligned with the time and value given to reflexivity described in section 5.8. This method's overall 'qualitative sensibility' supported the multiple analytical layers needed to grapple with the participatory principles of both stages (Braun & Clarke, 2020). 'Qualitative sensibility' engages with the values, assumptions, orientation, and skills used to conduct reflexive thematic analysis. Braun and Clarke (2006, 2013, 2020) also advise establishing which lens the data is being explored through from the onset and pointing out any subjective bias the researcher may have.

5.11. Researcher's positionality

I used a child rights lens to analyse the data. As described in my introduction chapter, I am a staunch advocate for children to have plenty of opportunities to freely explore in natural environments. I advocate for the magnitude of learning and enjoyment that these first-hand experiences can offer, which includes developing a respect for the natural world. I believe that to learn democratically about Nature, every child as a rights holder must be in Nature and have regular access to local green areas within their own education settings and community (Chawla, 1998; Mannion, 2007; Davies, 2009; Ross & Mannion, 2012; Chawla & Rivkin, 2014; Mackey, 2014).

5.12 Coding system for stage one and rigour.

I used an audio recorder throughout the research sessions with the children, which I later transcribed by hand using Microsoft Word. In terms of rigour, it was essential for this process to be done manually to include the participation that was not clearly (verbally) articulated, such as interactions with the environment and others, which would not be picked up by technology. This is discussed in detail in Chapter 9. Additionally, through having ample time between research sessions for reflective analysis on the data and follow-up discussions with the children, site owner, and my thesis supervisors further supported my responsibility of maintaining rigour throughout this process. Acknowledging that another researcher may interpret the data differently is important (Braun & Clarke, 2011, 2020). Such is the beauty of rich qualitative research (Robert-Holmes, 2014; Mukherji & Albon, 2018). However,

providing a transparent and detailed account of a researcher’s thought process can also effectively demonstrate a qualitative researcher’s commitment to rigour (Braun & Clarke, 2011, 2020). To that end, I provide examples of this reflective thought process in the findings chapters' discussions.

The following is a list of codes that I identified in the initial stages of analysis from these transcriptions as a basis from which to establish possible themes:

Table 5.2: Initial coding system for stage one

Own ideas/experiences	Directing own Learning	Adults responding to children’s own learning/extending learning
Limited adult knowledge	Peer Learning	Adult Learning
Learning in/through Nature	Learning about Nature	Learning for Nature

The initial coding of ‘own ideas/experiences’ and ‘directing own learning’ derived from the research question, namely an exploration of children’s perspectives and lived experiences of Nature. My response to the participation and how the role of ‘peer learning’ to support the children as they formed their own ideas was also insightful as a means to support a child-initiated research agenda. I also categorised the research activities as ‘learning in/ through Nature’, learning about Nature’ or ‘learning for Nature’ and how that aligned with an ESD approach under Article 29 1 (e). These, in turn, folded into three prominent intertwined themes:

Figure 5.9: Overview of second stage coding for stage one.

The figure above provides an overview of how I categorised my initial coding system under three broader themes: **Nature learning, child participation** and **no rebuke**. The first two themes have been driven by the research aims and objectives, whereby the third of **no rebuke** emerged more organically.

The children's ownership of the research process and their capacity to confidently contribute to the research question was clearly evident at this stage of data analysis. For example, I could readily identify an abundance of views surrounding Nature learning. In addition, it was also apparent that they expressed their preferred means to take part in the activities in many different ways. And finally, they had a lot more expertise to share that I did not readily understand but were nonetheless of importance to them as research contributors. Therefore, the final three themes were renamed as **Nature Learning, Participatory Rights defined by Children** and **Making Space for Unicorns** to align with the data analysis process with the CRAG discussed in the following chapter and the findings chapters 8 and 9.

Chapter 6. Stage 1: Designing a child rights-based participatory methodology with young children.

6.1. Introduction

Chapter 5 outlines the broad principles of child rights-based research and explains how they are applied in this approach. To recap, the study took much of its guidance from Lundy and colleagues' child rights-based approach, where young children were involved in each of the research stages (Lundy & McEvoy, 2009, 2012; Lundy et al., 2011). This chapter gives a detailed account of that involvement. I begin by discussing the recruitment process and participant group criterion and demonstrate how decisions involving the children's input were made even at this very early stage. This is continued with an analysis of how the children's research advisory group (CRAG) evaluated research methods and how this process introduced a new research method that I had not thought of, which was particularly salient to the local context. In addition, the next section explores how the CRAG informed my understanding of the setting's culture and the relevance of this in designing an authentic approach with them. The same guidance also informed the elements of audience and influence of the *Lundy Model* to have more meaning for the young participants. I also explain how a change of roles was made for the CRAG's involvement following their input. The final section of the chapter discusses the data analysis process with the CRAG. I begin with a short discussion on how the role change brought complexities to that process. I describe how data analysis with the group became a stepped process in keeping with a rights-based research approach.

6.2. Recruitment process

The research site involved in this study was a privately-owned Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE)²³ sessional preschool located in Southeast Ireland. The site was unknown to me but was approached because of its access to the natural environment for children. Going forward, it would be important to carry out a similar study for settings that are limited in their access exploring both the implications and possibilities of that for children under Article 29 1 (e) (Osgood 2022, 2025). The setting had 18 children in total from a mixed age range of 2-5 years and a variation of socio-economic backgrounds. There were 4 ECEC practitioners working on a full/part-time basis, including the owner/gatekeeper. An initial gatekeeper's information evening was held using a presentation (Appendix B) to give an

²³ The Early Childhood Care and Education Programme (ECCE) is a universal two-year preschool programme available in Ireland to all children within the eligible age range.

overview of the project and provide an opportunity for questions. Although support for the project was readily offered, the meeting was followed by a two-week grace period to allow any further questions or thoughts to be accounted for from the gatekeeper's side (Appendix C). The gatekeeper distributed a subsequent research information package to all families at the research site (Appendix D). Included in this was a research poster that was placed on the site's noticeboard. Particular attention was paid to the visuals used in the poster to promote both myself and the project in a fun and playful manner and encourage a sense of rapport building and dialogue. All corresponding information material for the recruitment process is attached in the appendices. As a child rights-based participatory study, I anticipated working with the young children in two distinct groups during all the research stages, as follows:

6.2.1. Children's Research Advisory Group (CRAG) (Lundy & McEvoy, 2011).

Recruitment criteria for this group included their closeness in age (3-5 years) to that of the research participants (2-3 years) and, having already spent a year in the preschool, their existing knowledge, such as insight into the local culture of the setting. That and their own approaches to Nature learning positioned them as experts in an advisory role to support the study. It is important to note that the initial research plan envisaged the CRAG's involvement in the design stage (including the choice of research methods) and the data analysis and dissemination stages. How this role evolved is explained in more detail in section 6.7.

The recruitment process included an informal meet and greet morning at the preschool with the children and their families and distribution of information material, including a personalised storybook explaining the research process and proposed children's involvement to read at home for further discussion. This also included an invitation to contact the adult researcher with other questions or comments (Appendix E). For the most part, the children showed an initial interest in what I was distributing, but equally, as they were yet to give their assent, the dialogue was through their families. I mainly used the opportunity to put a face to the name at this point. Seven children were in this group: 2 girls and five boys.

6.2.2. Research participants.

This group consisted of younger children (2-3 years) who started new at the beginning of the preschool year. They were invited to engage in interactive, participatory

methods during the data collection phase to share their own perspectives of Nature as per Article 29 1 (e). The recruitment process for this group included a similar informal meet and greet session with children and their families and a distribution of information materials, including a personalised storybook. This book was designed with the guidance of the CRAG members to include interesting pictures. It also had an invitation to contact the adult researcher with any further questions or comments (Appendix F). Again, as with the initial meet-up with the CRAG members and their families, communication, for the most part, was done through the families, but interestingly, this time, it was the CRAG who made sure that the storybook was distributed to the younger participants. They also took one each for themselves. I considered this relational approach central to the recruitment process in terms of rapport building and integrating research in a manner that was authentic and non-invasive to the local culture. This was also furthered by reading the storybook as the adult researcher at the first research workshop to facilitate further understanding and questions from the process participants and inform me of their understanding. This session also included a bag of natural artefacts and my soft toy assistant, Hazel, following the CRAG's guidance that there should be plenty of interesting things to hold for each participant. There were nine children in this group: 2 girls and seven boys.

Figure 6.1: Research Storybook and props.

It is important to underline the role of rapport building already during recruitment. I read the book on the floor in the reading corner of the setting's hallway, where all the ECEC

practitioners and CRAG members fully viewed the research participants. The children sat on cushions reflective of how they would ordinarily read stories with their more familiar practitioners and joined the session freely, which I considered a more realistic and rights-respecting recruitment approach for this context. There was movement, plenty of it, going back and forth to see what everyone else was doing, washing hands, getting tissues, while this new activity was happening. It was not long before the questions and ideas began. There was a variation in verbal participation and a possible repetition of one another's ideas, but from working previously with the CRAG, I understood the centrality of this session. Its primary relevance was trust and relationship forming on both sides to better serve a rights-based research approach in the future as defined by the children rather than adults.

6.2.3. Recruitment of adult participants and an 'identified listener'.

Initially, the study also envisaged including adults as research participants towards the end of the overall process. There were two objectives for this: firstly, to explore what the practitioners and families learned from the children's involvement in the study (Appendix H), and secondly, to establish an 'identified listener' as outlined by Lundy and colleagues' rights-based research approach (Lundy, 2007; Lundy et al., 2011, 2012). An 'identified listener' is a party involved in decision-making matters affecting children, in this case, their education, under Article 29 1 (e). Establishing a commitment from one could offer the participants a meaningful audience for their research under Article 12. The preschool owner had agreed to take on this role, while recruitment letters were also sent to several external candidates (Appendix I). It is important to note that this was an element of the original research concept that was changed following the guidance of the CRAG members and participants, explored further below. For now, I will continue with a description of the CRAG role and their evaluation of suitable research methods.

6.3. CRAG research methods evaluations

Rights-based research requires that methods are chosen with great care, as it is not those chosen that are of stand-alone significance but how they shall be used that determines a fully rights-compliant approach (Bessell, 2017). Figure 6.2 extracts my reflective handwritten field notes (Appendix K) during the introductory workshop and subsequent informal rapport-building sessions. These notes offer a rationale for how I interpreted the initial advice from the CRAG members as possible criteria for suitable research methods.

Having reflected on those two sessions and on interactions with the CRAG, I considered methods that met the following criteria to be a good starting point in developing a methodology with them from their perspectives:

1. Explorative, sensorial, and aesthetic.
2. Free movement and facilitation of gross motor movement.
3. Plentiful.
4. Contain tools.
5. Encompass imaginary role play.

Figure 6.2: Extract of reflective field notes from Workshop 1 (The Icebreaker, May 15th) and Informal/Hangout Session (May 24th)

Direction from CRAG members from Workshop 1 (The Icebreaker May 15th) and Informal/Hangout Session (May 24th)

CRAG members voiced the following ideas in relation to the initial research topic

- *Do work*
- *Look at work*
- *Be with friends*
- *Go back to big garden*
- *Buckets are cute*
- *Likes bikes, planting, spiders, unicorns, drawing, animals, flowers, sticks*
- *Food*

Workshops 2 & 3 will look at research methods and further aspects of the research question. Given the local context, the layout of facilities (1 room and 1 outdoor area), and group size (18 approx.), along with the wishes of the young CRAG members to remain with their friends and move back and forth from a variation of activities, the next workshop will incorporate these elements to respect own perspectives into the methodology.

Aside from taking guidance from the group about suitable research methods, they also provided insight into how we could support adult/child power dynamics within the space. For example, I learned to understand how they chose to readily share thoughts by themselves and with the support of one another. This, in turn, helped me to develop a listening strategy, where we could readily take their ideas as children over mine as an adult to better engage with more child-initiated research. I developed the visual set out in Figure 6.3 after this session and used it in all subsequent sessions to monitor whose perspectives were being heard and how I reconciled them to reflect the research objectives. For example, when they told me that they wanted ‘*to do work*’ with me and that ‘*they wanted to be with their friends*’, I understood that these were their contributions to how we would establish our research group identity and what an inclusive approach should look like for them.

Several common methods used in participatory research with children were presented to the group for further evaluation for suitable research design in subsequent workshops. Complete copies of the reflective field notes from each session can be found in Appendices K, L and M. The CRAG members critically analysed each method to promote what Larkins et al. (2015) describe as children’s influence over the maximum range of research processes within the limited resources secured or created for the study. These methods and how the CRAG evaluated them are now outlined in turn.

6.3.1. Child-led tours.

A child-led tour is often considered an inclusive, participatory activity that can allow seeing a setting from a young child’s eyes. Clark & Moss (2011) describe how these ‘walking tours’ enable the child to set the agenda and reveal valuable information. This has manifold benefits

Figure 6.3: Power balance checklist visual – Workshop 1

from simply getting to know the research space, while also bridging the adult-child power gap by building relationships and understanding the practices in that cultural context (Roberts-Holmes, 2014; Green, 2015). However, in their work, Ceballos and Susinos (2022) argue that the methodology can require a combination of both voice and physical movement, limiting its inclusiveness.

6.3.1.1. CRAG evaluation of child-led tours.

The CRAG evaluated this method during each workshop to better understand its effectiveness. During Workshop 1, the CRAG was enthused to use the technique to show me what was in their garden, but after an initial fast-moving tour, enthusiasm dwindled, and they communicated their desire for more hands-on research work. Workshop 2, which involved more hands-on work, including insect/bird hunts, gave rise to a child-initiated second garden tour. However, again, preference was given to exploring materials I had brought rather than discussing certain spots in the garden. The following extract from my reflective field notes during a seed planting activity that the children preferred over taking me on tour (Appendix L) offers further insight into the session:

Figure 6.4: Extract (a) from reflective field notes Workshop 2

While the children came at various stages to engage, attention was given for the most part to the digging/ filling of pots with compost using buckets and shovels. CRAG members spoke briefly as to what other seeds they could grow (sweetcorn, berries) and making lots of pots to take home to their family members. The majority knew a seed needed dirt and water to grow, some spoke about planting seeds with family members, others were more interested in putting seeds into dirt, covering seeds with dirt. Extra resources were left after the session in the sandpit to support this interest. Limited ideas discussion **arose due to the large number of children. It was apparent that the CRAG members had ideas to share but eliciting these due to facilitating the large number proved difficult and stronger voices dominated.**

Workshop 3 started with a child-led garden tour, where the CRAG described their enthusiasm for using the large open space. This was also apparent in many of their own garden designs (discussed further in the arts-based research methods below). The overall evaluation of the child-led walking tour was that there needed to be more defined opportunities to explore because young children *‘like to do lots of things.’*

6.3.2. Drawings

Roberts-Holmes (2014) describes drawings as early writing and an inclusive, participatory technique if self-initiated, spontaneous, and non-invasive. When a child is drawing, they are putting their thoughts into action, which provides space to develop their visual thinking. They can be a powerful means of representation, with children concentrating for long periods on their creations (Clark & Moss, 2011). However, interpretations of drawings can be

ambiguous, and the meaning can be lost if a child is asked directly for a description. It is the process alongside a narrative discussion while the young child draws, where a more meaningful perspective can be found (Alderson & Morrow, 2011; Alderson, 2012). Ethical considerations with drawings included the overall principle of participation; for example, several participants expressed a need for more confidence to draw. The overall respect for a child's work is paramount and requires responsible researcher practices to ensure no adult interpretation or assumption of ideas in this format is made.

6.3.2.1. CRAG evaluation of drawings

A particular consideration that the CRAG members put forward was property ownership; they were happy for me to ask permission to make a copy of a drawing through a camera or photocopier but then to return it to its rightful owner. The group members evaluated this research method in Workshops 1 and 3. The children were highly enthused to explore drawing materials and mark-making from the onset. Four members engaged for long periods, while others preferred me to draw for them as they did not feel confident. While the discursive benefit of the drawing process was apparent in terms of creating a space to share and form views, not all children wanted to draw or felt confident to do so. Therefore, only a few members expressed a value for it in terms of a suitable research method.

6.3.3. Arts-based projects (*playdough, model making, visual images*)

As the group expressed the view that not all children may wish to draw or feel confident to do so, an alternative arts-based method was offered. Children can also use play dough, model-making with open-ended materials, or visual images (photographs/prints) to explore and think through creative projects meaningful to them and with which they feel competent to engage (NCCA, 2009; Nutbrown, 2013). As with drawings, the creative process and the narrative discussions coincide, which can provide insightful perspectives from the young child (Mukherji et al., 2018). Engaging with materials such as playdough, sand, water, and anything that can offer symbolic meaning gives the young mind the occasion to make sense of their experiences and is a rich means to explore and think (NCCA 2009). Also, being open-ended allows enormous scope for creativity. These visual, hands-on forms of communication can empower the preverbal or timid child or the child who prefers exploring with their senses and confirm that methods need not be limited to the spoken word (Clark, 2017; Mukherji et al., 2018). Ethical considerations included mysophobia (fear of

dirt/contamination) and tactile defensiveness, while being too open-ended could cause anxiety or fear of what might be expected.

6.3.3.1 CRAG evaluation of arts-based projects.

The group responded to this research method very positively. A sense of confidence in engaging with the materials provided (cardboard, paint, playdough, glue, cut-out shapes and images) among the members was apparent. I wondered if it was because they were materials often used in the setting or whether the open-ended nature of materials facilitated their exploration and learning. As it transpired, we did have one occasion where tactile defensiveness occurred while making bird feeders with peanut butter. It was quickly resolved by tying a string to the apple and wiping the peanut butter on my trousers. That evolved into a fun exchange with the group and could be viewed as a power dismantling or trust-building moment authentic to the research space. Furthermore, a confident atmosphere in the research space brought a natural conversation flow. The effectiveness of this method's discursive element was also apparent as the children's voices started to become more notable as distinct from my own as they engaged with the tools.

6.3.4. *Nature-based arts projects.*

Nature-based arts projects can be described as an extension of the arts-based method. They also incorporate the natural world and, therefore, align with the research topic. Activities ranged from planting seeds/bulbs/trees, insect hunts, making bird feeders and insect homes, playing with water and sand, exploring hedgerows, and creating waste management systems. I offered a range of activities to support an inclusive creative methodology for capacity building in forming and expressing ideas based on design workshops with the CRAG (Mukherji et al., 2018). Louv (2017) describes how Nature stimulates the senses, and direct contact with natural elements invites children's creativity through possibilities for exploring and thinking (Barrable & Arvanitis, 2019). Therefore, I considered these projects pertinent to the methodology because they were interest-led, participatory and inclusive. Again, like drawing and arts-based methods, it is through the creative process that children have the opportunity to put their thoughts into action and to form and express their own views (Lundy et al., 2011, 2012; Roberts-Holmes, 2014). Ethical considerations included sensitivities to natural materials/insects, infringement on contextual cultural practices, access to the natural environment, group size, time constraints, health risks such as insect bites, allergies, health and safety preschool regulations, and need for First aid. These did not emerge during this

study. Possible alternatives included using visuals such as books, posters, puppets, or a collection of pre-gathered natural materials.

6.3.4.1. CRAG evaluation of Nature-based arts projects.

One issue that emerged was group size, which limited my role as an adult listener and frustrated some of the CRAG. This was accommodated by enlisting the support of the other ECEC practitioners on site and organising extra sessions in smaller groups. Aside from that, the research site's flexible nature and the free-flowing participation process supported this method in this context (Huser et al., 2022). The CRAG members evaluated this method in Workshops 1 and 2. The group were invited to explore the imagery of native insects and birds and engage in an insect hunt. The free movement of this method was positively received. I also noted confidence in the group when they were deciding their own use of outdoor space and existing knowledge as to where best to locate insects. Looking at the imagery when insects were found promoted rich discussion, with participants sharing their own experiences of them alongside enthusiasm to hear new learning. This aspect was particularly indicative of the children's own definition of Article 13 and their right to information. Workshop 2 involved a large group planting project, where CRAG members and their friends were invited to plant sunflower seeds. Certain aspects of this project, such as gardening trowels, pots, and compost, were positively received. The same tools were taken to the sand pit for further exploration. As mentioned above, the group size also limited the number of views that could be heard. A smaller group stayed to engage with actual seed planting and a discussion about the children's own gardening experiences. However, some children felt frustrated about the small number of tools I had and a resulting reluctance to take turns, which caused several participants to drop interest and involvement. The following short abstract from my reflective field notes on workshop two further highlights this issue:

Figure 6.5: Extract (b) from reflective field notes from Workshop 2

Framing Workshop 3 – Research Methods

While the CRAG members had an opportunity to engage in nature-based activities, discussion and their ideas to Research design and questions were limited. With feedback from the children, contextual understanding is developing as is an understanding of group dynamics and interests, Workshop 3 will be framed as follows,

2 Small group (3 children) workshops (over 2 days June 12th & June 18th)

Comparatively, the open-ended nature of both the arts-based and nature-based art activities provided a space that supported the flexibility needed for the participants to have an influence on the research agenda. Furthermore, the rich peer discussions that occurred during the sessions resulted in the CRAG evaluating a research method that I had not initially thought to include.

6.4. Introducing a new research method: the influence of the CRAG.

Aside from hearing more children's voices, the open-ended nature developed in the research space also supported the CRAG to contribute their own topics of interest and change the research agenda with their own perspectives. This was essential learning because I could see that, apart from deciding suitable research methods in this design phase, the CRAG members simultaneously defined their participatory rights, contributing to the evolution of rights-respecting strategies for this context. Particularly notable was the CRAG members' enjoyment of storytelling as a communication mode. The following extract from my reflective field notes from workshop 3 (Appendix M) provide a further overview of the CRAG's guidance towards using storytelling to capture their views better.

The CRAG members were told the story with the assistance of Hazel the Hedgehog, with particular interest as to whose turn it was to hold her rather than the story itself. Once set up for junk art activity, engaging with all the different colour paints and paint itself showed a method, the children enjoyed and were **confident** to engage with. Participatory rights were emphasised through, choice of participation or not and for how long (one child did two), autonomy and agency through freedom of colour and paintbrush choice and freedom of expression of ideas as to what children like to do when they are outdoors, the decision as to what would go into each design and overall ownership of the design. Ideas formed as the CRAG members engaged with their '*creations*'. (CRAG member's own words).

Figure 6.6: Extract(a) from reflective field notes from Workshop 3

We can see from the above and below extract that a number of ideas were evolving and that while not all fit into my ideal of an outdoor area for children to explore Nature, they reminded me it was their ideal being expressed. I had been busy applying a strategy to monitor an understanding of the research thus far, but I was also learning the relevance of the children's own identity and matters important to them as they shared their views. They certainly did enjoy sharing stories, and right here in this moment, they had guided me to how a safe research space was defined on their terms and that it was time to consider storytelling as a research method.

*I love doing this. I am making it really purple. I am putting sellotape in the garden.
I have grass and the sun.
I have white clouds because you have different weather. And a seesaw.
I like to run around and play football.
I like playing.
There is a place for magic potions.
I am putting a MacDonal'd's in the garden.
I find Easter eggs in the garden. And rocks. And I throw the rocks into the water.
There are birdies and cows and we have trees. I am painting a tree.
Here is a puddle and a field and the grass and all this space for playing soccer and
going on my bike that is blue.
Children like building things in the garden. Like queen/king castles and my seesaw.*

Figure 6.7: Extract(b) from reflective field notes from Workshop 3

6.4.1. Storytelling research method.

Davies (2007) describes storytelling as a socially inclusive research method. It does not need to be written or read, and depending on the adult's ability and willingness to connect with how the young child chooses to engage, the story content can be open to any form of collaborative construction. That part is key in creating an opportunity to dismantle adult power and support children to drive their own learning agendas. While the content can appear strange from an adult perspective, which happened all the time for me, it is meaningful to the child in their linguistic repertoire, and therefore, it is the function of the researcher to engage with it respectfully (Davies, 2007; Moore, 2014). Listening attentively when not fully understanding and not interrupting shifts the power to the child and can support the researcher to better incorporate children's everyday theories and practices (Davies, 2007; Moore, 2014; Lyndon et al., 2019; Shaik, 2021).

Storytelling can captivate people, allowing them to see and feel the perspectives of others while also allowing for greater individual understanding and interpretation (Phillips, 2013). As mentioned above, in Workshop 1, it became apparent that the group were eager to share their stories, ranging from fictional stories to their own experiences and imaginative thoughts.

Interestingly, while the stories were shared, peer discussion was provoked, with other members adding their own ideas and meaning. This provided insight into the elements of storytelling, namely the social and relational aspects, that supported the children together as a group to bring one another's views forward (Garvis et al., 2015). Equally, this mode of peer communication, aside from being fun, also had an empowering feel. The children's knowledge was being represented and valued, offering a workable power-dismantling strategy to implement in that I could actively replace my research agenda with theirs. During my interaction with the group, I noticed a certain level of confidence in their storytelling that was not present when answering direct questions.

Ethical considerations for this method are related to the issue of group discussion. It can be intimidating, with some voices being more dominant, making it less inclusive for all children (Green, 2015). Questions needed to be carefully considered to ensure that all children understood them, alongside acknowledging a genuine fear that children experience of needing to get something right for fear of being ridiculed (Lundy et al., 2011). It was also difficult to distinguish individual views from group views (Roberts-Holmes, 2014; Fane et al., 2018). Group power dynamics can be a barrier to collecting high-quality evidence with more dominant voices being represented. Therefore, I did the storytelling in chat form or smaller groups to make the environment more relaxed, comfortable, and appealing. Further sensitivities include disclosed personal information, managed through the ethical principles of confidentiality and informed consent processes outlined above.

As part of Workshop 3, the CRAG members were invited to engage with a tailored storytelling method (Appendix N) that depicted an adult needing the help of young children to better understand what young children think about Nature. I had two reasons for writing this story. Firstly, resonating with Mayne et al.'s (2017) argument that the quality of overall child participation stems from the quality of strategies to establish how understanding has been achieved, discussed further in the following section, I wanted to take the opportunity to explore with the CRAG their knowledge of the research topic this far. Also, I wanted to give them a chance to assess a research technique that seemed to meet many of the criteria for engaging in discussions, which had been a recurring theme throughout our prior sessions.

6.4.1.1. CRAG evaluation of storytelling

The story's impact, particularly the idea of debunking the adult's position and underlining the importance of the children's expertise, was remarkably evident amongst the CRAG members. The space became lively in the discussion, which carried through into the follow-on activity, whereby the children were invited to design an outdoor area with loose parts to explore the ideas they had shared further. However, the group expressed their disappointment about my lack of props or puppets for the workshop. They suggested that if using this method with the research participants, I would need a more plentiful supply so that everyone had one to hold. I was also advised to add pictures to look at when storytelling. Overall, the members' enjoyment of this means to participate was clear and indicated a method which echoed a research space that fits with the culture of this context.

In addition to evaluating suitable research methods for a proposed research toolbox, the guidance from the CRAG members again underlined to me that an understanding of the cultural context of the research site was fundamental to developing authentic rights respecting research strategies (Lundy, 2007; Lundy & McEvoy, 2011; Lundy et al., 2012; Mayne et al., 2016).

6.5. CRAG guidance in understanding the cultural context for research design.

Some CRAG members' interest in participating in the project was high. Coming into the setting as a first-time researcher and meeting this interest as an unfamiliar ECEC practitioner was exciting and somewhat daunting. Before the first workshop and engagement with the CRAG, it had been decided to locate the research space outdoors in a separate, quieter area to minimise distraction. I had brought a picnic blanket, my signature toolkit (a picnic basket), Hazel the hedgehog (the soft toy research assistant featured in the research introduction story), a notebook and a pen. Their disappointment that I had not brought an actual picnic will forever haunt me. This was followed by their disappointment that I had not brought anything of interest to explore in the basket, and, aside from holding Hazel and trying out my notebook and pen, the novelty of sitting on a blanket with nothing to do wore off quickly. This was a significant intervention by the CRAG. I had assumed that I would be leading participants if I had brought adult-initiated materials (Shier, 2016), but the CRAG showed that this was misplaced.

I had underestimated the value of simply bringing loads of interesting stuff, not to dive into the research question right off the bat, but rather to help build rapport and develop an understanding of the local culture (Lyndon et al., 2019; Clark, 2020; Husar et al., 2022). Indeed, I had rapport-building as part of the workshop objective. Still, I had presented it more as an obvious given in the design phase and had not understood its centrality in keeping the project grounded in children's perspectives.

Figure 6.8: Hazel the Hedgehog and the research basket

Nevertheless, all was not lost; being outdoors in a new area to explore offered an unplanned democratic space to do that and gain first-hand insight into how this group of children each defined their participatory rights. For example, one child sat on a bike for the duration of their participation; a couple played with the setting owner's dog while expressing their views; one drew pictures in my notebook, one told funny Nature stories and one left to go back and play with friends in the main outdoor area. I left the workshop with a list of suggested materials from the CRAG for the next session and a significantly heightened understanding of the need for reflexivity (Lyndon et al., 2019). Time and space between the workshops as part of the research design were needed for me to grasp the CRAG's guidance better and navigate the rest of the research journey. Further examples of their guidance relevant to understanding the cultural context are explored in Chapter 9.

6.6. Audience and influence at a local level

Although continuous reflection helped ensure that participation was authentic rather than tokenistic, just listening to the participants' ideas was not enough (Shier, 2016; Tisdall,

2015). Instead, what weight I gave them would determine any real substance to realising the children's own participatory rights under Article 12 (CRC, 2006; Ceballos & Susinos, 2022). McNaughton, Smith, and Davies (2006) state that, in practical terms, all formal research involving children requires some level of adult direction. While children's research participatory rights must be supported, Tisdall (2016) highlights that exploring how it is done is still necessary. Wall et al. (2019) put forward an intergenerational approach to strike the right balance to represent young children's participation while meeting research objectives. The adult researcher should not be afraid to shape the research agenda but must do so in a responsive, sensitive way and by how the children expressed their participation preferences. For this part, I reflected at length on how I could bring to life the specific aspects of 'audience' and 'influence' of the Lundy model for the participants to enjoy their rights definitions first-hand. At this stage, I had still not found a suitable external 'identified listener'. Establishing an 'identified listener' early in the research stage is something that Lundy and colleagues recommend in committing that participants' contributions will be given due weight by a person directly involved in decision-making. One of the study's main objectives was to contribute to developing a rights-based ESD approach for the early education sector. I initially approached the local Department of Education inspector (Appendix I) but did not receive a response. This caused me to question their suitability, and as I began to build a rapport with the CRAG, I did not consider a decision-maker that far removed from the children's own lives to be that meaningful for them. This also panicked me, mainly because research has found that children have been disappointed that little account of their views was taken despite their engagement with research (Lundy, 2018). In turn, I started a further scouting exercise to find a suitable source of listening they enjoyed. That involved reviewing candidates' media profiles online, discussing their suitability with my supervisor, and attending local meetings at which they spoke. This was quite accessible as several candidates were local government representatives, and there were both local and national elections and plenty of canvassing taking place at the same time. Again, however, this scouting did not find a suitable identified listener for the context but instead informed me of what would not be appropriate and what could potentially expose the children to more of a tokenistic affair (Lundy, 2018). I understood it was important that the children could see the influence of their research participation up close. Like Mayne et al. (2018), I began to move the focus on them directly experiencing influence-making in the research space rather than influencing policymakers at a macro level. Cassidy et al. (2022) contend that for young

children’s voices to have influence, someone must listen in the space where the voices are being shared. From working with this group, I learned that providing enough time and space to form, express and see their ideas in action was me and the children’s more familiar adults who were most suited to the role of ‘identified listener’. Figure 6.9 shows how this contribution was applied to the *Lundy model* to reflect a rights-based approach in a local context.

Figure 6.9: The Lundy model revised with CRAG guidance.

6.7. An influential change in roles

As already described, the CRAG had occupied an advisory role in the methodology, and initially, it was not envisaged that they would be involved in the data collection with the research participants. The following reflective field notes extracted from workshop three first highlighted this as a potential ethical issue:

What needs to be remarked on at this stage, is the possible blurred line between self and other given the closeness of age between CRAG member and research participant, the cognitive development of this particular age range (3-4 years) and the setup of the local context (both groups are together). However, it is the role of the adult researcher to continue to support both groups and develop capacity-building strategies that respect this sensitive consideration. At this stage, it is thought that both groups will share the same outdoor time and space but CRAG members will be involved in the analysis and interpretation of data collection (adult researcher with research participants only) in separate activities. **However, this requires more consideration and may not be respectful to the local culture.**

Figure 6.10: Extract (c) from reflective field notes Workshop 3

During phase 2 of the design process, I became concerned about the ethics of separating CRAG members. As I built rapport with the research participants, it became even more apparent that this approach was unfair and required careful consideration. In turn, it also translated into an opportunity for me, as the identified listener, to provide a more effective and accessible form of influence defined by the participants' enjoyment of rights. This led to introducing a new 'field assistant' research role for the CRAG members during the data collection phase.

6.7.1. Field assistants

The local research space consisted of a large group of mixed ages (2-5 years old) who played and interacted daily. To separate the groups would not have been respectful to the local culture but would instead have created an atmosphere of segregation contrary to a rights-respecting research approach (Mertens, 2007; Shier, 2016). Furthermore, the CRAG members indicated how much they enjoyed constructing ideas and sharing information with me and one another throughout the design stage. To stop this, while I remained onsite and worked with other children for phase 2, brought up ethical issues regarding an infringement of their participatory rights as they had defined them and, consequently, the possibility for emotional harm. I also considered it a violation of Article 13 - the right to information and freedom of expression, which includes freedom to seek, receive and impart knowledge and ideas of all kinds. It also infringed on their overall education rights by the groups' own rights definitions in that they wanted to continue to be part of the study, while ordinarily, the whole setting carried out activities together in one large mixed-age group. However, ensuring that I had heard every participant's view in a busy large group dynamic where some voices dominated others was challenging. Therefore, to resolve this issue, we put in place extra small group information workshop sessions specifically for the CRAG where they could continue to enjoy these rights and support their capacity as research field assistants. This role included developing research activities to be more authentic for the younger participants and also supporting them to take part by sharing what they knew about Nature. This was communicated to their families as a newsletter (Appendix O). To limit repetition, the detailed participation from these sessions is discussed further in the findings chapters.

As there was a change in the initially planned data usage with the CRAG and COVID-19 was taking place, informed consent was sought electronically via email and accompanied by a

video shared by the gatekeeper to the CRAG members from me (Appendix P). What essentially took place in these new information sessions were small group discussions and hands-on activities using different learning materials with visuals about different aspects of Nature. This approach supported the CRAG in deciding what interests them, the younger participants, and other children (Shier, 2016; Ceballos & Susinos, 2022). Examples of some of the information explored with the CRAG can be seen in the following images:

Figure 6.11: CRAG Information Insects/Animals Workshop Session 1.

Figure 6.12: CRAG Information Waste Management Workshop Session 3

6.7.2. *A change to how the adults listened.*

While I have thus far described a change in my understanding and listening role from working with the CRAG, they also provided insight into how the other adults in the process could support a listening strategy meaningful to them under Article 29 1 (e).

ECEC Practitioner - You made a whole book!
these are our pictures (CMG1)
and there's and my pictures (CMG1)
and that's mine (CMG2)
CMB1 is looking at the book and points to ants
EP - oh, ants!
That was a bit wiggly (CMG2)
EP - oh, I really like them hedgehogs
the worm is my one (CMG2)
the spider is my one (CMG1)
worms eat dirt (CMG2)
EP - What did you learn about the ants?
The feelers !!! (holding her hands over her head touches adult researcher's hands) (CMG1)

Figure 6.13: Extract of relational support with 'familiar adult' in scaffolding capacity to form and express views.

Again, to prevent repetition, the development of the participants' own book, *The Children's Nature Book*, is discussed further below in the section on data analysis with the CRAG, but how they shared it with one of the site's ECEC practitioners in the information workshop session two demonstrated above was very insightful. Their sharing of ideas and the response of the listening adult brought to light the significance of relational support with a familiar person in scaffolding the capacity to form and express their own views (Lundy, 2007; Lundy et al., 2011; 2012). This prompted me to think about how I had initially conceptualised the adult role within this project. I had planned to interview consenting practitioners and family members about the participants' learning, but it did not fit our co-designed methodology. Instead, how the CRAG recounted the research activities with their familiar adult demonstrated elements of space, voice, and audience from the Lundy Model (2007) that were more conducive and respectful of the local context. In the above samples, there were no pre-set questions but relatively positive responses and admiration for their work, which offered a platform for more individual participation and exploration of children's own perspectives and

what was of relevance or interest in the study for each child involved (Robert-Holmes, 2014). For that matter, I concluded that interviewing any adults to gain ‘second hand’ insight into the children’s perspectives was not aligned with the study’s ethos. As an alternative, I provided resources to take home (sunflower seeds, bird feeding materials, insect charts and magnifying glasses, homemade recycling lists and a copy of *The Nature Book*) as tools to support the children better in sharing their research participation and have it responded to, in a format that they could themselves decide. The families and practitioners instead shared their feedback in dialogue form during the sessions or through email.

6.8. External audience and influence

As described, the dissemination process was redesigned to support the participants’ views to be listened to in an authentic manner under Article 12, which I renamed ‘internal audience and influence’. Extending this to ‘external audience and influence’ very much continues to be an ongoing process. Arguably, it differs from the concept of ‘identified listener’ (Lundy, 2007) in that the young participants are no longer aware of who exactly is listening to their views and how they are influencing decision-making processes. In the aftermath of the study (2019-2020) and the publication of *The Children’s Nature Book*, corresponding families were sent email updates on research outputs; however, there was minimal response. This was also the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, where many families had more pending issues and concerns to manage. From an ethical perspective, I decided that it was no longer appropriate or authentic for the participants and their families to continue sending correspondence on the study. In addition, the setting itself closed shortly afterwards, and the participating children moved to other settings and primary schools, ending our communication through the gatekeeper. However, the children’s contributions continue to have an audience, both in terms of practice and research, and pedagogical crossovers have been identified with early childhood theory, rights-based theory, and ESD theory.

6.8.1. Theory to practice teaching

I have used the opportunity to share participants’ contributions in my own delivery of early childhood education and care modules at the South East Technological University in Ireland. Modules include *Early Childhood Pedagogy*, *Creative Arts in ECEC*, *Children with Additional Needs*, *Critical Perspectives on Children’s Health and Well-being in ECEC*, *Transformative Children Rights Education* and *Arts-based Research in ECEC*. I consider this

an authentic means of ‘external audience and influence’ for the study. As outlined above, I had struggled with my own understanding of the practicalities of embedding rights-based theory into practice, and using the children’s research contributions in the teaching space offers a real opportunity to provide practitioner-based learning in furthering rights-based pedagogy.

6.8.2. Publications and conferences

I have also had the opportunity to publish articles on different aspects of the study in both peer and non-peer-reviewed learning resources. Audiences for these publications include early childhood students and lecturers, which provide further opportunities for the participant’s views to influence practice. Publications in international journals such as the *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal (EECERJ)* and *An Leanbh Óg* have furthered this audience by providing new knowledge in the areas of both education and participatory rights for young children. In addition, the children’s contributions were presented at national and international conferences, including *the European Early Childhood Education Research Association (EECERA) 2022, Glasgow, Scotland, and 2024, Brighton, United Kingdom, Early Childhood Voices (ECV) 2022, Charles Stuart University, Australia, Human Rights Education Conference 2023, University City Dublin, Ireland*. At a local level, I have also used the research to support school children and children living in my area in having their contributions heard in urban development plans with local authorities.

6.8.3. International research collaboration

More recently, I have also become a member of a transnational dialogue research group that meets annually to examine the gaps and issues pertaining to developing ESD approaches for early childhood. Other international collaborations also include being a member of the EECERA Sustainability Special Interest Group, where I had the opportunity to share the children’s contributions to their position statement on ESD in ECEC. The *EECERA Board of Trustees* ratified this statement, and this year’s *EECERA 2024* conference was on ESD at which I presented. I am also a committee member of *OMEP Ireland* and have been elected president for 2024. Since becoming a committee member, *OMEP Ireland* has organised a national ESD conference and published a special issue on ESD in association with *An Leanbh Óg*. This is particularly noteworthy given *OMEP Ireland’s* limited involvement in earlier *OMEP* initiatives for ESD, as described in Chapter 3.

6.8.4. *Free online learning resources.*

One aspect of dissemination by the CRAG was to create a learning resource about Nature for other children. We did this as described with their publication of *The Children's Nature Book*. A more generic form of this was created in our research blog, which shared updates on the research activities and the resources that we used. Originally, this had been created for the children's families to gain insight into our work. As interest in the research grew, it was also shared with other ECEC practitioners and those working in the area to learn how we created a rights-based ESD curriculum in a local context. Similarly, as part of my work with *OMEP Ireland*, I have been involved in developing a free online module, *Sustainability from the Start*, created for the early childhood sector as part of an Erasmus Plus project. This has also given an opportunity to share practical contributions from the participants, such as the importance of having enough tools for each child, facilitating colour preferences and making space for storytelling.

6.8.5. *Submission to the Aistear Updating Process.*

Most recently, the study has also had the opportunity to submit feedback on the topics of ESD and children's rights (Appendix V) as part of the updating process for the national curriculum framework Aistear (NCCA, 2024), previously discussed in Chapter 4. This has included a recommendation to present sustainability as an evolving concept with different starting points depending on local context for more effective and respectful learning. The submission also provided the framework writers with suggested reading putting forward the relevance of integrating all of the sustainability pillars (ecological, economic, social and cultural and political) (UN, 2010) into daily practice. Finally, the study's submission raised the point on the familiar phase of children's 'rights and responsibilities' (NCCA, 2009) and recommended to separate these two concepts to avoid misrepresenting children's rights being dependent on anything, for example their capacity to take responsibility for social action or overall actions towards common good. A full copy of the submission report can be found in Appendix V.

This evident traction from the research provided much of the rationale for developing a second stage of the study. One of the research aims was to build the capacity of practitioners to integrate child rights-based ESD into their practice. Equally as described in Chapter 4, it

has been identified that further research is required to examine the type of transformative leadership necessary to better support effective ESD. Therefore, I decided that the next step in terms of authentic ‘audience and influence’ for this study was to share the children’s contributions with early childhood practitioners to gain their insights in furthering the development of a transformative ‘bottom-up’ approach to ESD for the sector under Article 29 1 (e). Findings of which are discussed in Chapter 10.

Table 6.1: Overview of research workshop sessions for Phase 2

<p>Phase 2</p> <p>Session 1 – Introduction to the project with research participants</p> <p>**Session 2 – Understanding local context/building rapport. Large group session wildflower seed sowing with CRAG members, research participants & ECEC practitioners</p> <p>**Session 3 – Developing field assistant role small group discussion with CRAG exploring suitable topics of interest</p> <p>Session 4 – Insect hunt large group with research participants and CRAG members in field assistant capacity</p> <p>Session 5 – Bird feeding small group session with research participants</p> <p>Session 6 – Large group session planting trees with CRAG members, research participants & ECEC practitioners.</p> <p>Session 7(a) – Small group initial data analysis session with CRAG members</p> <p>Session 7(b) – Large outdoor mixed group session with research participant led tours</p> <p>**Session 8 – Developing field assistant role small group discussion with CRAG exploring suitable topics of interest</p> <p>Session 9 – Waste management small group session with research participants</p> <p>Session 10 – End of phase 2 research party.</p>

6.9. Data analysis process designed with the CRAG for phase 2.

As I have explained above, phase 2 involved a change in the role of the CRAG, including being ‘field assistants’. Additional research workshop sessions (sessions 2, 3 and 8) were implemented to facilitate this change, as seen in Table 6.1. Each session was one hour in length and comprised activities relating to arts-based Nature projects and storytelling research methods. Sessions were recorded using an audio recorder and later transcribed into MS Word documents for analysis. However, these changes brought complexities in terms of overlapping the data collection and analysis processes to develop a methodology that would authentically respect the participants’ participatory rights definitions. Session 7 (a) was designed to analyse the data produced through the research activities (presented as

photographs, see Figure 6.14) with the CRAG (in their role as field assistants).

Figure 6.14: Photo Walls used in the data analysis process with the CRAG.

As per my first research aim, I hoped to gain insight into their perspectives, which could contribute to achieving authentic education for early childhood under Article 29 1(e).

There were a number of considerations as to why I presented the ‘data’ to the CRAG in this form. For example, how or what I presented as ‘data’ to the CRAG had the potential to push an adult rather than child-initiated interpretation. This is because I would be the one to decide which elements of our research were relevant and could ultimately miss out on essential knowledge (Shier, 2016). The session began in a similar way to the others with our negotiated participation process, namely a look at what I had brought in my basket and if it interested the members. The next step in the process was to lay the ‘data’ out, which first involved how many photo boards could be stacked on top of one another. This also involved discussing how I made them, what materials I used, and why some had black markers on them and some did not. Incidentally, they were made from green cardboard from the

recycling bin on campus, and the black marker was unintentional on my part. Then we started:

AR - I want to hear what you thinklet's take one at a time, will we? And this is data analysis

I never knewed that before (CMB5)

Figure 6.15: Starting the data analysis process

I smile at this captured moment for several reasons. Firstly, I am reminded of the excitement and interest in the space with the CRAG, but when I said this was ‘data analysis’, there was something in the back of my head thinking that I sounded quite artificial and that the term was misplaced. Similar to the work of Lundy et al. (2011), I had expected that we would be producing statistics or concrete representation using some creative ‘child-appropriate’ sorting activity that would inform a child rights-based ESD approach. But I did not get what I expected. The reality was that the CRAG had many perspectives about Nature that they eagerly shared, but I cannot distinguish how the session differed from that of data collection. Certainly, there was a buzz of dialogue while engaging with the ‘data’ and an authentic interest in sharing perspectives and lived experiences of Nature in accordance with my research question. However, the outcome of the session has made it difficult to articulate the process of analysing data with the CRAG using tidy research terminology. Instead, the CRAG continued their advisory role as experts on engaging in research with young children while also providing concrete data surrounding children’s perspectives under Article 29 1 (e), suggesting that the line between data collection and analysis can be porous. Dipping back and forth between the two processes is what happened, and it is, therefore, necessary to acknowledge this and discuss it to shed further light on child rights research methodology.

6.10. A stepped data analysis process

The data analysis process with the CRAG can be best described as a stepped process that is summarised in Figure 6.16:

Figure 6.16: Stepped process for data analysis with CRAG

I will use each step as a subheading to give a more detailed discussion of the process.

6.11.1. Step 1. Identifying own interests and ideas as 'themes'

The CRAG's enjoyment of sharing stories and accessing new information has been outlined in the previous chapter. This approach offered an organic, non-invasive platform through which engaging with rights-based data analysis could also be undertaken. The children examined materials in these information sessions with my support and pointed out which topics they considered interesting. Examples of this step can be seen in the following stories from the first CRAG information workshop:

Spiders have 8 hairy legs and 48 knees. They eat meat.

Lots of insects eat meat. Meat and be ham or chicken. Some insects live indoors, and some live in leaves. There is a spider in my Nanny's house. This isn't any old spider. This spider lives in picture frames (CMB2).

They make webs, and they use these webs to catch flies, and they sleep in their webs (CMG2).

In the kitchen in my house and my Nana walked in, and she screamed like this ...AHHH... and she got her shoe and guess what she did ... She did this (bangs table) to the spider... My Dad always puts them outside when they are gigantic spiders like this! (CMB5).

Figure 6.17: CRAG's own perspectives of Nature.

Some CRAG members chose to share their ideas by drawing pictures of their own interests as follows:

Figure 6.18: *A spider with no body (CMG1).*

Figure 6.19: *I know spiders have eight legs, but I gave mine 10. This is pink and has red, and the rest is blue. This is a tarantula (CMG2).*

An interesting aspect of the first CRAG information session arose from the narrative of the spider with no body (Figure 6.18.) The CRAG member wanted to draw a spider but expressed disappointment with their lack of capacity to do so. When asked to draw the spider on their behalf, I hesitated and was concerned about leading the participant. I suggested that we first look at the images from the books to give them an idea. There was an element of

uncertainty from us both. I suggested that a circle might be a starting point for the body, and lines could be legs.

But the problem is that I can't draw a circleonly lines (CMG1)

Figure 6.20: Extract highlighting capacity building opportunity.

This was a learning moment for us both and arguably better placed in a findings chapter. However, it was also an essential aspect of building the capacity to engage with data analysis (Lundy et al; 2011, 2012). While my adultist mind-set shouted ‘Red card – leading the participant’, what was happening was a local capacity-building moment. In showing the young child how to draw a circle, I gave them the tools they wanted to continue exploring their own ideas on spiders. This gave me a real-life experience of Shier’s (2016) discussion of the implications of ‘child-led’ research. I drew one circle on the page, and the following evolved:

Figure 6.21: Spiders following capacity building support (CMG2)

The spider is gold, and the rest is gold, and the inside of the big gold is pink. I found a baby one in my house. It was in my bedroom, and I wanted to bring it downstairs, but Mammy was scared. It was funny (CMG2).

Figure 6.22: View expressed about Spiders following capacity building support (CMG2)

The moment offered insight into the role of the adult researcher and the interdependent nature of the same in providing children with authentic tools or guidance to form their own views

(Lundy et al., 2011; Lundy & McEvoy, 2012; Ergler et al., 2015; Mayne et al., 2018; Shier 2016, 2019). The black-or-white perception of ‘child-led’ ideas may restrain our confidence in the greyer area of child-initiated/adult-supported ideas in researching their own perspectives and lived experiences with children (Mannion, 2007; Horgan et al., 2017). The right to guidance from adults under Article 5 of the CRC is also pivotal in driving explicit child rights-based research methodology, as discussed in the previous chapter (Lundy et al., 2011; 2012; Mayne et al., 2018).

This also highlighted the significance of my own practitioner skillset to spot what may be needed to empower young children to form their ideas in an everyday moment (Lyndon et al., 2019; Wall et al., 2019). The interdependency of this role is discussed further under the themes of ‘participatory rights defined by children’ and ‘making space for unicorn moments’ in Chapter 9. For now, however, it is essential to outline the multiple outcomes of these sessions. Firstly, the agenda was driven by how the CRAG enjoyed their participatory rights. Secondly the crossover between data collection and data analysis became apparent. Thirdly, I became aware of the interdependent relationship of the adult/child role in eliciting child participation. Fourthly, the new field assistants helped shift the adult power dynamics by sharing Nature learning with the research participants. Following the discussion of how to draw spiders came a discussion on how to draw hedgehogs and an overall space to hear children’s own stories and thoughts about insects and animals:

Figure 6.23: *Like a circle but squiggly for the spikes (CMB2).*

Figure 6.24: Hedgehog (CMB2)

I was on my holidays and I was in this cave, and there was spikey things hanging from the roof and I was thinking to myself a hedgehog must be living in this cave 'cos of the spikes (CMB2).

Figure 6.25: A perspective expressed about hedgehogs (CMB2)

The space was an open platform to exchange ideas and new information about Nature in a fun manner and in keeping with what the CRAG had wanted while also informing my thinking. As we started to create an archive of their ideas about Nature, I asked them what we might do with this information or how it might be shared. Suggestions were offered that we might display them on the wall, while other members wanted to *'bring their work home'* (CMB1). In recognition of the different views, I suggested creating their own Nature book, where they could decide to share different aspects of the research study as it evolved. At this point, I was considering how this might work for our dissemination further down the line. We could photograph ideas with this approach while respecting property and ownership rights. This was readily received and furthered with a suggestion from the group that other children could now learn *'how to draw spiders and hedgehogs'* (CMB2). At that stage, this was how we perceived the creation of *The Children's Nature Book*, that is, as a book that could be shared by children with other children in order for them to learn about Nature. This sharing of ideas also supported how we redefined the CRAG research role to become informed field assistants. While the concept of sharing their own ideas and new information with other children was the initial intention of *The Children's Nature Book*, as the study progressed, the decision-making with the CRAG as to what went into the book also gave rise to a further step

of progressing to data analysis engagement. This is where the move from data collection to data analysis took place. Instead, the third field assistant session was presented as a specific data analysis CRAG workshop using the book's formation and photo walls displaying images of research activities as analytical tools to support data interpretation in group dialogue form (Clark & Moss, 2011).

6.11.2. Step 2: Identifying one's involvement.

Step two of the process involved the CRAG's wishes to establish how they and each of the younger participants were involved in the process. Presenting data visually is not without limitations and immediately points to the question of who is choosing the images and, therefore, the data to present to the children from the offset as described previously (Shier, 2016). Mindful of this implication, a large number of images (Figure 6.1) from each activity involving both groups were presented with a minimal adult description other than asking the following sample questions:

- Do you remember this day?
- What happened?
- What did you like?
- Do you think other children would like that? Why?
- What did you not like?

An interesting part of this session was how the group began identifying aspects of the data meaningful to them. For example, it was important for them to establish 'ownership of ideas' and 'their own and others' involvement' in the research activities. The following extracts provide further insight into this step:

That was mine (CMG1)
Where's mine? (CMB5)
That's mine (CMG2)
That was my hat (CMG1)

Figure 6.26: Mine

That's my slug (points to a picture of a worm (CMG2)
Adult researcher: *What makes it your slug?*
since I like slugs (CMG2)
AR: *ah so it's yours?*
Yeah (CMG2)

Figure 6.27: Ownership of ideas (a)

the worm is my one (CMG2)
I want to draw a worm (CMG2)
the spider is my one (CMG1)
I want to draw spiders.... I want to draw a green spider (CMG1)
nobody is able Nobody is not allowed to play my game (CMB3)

Figure 6.28: Ownership of ideas (b)

The ownership of ideas and games featured in conversations throughout the study to the point that it may have been considered an aspect of the children's particular cultural context. It was through recognising the significance of this for the children that I began to think of ownership as a common language rather than just possession. For example, my adultist mind was immediately taken aback by the idea that humans should own the slug. Nevertheless, becoming privy to reoccurring commonalities in the children's shared language helped me to recognise and step back from my knee-jerk judgement and instead respect this shared language as a strategy the participants used to form ideas. Respecting this enabled me to better support these evolving capacities, in this case, authentically analysing data with the group. A further critical lens through which the children chose to engage with the images was 'their own and others' involvement' in research activities. Examples of this can be seen as follows:

Where's me? (CMB5)
Well, actually, that was the day I wasn't in when you brought magnifying glasses... I wasn't in... I was sick for two days (CMG2)

Figure 6.29: Establishing their own involvement.

there's me (CMG1)
and did you see me? I was right there (CMB1)
I wasn't in that day (CMG2)
I didn't know (child's name) was in that day (CMG2)

Figure 6.30: Establishing their own and others' involvement.

The CRAG also discussed what their friends were doing in the pictures... *It's (child's name) (CMG2): I think she finded (CMB5) your notebook (CMG2)*. Again, these child-initiated discussions were relevant because the group engaged in the data analysis process through a lens led by their own interest. This group of children did this readily at the beginning of any of the research sessions and informed my listening role (Ceballos & Susinos (2022)). The significance of one and each other's involvement and ownership of ideas can also be identified as they transitioned to the next step of interpreting the images.

6.11.3. Step 3: Children's interpretation of images

The following extracts from the project came from a discussion on images from the insect hunt activity shared with the CRAG and give insight as to how they connected with them:

Figure 6.31: Insect poster

Figure 6.32: Insect house.

what is the pictures? (CMB3)

we put a picture there (points to a large outdoor poster of insects) (CMB3)

we put it that there (points to a photo of a wooden log) (CMB3)

Because we wanted to see insects under there (CMG1)

But someone keeps moving the other one (CMG1)

yeah... there was so many (CMG1)

I remember this !!!!(CMB1)

I liked when I was sitting down with you (CMG1)

because I like to speak with you (CMG1)

Figure 6.33: Group interpretation of their insect hunt

Figure 6.34: Horse chestnuts and pinecones

Figure 6.35: Collecting stuff

hey wait, did you bring loads of pinecones and stuff? (CMG2)

hundreds? (CMG2)

there might have been hundreds cos I seen loads (CMG2)

a hedgehog? (CMG1)

mmm, a hedgehog? (CMG2)

I think it's the bread nuts ... (CMG2)

Mmm| a leaf? (CMB1)

We were putting stuff in it (CMG1)

That was my hat (CMG1)

We were picking up acorns and(CMG1)

Figure 6.36: Group interpretation of the Nature game.

The reason for highlighting these extracts is twofold. Firstly, to demonstrate how effective a large number of visual images was for supporting the CRAG in data analysis (Clark & Moss, 2011; Mukherji et al., 2018). Secondly, I aim to give insight into how their capacities evolved together in forming ideas and engaging in the research through peer group discussions with

minimal lead from me. Furthermore, from the above and the following extracts, we can also detect what they enjoyed in the sessions:

Figure 6.37: Tree planting (a)

Figure 6.38: Tree planting (b)

Planting the trees (CMB1)

I liked measuring (CMG1)

we planted the trees (CMG2)

I planted a tree... I think they are growing (CMG1)

they are growing to the same size as the other trees (CMG2)

AR: Do you think children like planting trees?

Yeah (CMG1)

cos it's so fun! (CMG1)

to mess around (CMG1)

the digging (CMG2)

I liked when I was measuring my height myself (CMG1)

Figure 6.39: CRAG group interpretation on tree planting

(CMB1) looks at photo walls and points at a photograph of birdfeeder

What is this? (CMB1)

What is that? (CMB1)

where is the peanut butter? (CMB1)

Figure 6.40: CRAG interpretation on birdfeeder

Figure 6.41: Birdfeeder

Figure 6.42.: Flowerbed.

Soil (CMG1)

we planted in it (CMG2)

they grewed !! They grewed a lot! (CMG2)

They did! (CMG1)

and for the birds (CMG1)

Figure 6.43: CRAG group interpretation of flowerbed

Considering the overall research question, namely exploring children's perspectives and lived experiences of Nature, the following common themes can be identified from the groups' analysis of the images:

- An interest in animals and insects
- An enjoyment of tree planting
- An enjoyment of digging
- An enjoyment of sharing ideas and learning new ideas about Nature
- Making their own connections and observations of the natural world

However, the above remains an overall adultist conjecture of the data analysis process (Shier, 2016). The child participation in this project was individual and interchangeable, meaning that this list was far from fully representative of every participant's enjoyment of Article 29 1 (e). This would suggest that the most accurate representation of the participants' perspectives

and meaningful engagement must come from each child themselves (Mayne et al., 2018; Shier, 2016; 2019). The outcome of the data analysis workshop was that education under Article 29 1 (e) is not a premeditated list of stuff but rather an approach where the curriculum is designed with respect to the local context and, specifically, each individual learner involved. The list was helpful as a starting point to connect with the young participants and use it as a means to build relationships and gain a deeper understanding of their vast range of participatory definitions.

6.11.4. Step 4: Further interpretation with relational support

In the data analysis session, I also noted how comfortable and confident the CRAG members were in retelling their research story to their familiar adult, an ECEC practitioner from the setting (Figure 7.13). Rather than asking direct questions such as ‘What do you like about or do with Nature?’, the practitioner offered words of wonderment or enthusiasm instead. This effectively supported a listening space more conducive for the children to decide independently which parts of the research they wished to interpret and talk about (Ceballos & Susinos, 2022). The significance of how relational support extended the elements of space, voice, and audience to reflect the local context was established earlier. Here, I want to demonstrate how it fits in as the final step in the process initiated by the CRAG to engage with meaningful data analysis. As the children defined their participatory rights in so many different ways I concluded that to ensure that I had not missed an essential aspect of the study for any participant, it made sense to provide each of them with their own copy of ‘data’ or, in this case, The Children’s Nature Book which also contained photographs of the research activities. By doing so, I hoped to create further ‘listening spaces’ for the participants where each child was enabled to engage with a familiar adult and then share what was important to them. By doing this, the book now also doubled up as a dissemination tool that empowered each participant to decide which (if any) aspect of their research about Article 29 1 (e) they wished to share.

Unfortunately, the extent of the book's effectiveness as a data analysis tool was cut short following the outbreak of COVID-19 in March 2020. Some feedback from families was collected via email in the following extracts:

CMG2 and CMB1 still talk about all the fun they had with you, and they still love finding bugs in the garden.

Figure 6.44: Feedback of research from families (a)

CMG1 was absolutely delighted with her copy of the book...really enjoyed showing us the different activities you and Hazel got up too.

Figure 6.45: Feedback of research from families (b)

Thank you for showing our lovely pictures of insects and apples and recycling in the book. I loved making the bird feeder and watching the birds eating the seeds in my garden. We had lots of laughs together. I love you (G1).

Figure 6.46: Feedback of research from families (c)

CMB2 was made up with it; as we read through it, he said they were happy memories Mammy. He was able to tell me all about recycling, and he loved the insects. We were in yesterday and we got back to car, there was an insect on the boot he insisted we took a photo of it to send it to u.

Figure 6.47: Feedback of research from families (d)

B5's torso and legs making into the book was the highlight for both.

Figure 6.48: Feedback of research from families (e)

Perhaps we can consider a common interest in insects and birds evolving in the above feedback with the children's families comparable to the CRAG's interpretations. Of course, this is still limited to only a few respondents (5 families). What is more notable for me are the words *fun, love, delighted, enjoyed, happy memories, lots of laughs* and *highlight*. This analysis with their families arguably identifies the realisation of individual rights in this research space. However, any number of activities could be considered as possibilities for supporting learning under Article 29 1 (e), but precisely one cannot be pinpointed. What the feedback does portray is instead an overall sense of fun and enjoyment that was experienced throughout the research stages.

Supporting the children to engage with data analysis was a journey that developed through a stepped process. Listening to the CRAG members and their desire to share their own ideas

about Nature, as well as those that were new to them, was a crucial tenet in respecting authentic engagement with them. Facilitating them to examine a large selection of data with minimal adult description helped to manage external manipulation (Shier, 2016; Ceballos & Susinos, 2022). Keeping the adultist perspective in check was further supported by understanding and respecting several cultural aspects of the local context as the lens through which the CRAG members explored the data. This meant a crossover in data collection and analysis activity, which may be perceived as limited ‘traditional’ data analysis processes. However, this research does not look to measure the capacity of children’s engagement in ‘traditional’ research processes. I aimed to work with children to develop approaches that are respectful and authentic to how they themselves define their participatory rights throughout a research process, which this chapter has demonstrated.

Chapter 7 Stage 2: Audience and influence: A participatory action research approach with ECEC practitioners.

7.1. Introduction

The second stage of this study involved a participatory action research (PAR) approach with ECEC practitioners. This chapter begins with a short discussion on the rationale for choosing a PAR as ‘the next step’ in a transformative child rights research approach. I continue with an exploration of what PAR methodology is and how I applied it in my data collection for stage two. This exploration also includes a discussion on the fundamental principles of participatory methodology, particularly the principles of safe space, democracy, trust, and inclusion (Bergold & Thomas, 2012), which were pertinent to balancing power dynamics within the research sessions. This section highlights similarities in the methodology design for both stages and demonstrates how guidance from the Children’s Research Advisory Group (CRAG) helped make the adult process inclusive. I also include a section on the tension between implementing participatory principles and providing a rigorous critical account of the data collected. I continue by discussing the action element of a PAR approach and some challenges that were encountered. I conclude the chapter with a section on the data analysis process for this stage.

7.2. Rationale for using PAR for stage two.

The third aim of this study was to build the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate child rights-based ESD into early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e). Furthermore, as outlined in the introduction chapter, the research objectives in line with this were as follows:

- To identify ways of promoting authentic learner participation among young children under Article 29 1 (e).
- To explore the ECEC practitioner’s skillset and evaluate its contribution to eliciting learner participation to realise Article 29 1 (e).
- To collaborate with ECEC practitioners to create a rights-based ESD/CCE module.

To recap the epistemological position taken in the study was to recognise and respect the multiple layers of knowledge that do exist amongst ECEC stakeholders and collaborate with it to construct new knowledge relevant to transformative child rights theory. Also as with the ontological position, I have highlighted the adult/child power dynamic that exists in early

childhood (Edwards, 2010). Therefore, using a PAR methodology aligns with these positions. Notably, while we are all adults in this approach, the concept of power dynamics and the effect it may have on not all knowledge being included continues to be relevant for stage two. In keeping with the concept of a ‘bottom up’ education approach, I needed to create a safe inclusive research space like a ‘community of practice’ (CoP) to work directly with ECEC practitioners to gain their professional insight. Lave and Wenger (1991) describe a CoP as a group of people who share an interest or passion for something they do and collaborate regularly to learn how to do it better. Arguably, learning how to do ESD better could imply that there are not already excellent sustainability practices in place, and assuming that I always knew better was not the tone that I wanted for this stage. Rather, I wanted the space to be for practitioners with a common interest to collaborate and reflect together through a process of sharing knowledge (including the young participants’ contributions), experiences from their own practices and theory from ESD research. It was then, through this form of CoP, that the objectives stated above could also be examined. Using this space to share the children’s contributions also offered an authentic means of achieving ‘audience’ and ‘influence’ as discussed in detail in the methods chapter for stage one (Lundy, 2007).

The following is a description of the participants and their settings who participated at the beginning of the sessions. Several of these withdrew later due to other commitments but consented to their contributions being included.

Table 7.1: Details of participants for stage 2

Name	Description	No. of Participants	Withdrew during data collection
Setting A	Large community based early childhood setting with afterschool service	3 participants ECECP1, ECECP2, ECECP3	NO
Setting B	Large community based early childhood setting with afterschool service	1 participant ECECP4	YES
Setting C	Privately owned full day early childhood setting with extensive access to outdoors	1 participant ECECP5	YES
Setting D	Small community based early childhood setting with afterschool service.	2 participants ECECP6, ECECP7	YES
Setting E	Privately owned full day early childhood setting with extensive access to outdoors	1 participant ECECP8	NO

7.3. What is participatory action research methodology?

Participatory Action Research (PAR) is described by Machin-Mastromatteo and Tarango (2019) as a participatory and mainly qualitative methodology whereby the researcher implements several actions to gain insight into participants' practices, views, and behaviours. This knowledge is, in turn, used to empower them to make changes to improve their situations through their own reflection and actions. Cornwall and Jewkes (1995, p.1667) describe this as ‘a process of sequential reflection and action, carried out with and by local people rather than on them’. Udvarhelyi (2020) explains PAR as an inquiry where people collectively investigate their own realities by themselves or in partnership with friendly outsiders. For this study, I was the outsider. To enact the PAR approach, I used findings from stage one to construct a scenario detailed below for practitioners to co-consider in light of their duty-bearing educator role under Article 29 1 (e).

Table 7.2: PAR Workshop Sessions Schedule

Iteration 2 – PAR Workshop sessions schedule (Mar – June 2022)	
Dates	Themes
Session 1 (Mar 24th)	Introduction to research and findings for Iteration one
Session 2 (April 7th)	Authentic learner participation
Session 3 (April 28th)	ECEC sustainability projects
Session 4 (May 19th)	Evolving sustainability projects in participating settings
Site Visit for Setting A (June 3rd)	
Session 5 (June 9th)	Authentic ESD moments
Session 6 (June 20th)	ECEC practitioners’ perspectives on a child rights ESD approach

Epistemologically, PAR is characterised by studying the interactions between theory and practice and focuses on knowledge generation through a group dynamic. It is a cyclical approach with six stages: diagnostic or analysis, planning, action, observation, evaluation,

and reflection (McTaggart, 1991). These stages are used to analyse changes taking place on the studied topic. This is done through implementing one or several actions, the effects of which are explored through a process of individual and group reflection. From this study's perspective, I presented the children's contributions to the participants and invited them to carry out a similar approach to ESD promotion that would be authentic to their own individual settings. I did this through a series of online PAR workshops that were structured around key concepts used to support the methodology and analysed in the group as outlined in Table 7.2.

The outcomes of the dialogue within each of these sessions - specifically the local knowledge and perspectives created from this analysis - were used to inform the action of the subsequent sessions (Cornwall & Jewkes, 1995). The objective was to shed light through the lens of the ECEC practitioners' professional skillset on how a child rights-based approach for ESD could (or could not) occur for the early childhood sector. Table 7.3 and 7.4 provide an overview of the content from the first two sessions to demonstrate this in context:

Table 7.3: Overview of PAR Workshop Session 1

Iteration 2 – PAR Workshop sessions schedule	Agenda	How was it presented to participants?	Responses	Reflection	Action	Actual Action
Session 1 (Mar 24th)	Introduction to research and findings for Iteration one	PowerPoint slides with areas to prompt dialogue:	Details of settings provided. Some participants described being nervous . Good overview of diversity .	Excited for a diversity in settings. Conscious of individual participation Conscious of my domination of conversation (power) Conscious of staff/manager dynamic	Reflect on your own setting, the children in it, and their interests as a launch pad for sustainable learning.	One setting provided photographs.
***6 participants from 4 settings	Learning about participating settings	Type of setting Access to Nature Existing Sustainable practices Existing rights-based approach				

Table 7.4: Overview of PAR Workshop Session 2

Iteration 2 – PAR Workshop sessions schedule	Agenda	How was it presented to participants?	Responses	Reflection	Action	Actual Action
<p>Session 2 (April 7th)</p> <p>**1 participant withdrew</p> <p>**5 participants and 3 settings</p>	<p>Getting feedback on reflections on individual settings (children, interests, local culture)</p> <p>Introducing the term authentic learner participation</p> <p>Establishing different types of participation</p> <p>Using the concept of authentic learner participation to identify sustainable projects?</p>	<p>Power slide with areas to prompt dialogue,</p> <p>Initial Thoughts on Session 1 Questions/Concerns? Children’s interests & are any interests ESD related?</p> <p>Participation variations Dominant participants non-verbal participants English as a second language sensory issues Participants’ own engagement/learning with equipment/Nature</p> <p>Examples of participation from ‘Can we see our voices’?</p>	<p>Dialogue surrounding sustainable projects.</p> <p>Dialogue on interests: Some children like bunnies, making rainbow rivers, and playing music.</p> <p>How can sustainable projects include interests in bunnies and rivers?</p> <p>There are often other things that happen as these adult-initiated projects take place.</p> <p>Sharing a variation in participation</p>	<p>Raised a query on adult-initiated projects, problematic for authentic learning. (Is there a need for <u>this</u>, however, but with flexibility to then make it rights-based)</p> <p><i>No issues with sharing....</i> Are there assumptions? Or is the setting well-equipped?</p> <p>Is there a difference in understanding amongst individuals of the same setting?</p>	<p>Reflective work to establish authentic participation.</p> <p>Tunnel further into what authentic learning looks like in your setting.</p> <p>Open up a little bit more as to how we can establish this being authentic for the children as well</p>	<p>One participant sent a reflection</p>

I will refer to these tables in the following section on how collaborating with the participants informed the agenda, the methods and the actions within the PAR approach while remaining respectful of how they chose to be involved.

7.4. Fundamental principles of participatory methodology.

Bergold and Thomas (2012) describe the fundamental principles for a participatory methodology to be a **safe space, democracy, trust, and inclusion**. They also highlight that a PAR researcher's diverse requirements and roles demand very different competencies and skills, including a high degree of flexibility and reflexivity. They describe these skills as ‘things that are not acquired in the course of conventional university education’ (Bergold & Thomas, 2012, p.203) despite reflexivity being a quality indicator for participatory research. In the following discussion, I will apply these four principles and a reflexive approach (including the learning I drew from while working with the CRAG) to design an authentic PAR methodology for working with ECEC practitioner participants.

7.4.1. Safe space

The research consisted of six meetings in total, which occurred every three weeks (Mar-Jun 2022). The online video conferencing platform, Microsoft Teams, and corresponding shared drive for relevant documentation (mainly reflections, ESD resources and transcripts from each session for participants to access) were used. First, this platform was made safe in line with safeguarding procedures guided by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (2016) and the Institute of Technology Carlow's Ethics in Research Policy (2021). A protocol for using a shared drive was also provided and signed by each participant prior to our first session (Appendix S).

During the first session (Table 7.3), a participant described how nervous they were to talk. Examples of this included: *'I'm a little bit nervous, so I'm sorry if my voice is a little bit shaky'* or: *'I didn't mean to be like a negative nelly'*. This also occurred again when a new participant joined: *'I don't know if this is right or wrong, and maybe you can highlight this.'* To recap from stage one, Lundy (2007, p.934) describes a safe space in research with children as an inclusive place 'without fear of rebuke or reprisal'. Like stage one, I realised I needed to acknowledge and respect this aspect in my facilitating role to develop a sense of safety. I did this with reassurance, underlining that all contributions were considered valuable for the development of ECEC practice (the abbreviation **(LR)** represents the lead researcher, which was me): *'You have nothing to be sorry about you ...you're following exactly what we wanted, which [is] ...to get an idea of the different settings...there is diversity here, and that's fantastic'* **(LR)** or: *'I thought that it was very insightful'* **(LR)**.

I also presented a set of guidelines to prompt or support dialogue among the participants. This still, perhaps, could have inadvertently put them 'on the spot' as some form of examination of their knowledge. I was also conscious that I was clearly the dominant voice and reminded of Cornwall and Jewkes's (1995, p.1667) point on 'the location of power' in creating a safe research space. On the one hand, we can think that a dominant or lead voice would be expected as it was the introductory session and a new space for participants. However, on reflection, an early power dynamic may have been established and something that I would need to be aware of in further sessions. I discuss the issue of power at length in the findings

chapters. My approach within the PAR remains the same as with stage one's methodology when I focused on balancing power dynamics. I needed to be aware of how I structured the sessions to promote a comfortable space that valued free-flowing dialogue and, therefore, all forms of knowledge in this PAR approach. In subsequent sessions, I deliberately kept the usual housekeeping bits (updates or agenda) brief at the beginning (Cornwall & Jewkes, 1995) and invited participants to share their thoughts as a launch pad for dialogue.

Bergold and Thomas (2012) and Cook (2021) write about instilling confidence and creating spaces to empower participants. Similarly, time is needed to reflect, analyse, and evolve to more collegiate learning processes. Within this research space, we readily connected through an informal style of dialogue, which also supported participants to feel comfortable and safe to share. This also demonstrated the participants' role in co-creating a safe space relevant to this particular group. Reassurance from me and the use of humour also lent itself to a sense of collegiality and, at times, excitement for ideas (hooks, 1994). Additionally, instead of delivering the children's perspectives and findings in one block presentation, I introduced them into conversations throughout the sessions. hooks (1994) describes excitement as fundamental to a community's learning process. Our capacity to generate excitement is affected by our interest in one another, in hearing one another's voices and acknowledging each other's presence. Of course, every community or group of individuals is different, and strategies for effective communication, listening and constructing ideas will be repeatedly remoulded. For Bruner (1996), the overall recognition that the contributions of each community member are valuable resources from which to begin authentic knowledge creation is central to a rights-based participatory research approach. Enthusiasm for one another's shared experiences in ECEC was apparent throughout each session and arguably contributed to co-creating an authentic, safe space.

7.4.2. Democracy

The recruitment process for stage two was underpinned by the same participatory ethics detailed in the methods chapter for stage one. To summarise, all participants were viewed as subjects, not objects, with rights to participate in the research activity, either directly or indirectly, actively or passively or indeed not at all. Furthermore, no participant was treated

with prejudice or excluded because of their identity (ITC, 2021). Equally, ECEC is a highly gendered workforce, and while positive steps were taken to recruit practitioners of all genders (Barry & Jennings, 2021), all of the participants were women.

Recruitment included an initial research participation information blurb (Appendix Q), circulated on social media and also distributed through local childcare committees with an open invitation to all early childhood settings and practitioners in the Republic of Ireland. There is a childcare committee in every county that, in turn, distributed the study's participation information to every setting in their locality. This was essential to ensuring as inclusive an approach as possible. Interested practitioners worked in both privately owned and community-based services, and all received further information and consent materials (Appendix S) and follow-up phone calls for further questions. The right to withdraw at any time was also respected (Institute of Technology, Carlow, 2021). Several participants withdrew for personal reasons and time constraints but consented to have their involvement included in data analysis up to that point.

Within the research space itself, democracy came in the form of ensuring every voice could be heard (Lundy, 2007; Cook, 2021). In the previous section, I describe how power dynamics could have caused some participants to be less confident in contributing and how being aware of balancing power going forward could better support their participation. However, the power of the researcher was still there in some form. For example, I continued to set the agenda but left it flexible enough for the participants to change it. Cornwall and Jewkes (1995, p.1670) believe that it is the role of the researcher to change 'from director to facilitator to catalyst'. Enabling meaningful dialectical participatory processes that supported reciprocal and in-the-moment conversations amongst my participants effectively gave rise to new knowledge being heard. Freire (2000) describes knowledge as 'a field in which we all labor', connecting ideas learned in university settings and those learned in life practices. Dismantling or reclaiming more subjugated knowledge opens a path for revisioning and including other expertise, which became an integral part of this PAR approach. We can see how this featured significantly in the overview of session 3 as follows:

Table 7.5: Overview of PAR Workshop Session 3.

PAR Workshop sessions	Agenda ESD projects for ECEC	How was it presented to participants	Responses	Reflection	Action	Actual Action
<p>Session 3 (April 23rd)</p> <p>***1 participant withdrew, and 1 new joined</p> <p>4 participants and 2 settings</p>	<p>Participant reflections</p> <p>Examples of projects /resources from the 'Can we see our voices' study.</p> <p>What might align?</p>	<p>Photographs provided by the setting were presented in PowerPoint slides, and participants themselves discussed them.</p> <p>I presented one participant's reflection</p> <p>I presented examples of rights-based ESD projects, linking authentic learning with ESD.</p>	<p>Participants gave detailed accounts of the settings and opportunities for sustainable learning</p> <p>From these examples and the concept of authentic participation, I intersect with suggestions for meaningful rights-based ESD learning (learning that involved water, messy play, bunny rabbits, rivers, and insects)</p> <p>Reflection spoke about workshop contents causing confusion as,</p> <p>How can something be authentic when an adult has chosen it?</p> <p>How can something be authentic if an adult chooses which child's learning to concentrate on?</p>	<p>I noted that while dialogue included concepts of child-initiated learning when probed, examples of that were given as,</p> <p><u>Some children did not like to touch the soil; children enjoyed playing with messy art materials instead of following planned activities and were given the space to do that.</u></p> <p>Interestingly this aspect of individual or change in agenda learning was not evident when discussing/suggesting rights-based ESD projects, although it is an identifiable rights-based approach.</p> <p>Practitioners demonstrated a clear alignment of professional expertise and how authentic participation can need interdependent support to be elicited. <i>It's a balancing act.</i></p> <p>Struggle to understand authentic participation.</p> <p>Lack of time is a barrier to authentic participation.</p> <p>Flexibility in practice is key for authentic participation.</p>	<p>Take the examples of ESD projects and concepts of authentic learning and use them to consider a rights-based ESD approach</p>	<p>One Setting sent photographs of a litter-picking activity.</p>

It is evident from this table (Table 7.5) that the participants contributed a range of practitioner knowledge and experiences, which will be discussed in Chapter 10. The knowledge that was shared continued to inform the agenda and content of the subsequent sessions, further supporting a democratic research approach.

7.4.3. Inclusion

Inclusion is conceptually linked to democracy, making it difficult to understand its separation by Bergold and Thomas (2012) as fundamental participatory principles. For example, the strategies taken to ensure a democratic research approach in this study described above, such as balancing power dynamics and ensuring a participant-driven agenda, are also applied to support an inclusive approach. Therefore, to avoid repetition, I will use this section to detail what was done practically to include different types of participation.

In creating a ‘safe space’, discussed above, the participants were also invited to use a shared drive described above to upload their contributions on any aspect of the research for a group discussion during the sessions. This was both optional and anonymous. Several participants sent their self-reflections to me before the sessions, which I shared during the live sessions with the larger group. This facilitated them to speak about their reflections more comfortably in the established informal dialogic process. This gives insight into where flexibility was required in the research context to reach a mutual understanding and be responsive to individual needs to support an inclusive PAR approach (Bergold & Thomas, 2012; Parry, 2015). Table 7.6 provides an overview of the fourth workshop session.

Table 7.6: Overview of PAR workshop session 4.

Workshop sessions schedule	Agenda	How was it presented to participants?	Responses	Reflection	Action	Actual Action
<p>Session 4 (May 19th)</p> <p>***2 participants withdrew and***1 new participant joined</p> <p>4 participants and 2 settings</p>	<p>Evolving sustainability projects in participating settings</p>	<p>PowerPoint including photographs of one setting litter picking, with the following areas for discussion,</p> <p>Introduction of new participants and setting</p> <p>What is currently happening in settings?</p> <p>How are the children contributing to ESD ideas?</p> <p>Where can you find learning resources?</p>	<p>The setting explains how litter picking was authentic in that children had seen a caretaker with a litter pick and wanted to do the same. The project extended from that to include dialogue on recycling.</p> <p>Some used litter pickers, some used hands, and all were proud to fill buckets and tell what was found.</p> <p>Some looked for rubbish, and others picked it up.</p> <p>Group discussion on how it could be extended. Story shared on a project coming from a child’s experience of dirty nappies on a beach.</p> <p>Other participants share their activities with litter-picking.</p>	<p>I was conscious that the litter picking project may be limited to recycling and intersected with ideas also aligning with earlier mentioned interests of animals and planting and that further dialogue/reflection was needed. Practitioners needed more guidance with that.</p> <p>The suggestion was that I could visit a site to give further guidance from a local perspective.</p> <p>It is evident from the dialogue that acknowledging existing sustainable practices was also relevant and important to highlight and refer to.</p> <p>A central bank of resources authentic to ECEC would also be a good idea for easy access. Resources could be categorised under interests and open/flexible enough to adapt to the local context.</p> <p>From reading a new national learning resource on ESD practices, practitioners were happy that they already carried out several of them, using email rather than paperwork, biodegradable outdoor toys, reusable plates/cups, waste management, and composting.</p>	<p>Practitioners were guided to take the area of litter and create activities under this topic that may interest their children.</p> <p>Rather, the key now was to reflect on the children’s participation as to how to support a rights-based approach to this activity.</p> <p>Example – how are they engaging with ideas? Have they other ideas? How are they engaging with tools? Are other aspects of sustainability emerging?</p>	<p>I visited one site to gain a better understanding and respect of the local context.</p> <p>A reflective email was sent by the second participant.</p>

There was also, at times, an issue with dominant voices amongst the participants themselves. From the onset, I was mindful of potential obstacles to including all participants’ perspectives. Firstly, within the group, there was a variation in the level of qualification amongst practitioners, and secondly, there were managers and practitioners from the same

setting present. This was also the reason that I had invited participants to share anonymously or offline on a one-to-one basis with me, as described above. Within the sessions, I was responsible for facilitating the representation of less dominant voices. Practically, that included me verbally inviting them to speak and sending each participant a transcript from the session with an opportunity to amend confidentially and add or withdraw any aspect of their participation (Roberts-Holmes, 2014).

7.4.4. Trust

Bergold and Thomas (2012, p.203) emphasise that trust must be allowed to develop. It takes time and is built on ‘long-term, honest relationships that are characterised by closeness, empathy, and emotional involvement’. A combination of reassurance, the use of humour and a common practitioner identity that existed between us lent itself to the sense of collegiality described above in furthering the overall space for relaxed, open, and inclusive dialogue (Cook, 2021). An outcome of workshop session 4 was that some practitioners remained unsure how to make an ESD approach rights-based in their context. For that reason, we agreed that I would come to visit the site for further support. This consisted of a morning visit where participants and some young children gave me a tour of their setting. It was helpful in terms of gaining a better understanding of the local context and connecting ideas. Equally, I also believe it important to note that inviting someone to analyse (albeit from a strengths-based perspective) takes a certain level of trust on the part of the practitioners.

As described above, power management is significant for effective participatory research with adults (Cornwall & Jewkes, 1995; Cook, 2021). From a trust perspective, power also played a role and building trust needed time and reassurance from me as the facilitator. For example, the term ‘expert knowledge’ may give off a power connotation for some. Therefore, inviting that ‘expert’ to evaluate your knowledge (in this case, ECEC practice) and showcase that evaluation in a piece of research surely takes trust, as mentioned above. Yes, the overall objective of the PAR was to create a form of CoP to explore developing an effective child rights-based ESD approach, but in reality, there was no guarantee that a favourable evaluation of practitioners’ work would emerge. Furthermore, one of the reasons for not

initially including site visits as part of the PAR was to avoid the potential that might cause. As the sessions continued, some participants began to feel more confident in the trust that had been built and saw the potential for a site visit to provide guidance tailored to their unique circumstances in alignment with the research goals.

7.5. Rigour and tensions in balancing participatory principles

Qualitative research has often been criticised for a lack of transparency in its analytical processes (Baldwin et al., 2022). As I described in Chapter 5, although researchers may interpret data differently, we render our work transparent by demonstrating rigour and reflexivity (Braun & Clark, 2020). To that end, I have used the same analysis approach from Stage 1, and again included my reflective thought process and my field reflective notes (Tables 7.1- 7.6) in my discussions and arguments in putting forward Stage 2's findings (Roberts-Holmes, 2014; Mukherji & Albon, 2018).

To also maintain a rigorous PAR approach, it is important to acknowledge the tensions that arose within my role as a researcher respecting participatory principles such as safe space, democracy, inclusion and trust. In addition to the practical aspects of supporting an inclusive approach within the workshops, it is also important to note that there were moments when I felt frustrated with some of the participants' responses. It was an internal sense of exasperation, which I did not share in case it could cause practitioners to stop contributing and, of course, that it would undermine the very principles underpinning the study. For the most part, it happened when certain terms were used inaccurately to describe a child rights-based approach. As it transpires, this is a significant finding on the role of language that I discuss in Chapter 10. There was a clear frustration on my part as a child rights advocate that needed to be kept in check as the discussion was taking place. For example, had I critiqued the terms there and then, it may have impacted that 'safe space' that was needed for participants to share their perspectives. Of course, I still had a responsibility to provide a critical analysis of ECEC practice. To that end, I sent each participant a copy of my write-up and invited them to give their feedback, either written or through an online meeting. Only one participant raised an issue on how I had described adults as having an 'unearned privilege role' in children's lives for no other reason than an age difference. The participant believed that they had earned their privilege through training and obtaining an ECE degree and that

they were very much aware and appreciative of the role they played. The feedback provided further insight into the role of language and an opportunity to further support the democratic nature of the research approach. I updated the write-up to include this perspective.

7.6. Challenges in implementing change

As described in section 7.3, PAR research involves ‘action’. It involves action on the part of the researcher to gain insight into participants' practices and action from the participants themselves to make changes to improve their practices as part of the research process (Cornwall & Jewkes, 1995; Machin-Mastromatteo & Tarango, 2019). For my part, the action came about in terms of creating a CoP space (Lave & Wenger, 1991) and facilitating dialogue between participants as a means of reflecting on their current sustainable practices. This is also evident from the content of the research workshops provided in tables 7.3-7.6 presented above. However, the participants’ actions are not as identifiable. Each workshop provided a space for dialogue and reflection on sustainable practice with a corresponding action for the participants to carry out between the sessions. The process was designed this way so that the participants could then reflect on their actions (Schön, 1991) in the follow-on workshop. The last column of the table outlines the participants’ actions in this regard. There were some actions in terms of reflective tasks which were intended to support participants to analyse current practices but the follow on actions from there were not as apparent. More often than not, the participants did not effectively engage in the actions, often citing a lack of time to do so which limited the overall commitment to the cyclical process of a PAR approach (McTaggart, 1991). However, I would also argue that this very limitation is a significant finding for similar PAR research in early childhood settings. A lack of resources as a barrier to rights-based ESD is amongst the barriers that will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 10 of the PAR findings.

7.7. Data analysis approach for stage two

I used a reflexive thematic approach for stage two (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2013, 2020) and continued to use a child rights lens to analyse the data and keep to the research aims. The following is a list of codes that I identified in the initial stages of data analysis for stage two as a basis from which to establish possible themes:

Table 7.7: Initial coding system for stage two.

Existing knowledge	ESD practices	Rights-based practices	Access to Nature
Extending knowledge /Critical Analysis	Limitations	Suggestions	Module Content

The initial coding of **existing knowledge** was used to highlight the participants’ expertise in early childhood practice as the starting point to explore new ideas and perspectives relevant to the research questions. This notion of expertise was also recognisable under the codes of **existing ESD** and **rights-based practices** in their individual settings and, therefore, relevant to the analysis of synergies between ESD and ECEC pedagogy. I chose the code **access to Nature** (the degree to which settings had valued access to Nature) given that the research is underpinned by the educational right to develop respect for the natural environment and that the children had also put forward their expertise in connecting with Nature.

Based on Jerome's (2018) argument that valuing children as learners is crucial for rights-respecting teaching practice, I developed two additional codes for my research. These codes included opportunities for **extending knowledge and critical analysis**, which identified areas of new learning for the participants in creating a rights-based ESD approach. The second code addressed **limitations**, which highlighted potential barriers to promoting the same approach. The final two codes were **suggestions** and **module content** to gather practitioners’ views on what should be included in a rights-based ESD for ECEC module. These eight codes, in turn, folded into three larger themes: **existing knowledge**, **change agency capacity** (Ferreria et al., 2012) and **paradigms of pedagogy** as follows:

Table 7.8: Overview of second stage coding for stage two.

Existing Knowledge	Change agency capacity	Paradigms of pedagogy
Existing knowledge ESD practices Rights-based practices Access to Nature	Existing knowledge ESD practices Rights-based practices Extending Knowledge/Critical Analysis Limitations	Extending Knowledge/Critical Analysis Limitations Suggestions Module Content

I identified elements of child rights participatory approaches in participants’ accounts of their existing practice. Considering this and the overall research aim to collaborate with ECEC practitioners on how to support young children’s own rights definitions, the first theme of **existing knowledge** seemed most suitable.

The settings varied regarding established sustainable practices. This gave rise to the second theme of **practitioners’ capacity to enact change** or Ferreira et al.’s (2012) term, ‘change agency capacity’ to support a rights-based ESD approach. The final theme of **paradigms of pedagogy** was a term I came across when reading hooks (1994) work on creating communities of learning. Hooks (1994) describes how paradigms shaped their own pedagogy to help develop a blueprint for their own pedagogical practice. I use it to acknowledge the multiple pedagogies at play in early childhood education and the diversity of understanding and engagement of these pedagogies from each participant. These different understandings provide insight when exploring transformative aspects of learning to support a child rights-based ESD approach. Figure 7.1. provides a visual overview of the coding process. These three themes will be explored in chapter 10 on the PAR findings.

Figure 7.1: Overview of the coding process for stage two

Chapter 8: Young children’s own perspectives and lived experiences of Nature under Article 29 1 (e).

8.1 Introduction.

This chapter concentrates on the study’s first aim of exploring young children’s own perspectives and lived experiences of Nature under Article 29 1 (e). The section begins by exploring how the young participants made their first Nature connections, not as a means of examining their competencies to do so, but rather to give respect to how they chose to connect overall. This also offers insight into how learning in or through Nature offers a more democratic approach to ESD in that it provides an opportunity for child-driven curricula. I continue by analysing how a responsive adult engages with these Nature connections as starting points for learning about sustainability, which can further a child rights approach. Doing so demonstrates how we can holistically transfer from the ‘in’ or ‘through’ to the ‘about’ Nature learning. The final section continues with these same holistic approaches. It identifies where, in the data collection phase, opportunities to extend this to learning ‘for’ Nature could be seen that were both authentic and participant-driven.

8.2. First Connections

The first data collection workshop consisted of an indoor small-group storytelling activity to begin exploring with the young participants their own perspectives and lived experiences with Nature. While we were indoors, the CRAG members were not present. A ‘magic bag’ containing images and natural artefacts, such as shells, stones, and pinecones, was introduced as a starting point to elicit ideas both through and about Nature (Figure 8.1).

Figure 8.1: Magic Nature Bag with artefacts and Hazel the Hedgehog

The following table (Table 8.1) accounts for the participants' first verbal connections with the bag's content.

<i>Spider (B2)</i>	<i>a butterfly (B2)</i>
<i>in the zoo (B2)</i>	<i>My see in the zoo (G2)</i>
<i>Yeah , My seen a spider in the zoo (G2)</i>	<i>a haycorn (pinecone) (G1)</i>
<i>me too (G1)</i>	<i>Acorn (G1)</i>
<i>She's a hedgehog (B2)</i>	<i>From the zoo (G1)</i>
<i>So cute! (G1)</i>	<i>In the Africa (B3)</i>
<i>a ladybird (B2)</i>	<i>My touched it (G2 laughing)</i>
<i>a ladybird (G1)</i>	

Table 8.1: Connections with artefacts

Figure 8.2. The broken stone or acorn

<i>I found a stone (A white shell) ... It's a white stone (G2)</i>
<i>that's not a stone ... It's an acorn ... (G1)</i>
<i>it's broken ... It's my stone (G2)</i>

Table 8.2: Connections with Figure 8.2

A collection of natural materials was put in place to conceptualise Bruner's (1961) discovery learning theory and for me, as the adult researcher, to develop an understanding of the young

participants' existing ideas of Nature. This was not an assessment of children's knowledge but an investigation into their connections with Nature. Such connections are unique to individuals and depend on their environment and access to Nature (Ross & Mannion, 2012). Bruner's discovery learning theory is particularly relevant in a child rights-based research space that looks to elicit children's own perspectives. The concept of discovery learning implies that children are constructing their own knowledge, and the role of the adult is not to dominate the space but rather to present the information or material and facilitate the learner to develop their own relationships with the same (Bruner, 1961;1996). The extracts above demonstrate how the participants put forward their first connections. The following were also shared as further connections representing own lived experiences:

them circles are an acorn, and it's broken there, cos a little egg got out of it, cos it's broken, ...and then when the chicken comes out of that, it's holding and sleepy, and it slips on the ground, on its shoes, then we put them back on, and there's hay ...From the floor yesterday and then, and then somebody minding us
We were on our own looking for the chicken (G1).

Table 8.3: Connection with the seashell

A similar style of lived experience was shared when one participant examined a horse chestnut:

A conker ... on the other side of our field ... My Daddy drilled holes in them ... He was putting them into the boxes (B2).

Table 8.4: Connection with the horse chestnut

To further explore these connections, the young children were invited to go outside with me as the adult researcher and search for other natural artefacts that may be interesting to them. This offered an opportunity to engage with learning in Nature while enabling a more child-driven angle to discover their own connections with Nature, leaving behind the prescribed activity indoors. The CRAG members were also here to take on their new role as field assistants.

8.3. Learning in Nature – making Nature connections more democratic in Nature and with peers

When outdoors, the CRAG and younger participants gathered to explore the natural

materials. The children were initially interested in the above shell (which had yet to be identified as a shell). The following extract offers an insight into how the children made their own connections in the company of their peers and how the CRAG took to their field assistant responsibilities:

It's a egg (G2)
It's a shell (CMB1)
See ! Hear what's inside (CMB1)
It's a egg (G2)
No! (CMB1)
It's a egg, it's a crocodile comes ... crocodile comes here (G2 points to opening of shell)

Table 8.5: Connections with the seashell in a peer group

With their own unwavering connection, the younger participant expresses the view that it is an egg from which a crocodile comes; the CRAG members suggest putting the shell to their ears to hear what is inside:

Let me try ... Let me try (CMB1)
I want to try it (CMG1)
Adult researcher – Do you want to try?
I do (G2) puts shell to ear
Not a thing (G2)
Let me hear something (CMB2)
CMG1 giggling

Table 8.6: Further connections with the seashell in the peer group

What was interesting in this brief interaction was the sharing of different individual connections with minimal adult lead. Elements of ESD pedagogies, such as experiential learning, curiosity and critical thought, were also evolving holistically (Davies, 2009, 2015; Pramling-Samuelsson, 2011; Boyd, 2018; Luff, 2018). The debate on what the shell was, and not hearing anything when they placed it to their ear are good examples of this. Equally, the moment also readily reflects how early childhood pedagogy has an advantage in helping to realise Article 29 1 (e). This is because it is a pedagogy that emphasises inquiry-based learning and recognises children as individual learners with their own funds of knowledge.

Additionally, respecting young children’s individual learning pace rather than intervening with adult-initiated ideas is heavily underpinned by ECEC theory (Pramling-Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; NCCA, 2009; 2015; Davies & Elliot, 2014). How children’s connections evolved in the following extracts offers further insight into this same point:

Figure 8.3: My hat

I have eggs in my housein my house. I am putting them my house and finding them a little bag ... I am putting in my hat ... they conkers!

All ... all... it's going in my hat... For my... they go into animals ... I am going them my Granny's house ... They are for my house, they are going in my house (G1).

Table 8.7: Connection with Nature through imaginary play

Figure 8.4: Connections with hat and horse chestnuts

B3 is gathering the pinecones in his hat.
I don't know... I have these many.
That's for ... that one ... (B3)

Do you want to bring it home? CMG1
these are in mine...It's a pinecone CMG1
I'm going to bring one home CMB1
I'm putting them in my hat CMB2

Table 8.8 & 8.9: Horse chestnuts and pinecones

An interesting aspect of this peer sharing of Nature connections is that it originated from the younger participant and evolved into a game of collecting things in hats that was much more interesting than listening to a shell. From a rights-based education perspective, it was child-driven and in Nature, which can be described as an embodied first-hand learning experience authentic in different ways to each child (Ross & Mannion, 2012; Chawla & Rivkin, 2014). This again can offer insight into children’s own agency in making decisions about how they like to learn and how, as duty bearers, we can further understand what enjoying rights looks like to them (Mackey, 2014; Tisdall, 2015; LeBorgne & Tisdall, 2017; Robson, 2016;

Martínez Sainz, 2018). A separate connection was captured in the following extract as another child-driven game took place in the playhouse as a small group engaged with the natural artefacts:

Oh dog have its ... There he is! ... he's a big doggy (G1).
CMB4 is pretending to be the dog
I have an acorn (holding a pinecone) ... No no no Don't eat it... it's an acorn...NO NO NO NO (CMB3)
NO NO NO NO NO (CMB3)
Doggy turn around (CMB3)
Doggy don't do that ... cos you might get ... off (G1)
CMB4 smiles and keeps lips closed

Table 8.10: Connection with Nature through imaginary play.

In terms of rights-respecting spaces, Mackey (2014) emphasises the significance of valuing this agency and creating a culture that provides children with meaningful first-hand experiences that can nourish an overall sense of empowerment in them. Neither of these instances had any adult input but instead can be considered child-driven in that the children independently made their own Nature connections. This first data collection session gave a vivid insight into the young participants' own connections with Nature. As early years' pedagogies underline the integral role of learning through holistic and organic means, the children also demonstrated how they enjoyed Nature learning in a space that supported and respected all engagements.

8.4. The responsive adult – a companion in wonder

Bruner (1961; 1996) emphasises the role of social learning in the construction of the learner's own meaning and the relevance of a responsive teacher and community in scaffolding that meaning. In other words, as Elliot (2014) puts it, access to rocks alone does not necessarily equate to developing respect for Nature. Instead, a proactive response and collaborative learning between children, ECEC practitioners and families is critical to its fullest realisation. Constructivist learning requires the teacher to be sensitive to the context and individual experiences to scaffold the learner to be willing and capable of building on their own ideas. This responsiveness better supports evolving capacities to build on children's perspectives to form views and meaning. It is also in keeping with a rights-respecting learning space under the CRC (Lundy, 2007). The following extracts from an insect hunt data collection session

provide further insight into how democratic dialogue and child-led curriculum design shift social pedagogy towards a more rights-based one in the realities of early childhood lives.

Magnifying Glasses. Look I have the same as you ... For looking at people...You can look at eyes on them (G1).

G1 puts magnifying glass to eye and adult researcher does the same

it looks very big (G1).

Why ... where? (G1).

I see a caterpillar... he's under the leaf where you are doing it (G1).

I want to see your eye again (G1).

Table 8.11: Exploring with magnifying glasses.

B5 and B6 explore the magnifying glass stand

Oh it's broken now (B5)

Adult Researcher demonstrates how the magnifying glass can stand alone

B5 now lying on ground and looking through magnifying glass using stand

you know what It went down like here (B6)

and it wasn't like And it stayed up with a thing like that (B6 pulling at stand with 4 magnifying glasses in his hand)

Table 8.12: Connection with a magnifying glass and supportive adult

They are in the little holes ... in the nest ... cos they are asleep

yeah and when they wake up ... It's Spring and you can see them again and then you look at them with your magnifying glasses (G1)

AR: Do you know what that is called?

What? (G1)

AR: Hibernating

yeah because someone else told the same ... Hibernating and hibernating

So bears do ... cub bears ... and squirrels ... and snails do ... Because every different animal not hibernates and hibernates (B4).

Table 8.13: Seasons and hibernating -sharing their own Nature knowledge.

The above extracts can be seen as examples of Bruner's discovery theory alongside social learning, whereby the responsive teacher uses context to structure how learning may be

transferred. It is not simply the mastery of facts and techniques but involves collaborative methods and supportive strategies to meet the learners where they are in terms of their own knowledge construction (Bruner, 1961; Raw, 2014). Taking the time to hear the children’s knowledge and gently reciprocate with another piece of knowledge underpins the organic flow of early childhood learning. This could include knowledge pertaining to ESD thinking through a rights-respecting education approach. In terms of how Nature itself took on a teaching role for discovery theory, the following extracts illustrate the participants’ first-hand experiences in their garden. It also demonstrates the corresponding shared wonderment from the responsive adults and how the connections were respectfully elicited:

B5 touches slug
Em soft (B5)
It’s moving! (CMG1)
Adult Researcher – What’s coming out of his head?
Eyeballs ... (B4)
Children — OHH AHHH
There’s ... coming out of him (G1)
I see something (B4)
Adult Researcher – Look what XXX found, oh this is amazing

Table 8.14: Connections with slug (a)

is it a pincher? A slug! ... That’s just slug’s poop (CMB1).
Yeah slime (CMG1)
Poop (CMB1)
can I touch? (G1)
I don’t want to touch it or my hands will get slimy (CMG1)

Table 8.15: Connections with slug (b)

Figure 8.5: Place-based insect poster

Table 8.16: Connections with a centipede

Children are chattering and screaming as a centipede has just been discovered.
ECEC Practitioner – Is that on our chart?
Adult Researcher – What have you found?
I don't know! ... I don't know what it's called (CMG1 jumping up and down)
AR – It's called a centipede and do you know why he's called a centipede?
Why? (CMG1)
AR – Can you see what he has lots of?
What? (G1) Legs! (CMB1)
AR – That's it, he has loads of legs walking along.
I love it! (CMB1)
AR – Do you love it do you? would you like to try the magnifying glass to see?
EP - look at him, he is nice, he has little feelers on the top of his head too
AR – do you remember what we were saying last week about the ants' feelers?
they talk to you ... (puts fingers up like antennas) (CMG1 laughing)

Table 8.16: Connections with a centipede

Figure 8.6: Crocus

these stones might grow (B8)
AR – The stones might grow? ah! Do they look a little bit like bulbs or seeds?
Yeah (B8)
AR – How would you make a stone grow? What would you need?
only ever step on these. Look look ... Look at the nut (G1)
and raspberries as well (B8)
AR – and raspberries as well? Aha I see look a nut! (G1)
AR – A nut? Where do you see the nut?
There (G1)
AR – ah do you know what that is? It does look like a nut that's a bulb and now that's the sprout that has come out of the bulb

Table 8.17: Extending own ideas with adult support (a)

AR – I have a feeling that this little one here is a crocus

Is it a crocus? (G1)

AR – Aha but I don't know what colour it's going to be

It's going to be yellow! (G1)

AR – Oh lovely

It looks like they are growing out noodles (G1)

AR – Noodles? ... you think it looks like noodles?

Yeah (G1)

AR – Oh yeah

... Like grass (G1)

Table 8.18: Extending own ideas with adult support (b).

Carson (1956) describes the shared wonderment between young children and others as positive Nature experiences that can contribute to a lifelong respect for the environment. Early education's holistic, gentle and relational pedagogies in the extracts above demonstrate the authenticity of everyday moments as the seeds from which this respect can be developed (Barratt et al., 2014; Chawla & Rivkin, 2014). Aligned with Bruner's discovery learning and spiral curriculum theories, using the children's own connections with Nature as the starting point to develop learning supports them to define their own participatory rights in their education and can offer an approach that remains individual and meaningful of the subject matter (Chawla, 2007; Elliot & Davies, 2009; Mannion et al., 2013; Croft, 2017). When looking at the above extracts from children's engagement with the flowerbed, the two young participants explore their individual connections with the artefacts in front of them; these *stones might grow (B8)*, *look there's a nut (G1)*, *it looks like they are growing out noodles (G1)*. While I struggled with the thought of sowing a stone, I could recognise the significance of this moment and how my response would either elicit a young child's own Nature connection and empower them in the decision-making surrounding their learning or smother that connection with mine. The power dynamics which control the effectiveness of child participation and how it is applied are dependent on the will and understanding of the adults in the learning space (Mannion, 2007; Sargent & Harcourt, 2012; Mackler & Groundwater-Smith, 2015; Leonard, 2016; Horgan et al., 2017). The extracts on shared joint wonderment offer insight into how central the role of the listening-responsive adult is to the

authentic embedding of young children's voices in daily education experiences (Bae, 2010; Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2015; 2018; 2019).

Understanding and respecting this social and ecological construction and embodied learning emanating from living real experiences is fundamental to a much more profound transformative realisation and enjoyment of Article 29 1 (e) (Elliot, 2014; Gilbert et al., 2014). From beginning with an interpretation of children's own Nature connections to how these connections might be elicited to encompass a child rights-based education by responsive adults, the final section of this theme explores how a combination of both should be considered to further the development of respect for the natural environment.

8.5. Learning for Nature

Positioning children as sustainability saviours responsible for rectifying adult environmental damage is unethical. However, the climate crisis and overall sustainability development are modern-day issues in which our education systems can play proactive roles (Dahlberg & Petrie, 2002; Davies & Elliot, 2014; UNDP, 2015). With sustainability development described as an evolving process, the room for different starting points is large and dependent on context, issues, interests, knowledge bases and resources (Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008).

Project-based learning derived from children's own interests is a common practice in early childhood. It supports individual experiences that can embrace authentic child participation while also lending themselves to transformative education approaches that promote Article 29 1 (e) (Pramling et al., 2008; Davies, 2009, 2014, 2015; Davies & Elliot, 2014; Mackey, 2012, 2014; Luff et al., 2016; Hirst, 2019). During the research design stage, the CRAG members readily advised of their interest in animals and enjoyment of hands-on tools. This was the local contextual starting point from which an exploration of the participants' own experiences of Nature learning under Article 29 1 (e) evolved. The last section offered insight into how the young children individually and collectively engaged using child-driven Nature-based activities. The following extracts demonstrate an extension of those activities to include ESD thinking that remained authentic and respectful to the local context.

Figure 8.7: A horse chestnut

Do you want to bring it home? CMG1
these are in mine...It's a pinecone CMG1
I'm going to bring one home CMB1
I'm putting them in my hat CMB2

Table 8.19 Connecting with horse chestnuts (a).

all.all...it's going in my hat ... For
my...they go into animals ... I am going
them my Granny's house ... They are for
my house; they are going in my house
(G1).

Table 8.20: Connecting with horse chestnuts (b).

Conversations surrounding a desire to take materials home were common throughout the research process. In my early learning practice experience, bringing things home and ownership more generally have often been an important aspect of early childhood culture. However, removing natural materials, be those flowers, pinecones or seashells, comes with a loss to our biodiversity and its inhabitants (Kowalewski, Domènech, & Martinell, 2014). Thus, the children's desire to bring the pinecones home, highlighted in the extracts above, offers a possibility for a supporting sensitive adult to develop a real-life learning moment to motivate more sustainable behaviours. This was discussed with the children and most were okay with leaving them there. From a post-humanist perspective and in keeping mainly with

Steiner's (1924) pedagogy, this was an opportunity to discuss the young child's own part in Nature and their interrelated identity of belonging (Shava, 2013; Davies, 2014; Boyd, 2018; Barrable, 2019).

Examining insects in the garden.
What? (CMB2)
What I want to see these? (G1)
AR - Look
What is it? (CMG1)
AR – I have no idea!
A spider!!! (B)
AR – Do you think it's a spider?
I think it's squished (CMB2)
AR - a squished spider?
Children are pushing to make room to watch the insect in action
Aaaaah stop (CMG1)
AR – let's have a look with our magnifying glass ... let's move back a little bit
a little bit (G1)
I want to see it (CMG1)
I want to see ... pushing
AR – You know what's happening?
..... there's no more room (G1)
AR- But you know what might be an idea
What? (CMB5)
AR – if you waited a moment and we take turns? So there's a little fella moving there Do you want to try your magnifying glass?

Table 8.21. Changing to pro-environment behaviours with adult support (a)

The social interaction outlined in Table 8.21. was common throughout the research activities. Again, in my early childhood practice, social pedagogy of this kind, characterised by turn-taking and enthusiasm, can be considered real live moments in childhood culture. Such moments can also present opportunities for dialogue to reflect on one's own behaviours and their impact on other living species. They can help us recognise that other living species need

us to change our actions to keep them safe, given our physical size or behaviours. Focusing on a ‘pedagogy of connectedness’ with the young child’s own connection and part in Nature as the starting point has been described as an effective means to support the young child in developing empathy and compassion towards non-human Nature and subsequent responsible environment behaviour (REB) (Barrable, 2019). This also reflects Davies’s (2009) call for learning to begin in and through Nature to form a deep affective connection with it that motivates learning about and for Nature. In ways I explain further below, the extract above gives insight into how this looked in the real-life moments of data collection.

CMB2 – we should bring it over to our poster and see
AR – you want to bring it over?
Children start to huddle to transport slug
AR – but you remember though when we are carrying those insects how do we carry them
Put a leaf (CMB2)
AR – ah that’s it! So we are really super careful, cos we don’t want to hurt them These are important aren’t they?
AR – why do we think they are important?
because they are part of our Nature (CMG1)
I want to hold him (CMB1)
Can I see? (CMB2)
Hey CMB1 pushes CMB2 away
I’ll bring it over (CMB2)
I would like to (CMB1)
I do (CMB2)
B3 holds out his hand to take the slug on a leaf to the poster
AR – are you happy with that? Come on so!
B3 walks slowly over to the poster with hand out. The other children follow him.

Table 8.22: Changing to pro-environmental behaviours with adult support (b).

Moving from the view of non-human Nature as merely a learning environment towards this eco-centric orientation can open a space to further explore with the young children that they themselves are part of Nature (Davies, 2014; Croft, 2017; Barrable, 2019). An understanding of our interdependence with Nature and how that connected with a change to more pro-environmental responses is given in the above extract (Table 8.22).

Figure 8.8: Transporting a slug on a leaf.

This second extract took place as one participant wanted to bring me over to show me that the seeds we had planted were beginning to grow:

Look, Look, your baby plants are growing!! (G1)
AR – my baby plants are growing !!!! well you know what that means, we have to be super careful not to stand on them, you know what I'm thinking let's stand here so we don't stand on the plants
Ok (B5)
AR – Because we want them to grow
I'm off it now (B5)
AR – Ahh that's good because if we want them to grow we have to not touch them

Table 8.23 Changing to pro-environmental behaviours with adult support (c).

Figure 8.9: The flower bed

But why can't we dig up here? (G1)

**AR – well because if you dig that up then it won't grow and then there will be no flower ...
But you can dig in the sandpit? But here right now, things are growing**

But some of them are dead (G1)

AR – Some of them are dead?

Yeah (G1)

AR – Well you know all these green ones, I can see here ... can you see right here?

Yeah (G1)

AR – Right inside this is a beautiful flower ... so right inside here ... If you come back and keep watching it and in a couple of weeks, the flowers are going to come out ... But if you dug it up then we would have no flower

But I'm not going to dig up these ones I'm going to go dig up in that sandpit (G1)

AR – Ah ok so when you feel like digging you're going to go to the sandpit and you are going to leave everything here to let it grow?

Yeah (G1)

Table 8.24: Participant explains how they will change their behaviour to be more respectful of Nature.

The dominant adult voice in these extracts cannot be missed and raises the question of the appropriate role of the adult in developing more effective ESD. Intentional teaching, as outlined in Chapter 3, comes with controversy amongst traditional early learning thought, which is instead underpinned by the principle of uninterrupted learning through free play (Broström, Johansson, Sandberg & Frøkjær 2014). Admittedly, my own practice has been principally the same. However, Elliot and Davies (2009) describe this traditional view as impeding a fuller engagement with ESD pedagogy within the early-year sector. As outlined

above, learning in and through Nature is foundational for developing sensitivity toward the natural world. However, recognition has also grown that it is not enough to develop conceptions of the environment and sustainability issues (Elliott, 2014; Innoue, 2014; Moore et al., 2014; Innoue et al., 2016; Sageidet, 2014). Education remains critical in bringing about the changes in behaviour needed to respect other living species. I highlighted these two moments to underline how the young children contributed to this type of learning by changing their own behaviours. In Table 8.24 the participant explained how they could change where they would dig so that the flowers could grow. Aside from just talking about ESD principles, using authentic moments and taking the time to demonstrate principles relatable to everyday behaviours rather than ‘Do’s and Don’ts’ could better support a more child-driven curriculum. Extending individual interests in the local context to gently integrate sustainable thinking provides a more holistic means of learning that meets the needs of the contemporary world while remaining respectful to young children’s own democratic participation. For example, the starting point was the participants’ own interests in animals and engagement with the magnifying glasses. Each child’s connection with this varied and required a sensitive adult response to help elicit it and to provide an opportunity for children’s own meaning-making. Using one’s own connections in Nature as a critical knowledge-producing process introduces an interplay of ideas and possibilities that can give rise to a whole new body of knowledge being formed. For example, taking home all of the pinecones would leave the squirrels without food. The response to this idea, leaving some for the squirrels, maintained an authentic enjoyment of Nature learning while also furthering Article 29 1 (e) to be realised.

Taking guidance from working with the CRAG to slowly build up a rapport and learn how this group of children chose to engage with Nature learning opened the space for a more rights-based form of intentional learning. Positioning the young child as a rights holder with their own contributing agency offers a legitimate rights-respecting means of embedding ESD in early learning. Cutter-Mackenzie and Rousell (2019) describe such ‘bottom-up’ contextual projects as empowering young children in their own agency to actively engage in developing sustainable practices and curricula that are meaningful to them in their everyday lives. Contextual, relational and meaningful projects support children to become informed, building their capacity to form their own views and ideas on authentic, sustainable practices (Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; Davies, 2009, 2014; Duhn, 2012).

8.6. Conclusion

The purpose of locating this theme first was to drive home the relevance of a child's connection and knowledge with Nature and our response to them as educators in defining a democratic approach to Article 29 1 (e). While I never intended to prove an overall competency in young children in their engagement with ESD, we can see from the research data that they, as research participants, created any number of opportunities to do so in practice and through a rights-respecting lens. As outlined in Chapter 3, UNESCO (2010) considers ESD as comprising four pillars of sustainability: ecological, economic, social and cultural and political. Davies (2014) argues for the need for an overall revisioning of rights and related concepts to better meet the current challenges confronting humanity. Hägglund and Johansson (2014) call for an overall augmentation of rights-based practice in early childhood if the sector is to make any real transformative contribution to ESD. For this reason, while this chapter prioritised the ecological or learning in Nature pillar of sustainability and how that can be developed to promote a further realisation of Article 29 1 (e), Weldemariam et al. (2018) and Grindheim et al. (2019) argue that a more comprehensive examination of the social, cultural and political pillars is also necessary. To that end, the following chapter offers an analysis of child participation and how the participants themselves defined participatory rights.

Chapter 9: Towards a child's rights-based approach to ESD/CCE in ECEC

9.1. Introduction

This chapter concentrates on how the children defined their own participatory rights during the data collection phase. There is an evident overlap at times between this chapter and chapter 6 which discussed the CRAG's participation in the methodology and data analysis processes. However, the primary focus of this chapter is how respecting these definitions can contribute to a child rights-based ESD/CCE approach. How the children enjoyed their participatory rights in the study varied and was supported by the local context, which already embedded a free-flowing culture of child movement in their daily practice. I begin with a section that analyses six ways in which children enjoyed their participatory rights ('free-flowing participation', 'the child's clock', 'verbal/non-verbal participation', 'relational participation', 'children's engagement with research tools', and 'participation that respects local culture'). It continues with a discussion on children's own terminology and the necessity to respect both that and many other aspects of their lives. This is followed by a second section that I have entitled 'Making space for unicorn moments', which came about as the participants led me to understand the relational aspect of supporting authentic child-rights approaches.

9.2. Free-flowing participation

In line with ethical guidelines detailed in Chapter 5, the young participants' assent to participate in research sessions was negotiated as an ongoing process. Chapter 6 has described how the free-flowing culture of the local context, with children moving freely indoors and out, supported their own decision-making whether to take part or not in a respectful, organic manner. Negotiations before the sessions started were not captured through audio recording but often included exploring research tools before deciding to participate. During these negotiations, children sometimes wanted to play with their friends first, have a familiar adult present, wear fancy dress costumes or choose their own seating arrangements. The participants themselves took the lead in defining how their participatory rights should look. My first insight into this took place in the first session with just the younger participants present, as we sat on the floor of the setting's hall. The session involved telling a story with visual aids, as seen in Figure 8.1 in the previous chapter, that was specifically designed to promote discussion with the children about their understanding of the research aims and their involvement in the research process (Alderson & Morrow, 2011;

Mayne et al., 2016; 2017). The following extracts give an account of their participation in this:

and who is that? (G1)
AR - who is that? That is Hazel. And we are researchers.
Hazel isn't that small ... No, he's not(G1)
AR – Do you know what a researcher is?
it's a polar bear ... Let me see who is in there(G1)
What's that? (G2)
AR – What's that? That's a child.

Table 9.1: Defining their own participatory rights when introduced to research

Who's that? (G1)
AR – and that's a child
What's that? (B1)
AR – That's another child. I think that might be XXX. Is that a little boy or a little girl?
There's a little girl (G1)
AR – And so all these children have lots of ideas about Nature, do you have any ideas about Nature?
Spider (B1)
AR – Spider? Do you XXX?
Can I hold it? (G2)
AR – You can hold it, of course you can, do you like spiders?
B1 climbs on AR to get onto couch behind ... lies on couch and looks over AR shoulder at storybook
I lie down (B1)
Is that one me? (G1)
is that me? (B3)

Table 9.2: Defining their own participatory rights when introduced to research.

Admittedly, I had not expected to be climbed on. However, these interactions gave an authentic overview of how participation looked in this local context and how the young participants engaged by asking meaningful questions. The story with accompanying prompts

was designed to explore young children’s own perspectives of Nature. Nevertheless, how they navigated their own participation became instrumental in informing what research strategies could be considered to explore the research topic with them further (Lundy, 2007; Lundy et al., 2011, 2012; Shier, 2016; Fane et al., 2018). One particular strategy was that of the child’s clock, which came about through an understanding of the elements of time and flexibility necessary to support the young participants in asking questions and sharing stories and lived experiences that were meaningful to them.

9.3. The child’s clock.

The Lundy Model (2007) emphasises the significance of a safe space without fear of reproach or reprimand for children to share their views comfortably. While the safe space offers a platform to express views, an audience and ensuring these views influence matters affecting the child are necessary to fully meet the legal imperatives of participatory rights (Lundy, 2007). As discussed in Chapters 4 and 6, the overall aspiration for the audience and ‘external’ influence for this study is to impact education policy to realise Article 29 1 (e) further. Within this research space, the participants readily shared views and their own lived experiences. Even though they were not necessarily always Nature related, the time given by me as a listener to these views and how they, in turn, led the direction of proposed research activities supported an ‘internal’ audience and influence in meaningful real-life moments (Mannion, 2007; Percy-Smith; 2010, Horgan et al., 2017; Tisdall, 2017; Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2019). Examples of such moments are captured in the following extracts:

AR – ok, do you want to come and hear my story?

well you can read it over here (B4)

AR – I can bring it over there where is it now?

I'll carry I'll carry this (G1)

AR – Thank you

OH! It's very heavy (G1)

AR – It is! Do you want me to help you?

You... no (G1)

AR – No? You are so strong!

Table 9.3: Participants' decision-making in participation

This small moment demonstrates how the children decided they needed time to first decide where we would sit for our session, hence the term ‘child’s clock’. In contrast, the next lengthy moment on the following page displays a web of interactions taking place before we began to engage with the research materials and demonstrates how complex dialogue can be supported from a rights-based perspective (Table 9.4).

Both extracts offer an overview of a variation of child participation meaningful to this small group within their own context while engaging with research. While the proposed activity involved telling a story about native birds and making bird feeders, the narratives throughout the session brought to light real opportunities to elicit the children’s voices in sharing ideas and their own life matters. Moore (2014) recounts that adult-devised techniques are unnecessary to enable young children to say something worthwhile. Instead, it is essential to stop and give the time to quietly listen to them as facets of being and the narratives that unfold that bring a more accurate representation of their lives. Within the extracts are movement, decision-making that influences seating practicalities and discussion topics, and an audience respectfully listening to matters being shared.

(B4) is trying to sooth his cough

AR – Now XXX pet would you like to take a drink to help that auld cough?

We need ... you need to get all better (G1)

we like think if we like just give me some cough medicine and then water and like ~~em~~ Calpol but that don't help my cough like and it likes help like everything water didn't help it either and coughing made it worse.... (B4)

AR – makes it worse?

anyway I don't know how to make it better (B4)

I am just checking to see if they have gone out they are not gone out (G1) (walks out to hall)

AR – they are not gone out yet?..... So you don't know what's going to help make it better would you want to take a little sip of that?

(B4) drinks some water

AR – How does that feel?

~~em~~ if I drink some water it to my cough and I swallow it, it goes down to my tummy and down and down to my penis (B4)

AR – yeah so if you drink the water it goes all the way down through your body and it comes out when you are doing your wee wee?

Yeah (B4)

AR – that's right! and it's good to drink water isn't it? Do you like water?

and when it comes out, it comes into my legs and my toes and my whole body (G1)

AR – Oh it does the same as what XXX said? it goes all the way through your body?

(G1) nods head and points up and down body

AR – did you know...

and my legs (G1) (stands beside AR)

AR - and your legs? and do you know what if you were a tree, if you were a tree ... Let's say you are a tree right now, see your little tosie (points to toes and tickles G1 up along her legs) you would drink the water this way, you would take it from the ground and it would go UP your body!!!!

(G1) brings her hands from her toes up along her body and smiles

AR – yeah !!! laughing

and you close your eyes and walk to the castle (G1)

AR – you close your eyes and you walk through the castle?

yeah and then you stomp (G1) (stomps feet)

Table 9.4: Deciding the research agenda

Although in earlier sessions, I struggled with linking the relevance of these regular discussions to the research topic of Nature learning, I began to understand that this was the culture of these participants. How I responded to these discussions also reflected how I responded to their Nature connections, as discussed in the previous theme. The opportunity to explore the political dimension and position of contributing rights holders necessary for a further realisation of Article 29 1 (e) was in these moments, whether we talked about Calpol or trees (UNESCO, 2010; Davies, 2014; Hägglund & Johansson, 2014). I could insist on my adultist agenda of prescribed Nature-based activities, or I could recognise this child-driven strategy of eliciting their voices, handing over the reins and respecting how these children decided their participation. This type of approach is also echoed in *General Comment No.7* concerning the principles of participation as requiring:

.... adults to show patience and creativity by adapting their expectations to a young child's interests, levels of understanding and preferred ways of communicating.

(UN, 2006).

This point also considers the existence of the adult/child power dynamic in research realities. Giving the research space over to the child's clock offers flexibility within the research agenda that supports a dismantling of the dominant adult voice (Leonard, 2016; Bessell, 2017; Horgan et al., 2017; Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2015; 2018; 2019; Kucharczyk and Hanna; 2020).

It is equally important to say that I did not understand all their stories. Moore (2014) says that is ok; knowing and accepting that, as adults, we cannot expect to understand children and their worlds entirely is critical. It is instead the role of respectfully listening to the young child that must precede the rush to get on with our own clock that will lead to a space of more authentic engagement and participation (Lundy, 2007; Alderson, 2012; Moore, 2014; Shier, 2016; 2019; Mayne et al., 2018). Furthermore, these moments were fun and akin to the chaos and complexities of the spirals of interactions that are every day in early childhood (Edwards, 2010). However, not all engagement was verbal or communicated through narratives, which often dominated the research space. In order to ensure that the quieter voice was also included in the workshop sessions, several other strategies also evolved.

9.4. Verbal/Nonverbal participation.

Group discussions can be intimidating, with some voices being more dominant, making them less inclusive for all children (Lundy et al., 2011; Green, 2015). Communication was not always verbal, and children's own definitions of participatory rights and engagement in the research activities also unfolded nonverbally and in less obvious or quieter ways. The following extracts shine a light on how this variation of participation looked in the research space:

Figure 9.1: Moving like a slug.

I ...talking (B3) (whispers)

AR – you want to hear the talking?

(B3) nods head

AR – what talking do you want to hear?

(B3) points to book in AR's hand

AR – oh do you mean the story?

yeah this story (B3)

AR – Ah you want to hear the story?

Oh lovely!

Table: 9.5: Non-verbal/quieter participation (a)

AR – he has a foot !!! and you remember how we said he moved He goes in and out (uses finger) so he moves his foot along like this.... blip blip.... Blip blip

AR – can you move like a slug?

No!!! (CMB2)

(B3) lying on ground moving

EP – Excellent, you want to give it a go?

(B5) starts moving on the ground

(B3) still moving on the ground

I like this (CMB1)

EP - Did you like it too? So it was fun being slugs?

(B3) gets off the ground

(B3) giggles

Table: 9.6: Non-verbal/quieter participation (b).

This participant took part in all of the research sessions. Although quieter regarding verbal participation, their presence and contributions throughout the process were clear to see rather than hear. The following extract identifies where the participants' vocabulary was not familiar to me:

AR – we are real scientists aren't we? little researchers

(B7) arrives

AR – Hello XXX look what we are watching ... Oh ... he is going in

Oh! (B5) (B7) (whisper)

AR (whispers) - He is going into the dirt ... Look he is going in

where is he gone? So c...(B7)

AR – What?

So c...(B7)

AR – yeah

C ... cle (B7)

AR – making a circle?

So c...cle (B7)

EP – Oh he is so cute

.... (B5) (whispering)

AR – Oh! he is so cute?

Look the wiggly worm, look the wiggly worm (B5)

(B7) giggles and wiggles body

Table 9.7: Non-verbal/quieter participation with support of ECEC practitioner

This quieter participation was commonplace throughout the research stages and offered opportunities to explore and inform approaches for a more participant-inclusive space (Lundy et al., 2011). As discussed in Chapter 6, separate information sessions for the CRAG members were organised to support their wish to ask questions and share ideas on topics that interest them. A smaller group approach helped to provide a platform for these discussions that could be described as dominating in a larger group space (Roberts-Holmes, 2014; Green, 2015; Fane et al., 2018). Respecting the children’s right to information and facilitating the time for their enjoyment of this was a pivotal consideration in the research design where both dominant and quieter participation could be included (Alderson, 2008, 2012; Alderson & Morrow, 2011; Mukherji et al., 2018). It is important to note that the overall culture of the local context was a whole group learning space, and I needed to remain respectful of this. Research workshops consisted of a combination of both small and large group sessions.

The nonverbal participation often comprised quiet observation and listening, gross motor movements such as wiggly, crawling or pointing, smiling, or giggling and voice expressions including gasping, whispering, own language and short sentences in response to questions. One aspect that supported the elicitation of this quieter variation of participation was the engagement of the early years practitioners as more familiar adults with a much deeper understanding of preferred individual communication styles. Their involvement in bridging the gap in moments such as those depicted in the extracts above offered a strategy that was both gentle, non-invasive, and integral to enabling the participation of children who may have been left misunderstood and/or unheard (Shier, 2016, 2019; Fane et al., 2018; Mukherji et al., 2018). This was a central aspect of this research space and highlighted the significance of the practitioners’ skillset in supporting young children’s participatory rights.

What colour is yours? (G1)
Green (B3)
AR – green?
Green, mine is orange ... mine is blue (G1)
AR – yours is blue? ... What’s blue?
my toothbrush ... Mine is purple too! (G1)

Table 9.8: Rapport building to support quieter participation (a).

AR – would you like to pick?
(B3) picks green
AR – ha ha !!! how did I know? How did I know?
(B3) smiles

Table 9.9: Rapport building to support quieter participation (b).

AR – So eh XXX what colour would you like pet?

Green (B3)

Table 9.10: Rapport building to support quieter participation (c).

AR – XXX lovey, would you like to pick a colour.... Would you like to pick a colour too?

Yeah (B3) (hits the green one)

AR - That's so funny because I remembered you liked green

mmmmm (B3)

Table 9.11: Rapport building to support quieter participation (d).

The growing familiarity between me and the participants as we built rapport also supported a voice-inclusive space (Mannion, 2007; Wall, 2012; Leonard, 2016; Horgan et al., 2017). As the study progressed, individual personalities, particular interests and children's individual life stories became known and were used to help engage and bring forward the ideas of quieter children. This can be seen developing in the extracts above, where I recognised that one of the quieter participant's favourite colours was green, which I used to connect with them to support authentic participation.

The extracts above show the relevance of the researcher's familiarity with individual preferences and lives that can be used organically in dialogue as a means of bringing forward the participation from less heard children (Mannion, 2007; Percy-Smith, 2010; Horgan et al., 2017; Fane et al., 2018). In addition, this could be considered an example of how Article 12 can be implemented in real-life moments (Lundy, 2007). The participant expressed their preference for choosing green in several different workshops, which gave them the opportunity to bring to life both audience and influence meaningful to them. I listened to that view, which directly influenced what research tools were decided upon that the children might enjoy more (Davies, 2014; Hägglund & Johansson, 2014).

9.5. Relational participation

As explored above, the time spent building rapport and learning about the young participants' lives and matters important to them developed my capacity to create a more respectful and meaningful space that better supported their participation (Lundy, 2007; Lundy et al., 2011, 2012). The rapport-enriched dialogue reflected the local context and the role of reciprocal relationships, which are long considered fundamental tenets in early childhood pedagogy (NCCA, 2009; 2015). How this looked in this research space is shown on the following page:

I want pink (B4)

AR – You want pink ... no bother ... 2 pinks coming up! ok

two pinks! (B4)

AR – Two pinks coming up! So where is your apple with the peanut butter, is it on the ground?

No I wiped it on your pants (B4)

AR – Ya wiped it on me pants?

(B4) laughs

AR laughs

I wiped it ... And behind (B4)

AR (laughs) No bother, they are my gardening pants, I wipe everything on them! Are you eating the peanut butter?

Table 9.12: Example of rapport creating safe research space (a).

Figure 9.2: Peanut Butter

(B3) puts his finger into the jar of peanut butter

No... don't be touching it with your fingers (G1)

(B3) rubs finger

AR – Oh do you not like the touch of it?

(B3) shakes finger

AR – Ya know what, wipe it in my trousers.... Do you want to just wipe it in my trousers?

(B3) smiles

AR – I don't mind, they are my garden trousers so they will be dirty anyway

(B3) starts to wipe finger in AR'S trousers

Table 9.13: Examples of rapport creating a safe research space (b).

The nature of the dialogue in the extracts above may be described as informal chat or banter, confusing, humorous, familiar, or indeed messy. It was not easy at the beginning to appreciate its value. However, it was also through this type of dialogue that a safe and comfortable atmosphere developed where the participants shared a range of perspectives from their own lives (Clark, 2017). Similar types of conversations also took place in the CRAG workshops described in Chapter 6. They helped to inform me of how the local context enjoyed their participatory rights and also to become more comfortable in my listening role in the research design. The following demonstrates this with the CRAG members:

AR – (laughing) so what I did during my Christmas holidays, I looked at all your beautiful pictures

What did you get off Santa? (CMB5)

AR – What did I get off Santa? I got a lovely picture of a rabbit

Aaaahh (CMG1)

AR – and I got some really nice perfume that smells like lavender. How about you?

I love lavender (CMG1)

AR – Do you really?

Yeah (CMG1)

I got ... Motorbike... makes a ...real ... (CMG2) (squeaking Hazel's tummy at same time)

AR – Oh and what did you get?

I got everything of Santa (CMB5)

AR – Everything? Does he have nothing left?

No!!! (CMB5)

AR – What did you get?

I forgot! (CMG1)

AR – You forgot? Already? Oh my goodness ... So anyhow these are all ... (looking at photos for data analysis) Do you remember what we did that day?

Yeah (CMG2)

AR – What were we doing that day?

We were finding creatures (CMG1)

Table 9.14: Conversation styles with the research space (a).

What is that? (CMB1) (pointing at the bird feeders)

AR – we had apples, and we had peanut butter, and we rolled it around with the bird seeds

Where is the peanut butter? (CMB1)

AR – where is the peanut butter? I tell ya where the peanut butter is, It's in my kitchen at home and I had some yesterday for me breakfast with jam and a coffee and it was lovely

(CMG1) laughs

was it on toast? (CMG2) (squeaks Hazel again)

AR – Actually me toaster is broken

you gotta buy a new one (CMG2)

I remember this!!!! (CMB1)

AR – Show me, what do you remember?

Table 9.15: Conversation styles with the research space (b).

We can see how both groups readily chose any number of their own lived experiences to be discussed rather than a fixed, tidier adult-driven agenda of topics (Bae, 2010; Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2019; Kucharczyk & Hanna, 2020). The extract involving what we all got for Christmas coincided with the process of analysing data. Being asked what I got was a real-life moment where power dynamics were dismantled and represented first-hand the weight or time given to the young participant's own topic of interest (Roa et al., 2018; Kucharczyk & Hanna, 2020).

A second aspect of relational participation was the role of the early year's practitioner as the more familiar adult in eliciting participation that could have been missed. The extract above (Table 9.16), where a participant is responding to a worm, demonstrates a moment where I had not understood the participant's preferred communication means, and the support of the ECEC practitioner bridged this gap. Apart from a deeper understanding of individual participants, the presence of the ECEC practitioners helped create a safe space and offered comfort to support those unsure or perhaps fearful of this new adult and experience in their lives (Lundy, 2007; Lundy et al., 2011). The following extract highlights the significance of this role in empowering quieter participation:

ECEC Practitioner walks up to AR holding (B3)'s hand and a motorbike

AR – what is it?

EP – XXX fell off the bike and then when he stood up this was on the seat of the bike

AR – what is it XXX?

a slug (CMB2)

EP what is it XXX?

a slug (B3)

AR – you're right

EP– you know what that is?

AR – you guys are AMAZING

Table 9.16: Participation elicited with the support of an ECEC practitioner.

This moment took place during our insect hunt, which was in a large group. It was very busy, with many voices wanting to be heard. As can happen in group work, there is always the chance that the quieter voice can go unheard. This did occur in this scenario, but as it transpired, the participant approached their more familiar adult, who gave the child the space needed to express their view. As with the extract that describes engagement in how slugs move using their own bodies earlier in this discussion, the skill set of the early years practitioner supported the participation of the quieter child to be included in the research space. From these extracts, the relational aspects of rapport and familiarity between the children and the adults can also be considered with balancing power dynamics in research (Bessell, 2017; Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2019; Kucharczyk & Hanna, 2020).

9.6. Children's own engagement with research tools.

Another factor to be born in mind when developing a child rights-based ESD/CCE approach is the fact that children engage with learning tools/materials in their own individual ways. Again, recognising and respecting these individual engagements can further support a rights-based learning approach. The research workshops comprised a variety of Nature-based or storytelling methods that evolved from the CRAG's advice and the participants' interests. Hands-on activities involved the use of research tools such as art materials, magnifying glasses, natural artefacts, books and photographs, gardening tools, apples, peanut butter, bird seeds, knives, and waste bins, which the participants were invited to explore. Prescribed activities were helpful in terms of bringing focus to the research question and making the

time more effective; however, as described above, the confidence to be flexible and support the child's clock and own engagement with the tools was also necessary to build children's capacities to form and express ideas (Lundy, 2007; Lundy et al., 2011, 2012). The following extract sheds light on how children's own engagement with research tools looked in this context:

EP – there's something in there now XXX still wants to investigate don't ya?

(B3) nods his head

AR – what's that?

a bird (B3)

AR – a bird and have you seen this bird before?

(B3) – nods and starts to peel pictures off the card

how did you do that? (B3)

AR – how did I do that? I got some glue, and I put it on, and I stuck it on the card, to make it a bit stronger ... You can take it off if you like, is that what you'd like to do?

(B3) – nods

and then this (B3)

AR – and then what?

then it's a bird again (B3)

AR – and then it's a bird again? – do you know what type of bird that is?

Yeah.... It's a(B3)

AR – what? Do you know what he is? He's got a red belly. And he's called a robin

a robin? what's that? (B3)

AR – It is a spider

It doesn't look like a spider... It doesn't like a spider ... Ah is that a stone ... Oh that's a snake (worm) ... Is this a stick? What else is in it ... Is that everything? How do I open this one? How does that come off? Oh why do you do that? (B3) (starts to peel picture off card)

Table 9.17: Own engagement with research tools

During this moment, the other participants had left to go outdoors, but this one participant was not finished exploring the research tools. Their particular interest was in how the images were made and whether they could be peeled off like stickers. The participant had previously chosen to watch others' engagement with the tools and to not verbally communicate in the large group discussion. The flexibility within the research space allowed me to recognise and respect this child's particular way of engaging to change the research space to how they enjoyed and elicit meaningful participation that could have been missed (Mannion, 2007; Sargent & Harcourt, 2012; Mackler & Groundwater-Smith, 2015; Leonard, 2016; Bessell, 2017; Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2019).

Figure 9.3: The Magic Nature Bag

As previously described in Chapter 6, the workshop involved a bag of natural artefacts to explore with the young participants their own ideas about Nature. The group had engaged in a game introduced by me of taking turns pulling out something from *The Magic Nature Bag*. As the game evolved, the participants chose not to sing the adult-proposed lead-in song, and either sang their own chosen song or did not sing at all. Furthermore, while the game was originally about turn-taking, it evolved into emptying the contents of the bag onto the floor from which the participants could choose to take and hold artefacts that were of interest to them.

The flexibility in the research space to adapt the activities to support this engagement with the tools served multiple purposes. Firstly, there was the opportunity for the participants to be involved in the decision-making of the research methods and their use to be meaningful to them. Secondly, as this was an early workshop session, the engagement also offered insight into group dynamics, personalities, participation variations and cultural aspects, which also influenced my thinking in developing further effective strategies that could support and respect authentic participation (Lundy, 2007; Lundy et al., 2011, 2012; Mayne et al., 2018; Shier, 2016;2019). Thirdly, there was the chance again to dismantle the adult power dynamic in a real-life moment and recognise that the participants had ownership of how they would engage with the research tools and respond and respect that accordingly (Alderson, 2012; Moore, 2014; Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2019; Kucharczyk & Hanna; 2020). The following extract from a later workshop session gives a further overview of children’s own engagement with the research tools. The research tools comprised a visual story about native birds and materials to make their own bird feeders, including apples, bird seeds, peanut butter, knives, and string.

Figure 9.4: Research tools for exploring birds and making birdfeeders.

I will ... for you (B4) (hands AR apple to go get water)

AR – what were you doing with the apple?

I was cleaning it (B4)

AR – you cleaned it for me?

yeah But I am not finished yet with cleaning (B4)

AR – you're not finished yet? I will hold on to it then, OK?

(B4) cleaning the apple

AR – you are still or are you finished cleaning it?

(B4) hands AR the apple

AR – Oh thank you! that's very helpful! thank you very much ... should we? Would you like to look at my story?

I cleaned an apple for you ... I'm cleaning the (G1)

AR – are you going to clean all the apples for me?

I'll clean this (G1) (takes out a shell)

Table 9.18: Giving participants the space and time to engage in their own way with research tools (a).

The extracts (Tables 9.18 & 9.19) also reflect the free-flowing nature of the local context and the culture of sharing one another's ideas. Again, the flexibility within the session and recognition of the children's conversations as opportunities to replace the adult's preconceived research agenda with the child's offers insight into a strategy that evolved through familiarity and adult confidence. This strategy can be considered supportive of view forming and expression in a meaningful and non-invasive manner in the local context (Lundy, 2007; Lundy et al., 2011, 2012; Mayne et al., 2018; Shier, 2016, 2019).

we can't eat the apples (B4)

AR – You can eat the apples, do you like apples?

Yes (B4)

AR looks at (B3) – do like apples XXX?

(B3) –

yeah I like them peeled (G1)

AR – Oh you like them peeled?

Yeah (G1)

AR – do you eat them with the peel or without the peel ...?

With (B4)

AR – and what about you XXX do you eat them with the peel or without the peel?

without the peel (B3)

AR – without the peel?

(B3) nods head

(B4) (pretends to eat apple) ...I am just joking

AR – You're just joking? Do you want to eat it?

(B4) smiles

AR – Would you like to eat the apple?

(B4) nods head

AR – You can eat the apple if you like, I don't mind, we have loads! Would you like to eat XXX? oh no you'd like me to peel it, I'll tell ya what, if I finish my story can I peel you an apple then? and cut it into slices?

No I want it like a big one and you give it to me (G1)

Table 9.19: Giving participants the space and time to engage in their own way with research tools (b).

Cleaning the apples and discussing the participants' own preferences in apple eating brought forward a cultural aspect that was important to them. Furthermore, the idea of pretending to eat the apple as a joke and then offering it back as their own decision-making opportunity to eat one could also be described as a moment that supported the young participants to enjoy their rights authentically (Percy-Smith; 2010, Horgan et al., 2017; Tisdall, 2017; Gillet-Swan & Sargent, 2019).

9.7. Participation that respects local culture

Recurring conversations throughout the research illuminated cultural aspects of the local context. What I mean by this is that other than routines and systems the setting had in place, the children regularly engaged in their own self-directed conversations. Interestingly the conversation topics were some that I also noted as often encountering over years in practice

as an ECEC practitioner. The ownership of ideas, telling stories, having preferred colours, the importance of turn taking and bringing things home could be considered commonplace within early childhood culture and, therefore, needed respect in this research space. Other aspects included more one-off topics that occurred but appeared to be important aspects of the participants' own lives. The colour of one's toothbrush, Santa Claus presents, birthdays, grandparents, being ill and apple-eating preferences offered insight into everyday cultural matters. Respecting their importance supported the research study to be less strange for the young children, and over the timeframe, the study became an extension of the local setting's culture. I arrived at the same time each Friday morning to a flurry of stories saved up to share with me: what was seen in the garden, whose birthday it was, who is collecting who today, excitement and exploration of what was in the research basket, while also helping the participants with their outdoor gear. This all reflected the busyness of early childhood culture - a living mess (Alderson, 2012; Moore, 2014; Parry, 2015).

Children's views are expressed in that busy social world where thousands of things go on simultaneously. It consists of a shifting network of complex interactions between children and adults, which can provide both constraints and possibilities for interpretation (Edwards, 2010). However, sidestepping the mess or overlooking a cultural aspect or topic not on the research agenda could leave those views and real-life matters unheard (Mertens, 2007). The following extract is from the bird feeder workshop with one young participant explaining their reason for not liking goldfinches:

Figure 9.5: Goldfinch

No but I don't like What I don't like is this one (G1) (points to a picture of a bird)
AR – you don't like that one?
No (G1)
AR – That's Gordon the Goldfinch, why don't you like him?
Cos it's, Cos it's cos I don't like black anymore (G1)
AR – Oh you don't like black anymore ... Ah I see ... ok

Table 9.20: Participant's own perspectives on a goldfinch

The following extracts from the data analysis workshop with the CRAG shed light on cultural aspects of participation. I had intended to come outside to join the younger participants outdoors as they also expressed their wish to be involved in the morning's research session. On arrival, several participants were keen to share their own stories and interests with me:

AR – HI! How are you? XXX has some news for me!!!
(B4) whispers in AR's ear
AR whispers back ... it was what?
AR – what was today?
my birthday! (B4)
AR – your birthday !!!! well Happy Birthday!!! How old are ya?
4 (B4)
AR – Oh my goodness!!!
And I'm 4 (B6)
AR – Did you get a birthday present?
I didn't get one yet (B4)
AR – you didn't get one yet?
or we don't know (B4)

Table 9.21. Participants' own stories influencing discussion topics

Figure 9.6: Sandpit

I want to show you something ... takes AR's hand and walks away (B6)
AR – you want to show me something Come on so!
and you put the sand in there (B6)
AR – what's in there?
you put the sand in there (B6)
AR – oh you put the sand in there!
Yeah (B6)
AR – yes
and it turns around (B6)
AR – Oh! Do you like sand?
yah I love it so much cos I can do what I want (B6)
AR – you love sand so much cos you can do what you want?

Table 9.22: Space to share participants' chosen topics of discussion (a).

on my third birthday I'm going to be 17 (B4)

AR – on your third birthday you are going to be 17? Oh wow!

No 16 (B4)

AR – On your third birthday you are going to be 16!

Watch watch (B4)

AR – Oh wow!!! I'm learning how the sand works!

Do you want to do something that would be fun? (B4)

AR – I would love to do something that would be fun ... come on so!

Look at me (B5)

AR – Oh are you a fireman? ... What do you like to do when your outside XXX?

I like climbing up on that fence (B2)

AR – you like climbing that?

I had to bring my drink all the way over (CMB1)

AR – So you like climbing here and you like climbing there?

B2 – Yeah

I like climbing here too

My mam is here to collect me (B4)

AR – Your mam is here to collect you? Ok. Would you like me to come over and say Hello?

No first I want to show something first (B4)

Table 9.23: Space to share participants' chosen topics of discussion (b).

We can see from the extract above that several interactions took place at the same time, reflecting the culture of free-flowing participation in the setting and how the participants engaged in their own storytelling in their local social world. I was reminded of an earlier research method from Clark and Moss (2011) of the child-led tour explored with the CRAG during the design phase. The children at that stage evaluated the method as limited or ineffective in eliciting voice or ensuring fun for the members. Interestingly, a child-led tour was now organically taking place where perspectives and having fun were very much apparent. What was different? Rapport had been built, which supported familiarity and understanding of the local context and culture. The confidence in recognising real-life matters

that were of importance to participants gave me an understanding of how to adapt my approach to be more reflective and respectful of their culture and world while furthering their participation in a non-invasive and meaningful way (Wall, 2012; Horgan et al., 2017). The extract illustrates everyday life playing outdoors in this local context. It also provides several examples of children sharing their perspectives on Nature learning which, if listened to and respected, could contribute to developing an authentic child rights-based ESD/CCE approach. I had no prescribed questions. I was invited by the children to come and look at their ideas and to listen to their stories. This was child-driven participation with no need for adult parts other than adult ears and respectful listening (Shier, 2016;2019).

9.8. Respecting children’s terminology

A final aspect of participation respecting the local culture is children’s language, which featured in our discussions. Respecting the use of children’s own terms also played a part in dismantling power dynamics:

AR - squeamish is like when you feel sick Uuuuugghhhhh!!!!
eh like puke? (CMB5)
AR – yes !!! exactly!
One time when I ... I got sick (CMG2)
did you puke? (CMB5)

Table 9.24: Participants' own terminology (a).

then you put some sprinkles on it (G1)
They are little seeds (G1)
Look at mine!!!! It's so sprinkly !.... It's all sprinkles (G1)

Table 9.25: Participants' own terminology (b).

Can I use this yolk? (B4)
AR – Ya can, you can use that yolk Do you know what that yolk is? That’s a wooden butter knife from Finland

Table 9.26: Participants' own terminology (c).

An array of participants’ own terminology was featured in the narratives of the children as they shared their ideas. Earwigs were more commonly known as *pinchers*, bees and wasps

were *stingers*, bird seeds were *sprinkles*, pinecones were *hay corns*, and the *yolk* was used inadvertently to formulate ideas. Being mindful of an instinctive teaching reaction to correct this vocabulary, I became aware that the moment children actively expressed their views was not the right time. Like how the participants shared their Nature connections, interrupting these expressions and replacing their own words with mine could be incredibly disempowering and disrespectful under Article 12 while also missing an opportunity to explore the research questions. Learning this from the participants also informed the strategies to better support an inclusive rights-based approach.

9.9. Making Space for ‘Unicorn Moments’

This final section is best described as evolving from a process of critical reflection and analysis of perspectives shared by the young participants that I did not initially understand. As a first-time researcher in the field, I arrived at the setting with a pre-set theory-based agenda intending to learn how these young children enjoyed Nature and produce a piece of rights-based research. We can see from Chapter 8 and the first section of this chapter that the children readily gave any number of perspectives and lived experiences, which I have endeavoured to highlight and link to the possibilities of furthering the realisation of Article 29 1 (e). However, there were also other perspectives, stories, and ideas shared that I did not understand. Nonetheless, they were delivered with such enthusiasm and enjoyment that I must somehow bring them forward as a child’s rights researcher committed to challenging power dynamics in eliciting children’s voices and participation. To do that, I have chosen first to discuss particular aspects of reviewed literature that stood out to me as being difficult to grasp or implement in early childhood research. They were children as experts in their own lives and Lundy’s (2007) description of a research space with no rebuke.

9.10. Children are their own experts.

Although this discussion stems from the work with the CRAG, I consider the discussion to be significant in considering an overall rights-based approach to ESS/CCE. From the beginning of my research studies with children, I have been met with the concept that children are experts in their own lives (Mason & Danby, 2011), but I never fully grasped it. I found the sentence problematic as I battled with the image of my children making themselves sick from

choosing chocolate as their only food source. I left it to linger like that with me and hoped that it would become more apparent as I read more. Fast forward to the first research design workshop and a child-led walk around their garden; I asked the CRAG members *what they liked about Nature*. When the reply was unicorns, I was aghast. There were other suggestions, such as spiders, flowers, and puppies, but I remember having some flash of judgement in my brain as to how the planet would have any chance of survival when Disney was infiltrating the minds of our children. The CRAG member continued describing how beautiful, cute, and magical unicorns were and how much they loved them and wanted to hug them all day long. All I could think was that *they do not even exist!* When the session was over, the CRAG expressed their disappointment that I had not brought more fun things to do and offered me a list of what to bring next time. The list included a unicorn and a puppy.

At our next session, I arrived with a car boot full of loose parts and a particular commitment to creating fabulous unicorns for an open-ended arts-based session exploring what young children would choose to put in outdoor spaces. Unicorns did not make an appearance that day, but flowers, ladybirds, clouds, worms, trees, spaces for cycling and a giant minion did:

Figure 9.7: Outdoor designs with clouds and flowers

Figure 9.8: A giant minion

It was fun and messy. At one point, it was snowing, and a garden where children could play with flour, glue and stick things into playdough for as long as they liked was considered a great outdoor space. While my eco-friendly research tools were being generously used to make that snow, there were a lot more children's voices that day than had been the case during our first session, and an array of ideas was being shared in the process (Nutbrown, 2013; Clark, 2017). I did swallow hard when there was a suggestion to build a large

McDonald's in the middle of their ideal outdoor areas which was met with heartfelt peer agreement. However, I was reminded of Parry (2015) and Klitgaard Povlsen et al.'s (2021) warning to avoid limiting my research methods to a means of simply getting inside children's minds and instead to concentrate on the value they brought as an integrated process of co-constructing knowledge informed by participants' cultural, social and creative contexts. As Fane et al. (2018) have argued, the onus was on me to make peace with fictional characters and fast food chains and to make space for them to be included in the research dialogue to better support the young participants to form their own views on the research questions.

Roa et al. (2018) recognise that learning to listen to young children is pretty complex. However, while we were only at the design stages and rating suggested research tools, I could identify the CRAG members' guidance on what kind of listening environment would better support this project. It took a while to tidy up, and it was all very fast and in the moment. However, in the days of reflection that followed, a deeper understanding of what children as experts in their own lives meant to the CRAG informed my thinking as to how respecting and listening to their expertise without judgement could ensure a safer and more inclusive rights-respecting research space (Lundy, 2007; Leitch, 2008; Lundy et al., 2011; Roa et al., 2018). This gave rise to a new category in my head that I called 'unicorn moments', which aided my adultist need to tidy my fast-paced research space and keep my rebuke in check. I also began to think about the terms 'expert' and 'knowledge' overall and how they are perceived as possible barriers to more effective rights-based research and pedagogy.

In keeping with the study's epistemological position, while I came with my own knowledge, it was the young participants' expert knowledge of their own lives that I required to construct knowledge for a fuller realisation of their rights under Article 29 1 (e) (Mertens, 2007). Bruner (1996) argues that only individuals can live and feel experiences of their own lives, and this can only be shared through a narrative of life stories that are jointly constructed with perspectives of all actors that participate in the re-creation of that life and experience.

However, I did not understand all the perspectives, which made collaborating difficult. Kucharczyk and Hanna (2020) describe the need for adults to go beyond their comfort zones

to support the co-construction of knowledge with children as the experts on specific topics. The ‘unicorn moments’ described above were hugely insightful to the second research aim of exploring how to create a child rights-based ESD approach. I had to be mindful of the knee-jerk judgements in my head and the implications they could have in excluding a young participant’s view (O’Toole, 2020). It showed me how I needed to remain open and reflective of all new ideas to support a better rights-respecting environment they enjoyed (Roa et al., 2018). This relates in particular back to Grindheim et al.’s (2019) argument for the role of ‘subjectification’ in ESD where learners feel safe and are encouraged to go against the grain and explore more abstract thoughts needed to challenge existing ideas/traditions and support more transformational aspects of ESD.

9.11. No rebuke

One aspect of the storytelling research method that the young participants enjoyed was naming the characters in the stories being told.

Figure 9.9: Just Hazel

Figure 9.10: Roby the Rob...Robin the Ribs

The way in which the young participants enjoyed books in our research space gives further insight into this as follows:

(G1) points to the blackbird...that's Lily Lili Li Yeah. No no no he is ... Hazel the h ... No he's Robin the Ribs...

AR – He is Robin the Ribs? There's Robin the Ribs, He was Simon the Song thrush ... Do you like the name Simon the Song thrush or will we call him something else?

Call him Robin the s.....s, Call him, call him Hazel (G1)

AR – Hazel? Will we call him Hazel the Song thrush?

Yeah (G1)

that's like the hedgehog (B4)

AR – It is like the hedgehog..... so this is Hazel the Song thrush and that's

NO! Hazel..... just Hazel (G1)

AR – well that type of bird is a goldfinch..... but what will we call him?

He eats fish (B4)

AR – Oh! Cause I said goldfinch does it sound like fish?

(B4) laughing *yeah*

AR – what I meant to say was goldfinch ... But it sounds like goldfish ... You know what maybe I said it too fast!! Gordon Goldfinch! What does it sound like?

(B4) laughing *sounds like plant*

Table 9.27: Listening with no rebuke during our native bird story.

This story was intended to explore caring for birds where the children could share their own experiences and views. The session was full of laughter and the participants' ideas despite not finishing the book or hearing the actual written story. The engagement continued with the participants deciding together on new names for the native birds that I had to remember. I also had to use the new names while telling the story as they ate the apples I had brought to make bird feeders, and listened to the sea from the shell in my basket. I purposely highlight such detailed extracts of this session to offer insight into how the children guided the session, how busy it was, and how they enjoyed their participation to demonstrate its relevance to the development of a child rights-based education for early childhood.

It is evident that the data here is similar to that of the last section on children having their own expertise with a common theme of children's own connections with their learning. What differs, however, is that plenty of moments contradicted my adultist agenda or perception of

what learning should look like under Article 29 1 (e). Respecting these moments without rebuke created a listening strategy that better supported the participants in building and expressing their own views, which was the study's whole objective.

(B4) takes shell
AR – Oh ... what are ya doing?
(B4) *I am trying to ... hear the sea*
AR – you can hear the sea?
(B4) puts finger to lips *I ...*
AR – Do you need me to ... oh?
(B4) *I can*
AR – you can?
SILENCE
(B4) smiles

Table 9.28: Replacing adult with child agenda **Figure 9.11:** Seashell

The following ‘unicorn moment’ took less than a few minutes and involved all three participants engaging with a shell, which was momentarily more interesting than renaming the native birds. Although I did not see the relevance of this narrative to sustainability thinking at the time, this was an idea being shared and discussed amongst peers that was being thoroughly enjoyed.

Similar to the idea of planting stones discussed in the previous section, I still had the power to elicit or limit ideas that did not fit my thinking. Unicorn moments were also ideas or representations from the young children regarding how they readily enjoyed their participatory rights within the local culture. For me to respect and include them (despite rarely understanding them) provided valuable insight into the participants' perspective of a culture that respects human rights. It also highlights a means to extend learning around the

social and cultural pillar under UNESCO's sustainability definition (2010), which often gets less attention in early childhood education.

AR – Did ya hear anything puts it to (B3)'s ear?

(B3) – No

(G1) – And now my turn ... em I see some and it's ... Away ... and the sea is waving away ...cos the sea is scared of Spiderman points to (B3) who is dressed as Spiderman

AR – who is scared of Spiderman?

(G1) – cos the sea is scared

AR – who is scared?

(G1) – the sea in this (points into the shell)

AR – Oh the sea in that?

(G1) – yeah cos in that little hole

AR – it's in that little hole?

(G1) – yeah

AR – what's in the little hole, the sea?

G1 – yeah

AR – aha! and the sea is scared of Spiderman?

(G1) – yeah

AR – Oh!

(G1) – only it's not scared of ... or it's not scared of a princess (G1 is dressed as a princess)

AR – he is not scared of princesses?

(G1) NO!

AR – that's interesting

G1 – Yeah ... looks back to story book I see another one! (points to a bird)

Table 9.29: Complexities of 'unicorn moments' and giving them a space to support participatory rights authentically.

In addition, decisions within the research space were influenced by actively including these 'unicorn moments', which readily supported many child-initiated elements and an authentic realising of Article 12. A further example of this can be seen in the following final section.

9.12. Child-initiated elements.

The ongoing assent for participating in this session was negotiated on what fancy dress could be worn and an examination of what *cool stuff* was in my research tools basket as described in Chapters 5 and 6. This was followed by the children deciding the location of where the story was to be read, emptying the basket and sharing any number of ‘unicorn moments’ inspired by their engagement with and perspectives on the tools. Engagement included cleaning the apples and eating them while being told the story of *Robby the Christmas Robin* (presented with individual large photographs as seen in Figure 9.10), which had been my intended prescribed activity for the session. In turn, it led to an activity where participants could make their own birdfeeders while creating a space to explore how to care for our native birds.

Figure 9.12: Tools for Bird Care Activity

This was when a child-initiated discussion began on changing the characters' names as outlined in the previous extracts above. Deciding on new names and hearing them being said back as part of the story was much more fun than the original story itself.

Figure 9.13: Lily Lily Lil.

Figure 9.14: Goldfinch not fish.

This game also included ‘unicorn moments’ in this case, not listening to the sea, not liking some birds because of their colour, participants sharing their knowledge of what birds eat, still cleaning the apples, the implications of eating too many apples:

He eats apples (B4)

AR – he eats apples? Well lucky for him, we’ve loads of apples, although you are eating all the apples! Are you going to eat them all?

no how will I eat all those yolks? (B4) laughs

you will get sea sick ... You will get, you will get a black bum (G1)

AR – you’ll get a black bum? From eating all the apples?

Yeah ... you can’t do your wee wee or your poo poo (G1)

AR – You can’t do your wee wee or your poo poo?

No (G1)

AR – Oh dear ... That doesn’t sound good

Table 9.30: Examples of unicorn moments.

Also, counting them and then adding counting to the overall presentation of the story was another child-initiated element:

<p><i>How many birds do you have? (B4)</i></p> <p>AR – I tell ya, I'm not even sure anymore, we could even count them, would you be interested to count them?</p> <p><i>1,2, 3 ... 1,2,3,4, 5,6 (B4)</i></p> <p>(B4) (puts on voice) and starts to hop on pictures ... <i>1,2,3,4,</i></p> <p><i>I will take off my shoes and try what I will get (G1)</i></p> <p>AR – Oh you are going to count them by jumping on them?</p> <p><i>And if I get them wrong I am going to jump off them(G1)</i></p> <p>CHILDREN START TO JUMP ON THE PICTURES OF THE BIRDS</p>
--

Table 9.31: Replacing adult with child agenda.

I am giving such a level of detail of what happened within the space to represent the vast number of interactions that take place within early childhood realities and that took place in this session. I consider this to be both demonstrative and reflective of the complexities of reaching an enjoyment of individual rights. It was also necessary to do so in order to properly dissect how the participants were supported in the realisation of both their education and participatory rights and what respect and enjoyment meant to them. This study has highlighted the contentious positioning of our children as the saviours of the climate crisis alongside the argument that it is essential to introduce an intentional teaching of sustainability to combat the same crisis. This cannot be ignored or dressed up. However, examining how this learning can instead be put forward in a manner that encompasses democracy, which is enjoyed through respecting and including child-initiated elements such as those above, could better inform us on how to address this modern-day issue from a child rights-based approach. The following diagram offers an overview of the number of child-initiated elements that were elicited in this workshop session to support an inclusive rights-respecting culture for the young participants involved:

Figure 9.15: Child-initiated elements

As highlighted within Chapter 5, while participation is one of the guiding principles underpinning the UNCRC, how the child enjoys this right can be challenging to grasp (UNICEF, 2014; Mayne et al., 2018). This was such a busy session with only three young participants and me. The diagram above provides a tidied overview version of the interwoven interactions for a realisation of rights, the reality is that it was a living mess (Edwards, 2010; Alderson, 2012; Moore, 2014; Parry, 2015; O'Toole, 2020). However, despite how perplexing it can be to our adult ears, just eliciting the bits we understand or that fit in with our agenda, limits children's views and rights (Lundy, 2018). The extracts highlight the participants' enthusiasm to engage with the research topic and their competency in contributing various perspectives to inform better, more effective rights-respecting cultures in early childhood (UNICEF, 2014). I chose these extracts and these child-initiated elements to highlight how perceptions of knowledge and positioning of expertise can limit real opportunities in bringing forward an accurate representation of child voice and participation in research. I would never have thought that eating my research tools or renaming bird species, then counting them by jumping on them, but jumping off them if they got the new name wrong would be an authentic realisation of Article 29 1 (e). However, the children did.

9.13. Conclusion

In this chapter I argued for the centrality of respecting authentic child participation as an underpinning principle of a child rights-based approach for ESD/CCE. I focused on the social and cultural, and political pillars of UNESCO's sustainability definition and discussed the children's contributions to creating a child rights-based education approach, which was my second research aim. The first section explored the multiple variations of how participants enjoyed their participatory rights during the research stages. This included 1) free-flowing participation, 2) the child's clock, 3) verbal/non-verbal participation, 4) relational participation, 5) children's engagement with research tools and 6) participation that respects local culture. I also include a discussion on the relevance of respecting children's own terminology and making space for 'unicorn moments' in claiming a child-rights approach. The second section was underpinned by recurring themes of how a rights-respecting space of listening with no rebuke looked like in the local context. The final part of this section provides a tidied-up diagram from one workshop session highlighting the number of child-initiated elements included to make this research approach as rights-respecting to the local context as possible. Early childhood is messy, and being a rights-respecting ECEC practitioner is a busy, highly skilled job. However, it is right in the thick of that mess where all sorts of expertise and ideas of democracy can be found. Therefore, we must get into the mess, embrace the mess, and recognise that we do not fully understand the mess, but by respecting the mess, we can advocate for much more rights-respecting cultures for our young children. The following chapter concentrates on contributions from ECEC practitioners and their perspectives of a transformative approach to ESD for early childhood under Article 29 1 (e).

Chapter 10. Building the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate child rights-based ESD into early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e).

10.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to analyse how to build the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate a rights-based ESD in early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e). Its first key finding is that while practitioners have their own existing knowledge of ECEC and ESD pedagogical synergies, some interpretations of these in practice are problematic from a child rights-based education approach. That said, the participants also gave insights into how child rights are interdependent and leads to my second finding that they often need to be ‘balanced’ for authentic enjoyment in practice and context. This is discussed under the themes of ‘practitioner existing knowledge’ and ‘paradigms of pedagogy’. My final finding is that with all the will in the world and commitment to promoting sustainability with young children, practitioners themselves are often limited in their capacity to make changes for the transformative approach needed for ‘whole system changes’. This can be because of a lack of time and resources or commitment to sustainability at management level or amongst co-workers. Participants provided several suggestions to support sector changes. This is analysed in the final theme of the capacity to enact change. The chapter concludes with a discussion on creating a transformative child rights approach for ESD with insights from the participants that they believe would further empower them in their duty-bearing roles under Article 29 1 (e). The section ends with an argument for a transformative leadership approach for effective change for climate action.

10.2. Participants’ existing knowledge of, and resources for, a child rights ESD approach.

From collaborating with my young participants, I came to stage two with a better understanding of how multiple realities and experiences impact meaning-making and knowledge (Mertins, 2007). While I had my own knowledge of the research topic and represented the children’s knowledge, the goal of stage two was to focus on bringing forward ECEC practitioners’ knowledge and expertise. Thus, in keeping with Bruner’s theory (1996) of constructivism, the first research workshop session started with an invitation for participants to share their lived experiences of early childhood education. I will explore these contributions under the initial first-round codes used for data analysis as ‘access to Nature’, ‘existing sustainable practices’, and ‘existing rights-based practices’. The section concludes

with a discussion on ‘non-rights’ language and ‘prioritising’ rights to support authentic child rights approaches in practice.

10.2.1. Access to Nature

Two of the five participating settings were situated on grounds with extensive daily access to the natural environment, including forestry, streams, vegetable and flower gardens, and farm animals. Another, situated within local primary school premises, also had daily access to Nature in terms of vegetable beds, wildflower gardens, trees, flora, and fauna. The remaining two sites had an outdoor area to which children had open access: *‘Each room has an outdoor extension; we call it our outdoor room’ (ECECP4)*. One of these areas had a mud kitchen, a large sandpit, and a planting area, while the second was concreted, limiting access to natural activity. Both settings also took Nature walks around their local community. While it is not in the study’s remit to measure exact figures of everyday Nature access for young children, the young participants in stage one identified that children make their own connections with Nature. Therefore, it is important to point out the variation in Nature access that occurred amongst this small sample as a starting point for existing practices. In addition, having regular access to Nature (or not) is relevant for Article 29 1 (e) to be fully realised and is therefore pertinent to a child rights-based ESD approach.

10.2.2. Participants’ existing ESD practices

Having invited the participants to share how they currently supported sustainability in their practices, the following examples were given: *‘We compost, we recycle, we buy biodegradable and some of our toys in the garden are made from sugar cane’ (ECECP1)*. The participant continued to explain how they harvest water from a water butt for both plant care and water play and emphasised there was: *‘a lot of recycling within the rooms’ (ECECP1)*. I noted that recycling and other elements of sustainable waste management practice featured to varying degrees within all the participating settings, such as: *‘We’re trying, you know, to recycle as much as we can’ (ECECP4)* and: *‘We are very big on recycling’ (ECECP5)*. The aspect of reusing materials for artwork with children also recurred: *‘using a lot of loose parts and natural materials ... recycle pistachio shells’ (ECECP4)* or: *‘instead of always buying things like arts and crafts, things from the shops, we prefer to use sticks and anything that's found in Nature’ (ECECP5)*. Further aspects of waste management included how children were supported to use their art resources sustainably: *‘We*

would always encourage them to use both sides of the page, and then if they've used half a page, we have a scrap paper box for glueing or sticking' (ECECP8).

Participants from two different settings also reported having compost systems in place: 'There's a big compost outside that the children often will help put stuff in as well' (ECECP2), 'you would see them going with what's left over from break, and not to be wasting it ... it either goes to the bird table if it's fruit and little bits like that or if it's meat or something it will go to the brown bin (ECECP1). Two settings, which also had animals (pigs, rabbits, hens, and dogs) on-site, included the area of food waste management and animal care as follows: 'So all their waste food goes into a pig bin to feed the pigs or the hens (ECECP8). These short extracts give insight into existing ESD aspects that, while different in detail, demonstrate how approaches were adapted locally. In doing so, practices would have more meaning for the young learners at each site. This readily reflects the concept of engaging in children's own authentic sustainability participation (Davies, 2010; 2014; Andersson & Gullberg, 2012). In addition, we can see elements of McDonald's (2015) 'communitarian citizenship learning', where a setting supports connections between an individual and their wider community and values learning to work together for the greater good.

10.2.3. Participants' existing child rights practices

As participants discussed their experiences of child rights practices, they began with an account of inclusive approaches: 'There's not a difference between who can and who can't do whatever on a daily basis' (ECECP1). I also identified that examples of rights-based practices were predominantly based on following children's interests to support meaningful learning activities, such as: 'So our planning is based on the children's interests, and we really listened to them. It's not just what the teacher wants; it's really, we focus on what they want' (ECECP5) or: 'it all comes from the children and from what they're interested in' (ECECP6). From exploring this further with the participants, it was not until I asked further questions that aspects of rights-based approaches were more readily identifiable. A simple example of this was from ECECP5, who continued their example of following children's interests with: 'We focus on what they want, and we go at their pace, we don't rush them, so it's not just like a blanket cover for everyone'. This is also evident in ECECP6's example: 'You know children would have a large say in what we do, and we would run a very emergent

curriculum ... really it is up to the children who want to get involved, you know, and who doesn't want to get involved in different activities'. An insight into how one setting supported their children with participatory rights is demonstrated as follows:

So, in the morning, it's really their idea of what we're going to do, what their interests are in. Every room has a chart, and there's a lever on it, and they have their own pictures up on it. And there's inside or outside, it's a pointer for them to just look at and decide. Especially for children who don't have language, maybe yet, and stuff that they're able to point to what they'd like to do so that their voices are also heard and noted, you know for they might not be able to explain to you that they want to go to the garden, or they might not be able to explain they want to do a particular thing, but when they are able to point to it and it doesn't take long for them to pick up the language unless of course, if there is an additional need, which in that case, they will rely more heavily on being able to point at things (ECECP1).

Table 10.1: Supporting participatory rights in practice.

The emphasis on inclusion as an element of a rights-based approach can be noted again here and remained central to many of the participants' contributions to this theme. These included practical examples of simply having enough resources for everyone: '*We always have enough pots, soil, we have enough bulbs, we have little forks and little shovels*' (ECECP2).

Alongside an understanding of individual participatory rights: '*one or two who didn't like touching the soil, so they preferred to use the shovels*' (ECECP2) or: '*one girl has a particular interest in anything that is sensory, so she started pouring the paint pots*' (ECECP4). This is readily captured in ECECP2's example of when their 'planned weather activity' took a messy twist: '*Once I realised they weren't interested anymore, I kind of left them to it, and we added more water ... they had an absolute blast with it. They were destroyed going home, but they had loved it*'.

10.2.4. Using non-right language and prioritising rights to create an authentic child rights space in practice.

During discussions, practitioners sometimes used language, such as '*allowing*' or '*leading the children around to an idea*' or '*they were let to do that*'. This language would be considered contentious from a child rights-based perspective because it connotes power and authority. Indeed, it caused me to hesitate, like when I researched with the younger participants, and they expressed views that did not align with my thoughts on sustainable practice. However, from working with the children, I knew to take note of that hesitation and not make any assumptions this early on that would close down valuable contributions from the practitioners' experiences of supporting children's rights. I was also reminded of how

Martínez-Sainz (2018, p.4) describes practitioners in the human rights field as acting as *‘mediators within the discourse of human rights’*.

It is not unreasonable to say that the legal language of the CRC is removed from everyday vernacular and requires some form of translation into real life for effective implementation. For Bruner (1996), the overall recognition that the contributions of each community member are valuable resources from which to begin authentic knowledge creation is central to a rights-based participatory research approach. Freire in hooks (1994) describes knowledge as connecting ideas learned in university settings and those learned in life practices. He argues that taking the time to find more subjugated knowledge opens the path to including other experts (Freire, 2000). Child rights education has two broad aims. First, it seeks to provide learners with relevant knowledge and understanding of children’s rights. Second, it aims to empower individuals to develop attitudes and behaviours to promote and protect rights (Martínez-Sainz, 2018).

Children’s rights have also been intentionally designed broadly and flexibly to be relevant in different contexts. However, Martínez-Sainz (2018) highlights that this breadth and flexibility also creates challenges for implementing effective child rights education programmes. She underlines how child rights educators require a particular knowledge to address challenges such as misinterpreted rights. They also need to be able to translate different rights education programmes into specific practices. Martínez-Sainz (2018, p.110) describes this as: *‘translating the discourse of human rights into intelligible parameters applicable to everyday life.’* Aside from having a deep understanding of the theoretical underpinnings of human rights and frameworks established to implement them, educators also require other knowledge regarding pedagogical strategies and understanding learners’ contexts to advance meaningful child rights approaches. The data I discuss in this section highlighted an opportunity to identify challenges (from an explicit rights lens) and authentic learning launch points that can contribute to a transformative education approach.

Bruner (1996) also talks about ‘narrative’ and ‘paradigmatic’ modes of discourse. Narrative modes are characteristic of everyday speaking and reasoning, while paradigmatic modes are

typical of more formalised schooling. Terms such as ‘allow’ and ‘let the children’ suggest an adult permitting a child to enjoy their participatory rights instead of supporting a child to establish how they themselves want to participate. However, that was not the tone of the contributions. When listened to in their full context (Table 10.2.), it is evident that the participant also demonstrates an account of the importance of respecting individuality and their duty to support a child’s realising of rights:

‘I might have thought I’d never have eaten beans with pasta but if that’s what they point at and that’s what they want... and that’s what they ask for... then that’s what they are allowed to have’ (ECECP1).

Table 10.2: Example of contradictory language used to discuss children’s rights-based practice.

Similarly, in this extract: ‘We have little forks, and little shovels that are child sized but most of them didn’t want to use them, they wanted to use their hands, so we **let them**’ (ECECP2), the participant establishes that while tools were provided for a gardening activity, they respected how their young learners claimed their participatory rights.

Interestingly, a discussion on ‘choice’ took place in workshop session 3 that provided insight from the ECEC practitioners’ perspective on the role of choice to better support participation for the children in their setting:

‘it’s mainly you see that we have stuff set up beforehand though, when we come in the morning, we’d leave stuff left out for them on the table, like we have playdough and stuff like that, it’s still us leading it though’ (ECECP7)

Table 10.3: Contradictory practice to balance child rights.

The extract above demonstrates that the participant recognises the contradiction of adults leaving activities ready for the children to choose from when they arrive. However, as the conversation progresses, another participant also makes the following point: ‘I know for us for the very start of the morning, we would have something on the tables just to help the children settle’ (ECECP2). Therefore, while I argue that choice is a contentious concept in child rights, the practitioner highlights its role in supporting children’s rights on occasion. I critiqued the language in the national curriculum framework *Aistear* in Chapter 3 because it contains the terms ‘choice’ and ‘voice’, which can limit authentic child participation.

(Notably, this has been addressed to a point under the discussion of multimodal voice in the updated version (NCCA, 2024)). However, transitioning from the home environment to the

early childhood setting can be difficult, and having activities ready from which to choose can support the right to feel safe (NCCA, 2015). This highlights the importance of ‘other expert knowledge’, namely from the more familiar adults, in this case, the ECEC practitioners, in sustaining ‘the balancing act’ (ECECP3) or mediating child rights in practice (Martínez-Sainz, 2018).

The topic of ‘choice’ was further discussed in the workshops about its role in evolving capacities (Lundy et al., 2011; 2012) to better support children in forming ideas such as: *‘some of them you know are still learning what they like ... so if you don’t have anything available for them, they might not realise that they like playing with dolls’ (ECECP2)*. One participant explained that practitioners sometimes must be more directional to balance other rights or considerations. *‘So there will always be a certain amount that we have to provide, but as long as you are still listening to the children and letting them have those conversations and build on what they are talking about ... I think it balances itself out’ (ECECP2)*.

Chapter 2 discusses how rights are interdependent, and this discussion provides insight into how that looks from an ECEC perspective. Rather than having an all-out veto on the word choice, the participants put forward that how we respond to young children in moments of ‘choice’ is more relevant in scrutinising claiming a rights-respecting culture.

hooks (1994, p.11) describes how an engaged voice: *‘must never be fixed and absolute’* but rather *‘always changing, always evolving in dialogue’*. She used this point to highlight that to teach effectively in varied communities, it is not only our paradigms that need to shift but also how we think and speak. While hooks is referring to teaching, it was evident to me that this also applied to this research space. Respecting how other knowledge is shared and, therefore, heard is essential to a transformative education approach.

10.3. Paradigms of pedagogy

As highlighted in the previous section, taking the time to explore more subjugated knowledge is integral to a transformative rights paradigm. In addition to a deep understanding of human rights frameworks, a transformative rights approach requires the educator to have knowledge of pedagogical strategies and to understand the local context. In chapter 5, the child rights research methodology chapter, I identified several key pedagogies (listening, slow, relational and reflective) that I considered essential in supporting a transformative rights-based

pedagogy and, therefore, essential to explore further in stage 2. As outlined in Chapter 6, ‘paradigms of pedagogy’ was a term I came across when reading hooks’s (1994) work on creating communities of learning. I use it to acknowledge the multiple pedagogies at play in early childhood education and varied understanding of common early childhood concepts that contribute to the effectiveness (or not) of these pedagogies from each participant.

The different levels of understanding that I identified among the participants prompted me to examine how pedagogical concepts were being translated into their practice. These concepts, namely child participation, funds of knowledge and reflective practice, are dominant in contemporary early education theory (NCCA, 2015), feature throughout the national curriculum framework (NCCA, 2023) and must be understood and practised effectively in order to shift to rights-based pedagogy pertinent to a transformative ESD approach. However, like child rights, when we hear them being used, we can be blinded into thinking that they are being readily implemented in practice with young children daily (Lundy & Martínez-Sainz, 2018). But are they? How can we know otherwise? And to what degree?

10.3.1 Child participation

Child participation is underpinned by shared information, dialogue, and mutual respect. In addition, good child participation emphasises ‘*communication in a safe space*’ (DECDIY, 2021, p.31), and the participants gave many examples of listening to children: ‘*We are listening out for what they are saying and build on that*’ (ECECP2) and: ‘*You know, like listen out for something that the children are interested in*’ (ECECP7). Certainly, there was a purpose to this listening in terms of decision-making and promoting child-led activity. The importance of listening to the children in one’s practice as part of a practitioner’s role was described as follows:

but as long as you are still listening to the children and letting them have those conversations and build on what they are talking about (ECECP2)

Table 10.4: The importance of listening

However, there were moments in the sessions that indicated a gap in participants’ understandings of child participation, particularly in discussions that included references to children leading ‘*everything we do*’ (ECECP7). This was an example of a recurring misconception regarding child rights, namely, that children are given all the power or lead in

decision-making (DCEDIY, 2021). It was not apparent that children were being listened to so the practitioners could learn how they define their participatory rights. Nor was there evidence of the necessity to understand individual variations in child participation to fully realise rights in practice at a local context.

10.3.2. Funds of knowledge

The term ‘funds of knowledge’ is something that ECEC students should come across in the initial stages of their studies (NCCA, 2015; 2020). When we discuss a child’s ‘funds of knowledge,’ we recognise them as individuals with their own ideas, views, and life experiences. For the most part, it can be claimed that within contemporary early childhood studies, taking the time to recognise and understand individual children’s ‘funds of knowledge’ is an effective means to support learning dispositions and cultural diversity (NCCA, 2015, 2020).

In discussions with practitioners, I noticed that they used ‘funds of knowledge’ in a contradictory way. Sometimes, they used the idea to build upon children’s learning (NCCA, 2015). While building on children’s learning is part of what the concept means, it is much more than that. It is also about building dialogue and developing ‘sustained shared thinking’ (Sylva, 2004), which is essential for supporting a rights-based approach. Sustained shared thinking is when children and practitioners collaborate intellectually to solve a problem or clarify/develop an idea. However, when looking at examples from the workshop sessions, there were times that the children’s knowledge was being used to feed into a form of ‘required’ child-initiated activities, rather than developing ‘sustained shared thinking’:

Well we do do that so like we do listen out for some of the activities, you know like listen out for something that the children are interested in and something that we can hear them talking about quite a bit, now that does not happen every week but we do try to make sure that the theme we are doing that week, is what the children want to do and not like say we don’t always have to do Spring, it was just we picked Spring because we didn’t hear anything of interest that the children had straight up, so we picked Spring, so we you know it’s something like we have to put into the scrapbooks you know (ECECP7)

Table 10.5: Listening out ‘for’ children’s interests.

Within the same discussion, another practitioner described how they sometimes felt that children’s knowledge was being used instead for their own agenda:

While I pride myself in following the child’s lead, allowing most of the session to be led by child-initiated ideas, following along and extending their interests so that all their learning is based on their interests, encouraging freedom and autonomy in every aspect of the session, while keeping their best interests in mind, do I still have my own agenda? (ECECP6)

Table 10.6: Children’s interests and practitioner’s own agenda.

In keeping with Bruner’s ‘theory of learning’, a learner’s knowledge should be the starting point of any curriculum (1961). However, the point that **ECECP6** made is particularly relevant to how children’s ‘funds of knowledge’ might again be limited in some early childhood practices from a rights-based perspective. For example, it was still not evident from the workshops whether children’s ‘funds of knowledge’ were recognised as a set of expertise in their own right (Mason & Danby, 2011; DCEDIY, 2021). Nor could I clearly establish whether there was value placed on this expertise other than its use to develop (plan) child-initiated learning, as with the example above.

10.3.3. Reflective practice

The PAR workshops were designed to facilitate reflection in several ways. Firstly, participants were encouraged to self-reflect on any aspects of the workshop contents and share them either as a written piece in a secured shared folder or directly with me via email, which I could present later to the larger group. Participants used a combination of these methods to further the reflective dialogue among us. A few examples of self-reflection also gave insight into how involvement with the study and its content changed some participants’ thoughts on practice. The following piece describes how one participant was exploring cleavers with some children and showing them how they stuck to things as follows:

So look I just pulled some cleavers and I stuck them to one of the children and I pulled some more and I stuck them to another one and you know like straight away they started wondering why like, what’s happening and what are you doing, and can I have some and get me and whatever else so I kinda thought or I kinda just let them at it and I showed them where they were growing and where to find them and they made up their own little game of playing it and then this week, I left it at that then, you know I didn’t go any further that day (ECECP8)

Table 10.7: Participant reflecting on their own rights-based education approach (a).

The participant explained how one group of children enjoyed making potions with greenery, sand, water and sticks from the garden. Superheroes and superpowers have also regularly featured. Following on from being introduced to the cleavers, the participant asks the children what they might add to the potion to get a climbing superpower like Spiderman: *'and they said they were talking back and over about climbing and then somebody says, 'Oh he would need to be sticky' and I said, 'Oh we need to find plants that are sticky' (ECECP8)*. At this point, the practitioner acknowledges that they: *'had to kinda push that a little bit as they didn't quite recall' (ECECP8)*. The children, in turn, went to collect the cleavers for the potion, and the practitioner described how they (the practitioner): *'pulled back' and: 'I don't know. I don't want to be intruding in their game, and they were playing a really nice game. You know they were chatting and saying 'You get this, and you do that, and we can mix this' (ECECP8)*.

In a similar type of reflective dialogue, another participant described how their setting was recycling and reusing for so long that perhaps they had missed the opportunity to involve the children in the decision-making of how their waste management system should work from their own perspectives:

So you see we have been doing recycle, reuse for so long now that I can't even remember how long ago it is, that we introduced it into the rooms, the different bins and the bins do have different pictures on them so the children do know, what way to recycle, I suppose for me, maybe I don't wait for the conversation if you know what I'm saying, I realise that this is something that I've done for so long that I didn't wait for the conversation to start, or hopefully start about recycling to introduce it, so we might have pre-empted that because it's already part of our every day, that we do, you know as soon as they open their own lunch boxes, and their own wrappers, nearly from day one there's a place for it to go, there's compost, there's you know, we do it automatically, and because we have been doing it for so long, I haven't really thought about before, because it's part of what we do (ECEP1).

Table 10.8: Practitioner reflecting on their own rights-based ESD approach (b).

What I found interesting about these examples was the detail of the practitioners' own thought processes on their practice being shared. The two settings that are involved here in this discussion are at either end of the scale in terms of *'buy-in' (ECECP8)* from management and, therefore, *'change agent capacity'* (Ferreria et al., 2012; 2015) to promote an effective systems-wide ESD approach. Equally, on paper, one of the settings would

convey a very positive approach to everyday sustainable behaviours, although this was adult-initiated. While the capacity to engage in reflective practice effectively was readily identifiable, the time to reflect on everyday practice to establish a child rights-based ESD approach was still very much needed as an ongoing requirement (Van Krieken Robinson, 2019).

10.4. Practitioners' capacity to enact change.

It was evident from the PAR sessions that without the support or 'buy-in' from colleagues and management, participants found it challenging to include sustainability in their practice. Therefore, while I needed to examine the possibilities and barriers currently existing to support young children's education rights, I also needed to examine how ECEC practitioners were supported in their duty-bearing role under Article 29 1 (e).

10.4.1. Challenges to make change in practice.

Some participants reported difficulties in bringing about change: '*We are very fragmented in the place where we are*' (ECECP8) or: '*I know even people like who I work with don't care about recycling, and it's not something that bothers them at all*' (ECECP8).

When one participant was asked if efforts to implement sustainability in their settings were supported, the response was rather sobering:

No, no, no, I would say, well I won't discuss management because it's probably not for this spot, I will say no, there is no mention of sustainability, there is no mention of environmental anything and I know I can say that in the other Montessori rooms everything goes into the rubbish, there's no recycling that goes on, there's Twistables everywhere I look, anyway, so it's very much down to each person' (ECECP8)

Table 10.9: Example of support (or lack of) to implement sustainability practices.

The participant above understood the relevance of attitude for their duty-bearing role under Article 29 1 (e): '*I do think if the adults don't have the passion, they won't pass it on*' (ECECP8). However, outside their own room: '*again it depends on the room*' (ECECP4) and without support from their management, their capacity as change agents (Ferreria et al., 2012, 2015) was limited: '*you don't have the 'buy-in' I think*' (ECECP8). In contrast, one participant described an atmosphere or opportunity to collaborate in change-making where management was on board as follows:

all the staff are degree qualified, the administrator is degree qualified, we are on board with everything, it's altogether, recycling composting, we meet twice a week we chat about everything you know (ECECP1).

Table 10.10: Whole setting support for sustainability practices.

10.4.2. The necessary leadership skillset to enact change.

Ferreira et al. (2015) contend that it is notoriously difficult to change teaching practice.

Moody and Dahlberg (2019) underline that to effect change across a complex system such as ECEC practitioner training, change is required amongst a wide range of training institutes, universities, government agencies, statutory authorities, and early years settings. Leadership capacities are increasingly recognised as necessary in transitioning to sustainability.

However, being ‘in a position of leadership’ does not automatically mean a person has the right skillset to enact system wide change. As described in Chapter 4, Ferreira et al., 2015 argue that a ‘bottom-up’ network leadership approach is needed, where the opportunity is given for all those involved in an organisation to contribute. The participants did have their own ideas on how to get the support they needed in making changes for more sustainable behaviours in their practices:

‘I work for a business, so from a business point of view I think there has to be an incentive for a lot of managers to actually get behind it, and you know once it becomes a business, I don't want to say business problem but a thing that must be implemented for your business, managers will do it then because they have to’ (ECECP8).

Table 10.11: Participant’s suggestion to enact whole system changes.

Aside from being aware of resistance to embedding effective, sustainable practices (Waldron et al., 2020), the participants also identified the contradictory nature of their own suggestions:

‘I know that's not a good reason to be sustainable ... I was thinking a while back if the business was going to get a lovely green flag for being a fabulous sustainable business I know my manager in the morning would have us all doing it because it would be great for business, but then anyway who cares the reason we do it because it is being brought down to the children and then maybe attitudes are changing’ (ECECP8)

Table 10.12: Ambivalence in suggestion to enact system change.

This prompted a further group discussion on how to bring about a change in leadership that would better support the practitioners in their efforts:

So, something like the green flag in schools but for preschools or the layer underneath that would be a good idea ... I'm all day trying to think because we are not for profit; everything we get we put back in, you know (ECECP1)

Table 10.13: Suggestion to enact whole system change.

The participants also considered that linking sustainability practices with funding and policy could further changes in behaviour: *'It probably should be brought in a bit, and this is going to go down to Core Funding²⁴' (ECECP1)*. *'Core Funding is reliant on engaging with Síolta and Aistear' (ECECP1)*, which the participant considered *'an ideal place to bring sustainability in' (ECECP1)*. The group continued with the idea that with this *'whole demand for quality and quality practice and having goals now with the new Core Funding' (ECECP1)*, the opportunity was there for settings to collaborate in *'a sustainability goal, a biodiversity goal, that could be one of our goals' (ECECP1)*. It is evident that the necessary knowledge, understanding, and critical analytical thought to make changes featured in this small group of participants. These attributes could be marshalled by cultivating Ferreira's 'bottom-up network leadership' to address the deficits identified in the previous section. However, while network leadership is effective in order to have different expertise heard within a system for decision-making, it does not necessarily bring about the sense of empowerment needed to change mindsets and behaviours for sustainability. It is rather transformative leadership that does that (Baroudi & Lytras, 2024).

As described in Chapter 4, based on Mezirow's 'transformative learning theory' (1997), transformative leadership aims to empower people to change their mindsets and behaviours (Feriver et al., 2016). Mezirow's theory holds that as learners obtain new information, they evaluate their past ideas and understanding and shift their views through critical reflection. Providing accessible knowledge, resources, and support enables a transformation in thinking and practice (Ferreira et al., 2015; Feriver et al., 2016; Robson, 2016; Moody & Darbellay, 2019). Feriver et al.'s (2016) research also found that peer discussion and guidance from a more knowledgeable mentor in sustainability supported participants in recognising and voicing their disorientation while receiving new information. Aspects of a transformative leadership approach that I used could also be identified within our sessions as the participants

²⁴ Core Funding is a new strand of governmental funding for early childhood and after school settings designed to improve affordability, quality, inclusion and sustainability. It is optional and subject to an agreement of terms and conditions where settings must provide reports of evidence based high quality practice (GOI, 2022).

provided insight into elements of the sessions they enjoyed. I present these aspects under the subheadings of ‘journey’, ‘community’, and ‘mentorship’ to be considered for bringing about transformative change for effective ESD in the ECEC sector.

10.4.2.1 Journey

The following extract describes one practitioner’s experience of the research approach for stage two:

‘I probably found it a bit confusing in the beginning I kinda, I was more concerned about what you wanted from us at the end of it all, rather than concentrating on the journey and realising the end would kinda happen which is actually what did happen so I was probably confused in the beginning because I wasn’t seeing what was needed at the end, but now that I’ve gone through the journey and it was about learning as we go, it was about what practices were in place, this forum and the chats, and the conversations, so while I found it confusing in the beginning, if we were to do it again, I wouldn’t change how you did it, if that makes sense. It was to sit back and go through the journey really. The journey was the learning for me’ ECECP3.

Table 10.14: Practitioner’s description of their learning in the research process

In this example, the participant is describing their experience of how I introduced ESD concepts with them in my PAR approach. In transformative learning theory, the first step is usually the ‘disorientating dilemma’ (Mezirow, 1997) - supporting the learner to question their current perceptions or knowledge of a subject or practice. The thought process behind this is that for a person to really change or transform an existing behaviour, it is essential to recognise a possible contradiction in that behaviour with new learning being introduced. Through a process of reflection (self and/or peer) and critical thinking while engaging with new ideas, this disorientation should support the learner in transforming ideas/ thoughts/ actions to some degree. I am most drawn to the participant’s use of the word ‘journey’. As with Mezirow’s (1997) theory, there was confusion or disorientation, but now having gone through the: ‘journey’, which was: ‘*the learning for me*’ (ECECP3) and which consisted of: ‘*the chats and the conversations*’, the participant concludes: ‘*I wouldn’t change how you did it*’ (ECECP3). A second participant continues with their thoughts on this type of journey learning: ‘*The destination is undecided at the beginning ... because we don’t know where we are going to end up ... but we will keep learning as we go along*’ (ECECP1). hooks (2003) also describes learning as a process that does not force learners to hold theories. Instead, we should respect this process, the inquiry involved, the times of not knowing and the uncertainties that go with that.

These discussions reminded me of Sageidet's (2014) argument on the role of a practitioner's personal motivation for effectively promoting ESD in daily practice. I also thought of Feriver et al.'s (2016) point that practitioner training has historically been rooted in hierarchical and authoritarian cultures expressed through top-down decision-making and policy processes. In contrast, the participants describe their enjoyment of a journey-type learning process, where there was space for chats, conversations and exchanging of knowledge.

This journey learning approach also speaks to rights-based educational theory, particularly the educator's need to take time to understand and respect local context and culture as the first step to authentic learning. I could identify this journey aspect as a means that empowered the participants to think about sustainability which is relevant to the third research aim of capacity building. Notably, discussions revealed that capacity building was not just a question of providing ESD resources to early childhood settings. It also included the need to respect multiple forms of expertise and knowledge and strategies to make space for practitioners to share their contributions to building the capacity of the entire educational sector (bottom to top) for the effective promotion of ESD/CCE. The responsibility of all ECEC stakeholders was emphasised rather than the onus being put on the educators themselves.

10.4.2.2. Community

Another participant described the forum of the research workshops as a '*relaxed way to learn*' (ECECP8). The same participant also used words such as: '*safe*' and '*welcoming*', which aligns with the notion of inclusion and respect: '*everyone was very welcoming in listening and things*' (ECECP8). Equally, the opportunity to share ideas was highlighted as something that was enjoyed:

I kinda loved the opportunity to hear other settings or services, what they do, what they don't do, their ideas, even that idea with the fruit there, like just things like that are something that you don't get a chance to do every day, and when you are only in and out of your own setting sometimes you can't see anything else, so really I enjoyed that bit (ECECP8).

Table 10.15: Participant's enjoyment of their research participation

This caused me to think of Bruner's theory of 'community learning' (1991) in this regard and how rather than one person driving the dialogue in our space, multiple voices and, therefore, multiple expertise were shared. This diversity of voice also lent itself to Mezirow's point on

ongoing reflection to further feed one's learning or thought process change (1997). Furthermore, this theme of community reflects aspects of McDonald's (2015) 'communitarian citizenship learning' and equally reflects a democratic leadership style in bringing a large group along to take action and make changes (Ferreira et al., 2015).

10.4.2.3. Mentorship

As reported above, I visited one setting that was finding it difficult to establish a rights-based ESD approach. It gave insight into a form of mentoring the participants enjoyed: '*The site visit hugely helped us*' (ECECP3). The participant continues this by describing the '*in-person training*' (ECECP3) and a particular '*passion*' from a mentor to ignite an enthusiasm to learn. This is shared in a story about the participant's partner who enjoys attending workshops with an educator in their discipline:

She brings the classroom out to Oak park, and covers all the ecology tri Gaeilge every year, but he says it's the passion she delivers it with, now he really looks forward to it, and obviously he is getting long in the tooth now, it's not new stuff that he is hearing, but he has said he has never walked away from her without learning something new, but again it's that in person teaching, similar to the site visit (ECECP3)

Table 10.16: Learning from someone passionate about a subject.

A second participant also highlights enjoying mentorship as a form of learning when they describe their setting's experience: '*We wanted somebody to come in from the outside and come into us, and talk about how we were doing things, and it was actually like a really light bulb moment*' (ECECP1). Mentoring can be described as a reciprocal collaborative relationship in learning. As with the collaborative nature of the dialogue that supported reflective practice within our PAR sessions, the participants identified aspects of a learning approach they readily enjoyed (Maloney & Pope:2023).

The word '*enjoy*' is key, and if we look back, it also threads together the three areas of 'journey', 'community', and 'mentorship'. Both hooks (2004) and Freire (1970) emphasise the enjoyment of learning and that while democratic educators ensure an atmosphere where learning and teaching are taken seriously, it must also generate happiness. This reverts to Sageidet's (2014) point on personal motivation for an effective ESD approach. At first glance, we can consider these contributions relevant to informing a teaching philosophy for a

rights-based ESD approach being put forward by the ECEC practitioners' one that was underpinned by the learners' own sense of well-being and supported within a mentoring community of learning. In addition, I argue that these contributions could equally be considered in an overall discourse on the type of transformative leadership necessary to also bring about Ferreira et al.'s (2015) 'whole system change'. This would require much further investigation considering the change that took place within the research space was of itself limited.

10.4.3. Creating a 'bottoms up' transformative child rights based ESD module

Aside from support such as whole-system 'buy-in' to enable practitioners to make changes for more sustainable practices, there was also discussion on suggested content for a transformative rights-based ESD module for ECEC. Participants highlighted two specific areas that needed consideration: 'specific ESD knowledge' and 'a sense of wonderment' necessary to support a child rights-based ESD approach.

10.4.3.1. Specific ESD knowledge

From discussing each participant's ESD knowledge level, an initial response was: *'We don't really really have the nuts and bolts of where it's all coming from'* (ECECP1). When asked what they would like to learn about sustainability or what content should be included in an ESD module for early childhood, the following perspectives were also shared:

I think it would be more the technical, not technical but more of an in-depth knowledge, and probably a million other ways in that we can do things, and things that would be applicable to young children that we could learn more about would be interesting and good to do (ECECP1).

Table 10.17: Suggestion of content for ESD module for ECEC practitioners.

The participants were aware of gaps in their knowledge: *'we wouldn't have a massive, massive amount of knowledge; we have enough, you know, to try and do the best we can, but I think we could do more, so I think if we knew more you know.* (ECECP1), but also gave suggestions to address this. For example, some proposed bringing in speakers such as *'a biodiversity expert'* (ECECP1) and *'an ecologist'* (ECECP8), which could ignite: *'like this wondering awe we want to give to children nearly needs to be instilled in us'* (ECECP8). Appendix T provides a full outline for a proposed module which includes this contribution from the participants as follows:

‘... the module begins with an introduction of climate change and what the planetary crisis is happening. This includes an analysis of human behaviour and the effects of them on global warming, biodiversity loss, population displacement, water/food scarcity and sanitation and other impacts. Climate injustice and how certain groups of people are more at risk from climate change will be explored. This will lead to analysing how sustainability itself is an evolving concept and the multiple pillars of sustainability (ecological, economic, social and cultural and political). We will also explore alternative, pro environmental human behaviours and what changes need to be made on a global, local and personal level to combat the crisis’.

10.4.3.2. A sense of wonderment

One participant also shared the view that: *‘there has to be something in it that gives people that are studying the course a passion for the environment or for Nature’ (ECECP8).*

During a discussion on creating a possible ESD module for ECEC, the participant argued that its content needed to have an effect on the learner so: *‘that when a practitioner comes out of it ... they feel almost energised to pass on’ (ECECP8).* I found this insightful in addressing negative attitudes and values experienced by the participants in their efforts to embed sustainability practices. It was necessary first to take the time to develop the practitioners’ own sense of wonderment or: *‘the love of Nature’ (ECECP8)* before considering the more practical aspects of transferring sustainability knowledge to young children. The same participant suggested that: *‘a module more specific for us’* that: *‘makes us see how wonderful everything is’* would be more effective to an overall embedding of an ethos of sustainability as: *a thread that goes through every single thing that you do that no matter what you are teaching, even if it’s just Legos, I don’t know, there’s a way to bring in sustainability into it (ECECP8).* This is included in the module content as follows:

‘Connecting with Nature and extending these connections to develop sustainability thinking to develop a rights-based participatory approach with the young participants was another research finding. In addition, the ECEC practitioner participants also recommended the opportunity for students to develop their own ‘sense of wonderment’ of Nature as means to effectively support taking care of the planet in practice. To that end, the module will explore this aspect by providing learners to be in Nature (using the outdoor campus spaces/local outdoor amenities such as forests, rivers/beaches, mountains etc.) and through the use of technology and the digital world.

10.4.4. Time and enough hands

In addition to suggestions regarding module content, participants also pointed to changes that needed to happen in day-to-day practice to support a rights-based ESD approach. In the following extract, one participant discusses how a lack of time impedes practitioners from supporting child participation in their context:

Yeah, I get the science ²⁵behind it, but it's just hard to put it into practice because you know we are only with them for the morning (ECECP7)

Table 10.18: The science of implementing child rights.

When asked to provide an example of this, the participant described how that morning, one child had wanted to create an underground sea monster, and, in that case, they (the practitioner) could support this play as it was a one-on-one scenario. However, the participant also described how other children in the room: *'were looking for other things as well, but they were coming to me, and then I felt like, I couldn't move from him, because he still needed my attention'* (ECECP7). A similar example was given by another participant who described that while children were encouraged to go outdoors when they wished: *'That's again, you know, depending on the number of staff, 'cause there's always 11 and a number of staff that needs to be outside'* (ECECP4).

I was not clear on whether the issue was time or lack of it or whether it was a lack of support in terms of more practitioners being present to effectively support every child's participatory rights in practice. Possibly both, but certainly something that needs to be considered when committing to implementing a rights-based approach. The fact is that during stage one when collaborating with the children, my sole role was to listen. Moreover, designing the methodology required a tremendous amount of time to listen. It also required flexibility and an 'all hands-on deck' approach to support participation authentic to the local context. Feedback from academics and practitioners on this study suggests that, given the amount of time I had to devote to listening to children, I was in a privileged and unrealistic early childhood space. However, I did identify that it could be done with the right resources.

Clark (2020) talks about the lack of time and working within a contradictory culture in ECEC that, in one breath, promotes child rights as listening to children and following their interests, and, in the other, demands reporting quality practice standards through laborious paperwork. This contradiction has been identified as a barrier to promoting a child rights-based education approach (Clark, 2020). Insufficient time is featured repeatedly in the workshop sessions as

²⁵ When discussing the theory behind a rights-based approach we often referred to it in our workshop sessions as 'the science'.

the main barrier to engaging in a rights-based education approach: *'I only have one hour with the children outside'* (ECECP4) or: *it's just a big barrier, you know you'd love to do more and let them lead everything we do* (ECECP7). Not having sufficient time or physical support to effectively engage with every child's idea is a common limitation in ECEC and another aspect of practice that must be addressed if practitioners are to be empowered to enact change.

10.5. Conclusion

This chapter analysed how to build the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate a rights-based ESD in early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e). I began with the finding that while practitioners have their own existing knowledge of ECEC and ESD pedagogical synergies, some interpretations of these in practice are problematic from a child rights-based education approach. The participants also gave insights into how child rights are interdependent which led to my second finding that they often need to be 'balanced' for authentic enjoyment in practice and context. This is discussed under the themes of 'practitioner existing knowledge' and 'paradigms of pedagogy'. My final finding is that practitioners themselves are often limited in their capacity to make changes for the transformative approach needed for 'whole system changes'. This can be because of a lack of time and resources or commitment to sustainability at management level or amongst co-workers. Participants provided several suggestions to support sector changes. This is analysed in the final theme of the capacity to enact change. This section also discusses the necessary leadership skillsets required to empower practitioners to make changes. I conclude with the argument that creating a transformative child rights approach for ESD with insights from ECEC practitioners would empower them more effectively in their duty-bearing roles under Article 29 1 (e).

Chapter 11. Conclusion

11.1. Introduction

This thesis sets out to explore the perspectives and lived experiences of young children and ECEC practitioners on Nature under Article 29 1 (e) of the UNCRC and how they can contribute to a transformative child rights-based ESD approach for early childhood. Chapter 2 sets the context by discussing how the climate crisis impacts children's lives and explaining why it is a child rights crisis (UNICEF, 2021; UNCRC, 2023). The chapter also highlights the obligations of the ratified States to ensure that any decisions taken on climate action do not negatively impact the rights of children or future generations (UNGA, 2018). I conclude with a discussion on the critiques of the Convention and the necessity to reframe rights for the type of action needed to combat the crisis (Davies, 2014). Chapter 3 concentrates on policy and curriculum for supporting a child rights-based approach to ESD in early childhood. I examine international legal and policy context before providing a detailed analysis of national policy for children and ESD. This leads to an overall discussion on the ambiguity surrounding the value of ECEC for ESD promotion within Irish State policy. The second section provides a curriculum analysis from a national perspective and then an international one. It concludes with a discussion on the recent updating process of the national curriculum framework (NCCA, 2024) and its relevance for embedding transformative ESD.

Chapter 4 reviews literature and research on learning in, through, about and for Nature under Article 29 1 (e). I begin with an analysis of how Nature learning and young children as learners have been considered in early childhood pedagogies and examine the pedagogical synergies between ESD and ECEC. The second section explores ESD in early childhood research and the complexities surrounding sustainability as a concept. This involves a discussion of its various definitions and learning approaches, including an analysis of collaborative, participatory projects. The final section discusses the ECEC practitioner's duty-bearer role and how the perceived complexities of sustainability can act as a barrier to effective ESD implementation in early childhood. I also review transformative research studies in this section and changes in initial teacher training programmes, including specific content on leadership skills for effective sustainability.

The study involved two stages. I worked with young children in their ECEC setting for stage one and with ECEC practitioners on an online platform using Microsoft Teams for stage two. Chapters 5-7 are the methodology chapters. Chapter 5 begins with an exploration of child rights-based participatory research and its principles. I continue with a discussion on implementing the approach with young children and the ethical considerations involved. The central role of reflexivity within the methodology and the informed consent process are both examined. The chapter concludes with an explanation of the data analysis approach and coding system used. Chapter 6 gives an account of the young children's involvement in the design of the methodology. This includes the recruitment of a research advisory group and their evaluation of some traditional research methods used with young children. There is also an account of a change in research roles and an adjustment to the *Lundy Model* to suit the local context informed by this advisory group. The chapter concludes with a discussion of data analysis with the children and several process orientated findings used to further inform an inclusive research approach. Relating to that, I describe how there was, at times, a crossover between the data collection and data analysis processes which, while complex to follow, was respectful of authentic child participation. Chapter 7 concentrates on the participatory action research (PAR) approach I chose to use with the ECEC practitioners and the rationale behind that. I describe the fundamental principles of a PAR approach and how they were considered while working with this particular group. This is continued by a short discussion on tensions I experienced while following these principles and an examination of where the overall 'action' was in the approach.

Chapters 8-10 are the main findings chapters and are presented under each of my three research aims.

11.1.1. To explore with young children their own perspectives and lived experiences of Nature under Article 29 I (e) of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child.

Chapter 8 examines how both groups of young participants (CRAG members and younger research participants) shared many perspectives and experiences of Nature during stage one. In summary, the research found that given the right resources (access to Nature, time, flexibility, and a familiar listening adult), the young children defined their own relationship with Nature and made their own connections with it. This ranged from how they engage with natural artefacts to choosing their play to sharing knowledge and ideas. Taking the time to listen to these Nature connections and using them as a means to intersect with elements of

sustainability meant that the participants themselves could contribute competently to developing an ESD approach that had meaning to them. Furthermore, as the children made these connections, which are used to create meaningful learning for sustainability, they also established their own definitions of participation. Figure 11.1 gives an overview of their contributions, namely their connections with Nature and how when these connections are respected can inform a child rights-based education approach under Article 29 1 (e)

Figure 11.1: Respecting children’s Nature connections to inform a child-rights based education approach under Article 29 1 (e).

11.1.2. To develop a child rights-based research methodology with young children to support their participation in developing an Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) approach in early childhood under Article 29 1 (e).

Chapter 9 discusses how the children enjoyed their participatory rights throughout different research activities in a variety of ways, including ‘free-flowing participation’, ‘the child’s clock’, ‘verbal/non-verbal participation’, ‘relational participation’, ‘children’s engagement with research tools’ and ‘participation that respects local culture’. By taking these definitions of participation, alongside the participants’ own Nature connections, I could establish how young children can be supported as partners in creating education curricula to develop respect for the environment. The findings identified that the children readily defined their own participation. However, some of those definitions were not readily visible and at times required the support of a sensitive and responsive adult to be included. This, in turn,

underscored the importance of the ECEC practitioners' skillset in supporting a child rights-respecting learning environment for ESD.

11.1.3. To build the capacity of early childhood practitioners to integrate child rights-based ESD/CCE into early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e).

Chapter 10 sought to explore building the capacity of ECEC practitioners to integrate child-rights-based ESD into early childhood settings under Article 29 1 (e). It also identified a number of barriers to doing that effectively. Three themes were identified: 'existing knowledge', 'practitioners' capacity to enact change' and 'paradigms of pedagogy' that required an in-depth exploration of how they contribute to this research aim. For example, at times different perspectives were shared surrounding what practitioners considered to be a rights-based approach and provided insight on the necessity to 'balance rights' in practice for a child to fully enjoy their rights as they themselves defined. Additionally, the data provided a rich discussion on the type of leadership and overall teaching philosophy surrounding effective ESD for educators to better support authentic sustainability practices at the local level.

11.2. Research contributions

This research sits at the intersection of child rights-based research, early childhood pedagogy, education for sustainable development and climate change education. It draws on, synthesises, and further develops these fields in several ways. The thesis responds to a gap in research with a rights-based theoretical framework on ESD for early childhood (Davies, 2009; Hedelfalk et al., 2015), which is one of my key contributions. I integrated a child rights theoretical framework with early childhood practice while researching with children in a local context. I learned from the children the relevance of acknowledging and respecting the complexities and everyday routines of their local early childhood culture in order to provide insight into how rights respecting education can be achieved in practice. Doing so led to creating and interpreting new knowledge in early childhood education, children's rights, and education for sustainable development. This new knowledge can be broadly summarised under the following subsections:

11.2.1. A 'bottom-up' approach for realising child rights.

Although the CRC was ratified to protect and promote the human rights of children specifically, it has also been critiqued for its universality and lack of explication on how it

can be applied diversely and at a local level. Related to this, Robson (2016) and Lundy and Martinez Sainz (2018) have argued that a ‘top-down’, policy-to-practice approach to implementing children’s rights is restrictive. They argue for its reframing to serve children in their living realities better. This research challenges an exclusively ‘top-down’ approach to realising children’s rights by providing new knowledge in the form of young children’s own perspectives and experiences of Article 29 1 (e). The study has supported the young participants in exploring their rights definitions under Article 29 1 (e) through creative participatory methods informed and designed with children from the same context. It, therefore, offers a more effective and pertinent ‘bottom-up’ approach for the authentic realisation of rights, which is especially important given that children did not contribute to the original drafting of the CRC itself.

11.2.2. Children’s own definitions of their rights

The project also responds to critiques of the CRC, which have suggested that it is an inadequate vehicle for sustainability development in the 21st century (Davies, 2014). Such critiques now call for a rethinking and ‘revisioning of rights’ defined by young children, to which this project also provides new insight. For example, within Davies (2014) *Expanded Rights Framework* (Figure 11.2) discussed in detail in Chapters 2 and 4, its **dimension 2 – agentic participation rights** calls for expanding and reconceptualising children’s agentic participation rights. Davies (2014) argues that the CRC needs clarity on the various forms of active participation that children can engage in. This study provides an account of the detailed variations in child participation and offers examples of strategies that support young children’s agency in defining their participatory and educational rights.

Furthermore, by engaging with young children and how they choose to enjoy both their participatory and education rights, this study also gives a platform through which their views on the topic can contribute democratically to further developing a child rights-based ESD approach. The research illuminates how rights-based research can be integrated into an early childhood context. Overall, I have demonstrated that learning how to support children to define their own education and participatory rights as contributing rights holders is integral to a shift to more child rights-based pedagogy.

Figure 11.2: Expanded Rights Framework

11.2.3. Extending the Lundy Model for early childhood participation.

The manner through which I adapted the child rights research participatory *Lundy Model* (2007) for the study further contributes to embedding rights-based participation in early childhood. The model has been fore frontal in national and international child participation discourse and featured heavily in the development of *The National Strategy on Children and Young People's Participation in Decision-Making (2015-2020)* and the recently published *Participation Framework – The National Framework for Children and Young People's Participation in Decision-Making* (DCEDIY, 2015, 2021). The thesis provides insight into how contributions from the participants were used to adapt each of the four elements of the model illustrated above as 'Space', 'Voice', 'Influence' and 'Audience' to make them meaningful to young children's lived experiences. From working with this group, I learned that having provided the children with enough time and space to form, express and see their ideas in action, it was me and the children's more familiar adults who were most suited to the role of 'identified listener'. As described in Chapter 6, an 'identified listener' is a party involved in decision-making matters affecting children. Establishing a commitment from such a listener can offer participants a meaningful audience for their research under Article 12. These findings are relevant to the elements of 'Influence' and 'Audience', shaped by the local context, to support real-life examples of a rights-based research approach. Figure 11.3

shows how this contribution was applied to the *Lundy model* to reflect a rights-based approach in a local context.

Figure 11.3: The Lundy model revised with CRAG guidance

11.2.4. Key strategies to design a rights-based approach in early childhood.

The thesis more generally offers a reflective, ‘warts and all’ discussion of applying rights-based research methodology amidst the complexities of early childhood culture. In addition to this thesis, I have published an article in the *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal* that offers those working with young children seven key strategies designed with the CRAG to promote a child rights-based participatory approach for both education and research. The strategies are: ‘creating a meaningful listening environment’, ‘reconceptualising the term ‘expertise knowledge’, ‘taking time for ongoing reflexivity’, ‘maintaining an ‘ethical radar’’, ‘understanding each other’, ‘ensuring meaningful participation’, and ‘balancing power dynamics’ (Ranta, 2023a). The article also provides readers with the following visual taken from Chapter 5 to use as a tool to support ongoing reflexivity for such an approach:

Figure 11.4: Ongoing reflexivity tool to support a child rights-based participatory approach.

11.2.5. Including young children in decision-making processes.

Both Elliot and Davies (2009) and Cutter-Mackenzie and Rousell (2019) note that ESD is often regarded as too complex to integrate into early childhood. Regardless, children have the right to be educated and participate as social actors for climate action. My research is concerned with scrutinising and reflecting on social norms and relationships and supporting children as rights holders to shape the world around them. The Irish government is currently promoting the development of a national dialogue strategy to contribute to a national Climate Action Plan (2021). Moreover, the Irish government has heavily cited child participation in policymaking and strategies. This research now provides an accessible pathway to ensure that the views of our youngest contributing rights holders are not excluded from any of those processes. It also contributes to the conversation around power dynamics as a barrier to

democratic spaces within our education systems. Although much work has already been done in this area, it remains in its infancy for early childhood. Reconceptualising the term ‘expert knowledge’ to include young children alongside practitioners’ expertise sheds light on the shift to more rights-based pedagogy for the ECEC sector. The sector in Ireland remains very much at a critical stage in its development. Shifting to more rights-based practice and research will be a crucial intervention.

11.2.6. Developing a transformative rights-based ESD approach.

In the thesis, I have highlighted reflexivity and relational competencies, which are at the core of ECEC practitioners’ skill sets. I demonstrate the skill of integrating complex knowledge sets by highlighting the practitioner’s pedagogical skillset and its relevance in a child rights duty-bearing role, through a detailed methodology chapter that effectively links theory to practice. Education and the role of the teacher are considered critical factors for advancing action against climate change (UNESCO, 1997; UNDESD, 2005; UNESCO, 2007; Pramling Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008; Davies, 2009; 2014; Siraj-Blatchford, 2009; Siraj-Blatchford & Pramling Samuelsson, 2015; UNDP, 2015; Waldron et al., 2020). In recent years, a growing literature has examined what this transformational change might look like (Feriver, 2016; Robson, 2016; Moody & Darbellay, 2019; Zanatta & Long, 2021). Most recently, contributions from the study (Appendix V), for example, the necessity to understand sustainability as an evolving concept and the importance of understanding and respecting a setting’s context and culture to embed effective ESD has been shared as part of the consultation process for updating Aistear (NCCA, 2024)

In keeping with a ‘bottom-up’ approach, I also bring forward contributions from practitioners themselves, such as recommendations for driving change within the sector. This includes guidance on the resources needed for practitioners themselves and the relevance of mentoring to be motivated in their teaching roles. They also contributed to the content of a transformative child rights ESD module (Appendix T) and its teaching philosophy which I argue could also be applied to a transformative leadership approach sought to enact a whole-system change to effectively develop transformative education for sustainable development. This is particularly timely given the recent arrival of *General Comment No. 26 on Children’s Rights and the Environment, with a particular focus on climate change* (UNCRC, 2023), which recommends more transformative ESD approaches.

11.3. Concluding remarks

Although the research did not look to measure young children's competencies in either ESD or research participation, they had an abundance of expert knowledge to contribute to a 'bottom-up' transformative child rights approach for ESD. Likewise, stage two identified a space where ECEC practitioners also had an opportunity to share their expertise on both the barriers and possibilities for this same approach. Therefore, this thesis demonstrates that given the right elements (time, space, rapport, flexibility, regular access to Nature, training and financial support), young children as rights holders can and should be partners in ESD curriculum making. By actively working towards a rights-respecting culture in early childhood, we can affirm democracy and empower young children to become active, engaged, and contributing social actors in their own lives and communities. Additionally, in order to build the capacity of ECEC practitioners, further development is required in training, resources and transformative leadership to enact whole system change for effective transformative rights-based ESD approaches under Article 29 1 (e).

Finally, given an overall diversity in the socio-economic backgrounds of early childhood settings, alongside limited access to the natural environment (Osgood, 2022), it would be essential to carry out further studies with the same research questions to contribute to how Article 29 1 (e) can also be realised for the children in these spaces.

Reference List

- Abebe, T., & Bessell, S. (2014). Advancing ethical research with children: Critical reflections on ethical guidelines. *Children's Geographies*, 12(1), 126–133.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14733285.2013.856077>
- Abtahi, Y. (2017). The 'More Knowledgeable Other'. A necessity in the zone of proximal development? *Learning for Mathematics*, 37(1), 35–39. FLM Publishing, Canada.
- Alanen, L. (2017). Childhood studies and the challenge of ontology. *Childhood*, 24(2), 147–150. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0907568217704539>
- Alderson, P. (2008). *Young children's rights: Exploring beliefs, principles and practice* (2nd ed). Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Alderson, P. (2012). Rights-respecting research: A commentary on 'the right to be properly researched: research with children in a messy, real world', *Children's Geographies*, 2009, 7, 4. *Children's Geographies*, 10(2), 233–239.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14733285.2012.661603>
- Alderson, P. (2016). The philosophy of critical realism and childhood studies. *Global Studies of Childhood*, 6(2), 199–210. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2043610616647640>
- Alderson, P., & Morrow, V. (2011). *The Ethics of Research with Children and Young People: A Practical Handbook*. SAGE Publications Ltd.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446268377>
- Anderstaf, S., Lecusay, R., & Nilsson, M. (2021). 'Sometimes we have to clash': How preschool teachers in Sweden engage with dilemmas arising from cultural diversity and value differences. *Intercultural Education*, 32(3), 296–310.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14675986.2021.1878112>
- Archard, D. W. (2002). Children's Rights, [online], in Edward N. Zalta (ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy* (Summer 2016 Edition).
<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2016/entries/rights-children/>
- Arvanitakis, J. (2008). The heterogenous citizen: How many of us care about Don Bradman's average? *M/C Journal*, [online], 11 (1), available: <http://www.journal.media-culture.org.au/index.php/mcjournal/article/view/27>
- Austin, S. (2022). The school garden in the primary school: Meeting the challenges and reaping the benefits. *Education 3-13*, 50(6), 707–721.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2021.1905017>
- Australian Government Department of Education [AGDE] (2022). *Belonging, Being and Becoming: The Early Years Learning Framework for Australia* (V2.0). Australian Government Department of Education for the Ministerial Council
- Australian Children's Education and Care Quality Authority (ACECQA). (2011). *Guide to the National Quality Standard*, Sydney, NSW: ACECQA
- Australian Children's Education and Care Quality Authority (ACECQA). (2023). *Guide to the National Quality Standard*, Sydney, NSW: ACECQA
- Bae, B. (2010). Realizing children's right to participation in early childhood settings: Some critical issues in a Norwegian context. *Early Years*, 30(3), 205–218.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09575146.2010.506598>
- Baldwin, J. R., Pingault, J.-B., Schoeler, T., Sallis, H. M., & Munafò, M. R. (2022). Protecting against researcher bias in secondary data analysis: Challenges and potential solutions. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, 37(1), 1–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-021-00839-0>
- Barnados Ireland (2021). Children's participation, *Childlinks*. Dublin: Barnados.
- Barnados Ireland (2023). Environmental sustainability in early childhood education and care., *Childlinks*. Dublin: Barnados.

- Barrable, A. (2019). Refocusing Environmental Education in the Early Years: A Brief Introduction to a Pedagogy for Connection. *Education Sciences*, 9(1), 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci9010061>
- Barrable, A., & Arvanitis, A. (2019). Flourishing in the forest: Looking at Forest School through a self-determination theory lens. *Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education*, 22(1), 39–55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42322-018-0018-5>
- Barrable, A., & Booth, D. (2020). Increasing Nature Connection in Children: A Mini Review of Interventions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 492. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00492>
- Barratt, R., Barratt-Hacking, E. & Black, P. (2014). Innovative Approaches to Early Childhood Education for Sustainability in England: Case Studies from the Field, In Davies, J.& Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Barratt-Hacking, E., Cutter-Mackenzie, A. & Barratt, R. (2013). Children as Active Researchers: The Potential of Environmental Education Research Involving Children, In Stevenson, R. (Ed.). *International Handbook of Research on Environmental Education*. Routledge.
- Barron, C. (2013). Physical activity play in local housing estates and child wellness in Ireland. *International Journal of Play*, 2(3), 220–236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21594937.2013.861262>
- Baroudi, S., & Lytras, M. D. (Eds.). (2024). *Transformative leadership and sustainable innovation in education: Interdisciplinary perspectives* (First edition). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Bartholomaeus, C., Gregoric, C., & Krieg, S. (2016). Young Children as Active Citizens in Local Government: Possibilities and challenges from an Australian perspective. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 48(1), 79–93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-016-0158-0>
- Bautista, A., Moreno-Núñez, A., Ng, S.-C., & Bull, R. (2018). Preschool Educators’ Interactions with Children About Sustainable Development: Planned and Incidental Conversations. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 50(1), 15–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-018-0213-0>
- Beazley, H. (2006). Participatory Methods and Approaches: Tackling the Two Tyrannies. In V. Desai & R. Potter, *Doing Development Research* (pp. 189–199). SAGE Publications, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781849208925.n20>
- Beder, S. (2012). Responsibility and Intergenerational Equity, In Murray, J. (Ed.). (2012). *Enough for all Forever: A Handbook for Learning about Sustainability*. Common Ground Pub.
- Bergold, J., & Thomas, S. (2012). Partizipative Forschungsmethoden: Ein methodischer Ansatz in Bewegung Participatory Research Methods: A Methodological Approach in Motion. *Historical Social Research Vol. 37, No. 4*, Volumes per year: 1. <https://doi.org/10.12759/HSR.37.2012.4.191-222>
- Berson, I. R., Berson, M. J., & Gray, C. (Eds.). (2019). *Participatory methodologies to elevate children’s voice and agency*. Information Age Publishing, Inc.
- Bessell, S. (2015). Rights-Based Research with Children: Principles and Practice. In R. Evans, L. Holt, & T. Skelton (Eds.), *Methodological Approaches* (pp. 1–18). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-4585-89-7_17-1
- Bessell, S. (2017). The Role of Intergenerational Relationships in Children’s Experiences of Community. *Children & Society*, 31(4), 263–275. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12197>
- Blaisdell, C. (2017). *Listening to Young Children: Meaningful Participation in Early Childhood Settings*. CRFR Publications

- Blaisdell, C., McNair, L. J., Addison, L., & Davis, J. M. (2022). ‘Why am I in all of these pictures?’ From Learning Stories to Lived Stories: The politics of children’s participation rights in documentation practices. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(4), 572–585. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2021.2007970>
- Blanchet-Cohen, N., & Elliot, E. (2011). Young Children and Educators Engagement and Learning Outdoors: A Basis for Rights-Based Programming. *Early Education & Development*, 22(5), 757–777. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2011.596460>
- Boardman, K. (2022). Where are the children’s voices and choices in educational settings’ early reading policies? A reflection on early reading provision for under-threes. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(1), 131–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2022.2026437>
- Bodén, L. (2021). On, to, with, for, by: Ethics and children in research. *Children’s Geographies*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14733285.2021.1891405>
- Bonnett, M. (2004). *Retrieving nature: Education for a post-humanist age*. Blackwell.
- Borg, F., & Samuelsson, I. P. (2022). Preschool children’s agency in education for sustainability: The case of Sweden. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(1), 147–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2022.2026439>
- Boyd, D. (2018). Early childhood education for sustainability and the legacies of two pioneering giants. *Early Years*, 38(2), 227–239. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09575146.2018.1442422>
- Boyd, J. K. (2010). *2048: Humanity’s agreement to live together* (1st ed). Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Brooks, E., & Murray, J. (2018). Ready, steady, learn: School readiness and children’s voices in English early childhood settings. *Education 3-13*, 46(2), 143–156. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2016.1204335>
- Broström, S., Johansson, I., Sandberg, A., & Frøkjær, T. (2014). Preschool teachers’ view on learning in preschool in Sweden and Denmark. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 22(5), 590–603. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2012.746199>
- Brundtland, G. H. (1987). Our Common Future—Call for Action. *Environmental Conservation*, 14(4), 291–294. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44518052>
- Bruner, J. S. (1977). *The process of education*. Harvard University Press.
- Bruner, J. S. (1996). *The culture of education*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University.
- Burns, H., Diamond-Vaught, H. & Bauman, C. (2015). Leadership for Sustainability: Theoretical Foundations and Pedagogical Practices that foster Change. *International Journal of Leadership Studies*, 9(1).
- Byrne, B., & Kelly, B. (2015). Special Issue: Valuing Disabled Children: Participation and Inclusion. *Child Care in Practice*, 21(3), 197–200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13575279.2015.1051732>
- Byrne, B., & Lundy, L. (2019). Children’s rights-based childhood policy: A six-P framework. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 23(3), 357–373. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13642987.2018.1558977>
- Byrne, L. (2021). *Social care placement-based learning: The incorporation story*. Institute of Technology, Sligo. <https://libsearch.itsligo.ie/cgi-bin/koha/opac-detail.pl?biblionumber=291180>
- Cameron, C., & Moss, P. (2020). *Transforming early childhood in England: Towards a democratic education*. UCL Press.
- Carson, R. (2017). *The sense of wonder: A celebration of nature for parents and children*. Harper Perennial.

- Cassidy, C., Wall, K., Robinson, C., Arnott, L., Beaton, M., & Hall, E. (2022). Bridging the theory and practice of eliciting the voices of young children: Findings from the *Look Who's Talking* project. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(1), 32–47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2022.2026431>
- Ceballos, N., & Susinos, T. (2022). Do my words convey what children are saying? Researching school life with very young children: dilemmas for ‘authentic listening’. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(1), 81–95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2022.2026435>
- Chalmers Annual Report. (2006). Göteborg: Chalmers University of Technology Foundation.
- Chawla, L. (1998). Significant Life Experiences Revisited: A Review of Research on Sources of Environmental Sensitivity. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 29(3), 11–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958969809599114>
- Chawla, L., & Driskell, D. (2006). The *Growing Up in Cities* Project: Global Perspectives on Children and Youth as Catalysts for Community Change. *Journal of Community Practice*, 14(1–2), 183–200. https://doi.org/10.1300/J125v14n01_11
- Chawla, L. & Rivkin, M. (2014). Early Childhood Education for Sustainability in the United States of America, In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Children’s Rights Alliance (2019). *No Child 2020 Initiative*.
- Christensen, P., & James, A. (Eds.). (2017). *Research with Children* (0 ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315657349>
- Christensen, P., & Prout, A. (2002). Working with Ethical Symmetry in Social Research with Children. *Childhood*, 9(4), 477–497. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0907568202009004007>
- Clark, A. (2023). *Slow knowledge and the unhurried child: Time for slow pedagogies in early childhood education*. Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group.
- Clark, A. (2020). Towards a listening ECEC system, In Cameron, C., & Moss, P. (2020). *Transforming Early Childhood in England: Towards a Democratic Education*. UCL Press.
- Clark, A., & Moss, P. (2011). *Listening to young children: The mosaic approach* (Second edition). NCB.
- Clark, A., & Moss, P. (2017). *Listening to young children: A guide to understanding and using the mosaic approach* (Expanded third edition). Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Cocks, A. J. (2006). The Ethical Maze: Finding an inclusive path towards gaining children’s agreement to research participation. *Childhood*, 13(2), 247–266. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0907568206062942>
- Cohen, L., Mannion, L., and Morrison, K. (2011). *Research methods in Education*. 7th edition. London: Taylor and Francis.
- Collins, T. M., Jamieson, L., Wright, L. H. V., Rizzini, I., Mayhew, A., Narang, J., Tisdall, E. K. M., & Ruiz-Casares, M. (2020). Involving child and youth advisors in academic research about child participation: The Child and Youth Advisory Committees of the International and Canadian Child Rights Partnership. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 109, 104569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2019.104569>
- Collins, S. & Garrity, S. (2023): Early childhood educators’ understanding of education for sustainable development, *Irish Educational Studies*, DOI:10.1080/03323315.2023.2266688
- Cook, T. (2009). The purpose of mess in action research: Building rigour through a messy turn. *Educational Action Research*, 17(2), 277–291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09650790902914241>

- Cook, T. (2021). Participatory Research: Its Meaning and Messiness. *Beleidsonderzoek Online*, 0(3). <https://doi.org/10.5553/BO/221335502021000003001>
- Corcoran, P. B., Wohlpart, J., & Hollingshead, B. P. (Eds.). (2008). *A voice for Earth: American writers respond to the Earth Charter*. University of Georgia Press.
- Cornwall, A., & Jewkes, R. (1995). What is participatory research? *Social Science & Medicine*, 41(12), 1667–1676. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536\(95\)00127-S](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536(95)00127-S)
- Correia, N., & Aguiar, C. (2017). Choosing classrooms: A structured interview on children's right to participate. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 82, 54–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2017.01.004>
- Cuevas-Parra, P. (2021). Positionality and reflexivity: Recognising and dismantling our privileges in childhood research through the use of windows and mirrors. *Global Studies of Childhood*, 204361062110522. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20436106211052295>
- Curriculum for the Preschool—Lpfö 18. (2019). Norstedts Juridik AB.
- Cutter-Mackenzie, A., & Edwards, S. (2013). Toward a Model for Early Childhood Environmental Education: Foregrounding, Developing, and Connecting Knowledge Through Play-Based Learning. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 44(3), 195–213. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2012.751892>
- Cutter-Mackenzie, A., Edwards, S., Moore, D., & Boyd, W. (2014). *Young children's play and environmental education in early childhood education*. Springer.
- Cutter-Mackenzie, A. & Rousell, D. (2014). Climate Change + Me: Children's and Young people's voices in Holocene and Anthropocene times, *Proceedings of the Australian Association for Research in Education Annual Conference*, Brisbane, QLD, Australian Association for Research in Education, Canberra, ACT
- Cutter-Mackenzie, A., & Rousell, D. (2019). Education for what? Shaping the field of climate change education with children and young people as co-researchers. *Children's Geographies*, 17(1), 90–104. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14733285.2018.1467556>
- Dahlberg, G., & Moss, P. (2007). *Ethics and politics in early childhood education* (Reprinted). Routledge Falmer.
- Daly, A. (2023). Intergenerational rights are children's rights: Upholding the right to a healthy environment through the UNCRC. *Netherlands Quarterly of Human Rights*, 41(3), 132–154. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09240519231195753>
- Davies, J. (2008). What might Education for Sustainability look like in Early Childhood? A case for Participatory, Whole-of-Settings Approaches. In Pramling Samuelsson, I. & Kaga, Y. (eds), *UNESCO Report: The contribution of Early Childhood Education to a Sustainable Society*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Davis, J. (2009). Revealing the research 'hole' of early childhood education for sustainability: A preliminary survey of the literature. *Environmental Education Research*, 15(2), 227–241. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504620802710607>
- Davies, J. (2014). Examining Early Childhood Education through the Lens of Education for Sustainability: Revisioning Rights. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Davis, J., & Elliott, S. (Eds.). (2014). *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Davis, J. M. (Ed.). (2015). *Young children and the environment: Early education for sustainability* (Second edition). Cambridge University Press.

- Davis, P. (2007). Storytelling as a democratic approach to data collection: Interviewing children about reading. *Educational Research*, 49(2), 169–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131880701369693>
- De Leeuw, R. R., Little, C., & Rix, J. (2020). Something needs to be said – Some thoughts on the possibilities and limitations of ‘voice’. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 104, 101694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2020.101694>
- Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth (DCEDIY), (2021). *The Participation Framework: National framework for children and young people’s participation in decision-making*. Dublin: The Stationary Office.
- Department of Children and Youth Affairs (DCYA), (2014). *Better outcomes, brighter futures: The national policy framework for children & young people 2014 – 2020*, Dublin, Ireland: Stationery Office.
- Department of Curriculum Studies, Faculty of Education, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa, Ontong, K., & Le Grange, L. (2018). Exploring sustainability as a frame of mind: A multiple case study. *South African Journal of Education*, 38(Supplement 2), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.15700/saje.v38ns2a1459>
- Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (DEEWR). (2009). *Belonging, being & becoming: The early years learning framework for Australia*. Canberra: DEEWR.
- Department of Education and Skills (DES), (2014). *Education for sustainability: The national strategy on education for sustainable development in Ireland, 2014- 2020*, Dublin, Ireland: Stationery Office.
- Department of Education and Skills (DES), (2018). *Education for Sustainability: The national strategy on education for sustainable development in Ireland report of interim review and action plan for Q4 2018-Q4 2020*, Dublin, Ireland: Stationery Office.
- Dockett, S., & Perry, B. (2007). Trusting children’s accounts in research. *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, 5(1), 47–63. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476718X07072152>
- Dolan, A. M. (Ed.). (2021). *Teaching climate change in primary schools: An interdisciplinary process*. Routledge.
- Duhn, I. (2012). Making ‘place’ for ecological sustainability in early childhood education. *Environmental Education Research*, 18(1), 19–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2011.572162>
- Duhn, I. & Ritchie, J. (2014). Making “Eco-Waves”: Early Childhood Care and Education Sustainability Practices in Aotearoa New Zealand. *Children, Youth and Environments*, 24(2), 123. <https://doi.org/10.7721/chilyoutenvi.24.2.0123>
- Dyment, J. E., Davis, J. M., Nailon, D., Emery, S., Getenet, S., McCrea, N., & Hill, A. (2014). The impact of professional development on early childhood educators’ confidence, understanding and knowledge of education for sustainability. *Environmental Education Research*, 20(5), 660–679. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2013.833591>
- Education Scotland (2018), *Learner participation in educational settings (3-18)*. Education Scotland.
- Edwards, A. (2010). Qualitative designs and analysis. In Naughton, G. M., Rolfe, S. A., & Siraj-Blatchford, I. (Eds). *Doing Early Childhood Research: International Perspectives on Theory & Practice* Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003115403>
- Edwards, C. P., Gandini, L., & Forman, G. (1998). *The hundred languages of children: The Reggio Emilia approach - advanced reflections* (Second ed). Ablex.

- Edwards, C. P., Gandini, L., & Forman, G. (Eds.). (2012). *The hundred languages of children: The Reggio Emilia experience in transformation* (3rd ed). Praeger.
- Edwards, M. (2015). *Global childhoods*. Critical Publishing.
- Edwards, S., & Cutter-Mackenzie, A. (2011). Environmentalising early childhood education curriculum through pedagogies of play. *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, 36(1), 51 - 59.
- Eekelaar, J. (1994). The interests of the child and the child's wishes: The role of dynamic self-determinism. *International Journal of Law, Policy and the Family*, 8(1), 42–61. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lawfam/8.1.42>
- Elliot, S. (2014). Early Childhood Education for Sustainability and Natural Outdoor Playspaces: Researching Change and Theorizing about Interfaces. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Elliott, S. (2015). Children in the Natural World. In Davis, J. (ed.), *Young children and the environment: Early education for sustainability* (2nd ed), pp. 32–54. Australia: Cambridge University Press.
- Elliott, S., & Young, T. (2016). Nature by Default in Early Childhood Education for Sustainability. *Australian Journal of Environmental Education*, 32(1), 57–64. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aee.2015.44>
- Engdahl, I. (2015). Early Childhood Education for Sustainability: The OMEP World Project. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 47(3), 347–366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-015-0149-6>
- Engdahl, I., & Rabušicová, M. (2011). *OMEP Report about ESD: Education for sustainable development in practice*. Sweden: OMEP.
- Engdahl, I. & Ärlemalm-Hagsér, E. (2014), Education for sustainability in Swedish preschools: Stepping forward or out of Step Interfaces. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group
- Ennew, J. & Boyden, J. (1997). *Children in focus – A manual for participatory research with children*. Save the Children.
- Ennew, J. & Plateau, D. P. (2004). *How to research the physical punishment of children*. Bangkok: Save the Children.
- Ergler, C., Smith, K., Kotsanas, C., & Hutchinson, C. (2015). What Makes a Good City in Pre-schoolers' Eyes? Findings from Participatory Planning Projects in Australia and New Zealand. *Journal of Urban Design*, 20(4), 461–478. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13574809.2015.1045842>
- Eriksen, E. (2018). Democratic Participation in Early Childhood Education and Care—Serving the Best Interests of the Child. *Nordisk Barnehageforskning*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.7577/nbf.2319>
- Ernst, J., McAllister, K., Siklander, P., & Storli, R. (2021). Contributions to Sustainability through Young Children's Nature Play: A Systematic Review. *Sustainability*, 13(13), 7443. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13137443>
- European Early Childhood Education Research Association (EECERA). (2015). *EECERA – Ethical code for early childhood researchers*.
- Evans, R., Holt, L., & Skelton, T. (2017). *Methodological approaches*. Springer.
- Fane, J., MacDougall, C., Jovanovic, J., Redmond, G., & Gibbs, L. (2018). Exploring the use of emoji as a visual research method for eliciting young children's voices in childhood research. *Early Child Development and Care*, 188(3), 359–374. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2016.1219730>

- Farrell, A., Kagan, S. L., & Tisdall, E. K. M. (Eds.). (2016). *The SAGE handbook of early childhood research*. SAGE Reference.
- Farrell, L. & Daly, M. (2023). Looking back as we look forward: Realising the Sustainable Development Goals through Aistear, the Early Childhood Curriculum Framework *An Leanbh Og ESD Special Edition*.
- Feriver, Ş., Teksöz, G. (Tuncer), Olgan, R., & Reid, A. (2016). Training early childhood teachers for sustainability: Towards a ‘learning experience of a different kind’. *Environmental Education Research*, 22(5), 717–746.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2015.1027883>
- Ferreira, J.-A., Ryan, L., & Davis, J. (2015). Developing Knowledge and Leadership in Pre-Service Teacher Education Systems. *Australian Journal of Environmental Education*, 31(2), 194–207. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ae.2015.24>
- Follari, L. M. (2019). *Foundations and best practices in early childhood education: History, theories, and approaches to learning* (Fourth edition). Pearson.
- Forde, L., & Kilkelly, U. (2021). Incorporating the CRC in Ireland. In U. Kilkelly, L. Lundy, & B. Byrne (Eds.), *Incorporating the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child into National Law* (1st ed., pp. 177–202). Intersentia.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781839701764.008>
- Franch, S. (2019). Reconceptualising Citizenship Education Towards the Global, the Political and the Critical. In P. Bamber, *Teacher Education for Sustainable Development and Global Citizenship* (1st ed., pp. 144–155). Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429427053-15>
- Freeman, M. D. A. (Ed.). (2012). *Law and childhood studies*. Oxford University Press.
- Freire, P. (2000). *Pedagogy of the oppressed* (30th anniversary ed). Continuum.
- French, G & McKenna. (2022). *Literature review to support the updating of Aistear, the early childhood curriculum framework*: Dublin City University
- Garvais, S., Ødegaard, Eriksen, E., & Lemon, N. (2015). *Beyond observations - Narratives and Young Children*. Rotterdam: Sense Publishers.
- Gilbert, L., Fuller, M., Palmer, S. & Rose, J. (2014). Early Childhood Education for Sustainability in the United Kingdom: Generating Professional Capital. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group
- Gill, T. (2014). The Benefits of Children’s Engagement with Nature: A Systematic Literature Review. *Children, Youth and Environments*, 24(2), 10.
<https://doi.org/10.7721/chilyoutenvi.24.2.0010>
- Gillett-Swan, J. K., & Lundy, L. (2022). Children, classrooms, and challenging behaviour: Do the rights of the many outweigh the rights of the few? *Oxford Review of Education*, 48(1), 95–111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2021.1924653>
- Gillett-Swan, J. K., & Sargeant, J. (2018). Unintentional power plays: Interpersonal contextual impacts in child-centred participatory research. *Educational Research*, 60(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2017.1410068>
- Gillett-Swan, J. K., & Sargeant, J. (2019). Perils of perspective: Identifying adult confidence in the child’s capacity, autonomy, power and agency (CAPA) in readiness for voice-inclusive practice. *Journal of Educational Change*, 20(3), 399–421.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-019-09344-4>
- Gove, A., & Black, M. M. (2016). Measurement of Early Childhood Development and Learning under the Sustainable Development Goals. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 17(4), 599–605. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19452829.2016.1243520>

- Government of Ireland, (GOI) (2019). *First Five: A whole-of-government strategy for babies, Young children and their families 2019-2028*, Dublin, Ireland: The Stationery Office.
- Government of Ireland (GOI), 2020. *Our Shared Future*, Dublin, Ireland: The Stationery Office.
- Government of Ireland (GOI), 2022. *ESD to 2030: Second national strategy on education for sustainable development*, Dublin, Ireland: Stationery Office.
- Government of Ireland (GOI), 2022. *Nurturing Skills: The workforce plan for early learning and care and school-age childcare 2022-2028*, Dublin, Ireland: Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth.
- Government of Ireland (GOI), 2022. *Policy framework for children and young people 2023-2028 Blueprint*, Dublin, Ireland: Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth.
- Government of Ireland (GOI), 2025. *Our Securing Ireland's Future*, Dublin: The Stationery Office.
- Green, C. J. (2015). Toward Young Children as Active Researchers: A Critical Review of the Methodologies and Methods in Early Childhood Environmental Education. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 46(4), 207–229. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2015.1050345>
- Grindheim, L. T., Bakken, Y., Hauge, K. H., & Heggen, M. P. (2019). Early Childhood Education for Sustainability Through Contradicting and Overlapping Dimensions. *ECNU Review of Education*, 2(4), 374–395. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2096531119893479>
- Gromada, A. & Richardson. (2021). *Where do rich countries stand on childcare?* UNICEF Office of Research: Innocenti.
- Groundwater-Smith, S., Dockett, S., & Bottrell, D. (2015). *Participatory Research with Children and Young People*. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781473910751>
- Hadzigeorgiou, Y., Prevezanou, B., Kabouropoulou, M., & Konsolas, M. (2011). Teaching about the importance of trees: A study with young children. *Environmental Education Research*, 17(4), 519–536. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2010.549938>
- Hägglund, S. & Johansson, E. (2014), Belonging, Value, Conflicts and Children's rights in Learning for Sustainability in Early Childhood. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group
- Halstead, F., Parsons, L. R., Dunhill, A., & Parsons, K. (2021). A journey of emotions from a young environmental activist. *Area*, 53(4), 708–717. <https://doi.org/10.1111/area.12745>
- Harcourt, D., & Conroy, H. (2005). Informed assent: Ethics and processes when researching with young children. *Early Child Development and Care*, 175(6), 567–577. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430500131353>
- Harcourt, D., & Hägglund, S. (2013). Turning the UNCRC upside down: A bottom-up perspective on children's rights. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 21(4), 286–299. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669760.2013.867167>
- Harcourt, D., Perry, B., & Waller, T. (Eds.). (2011). *Researching Young Children's Perspectives* (0 ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203830437>
- Hargreaves, A., & Shirley, D. (2012). *The global fourth way: The quest for educational excellence*. Corwin Press; Learning Forward; Ontario Principals' Council.
- Hartig, T., Mitchell, R., de Vries, S., & Frumkin, H. (2014). 'Nature and health'. *Annual Review of Public Health*, 35, 207–228.

- Hatch, J. A. (2013). *Early Childhood Qualitative Research* (1st ed.). Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203943502>
- Hedefalk, M., Almqvist, J., & Östman, L. (2015). Education for sustainable development in early childhood education: A review of the research literature. *Environmental Education Research*, 21(7), 975–990. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2014.971716>
- Heimlich, J. E., & Ardoin, N. M. (2008). Understanding behavior to understand behavior change: A literature review. *Environmental Education Research*, 14(3), 215–237. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504620802148881>
- Hirst, N. (2019). Education for sustainability within early childhood studies: Collaboration and inquiry through projects with children. *Education 3-13*, 47(2), 233–246. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2018.1430843>
- hooks, B. (1994). *Teaching to transgress: Education as the practice of freedom*. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.
- hooks, B. (2003). *Teaching community: A pedagogy of hope*. Routledge.
- Horgan, D. (2017). Child participatory research methods: Attempts to go ‘deeper’. *Childhood*, 24(2), 245–259. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0907568216647787>
- Horgan, D., Forde, C., Martin, S., & Parkes, A. (2017). Children’s participation: Moving from the performative to the social. *Children’s Geographies*, 15(3), 274–288. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14733285.2016.1219022>
- Houghton, C. (2015). Young People’s Perspectives on Participatory Ethics: Agency, Power and Impact in Domestic Abuse Research and Policy-Making: Young Survivors of Domestic Abuse Co-Develop Participatory Ethics. *Child Abuse Review*, 24(4), 235–248. <https://doi.org/10.1002/car.2407>
- Huser, C., Dockett, S., & Perry, B. (2022). Young children’s assent and dissent in research: Agency, privacy and relationships within ethical research spaces. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(1), 48–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2022.2026432>
- Inoue, M. (2014). Perspectives on Early Childhood Environmental Education in Japan: Rethinking for a Sustainable Society. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group
- Inoue, M., O’Gorman, L., & Davis, J. (2016). Investigating Early Childhood Teachers’ Understandings of and Practices in Education for Sustainability in Queensland: A Japan-Australia Research Collaboration. *Australian Journal of Environmental Education*, 32(2), 174–191. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aee.2016.4>
- Institute of Technology Carlow. (2017), *Ethics in research policy: Policy statement of ethics in research*. Institute of Technology: Carlow.
- Institute of Technology Carlow. (2019), *Ethics in research policy: Policy statement of ethics in research*. Institute of Technology: Carlow.
- International Collaboration for Participatory Health Research (ICPHR). (2013), *Position paper 2: Participatory health research: A guide to ethical principles and practice*. Berlin: ICPHR.
- IPCC. (2022). *Global Warming of 1.5°C: IPCC Special Report on Impacts of Global Warming of 1.5°C above Pre-industrial Levels in Context of Strengthening Response to Climate Change, Sustainable Development, and Efforts to Eradicate Poverty* (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157940>
- Jackson, A. Y., & Mazzei, L. A. (2013). Plugging One Text Into Another: Thinking With Theory in Qualitative Research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 19(4), 261–271. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800412471510>

- Jadue Roa, D. S., Whitebread, D., & Gareca Guzmán, B. (2018). Methodological issues in representing children's perspectives in transition research. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 26(5), 760–779. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2018.1522764>
- James, A. (2007). Giving Voice to Children's Voices: Practices and Problems, Pitfalls and Potentials. *American Anthropologist*, 109(2), 261–272. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.2007.109.2.261>
- James, A. (Ed.). (2014). *Constructing and reconstructing childhood: Contemporary issues in the sociological study of childhood; with a new introduction* (Classic ed). Routledge.
- Jerome, L., Emmerson, L., Lundy, L. & Orr, K. (2015), *Teaching and learning about child rights: a study of implementation in 26 countries*. Project Report. UNICEF PFP & Queen's University Belfast.
- Ji, O. & Stuhmcke, S. (2014), The Project Approach in Early Childhood Education for Sustainability: Exemplars from Korea and Australia. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Jóhannesson, I. Á., Norðdahl, K., Óskarsdóttir, G., Pálsdóttir, A., & Pétursdóttir, B. (2011). Curriculum analysis and education for sustainable development in Iceland. *Environmental Education Research*, 17(3), 375–391. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2010.545872>
- Johnston, K. (2022). Creating space for equity in early childhood educator's participation in documentation, assessment and evaluation. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(3), 360–371. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2021.2019291>
- Kahrیمان-Pamuk, D., & Olgan, R. (2018). Teacher Practices and Preschool Physical Environment for Education for Sustainable Development: Eco Vs Ordinary Preschools. *Mersin Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 14(2), 669–683. <https://doi.org/10.17860/mersinefd.391312>
- Kahrیمان-Pamuk, D., Uzun, N. B., Yıldız, T. G., & Haktanır, G. (2019). Reliability of Indicators Measuring Early Childhood Education for Sustainability: A Study in Turkey Using Generalizability Theory. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 51(2), 193–206. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-019-00243-6>
- Katz, L. G., & Chard, S. C. (2000). *Engaging children's minds: The project approach* (2nd ed). Ablex Pub. Corp.
- Kellett, M. (2010). Small Shoes, Big Steps! Empowering Children as Active Researchers. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 46(1–2), 195–203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10464-010-9324-y>
- Kellett, M. (2011). Empowering Children and Young People as Researchers: Overcoming Barriers and Building Capacity. *Child Indicators Research*, 4(2), 205–219. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12187-010-9103-1>
- Kiili, J., & Moilanen, J. (2019). Participation as a methodological and ethical issue in child protection research. *Journal of Children's Services, ahead-of-print*(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCS-02-2019-0009>
- Kirby, P., & Webb, R. (2023). Conceptualising uncertainty and the role of the teacher for a politics of climate change within and beyond the institution of the school. *Educational Review*, 75(1), 134–152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2021.1933392>
- Knauf, H. (2017). Documentation as a tool for participation in German early childhood education and care. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 25(1), 19–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2015.1102403>

- Knight, L., McArdle, F., Cumming, T., Bone, J., Li, L., Peterken, C., & Ridgway, A. (2015). Intergenerational Collaborative Drawing: A Research Method for Researching with/about Young Children. *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, 40(4), 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.1177/183693911504000404>
- Kok, X. W., & Yang, W. (2022). ‘Quilting’ a play-based anti-bias curriculum for very young children: The Mosaic Approach. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(6), 827–851. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2021.2009534>
- Korkmaz, A., & Guler Yildiz, T. (2017). Assessing preschools using the Eco-Schools program in terms of educating for sustainable development in early childhood education. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 25(4), 595–611. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2017.1331074>
- Kowalewski, M., Domènech, R., & Martinell, J. (2014). Vanishing Clams on an Iberian Beach: Local Consequences and Global Implications of Accelerating Loss of Shells to Tourism. *PLoS ONE*, 9(1), e83615. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0083615>
- Križ, K., & Skivenes, M. (2017). Child welfare workers’ perceptions of children’s participation: A comparative study of England, Norway and the USA (California): Children’s participation. *Child & Family Social Work*, 22, 11–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cfs.12224>
- Kucharczyk, S., & Hanna, H. (2020). Balancing teacher power and children’s rights: Rethinking the use of picturebooks in multicultural primary schools in England. *Human Rights Education Review*, 3(1), 49–68. <https://doi.org/10.7577/hrer.3726>
- Lambert, M., & Belliappa, J. (Eds.). (2019). *Practical research methods in education: An early researcher’s critical guide* (First published). Routledge.
- Larkins, C., Thomas, N., Carter, B., Farrelly, N., Judd, D., & Lloyd, J. (2015). Support for Children’s Protagonism. *The International Journal of Children’s Rights*, 23(2), 332–364. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718182-02302009>
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Le Borgne, C., & Tisdall, E. K. M. (2017). Children’s Participation: Questioning Competence and Competencies? *Social Inclusion*, 5(3), 122–130. <https://doi.org/10.17645/si.v5i3.986>
- Lenette, C., Stavropoulou, N., Nunn, C., Kong, S. T., Cook, T., Coddington, K., & Banks, S. (2019). Brushed under the carpet: Examining the complexities of participatory research. *Research for All*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.18546/RFA.03.2.04>
- Leonard, M. (2016). *The Sociology of Children, Childhood and Generation*. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781529714494>
- Lipponen, L., Rajala, A., Hilppö, J., & Paananen, M. (2016). Exploring the foundations of visual methods used in research with children. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 24(6), 936–946. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2015.1062663>
- Long, S. (2019), Learning about the principle of participation: Possibilities and barriers in the professional formation of early childhood education and care students. *Children’s Research Network Research Digest*: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332684457>
- Long, S. (2021), Participation: Some considerations for early childhood education programmes, *Childlinks*, (2), pp. 25-32. Dublin: Barnardos.
- Louv, R. (2010). *Last Child in the Woods: Saving our Children from Nature-Deficit Disorder*. (Rev.and updated). Atlantic Books.

- Louv, R. (2012). *The nature principle: Reconnecting with life in a virtual age* (1st paperback ed). Algonquin Books of Chapel Hill.
- Louv, R. (2017). *Vitamin N: The essential guide to a nature-rich life*. Atlantic Books.
- Luff, P. (2018). Early childhood education for sustainability: Origins and inspirations in the work of John Dewey. *Education 3-13*, 46(4), 447–455.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2018.1445484>
- Lundy, L. (2007). ‘Voice’ is not enough: Conceptualising Article 12 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child. *British Educational Research Journal*, 33(6), 927–942. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411920701657033>
- Lundy, L. (2018). In defence of tokenism? Implementing children’s right to participate in collective decision-making. *Childhood*, 25(3), 340–354.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0907568218777292>
- Lundy, L., Byrne, B., Lloyd, K., Templeton, M., Brando, N., Corr, M.-L., Heard, E., Holland, L., MacDonald, M., Marshall, G., McAlister, S., McNamee, C., Orr, K., Schubotz, D., Symington, E., Walsh, C., Hope, K., Singh, P., Neill, G., & Wright, L. H. V. (2021). Life Under Coronavirus: Children’s Views on their Experiences of their Human Rights. *The International Journal of Children’s Rights*, 29(2), 261–285.
<https://doi.org/10.1163/15718182-29020015>
- Lundy, L., & Martínez Sainz, G. (2018). The role of law and legal knowledge for a transformative human rights education: Addressing violations of children’s rights in formal education. *Human Rights Education Review*, 1(2), 04–24.
<https://doi.org/10.7577/hrer.2560>
- Lundy, L., & McEvoy, L. (2012). Children’s rights and research processes: Assisting children to (in)formed views. *Childhood*, 19(1), 129–144.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0907568211409078>
- Lundy, L., McEvoy, L., & Byrne, B. (2011). Working With Young Children as Co-Researchers: An Approach Informed by the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child. *Early Education & Development*, 22(5), 714–736.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2011.596463>
- Lynch, H., & Moore, A. (2016). Play as an occupation in occupational therapy. *British Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 79(9), 519–520.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0308022616664540>
- Lynch, J., & Mannion, G. (2021). Place-responsive Pedagogies in the Anthropocene: Attuning with the more-than-human. *Environmental Education Research*, 27(6), 864–878. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2020.1867710>
- Lyndon, H. (2019), Mosaic: Participatory research in the early years. In Lambert, M., & Belliappa, J. (Eds.). *Practical research methods in education: An early researcher’s critical guide* (First published). Routledge, pp. 103-113.
- Lyndon, H., Bertram, T., Brown, Z., & Pascal, C. (2019). Pedagogically mediated listening practices; the development of pedagogy through the development of trust. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 27(3), 360–370.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2019.1600806>
- MacDonald, M. (2015). Early Childhood Education and Sustainability: A Living Curriculum. *Childhood Education*, 91(5), 332–341.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00094056.2015.1090845>
- Machin-Mastromatteo, J. D., & Tarango, J. (2019). Participatory Action Research. In R. Hobbs & P. Mihailidis (Eds.), *The International Encyclopedia of Media Literacy* (1st ed., pp. 1–8). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118978238.ieml0178>
- Mackey, G. (2012). To know, to decide, to act: The young child’s right to participate in

- action for the environment. *Environmental Education Research*, 18(4), 473–484.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2011.634494>
- Mackey, G. (2014). Valuing Agency in Young Children: Teachers Rising to the Challenge of Sustainability in the Aotearoa New Zealand Early Childhood Context. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- MacNaughton, G. (2009). *Doing Foucault in early childhood studies: Applying poststructural ideas* (Reprinted). Routledge.
- MacNaughton, G., Hughes, P., & Smith, K. (Eds.). (2008). *Young children as active citizens: Principles, policies and pedagogies*. Cambridge Scholars Pub.
- MacNaughton, G., Smith, K. & Davis, K. (2006). Researching with Children: The Challenges and Possibilities for Building ‘Child-Friendly’ research. In Hatch, J. A. (Ed) *Early Childhood Qualitative Research* (1st ed.). Routledge, pp.167–184.
- Mannion, G. (2007). Going Spatial, Going Relational: Why “listening to children” and children’s participation needs reframing. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 28(3), 405–420. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01596300701458970>.
- Mannion, G., Fenwick, A., & Lynch, J. (2013). Place-responsive pedagogy: Learning from teachers’ experiences of excursions in nature. *Environmental Education Research*, 19(6), 792–809. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2012.749980>
- Martin, S., & Buckley, L. (2020). Including children’s voices in a multiple stakeholder study on a community-wide approach to improving quality in early years setting. *Early Child Development and Care*, 190(9), 1411–1424.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2018.1538135>
- Martínez Sainz, G. (2017). Building Professional Agency in Human Rights Education: Translating Policy into Practice," *International Journal of Human Rights Education*, 1(1) Retrieved from <https://repository.usfca.edu/ijhre/vol1/iss1/12>.
- Martínez Sainz, G. (2018). Human Rights Education and Training Programs in Mexico: A Cross-Case Analysis of Practitioners’ Professional Knowledge and Practices. *Mexican Law Review*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.22201/ij.24485306e.2018.1.12513>
- Martínez Sainz, G. & Su-Ming Khoo, (2020), Development Education and Climate Change, *Policy & Practice: A Development Education Review*, 13, pp.1-7.
- Mason, J., & Danby, S. (2011). Children as Experts in Their Lives: Child Inclusive Research. *Child Indicators Research*, 4(2), 185–189. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12187-011-9108-4>
- Mayne, F., & Howitt, C. (2022). *The narrative approach to informed consent: Empowering young children’s rights and meaningful participation*. Routledge.
- Mayne, F., Howitt, C., & Rennie, L. (2016). Meaningful informed consent with young children: Looking forward through an interactive narrative approach. *Early Child Development and Care*, 186(5), 673–687.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2015.1051975>
- Mayne, F., Howitt, C., & Rennie, L. J. (2017). Using interactive nonfiction narrative to enhance competence in the informed consent process with 3-year-old children. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 21(3), 299–315.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2016.1260833>
- Mayne, F., Howitt, C., & Rennie, L. J. (2018). A hierarchical model of children’s research participation rights based on information, understanding, voice, and influence. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 26(5), 644–656.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2018.1522480>
- McDonnell, D. & Minton, S.J. (2017). *An exploration into the psychology of education: The use of an ecological framework to address macro and microsystemic factors that influence individuals working within Irish education*. Trinity College Dublin.

- McFarland, L., & Dealtry, L. (2017). Hearing in the Early Childhood Setting: Children's Perspectives. *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, 42(2), 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.23965/AJEC.42.2.13>
- McGillicuddy, D. & Machowska-Kosciak, M. (2016), *Report on a consultation with children and young people on education for sustainable development*, Department of Education and Skills (DES) and Department of Children and Youth Affairs (DCYA). available: <https://researchrepository.ucd.ie/handle/10197/10268>
- McNichol, H., Davis, J. M., & O'Brien, K. R. (2011). An ecological footprint for an early learning centre: Identifying opportunities for early childhood sustainability education through interdisciplinary research. *Environmental Education Research*, 17(5), 689–704. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2011.572161>
- Meehan, C. (2016). Every child mattered in England: But what matters to children? *Early Child Development and Care*, 186(3), 382–402. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2015.1032957>
- Meland, A. T. (2022). Tracking education for sustainable development in ECEC institutions' annual plans. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(5), 791–805. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2021.2008464>
- Melrose, A. (2017). Understanding Early Childhood: Issues and Controversies. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 18(3), 351–352. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1463949117731030>
- Mertens, D. M. (2007). Transformative Paradigm: Mixed Methods and Social Justice. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(3), 212–225. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689807302811>
- Mezirow, J. (1997). Transformative Learning: Theory to Practice. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, 1997(74), 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ace.7401>
- Ministry of Education. (2017), *Te Whāriki: He whāriki mātauranga mō ngā mokopuna o Aotearoa/Early childhood curriculum*. Wellington: Ministry of Education.
- Mitchell, M., Lundy, L., & Hill, L. (2023). Children's Human Rights to 'Participation' and 'Protection': Rethinking the relationship using Barnahus as a case example. *Child Abuse Review*, e2820. <https://doi.org/10.1002/car.2820>
- Moloney, M., & Pope, J. (2023). Willing and unable or willing and able? Insights from an evaluation of a mentoring training programme for early childhood teachers in Ireland. *Education 3-13*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2023.2236118>
- Montessori, M. (2013), A new world and education. (1946/47) (Editorial). *AMI Journal*, December, pp. 69–76.
- Moody, Z., & Darbellay, F. (2019). Studying childhood, children, and their rights: The challenge of interdisciplinarity. *Childhood*, 26(1), 8–21. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0907568218798016>
- Moore, D. (2014). Interrupting Listening to Children: Researching with Children's Secret Places in Early Childhood Settings. *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, 39(2), 4–11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/183693911403900202>
- Morris, H., Edwards, S., Cutter-Mackenzie, A., Rutherford, L., Williams-Smith, J., & Skouteris, H. (2018). Evaluating the Impact of Teacher-designed, Wellbeing and Sustainability Play-based Learning Experiences on Young Children's Knowledge Connections: A Randomised Trial. *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, 43(4), 33–42. <https://doi.org/10.23965/AJEC.43.4.04>

- Moss, P. (2016). Why can't we get beyond quality? *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 17(1), 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1463949115627895>
- Moss, P., & Roberts-Holmes, G. (2022). Now is the time! Confronting neo-liberalism in early childhood. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 23(1), 96–99. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1463949121995917>
- Mukherji, P., & Albon, D. (2018). *Research methods in early childhood: An introductory guide*. SAGE.
- Mullenbach, L. E., Andrejewski, R. G., & Mowen, A. J. (2019). Connecting children to nature through residential outdoor environmental education. *Environmental Education Research*, 25(3), 365–374. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2018.1458215>
- Murray, J. (Ed.). (2012). *Enough for all forever: A handbook for learning about sustainability*. Common Ground Pub.
- Murray, J. (2022). Any questions? Young children questioning in their early childhood education settings. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(1), 108–130. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2022.2026436>
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2009). *Aistear: The Early Childhood Curriculum Framework Principles and Themes*. Dublin, Ireland: Stationery Office.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2015). *Aistear Síolta Practice Guide*, <http://aistearsiolta.ie/en/>.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2018). *Education for Sustainable Development: A study of Opportunities and Linkages in the Primary and Post-primary Curriculum* https://ncca.ie/media/3573/esdreport_final_june2018.pdf
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2021). *Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) International Curriculum Audit*, <https://ncca.ie/en/resources/education-for-sustainable-development-esd-international-curriculum-audit/>
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2023). *Consultation Report on updating Aistear: Phase 1*, <https://ncca.ie/en/resources/consultation-report-on-updating-aistear-phase-1/>
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2023). *Draft Updated Aistear: The Early Childhood Curriculum Framework. For Consultation*. Dublin, Ireland: Stationery Office.
- Naughton, G. M., Rolfe, S. A., & Siraj-Blatchford, I. (2020). *Doing Early Childhood Research: International Perspectives on Theory & Practice* (S. A. Rolfe, G. MacNaughton, & I. Siraj-Blatchford, Eds.; 2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003115403>
- Nolan, A. & McGrath, S. (2016). 'SDG 4 and The Child's Right to Education' in Norrag, *Education, Training and Agenda 2030: What progress one year on?* [online], available: <https://www.norrag.org/education-training-and-agenda-2030-what-progress-one-year-on/>
- Nolan, A. (2020). Poverty and Child Rights'. In Todres, J., & King, S. M. (Eds). *The Oxford Handbook of Children's Rights Law*. Oxford university press.
- NSW Office of the Children's Guardian. (2021). *Empowerment and Participation: A Guide for Organisations working with Children and Young People*. Australia: University of South Australia.
- Nussbaum, M. C. (2013). *Creating Capabilities: The Human Development Approach*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt2jbt31>

- Ødegaard, E. E., & Borgen, J. S. (Eds.). (2021). *Childhood cultures in transformation: 30 years of the UN Convention of the Rights of the Child in action towards sustainability*. Brill Sense.
- O’Gorman, L., & Davis, J. (2013). Ecological footprinting: Its potential as a tool for change in preservice teacher education. *Environmental Education Research*, 19(6), 779–791. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2012.749979>
- Olson, D. R., Greenfield, P. M., Gardner, H. E., & Cole, M. (2017). In Memoriam: Jerome Bruner (1915–2016). Polymath and pioneer in cognitive development and education / In Memoriam: Jerome Bruner (1915–2016). Erudito y pionero del desarrollo cognitivo y la educación. *Infancia y Aprendizaje*, 40(4), 744–753. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02103702.2017.1364059>
- Osgood, J. (2022). From Multispecies Tangles and Anthropocene Muddles: What can Lichen Teach Us about Precarity and Indeterminacy in Early Childhood?. In: Blyth, C., Aslanian, T.K. (eds) *Children and the Power of Stories. Children: Global Posthumanist Perspectives and Materialist Theories*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-9287-1_5
- Osgood, J. (2025). Worlding approaches in Early Childhood. Pursuing multispecies flourishing on a damaged planet. *Educational Studies Association of Ireland (ESAI) Seminar 19th February 2025*. Accesible: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xaPcUv_9Klo
- O’Sullivan, C., Maguire, J., Hayes, N., O’Sullivan, S., Corcoran, L., & McKenna, G. (2018). The wonder project: An early years arts education project with Traveller mothers and their children. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 26(5), 780–806. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2018.1522773>
- O’Toole, L. (2020). Participant Action Research (PAR) for early childhood and primary education: The example of the THRIECE project. *Problemy Wczesnej Edukacji*, 49(2), 31–44. <https://doi.org/10.26881/pwe.2020.49.03>
- O’Toole L., Walsh G., Kerrins E., Doherty A., Forde D., Kelleher F., McCartney S., Stafford P., Stokes T., Matson S., & Mooney E. (2023). *A consultation with babies, toddlers and young children to inform the updating of Aistear: the early childhood curriculum framework*, Dublin: NCCA, available: [consultationreport.pdf](https://www.ncca.ie/consultationreport.pdf) (ncca.ie)
- Pape-Pedersen, I. (2022). Teacher body(ing) kindergarten space(s) -an arts-based pedagogical development project for kindergarten teachers. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(5), 715–729. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2021.2011366>
- Parry, B. (2015). Arts-Based Approaches to Research with Children: Living with Mess. In E. Stirling & D. Yamada-Rice (Eds.), *Visual Methods with Children and Young People* (pp. 89–98). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137402295_6
- Payler, J., Georgeson, J., & Wong, S. (2016). Young children shaping interprofessional practice in early years settings: Towards a conceptual framework for understanding experiences and participation. *Learning, Culture and Social Interaction*, 8, 12–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lcsi.2015.09.003>
- Peleg, N. (2013). Reconceptualising the Child’s Right to Development: Children and the Capability Approach. *The International Journal of Children’s Rights*, 21(3), 523–542. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718182-02103003>
- Percy-Smith, B. (2010). Councils, consultations and community: Rethinking the spaces for children and young people’s participation1. *Children’s Geographies*, 8(2), 107–122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14733281003691368>
- Perry-Hazan, L. (2021). Students’ Perceptions of Their Rights in School: A Systematic Review of the International Literature. *Review of Educational Research*, 91(6), 919–957. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543211031642>

- Phillips, L. (2012). Emergent Motifs of Social Justice Storytelling as Pedagogy. *Storytelling, Self, Society*, 8, pp. 108–125.
- Phillips, L. (2014). ‘I want to do real things’: Explorations of Children’s Active Community Participation. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Porter, S., & Couper, P. (2023). Autoethnographic stories for self and environment: A reflective pedagogy to advance ‘environmental awareness’ in student outdoor practitioners. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning*, 23(1), 25–37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2021.1935284>
- Pramling, N., & Ødegaard, E. E. (2011). Learning to Narrate: Appropriating a Cultural Mould for Sense-Making and Communication. In N. Pramling & I. Pramling Samuelsson (Eds.), *Educational Encounters: Nordic Studies in Early Childhood Didactics* (pp. 15–35). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-1617-9_2
- Pramling Samuelsson, I. & Kaga, Y. (2008). *UNESCO Report: The Contribution of Early Childhood Education to a Sustainable Society*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Pramling Samuelsson, I. (2011). Why We Should Begin Early with ESD: The Role of Early Childhood Education. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 43(2), 103–118. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-011-0034-x>
- Press, F., & Cheeseman, S. (Eds.). (2022). *(Re)conceptualising children’s rights in infant-toddler care and education: Transnational conversations*. Springer.
- Pribišev Beleslin, T., & Travar, M. (2022). The Importance of the OMEP ESD Rating Scale for Building Future Preschool Teachers’ Professional Competencies in Bosnia and Herzegovina. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 54(1), 139–164. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-022-00319-w>
- Priest, S. (1986). Redefining Outdoor Education: A Matter of Many Relationships. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 17(3), 13–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.1986.9941413>
- Prince, C. (2010). Sowing the seeds: Education for sustainability within the early years curriculum. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 18(3), 423–434. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2010.500082>
- Quennerstedt, A. (2013). Children’s Rights Research Moving into the Future – Challenges on the Way Forward. *The International Journal of Children’s Rights*, 21(2), 233–247. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718182-02102006>
- Ranta, M. (2023) a. ‘Can we see our voices?’ Young children’s own contributions to authentic child participation as a pillar for sustainability under the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2023.2214716>
- Ranta, M. (2023) b. Positioning the young child as a rights holder within ESD curricula making under Article 29 1 (e) of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child. *An Leanbh Og ESD Special Edition*.
- Raw, L. (2014). Psychology and Adaptation: The Work of Jerome Bruner. *Linguaculture*, 2014(1), 89–101. <https://doi.org/10.1515/lincu-2015-0018>
- Reynaert, D., Bie, M. B.-D., & Vandeveld, S. (2012). Between ‘believers’ and ‘opponents’: Critical discussions on children’s rights. *The International Journal of Children’s Rights*, 20(1), 155–168. <https://doi.org/10.1163/157181812X626417>
- Ritchie, J. (2010). *Fostering Communities: Ecological Sustainability within Early Childhood Education*. *Early Education* 47 Winter, pp. 10-14.

- Ritchie, J., Duhn, I., Rau, C. & Craw, J. (2010). *Titiro whakamuri, hoki whakamua. We are The Future, the Present and the Past: Caring for Self, Others and the Environment in Early Years' Teaching and Learning*. New Zealand: Teaching Learning Research Initiative.
- Robbins, D. (Ed.). (2020). *Ireland and the climate crisis*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Roberts-Holmes, G. (2014). *Doing Your Early Years Research Project: A Step-by-Step Guide* (Third edition). SAGE.
- Robinson, C., & Taylor, C. (2013). Student voice as a contested practice: Power and participation in two student voice projects. *Improving Schools*, 16(1), 32–46. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1365480212469713>
- Robson, E. (2018). Ethics committees, journal publication and research with children. *Children's Geographies*, 16(5), 473–480. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14733285.2017.1392481>
- Robson, J. (2016). *Early Years Teachers and young children's rights: The need for critical dialogue*. <https://doi.org/10.15123/PUB.5091>
- Ross, H., & Mannion, G. (2012). Curriculum Making as the Enactment of Dwelling in Places. *Studies in Philosophy and Education*, 31(3), 303–313. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11217-012-9295-6>
- Rousell, D., Cutter-Mackenzie, A., & Foster, J. (2017). Children of an Earth to Come: Speculative Fiction, Geophilosophy and Climate Change Education Research. *Educational Studies*, 53(6), 654–669. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131946.2017.1369086>
- Rübsamen, K., & Engelhardt, W. V. (1975). Water metabolism in the llama. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology. A, Comparative Physiology*, 52(4), 595–598. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0300-9629\(75\)80006-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0300-9629(75)80006-5)
- Sageidet, B.M. (2014). Norwegian perspectives on ECEfS: What has Developed since the Brundtland Report'. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Sageidet, B. M. (2016). Norwegian early childhood teachers' stated use of subject-related activities with children, and their focus on science, technology, environmental issues and sustainability. *Nordic Studies in Science Education*, 12(2), 121–139. <https://doi.org/10.5617/nordina.955>
- Sargeant, J., & Gillett-Swan, J. K. (2015). Empowering the disempowered through voice-inclusive practice: Children's views on adult-centric educational provision. *European Educational Research Journal*, 14(2), 177–191. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474904115571800>
- Sargeant, J., & Gillett-Swan, J. K. (2019). Voice-Inclusive Practice (vip): A Charter for Authentic Student Engagement. *The International Journal of Children's Rights*, 27(1), 122–139. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718182-02701002>
- Sargeant, J., & Harcourt, D. (2012). *Doing ethical research with children*. Open University Press.
- Scottish Parliament. (2014). *Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014*. Edinburgh: Scottish Parliament.

- Shaik, N. (2022). Supporting student teachers for a participatory pedagogy through Shier's model of participation in Grade R (Reception Year) South Africa. *Journal of Early Childhood Teacher Education*, 43(2), 251–264. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10901027.2021.1881663>
- Shava, S. (2013). The Representation of Indigenous Knowledges. In Stevenson, R.B., Brody, M., Dillon, M.J. and Wals, A.E.J. (Eds), *International Handbook of Research on Environmental Education*. New York: Routledge, pp.384-93.
- Shier, H. (2001). Pathways to participation: Openings, opportunities and obligations. *Children & Society*, 15(2), 107–117. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chi.617>
- Shier, H. (2016). *Children's Rights in School: The Perception of Children in Nicaragua*. Queen's University Belfast, Belfast.
- Shier, H. (2019). An Analytical Tool to help Researchers Develop Partnerships with Children and Adolescents. In Berson, I., Berson, M. & Gray, C. (Eds), *Participatory Methodologies to Elevate Children's Voice and Agency*. USA: Information Age Publishing, pp. 295-316.
- Siraj-Blatchford, J., Smith, K.C. & Pramling Samuelsson, I. (2010). *OMEP Report: Education for Sustainable Development in the Early Years*. OMEP.
- Siraj-Blatchford, J., & Samuelsson, I. P. (2015). *Education for Sustainable Development in Early Childhood Care and Education: A UNESCO Background Paper*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3197.2564>
- Skånfors, L. (2009). Ethics in child research: Children's agency and researchers' 'ethical radar'. *Childhoods Today*, 3(1).
- Skehill, S. & Flaherty, L. (2023). Empowering babies, toddlers, young children and educators as global citizens: Action research as a means to facilitate education for sustainable development (ESD) in the early years setting, *An Leanbh Og ESD Special Edition*.
- Skehill, S. & Daly, M. (2023). Embedding sustainability in an updated *Aistear*. *An Leanbh Og ESD Special Edition*.
- Smith, K. (2012). Producing governable subjects: Images of childhood old and new. *Childhood*, 19(1), 24–37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0907568211401434>
- Smith, K. (2013). A Rights-Based Approach to Observing and Assessing Children in the Early Childhood Classroom. In Swadener, B., Lundy, L., Habashi, J. & Blancher-Cohen, N. (Eds.) *Children's Rights and Education: International Perspectives*, Peter Lang Publishing.
- Smith, K. (2015). Deconstructing Discourses to Rupture Fairytales of the “Ideal” Childhood. In J. Wyn & H. Cahill (Eds.), *Handbook of Children and Youth Studies* (pp. 21–33). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-4451-15-4_50
- Smyth, L. (2022). Multiple crises, multiple sticky plasters: Repositioning regimes of truth in ECEC policy to affirmative ethics of interconnection. *Irish Educational Studies*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2022.2074075>
- Sobel, D. (2008). *Childhood and nature: Design principles for educators*. Stenhouse Publishers.
- Somerville, M., & Williams, C. (2015). Sustainability education in early childhood: An updated review of research in the field. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 16(2), 102–117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1463949115585658>
- Spiteri, J. (2020). A reflection on research methods that engage young children with environmental sustainability. *An Leanbh Og*, 13, pp.149-170. Ireland: OMEP Ireland 2020.

- Spiteri, J. (2021). Why is it important to protect the environment? Reasons presented by young children. *Environmental Education Research*, 27(2), 175–191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2020.1829560>
- Stacey, S. (2018). *Emergent curriculum in early childhood settings: From theory to practice* (Second edition). Redleaf Press.
- Steiner, R. (1924), *The Kingdom of Childhood: Seven Lectures and Answers to Questions*. http://wn.rsarchive.org/Lectures/GA311/English/AP1982/KinChi_index.html.
- Stevenson, R. (Ed.). (2013). *International handbook of research on environmental education*. Routledge.
- Stirling, E. (2015). *Visual methods with children and young people: Academics and visual industries in dialogue*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Sundberg, B. & Ottander, C. (2014). Science in Preschool – A Foundation for Education for Sustainability? A view from Swedish Preschool Teacher Education. In Davies, J. & Elliot, S. (Eds), *Research in early childhood education for sustainability: International perspectives and provocations*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Thomas, N. P. (2021). Child-led research, children’s rights and childhood studies: A defence. *Childhood*, 28(2), 186–199. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0907568221996743>
- Thomson, P. (2008). *Visual research with children and young people*. Routledge.
- Tilbury, D. (1995). Environmental Education for Sustainability: Defining the new focus of environmental education in the 1990s. *Environmental Education Research*, 1(2), 195–212. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350462950010206>
- Tisdall, E. K. M. (2015). Children’s Rights and Children’s Wellbeing: Equivalent Policy Concepts? *Journal of Social Policy*, 44(4), 807–823. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0047279415000306>
- Tisdall, E. K. M. (2016). Participation, Rights and ‘Participatory’ Methods. In Farrell, A., Kagan, S. L., & Tisdall, E. K. M. (Eds.). *The SAGE Handbook of Early Childhood Research*. SAGE Reference.
- Todres, J., & King, S. M. (2020). *The Oxford handbook of children’s rights law*. Oxford university press.
- Tusla, (2018). *Quality and Regulatory Framework: Sessional Pre-School Service*, Dublin: Early Years Inspectorate, Tusla.
- Udvarhelyi, É. T. (2020). Participatory action research as political education. *Action Learning: Research and Practice*, 17(1), 24–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767333.2020.1712839>
- United Nations Childrens Fund (UNICEF). (2013). *Ethical Research Involving Children*. Florence: UNICEF Office of Research - Innocenti.
- United Nations Childrens Fund (UNICEF). (2014). *Fact Sheet: The Right to Participation*. Florence: UNICEF Office of Research - Innocenti.
- United Nations Childrens Fund (UNICEF). (2016). *Clear the Air for Children: The Impact of Air Pollution*. Florence: UNICEF Office of Research - Innocenti.
- United Nations Childrens Fund (UNICEF). (2021). *The Climate Crisis is a Child Right’s Crisis: Introducing the Children’s Climate Risk Index*. New York: United Nations Children’s Fund.
- United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC). (1989). *Convention on The Rights of the Child*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2001). *General Comment no 1. Article 29 (1), The Aims of Education*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2003). *General Comment no*

5. *General Measures of Implementation of the Convention on the Rights of the Child*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2006). *General Comment no 7. Implementing Children's Rights in Early Childhood*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2009). *General Comment no. 12. The Right of the Child to be Heard*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2013). *General Comment No. 14 (2013) On the Right of the Child to have his or her Best Interests taken as a Primary Consideration (art. 3, para. 1)** Geneva: UN General Assembly
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2016). *General Comment No. 19 (2016) On Public Budgeting for the Realization of Children's Rights (art. 4)*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2016). *Report of the 2016 day of General Discussion: Children's Rights and the Environment*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2016). *Concluding Observations on the Combined Third and Fourth periodic reports of Ireland*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2023). *Concluding Observations on the Combined Fifth and Sixth periodic reports of Ireland*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, (CRC). (2023). *General Comment No 26 (2023) On Children's Rights and the Environment with a Specific Focus on Climate Change*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2000). *United Nations Millennium Declaration*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Development Programme, (UNDP). (2015). *Sustainable Development Goals 2030*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, (UNESCO). (1997). *Educating for a Sustainable Future*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, (UNESCO). (2002). *Growing up in Cities*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, (UNESCO). (2007). *The UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (DESD 2005–2014): The First Two Years*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations General Assembly (UNGA). (2018). *Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Issue of Human Rights Obligations Relating to the Enjoyment of a Safe, Clean, Healthy and Sustainable Environment*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations General Assembly (UNGA). (2019). *Harmony with Nature*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations Human Rights (UNHR). (2021). *Frequently Asked Questions on Human Rights and Climate Change*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, (UNICEF), (1996). *Child Friendly Cities Initiative*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, (UNICEF), (2014). *2014 Fact sheet: The Right to Participation*.
<http://www.unicef.org/crc/files/RighttoParticipation.pdf>.

- United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, (UNICEF), (2021). *The Climate Crisis is a Child Rights Crisis: Introducing the Children's Climate Risk Index*. Geneva: UN General Assembly.
- Urban, M. (2016). At sea: What direction for critical early childhood research? *Journal of Pedagogy*, 7(1), 107–121. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jped-2016-0007>
- Urban, M. (2022). Scholarship in times of crises: Towards a trans-discipline of early childhood. *Comparative Education*, 58(3), 383–401. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03050068.2022.2046376>
- Urbina-Garcia, A., Jindal-Snape, D., Lindsay, A., Boath, L., Hannah, E. F. S., Barrable, A., & Touloumakos, A. K. (2022). Voices of young children aged 3–7 years in educational research: An international systematic literature review. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(1), 8–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2021.1992466>
- Vaealiki, S., & Mackey, G. (2008). Ripples of action: Strengthening environmental competency in an early childhood centre. *Early Childhood Folio*, 12, 7–11. <https://doi.org/10.18296/ecf.0193>
- Van Krieken Robson, J. (2019). Participatory pedagogy for values education in early childhood education. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 27(3), 420–431. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2019.1600811>
- Vekić-Kljaić, V., & Mlinarević, V. (2022). Documenting towards democratic early education curriculum in the Republic of Croatia. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(6), 810–826. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2021.1989473>
- Venninen, T., Leinonen, J., Lipponen, L., & Ojala, M. (2014). Supporting Children's Participation in Finnish Child Care Centers. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 42(3), 211–218. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-013-0590-9>
- Vincent-Snow, C. (2017). Bicultural Approaches to Sustainability within Early Childhood Settings in Aotearoa / New Zealand. *He Cupa*, 5 (2), pp. 69-75.
- Waldron, F., Mallon, B., Barry, M., & Martinez Sainz, G. (2020). Climate Change Education in Ireland: Emerging Practice in a Context of Resistance. In D. Robbins, D. Torney, & P. Brereton (Eds.), *Ireland and the Climate Crisis* (pp. 231–248). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-47587-1_13
- Wall, K. (2018). Building a bridge between pedagogy and methodology: Emergent thinking on notions of quality in practitioner enquiry. *Scottish Educational Review*, 50(2), 3–22. <https://doi.org/10.1163/27730840-05002002>
- Wall, K., & Hall, E. (2016). Teachers as metacognitive role models. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 39(4), 403–418. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2016.1212834>
- Wall, K., Hall, E., & Woolner, P. (2012). Visual methodology: Previously, now and in the future. *International Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 35(3), 223–226. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1743727X.2012.723923>
- Wall, K., & Robinson, C. (2022). Look who's talking: Eliciting the voice of children from birth to seven. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2022.2026276>
- Weldemariam, K., Boyd, D., Hirst, N., Sageidet, B. M., Browder, J. K., Grogan, L., & Hughes, F. (2017). A Critical Analysis of Concepts Associated with Sustainability in Early Childhood Curriculum Frameworks Across Five National Contexts. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 49(3), 333–351. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-017-0202-8>

- Willow, C. (2010). *Children's Right to be Heard and Effective Child Protection: A Guide for Governments and Children's Rights Advocates on Involving Children and Young People in Ending all Forms of Violence*, Stockholm: Save the Children Fund
- Wilson, R. (2012). *Nature and Young Children: Encouraging Creative Play and Learning in Natural Environments* (0 ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203119358>
- World Health Organisation, (WHO). (2017). *Inheriting a Sustainable World? Atlas on Children's health and the environment*. Geneva.
- World Wildlife Fund, (WWF). (2018). *Living Planet Report - 2018: Aiming Higher*. Gland, Switzerland: WWF.
- Zanatta, F. (2021). Examining Relationships and Sex Education through a child rights lens: An intersectional approach. *Human Rights Education Review*, 4(1), 49–69. <https://doi.org/10.7577/hrer.3991>
- Zanatta, F. & Long, S. (2021). Rights to the Front: Child Rights-based Pedagogies in Early Childhood Degree. *Journal of Early Childhood Education Research*, 10 (1), pp. 139–165.
- Zanatta, F., Martínez Sainz, G., & Gillett-Swan, J. (2019). A Critical Realist Reflection on the Use of Social Media as Third Space for Rights Education in Early Childhood. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 51(3), 319–333. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-019-00249-0>
- Zermatten, J. (2010). The Best Interests of the Child Principle: Literal Analysis and Function. *The International Journal of Children's Rights*, 18(4), 483–499. <https://doi.org/10.1163/157181810X537391>
- Zhang, T. (2023). Critical Realism: A Critical Evaluation. *Social Epistemology*, 37(1), 15–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02691728.2022.2080127>

Appendix A. Ethical approval by Research Ethics Committee, Institute of Technology, Carlow.

INSTITUTE of
TECHNOLOGY
CARLOW
Institiúid Teicneolaíochta Cheatharlach

ETHICS IN RESEARCH COMMITTEE EVALUATION REPORT

Faculty/Campus: Business and Humanities
Department: Humanities
Research Proposer: Muireann Ranta
Ethical Application Number: 226
Project Title: Article 29 1 (e) and me: A child rights based participatory study on young children's lived experiences of Nature (Working title)
Thesis Adviser: Dr Sheila Long, Dr Niamh McCrea
Medical Consultant: None

Evaluation Date: 7th March 2019

1. Procedures have been followed according to those laid down by the Institute Yes No

2. Ethical approval granted Yes No

3. Referred for resubmission Yes No

Reason for resubmission

Signed:
IVAN SHEERAN
Chairperson Date: 12/3/19

Appendix B. Gatekeeper Information Evening Presentation (April 2019).

ARTICLE 29 1 (E) AND ME: A CHILD RIGHTS BASED PARTICIPATORY
STUDY ON YOUNG CHILDREN'S LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NATURE
(WORKING TITLE)

RESEARCH QUESTION(S)

- Children's own perspectives and ideas about Nature
- Where or how do they connect or engage with Nature?
- What do they like to do in Nature ?
- What types of learning are taking place ?
- What materials or elements do they use ?
- How might this be developed or supported in terms of ESD? (Environmental education for Sustainable Development)

CHILDRENS RIGHTS RESEARCH APPROACH

Framed by all 52 articles of the UNCRC

- Children's involvement for the entire research process
- Children's Research Advisory Group (Framing, Analysis, Dissemination)
 - Research Participants (Data Collection)

Positions the young child as a current social actor, with the right to be involved in research about matters that affect them

Principle of participation

Article 12 Lundy Model – Space, Voice, Audience & Influence

PHASE 2: PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH WITH YOUNG RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS SEPT-DEC 2019

What is Required

1. Young children attending ECEC setting
2. 11 recruited participants approx.
3. Time and space to form relationships
4. Understanding children's interests and perspectives
5. Understanding local contextual behaviours
6. Agreed weekly time (Suitable for Setting/Routine)
7. Creative Participatory Methods
8. Ongoing assent
9. Keyworkers/family support

IDENTIFIED LISTENER - LUNDY MODEL

Being part of the Research from beginning

Being identified as the person who will listen to the research findings

Being recognized as the person who can affect change with the research findings

PHASE 3: ADULT PARTICIPANTS — DEC 2019

What is Required

1. Family members
2. ECEC educators

Semi structured interview to discuss what the adults have learned from the children and adults views on impact of research.

THE RESEARCHER

16 years experience of ECEC practice
7 years of nature based ECEC in Finland
Strengths based / Inclusive approach
Garda Vetted & Child First Protection Training
Indemnity from Institute of Technology, Carlow
EECERA Code of Ethics
Oversight of IT Carlow's Ethics Committee and Supervision

DISSEMINATING FINDINGS

Identified Listeners

Time frame: Early 2020, date TBC

DIAGRAM OF RESEARCH DESIGN

NEXT STEPS

1. Envelope containing gatekeepers letter and fliers to take back to setting
2. If interested, let me know by email muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie
3. Another information session with parents and ECEC educators can be facilitated by Muireann in April if necessary.

Appendix C. Gatekeeper's Letter (April 2019)

Re: Gatekeeper's letter

10/04/2019

Dear _____,

Thank you for meeting with us tonight. The purpose of this letter is to provide you with further details following our introductory session on Wed 10th of April. As you now know, this project aims to explore young children's own perspectives on Nature which may in turn, contribute to furthering our knowledge about an Environmental and Sustainable Development Education (ESD) approach appropriate and meaningful for this age group. The study requires the participation of two groups of children, young research participants (0-6 years) and young co researchers (5-8 years). It is envisaged that this study would take place in two phases; April – June 2019 and September –December 2019, with each research activity or workshop session lasting no more than 1 hour and at a time that is convenient to you and the children. As you are now aware, this is a child rights-based study, exploring young children's perspectives on Nature. This participatory research approach has been developed by Laura Lundy and colleagues at QUB (Lundy and McEvoy, 2011) although it is not widely used in ECEC in Ireland yet. It is explicitly framed in the UNCRC and so looks specifically at Article 29 1 (e) and the child's right to an education to develop a respect for the natural environment. I am writing to you, as I believe _____ is particularly appropriate for a study that is centred on outdoor learning and Nature and would be an ideal setting to be involved in the research as the primary research site.

Phase 1. Children's Research Advisory Group

As this project is about young children's own perspectives on Nature, initially, I wish to set up a Children's Research Advisory Group, known from now on as a CRAG (Lundy and McEvoy, 2011). This group will comprise of young children that will work with me as advisors to develop a study that is meaningful to the younger research participants. This is a key element to researching with children, as these advisors are closer to age and can contribute their expertise and perspectives to the research design, helping to ensure that the methods used are fun, child friendly and relevant. Their expertise will also be used to inform my thinking and help me to analyse themes emerging from the findings of the research with younger research participants. This is a key element in child rights-based research necessary for addressing power differences between adult researchers and children. The CRAG

members however, will not be research participants, rather their role is active advisors to me. It is my hope that the CRAG will be facilitated to meet for a number of workshop sessions (3) in phases one (April-June 2019) and 2 in phase two (September – December) 2019 where informal discussions will take place through interactive group activities, exploring different stages of the research. All activities will be explained in terms that children can understand.

Phase 2. Young Research Participants

This phase of the study consists of initially getting to know the group of young children who will take part in the research, forming trusting relationships and better understandings of their individual interests and learning mindsets. Data collection will consist of a series of fun, interactive nature-based learning activities, led by those preferred interests of the children, in line with a play-based, emergent and inquiry-based curriculum and in line with the national quality and curricular frameworks. Following the advice of the CRAG in phase 1, examples of research activities might include exploring natural materials such as sand/water, planting seeds, looking at animals/interests, all subject to individual and collective preferences. The activities will be explained in terms that children can understand. Only the research team will have access to data from the children. No images of children will be taken by the adult researcher; however, drawings and photographs will be used to capture ideas and the process. These images will also be stored electronically on a password -protected file on a password-protected computer in a locked office in IT Carlow. Any hard copies of work will be stored in a locked drawer in a locked office at the Institute of Technology Carlow. All data collected will be used solely for this project and will be deleted after a five-year period. Furthermore, any work or creations by the children are their property and ownership is respected accordingly. Only copies will be taken by researcher, if necessary.

Adult participants (ECEC educators and parents/guardians).

Towards the end of phase two, a small number of adults (parents/guardians and ECEC educators) will be invited to take part in semi-structured interviews. The purpose of these interviews is to explore with the adults what they have learned about nature from the young children, and their views on the impact of the research project on their understanding of children's learning and development.

Audience and Influence

The views and perspectives that emerge during this study will be reported in a dissertation format and are hoped to contribute to the development of meaningful learning experiences for young children as rights holders to explore and develop a respect of Nature under Article 29 1 (e) of the UNCRC. In addition, it is also hoped that findings from this study might also lead to some concrete recommendations for the development of resources and training for ECEC educators, as duty bearers and advocates for supporting young children to claim their rights under article 29 1 (e). It

is hoped that findings of this study will be presented at national and international ECEC conferences in 2020. Feedback from the study will be made readily available for the setting, parents and children. As the key decision maker, it is hoped that you will agree to be the identified listener, the influential adult who will listen to young children's views. To that end, I hope to present you with the findings of the report of the young children's views in the form of a report and possible dissemination event, to be organised mid to late 2020.

Ethical considerations

This project has been approved by IT Carlow's Research Ethics Committee in March 2019. Prior to commencing the project, I hope to distribute story booklets for you to use with children, to further inform them of the project design and encourage conversation and related questions. Information letters with consent slips for parents/guardians will also be included. Parents/guardians are very welcome to call me with any questions across either phase, or to speak with my supervisor, see contact details below. The study is a rights-based research project, which means it is grounded by deep respect and dignity for all children and the rights of parents/guardians as their primary educators. For this reason, it is very important to reiterate that participation is voluntary and that you, parents/guardians and the children can choose to participate or not and/or withdraw at any time and at any stage. Furthermore, the children assent will be sought as an ongoing process, if they wish to participate or rather do something else for each activity. Their choice to participate or withdraw will always be respected, however children will not be made feel excluded if you, they or their parents/guardians do not give permission. It is clear in the informed consent materials for parents/guardians that their decision to consent or not to their child participating in this study will not affect the services normally provided to their children in your early years setting. While confidentiality and anonymity of the research site are key considerations of this study, please note, there is a limitation in confidentiality should information be disclosed that causes concern for the protection and welfare of the young child. In such an event, I will take the guidance of Children First: National Guidance for the Protection and Welfare of Children (DCYA, 2017) and refer to the designated liaison person in your setting. I have received the required Children First training and will also be fully Garda Vetted through IT Carlow. In order to keep the process gentle and non-invasive, an audio recorder will be used to record children and adults' interviews. Confidentiality, anonymity and data safeguarding methods are guided by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (2016). Recordings will be manually transcribed to Microsoft Word by myself and will be stored on electronically protected with password. The write up will omit any disclosed data such as child's name or other personal information. Recordings will then be deleted from recording device.

Following your consideration of the information presented at the information session on Wed 10th of April and the content of this letter, I would now respectfully ask you to consider partnering with me in this project. As the owner and manager of the setting with ultimate responsibility, I understand you will need some time to consider this and its implications for your setting and staff. Please feel free to discuss with your

colleagues, families and children, and should you wish, I am happy to facilitate another information session with them in your setting, and another session with the young children prior to data collection. Please find below my contact details should you wish further clarification or wish to discuss any other aspect in detail. I also include with this letter a number of fliers you may wish to post or distribute in your setting to spark initial interest and conversations among children, educators and families, prior to official recruitment and distribution of informed consent materials. I do hope you will look favourably on this request and I anticipate a very enjoyable and mutually beneficial process for the children, myself, your setting and the wider environment, should that happen.

Yours Faithfully,

Muireann Ranta

muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie

CHILD EXPERTS WANTED

Who ?

Muireann Ranta is a postgraduate research student at IT Carlow

What?

She is conducting a participatory study with young children on their rights to learn in, through and for Nature but first needs young experts to help advise her on how best to design her project and also explore any information she collects from her young participants

Where?

When?

Six fun, inclusive, creative workshops will be organised in May-June 2019 and September-December 2019

Why and How?

These experts will form what is known as a Children's Research Advisory Group (CRAG) (Lundy and McEvoy, 2011). They will not be taking part in the research, but will instead be advisors to the researcher

Want more info?

For more information on this study and informed consent processes for parents and child friendly information booklets for children please speak to ___ or contact researcher Muireann.Ranta@itcarlow.ie

Article 29 1 (e) Children's Rights in Early Childhood - Learning in, through and for Nature

Email : Muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie

Who is the adult researcher ?

My name is Muireann Ranta and I am a Masters by Research student at the Institute of Technology College in Carlow. I am also an ECEC practitioner with 16 years experience working with young children.

What is the research project about ?

The project is about the young child's right to learn in Nature enabling them to develop a respect for Nature under Article 29 1 (e) of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC).

Learning in, through and for Nature

Mixing, stirring, collecting, rolling, splashing, jumping, watching, gathering, touching, smelling, tasting, running, climbing, pouring, floating, digging, building, young children learn in, through and for Nature in many different and unique ways. This project looks to work with young children in two groups to explore with them what their own perspectives and lived experiences are in Nature and in doing so will shine light on some of the ways Article 29 1 (e) can be implemented in early childhood as part of a play-based, emergent and enquiry based curriculum in line with *Aistear* and *Síolta*.

Article 29 1 (e) – Learning in, through and for Nature.

The Groups

Children Research Advisory Group - CRAG CORESEARCHERS

This is a group made up of slighter older children in the setting (preschoolers that will be returning to ___ in Sept 2019). As they are closer to age with the research participants, they are better informed to advise me on the design of the project and also help me to better understand ideas and perspectives that evolve. The CRAG will meet in workshop sessions with me (1 hour approx) and participate in fun activities that will enable them to form ideas for this advisory role. They can chose to participate and/or withdraw from the sessions, at any given time. Sessions are scheduled as follows;

May – June 3 workshops

Sept – Dec 3 workshops

Spring 2020 Final project presentation

Further information and Consent Letters for you and your child are available below. Should you have any further questions you are very welcome to contact either myself or ____. You can return consent forms in the box provided and please feel assured to know that your right to chose to participate or not in this study is fully respected.

RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

This is a group of younger children who will start at ____ in September 2019. They will have the opportunity to participate in the fun activities that the CRAG CORESEARCHERS have helped design in regular sessions over a three month period. Such activities are envisaged to help the younger children explore their own ideas and perspectives about Nature and to share these with me. Further information and Consent letters for this group are now available.

Article 29 1 (e) and Me – Information Booklet for Children Research Advisory Group (CRAG)

WHAT IS THE STUDY ABOUT ?

Rectangular Ship

- Young children's ideas about Nature
- Your right to learn about Nature. This is called Article 29 1 (e).

The illustration depicts a bright, sunny day in a park. A large rainbow arches across the sky. In the foreground, three children are playing: a girl in a red dress on the left, a girl in a white shirt and pink shorts in the center, and a boy in a red shirt and blue shorts on the right. There are several trees of different shapes and sizes, and a smiling sun in the sky.

WHY IS THE STUDY IMPORTANT?

- Every child in Ireland has a right to learn about Nature.

© CanStockPhoto.com - csp47118379

WHO IS THE ADULT RESEARCHER?

- My name is Muireann Ranta and I go to college, in the Institute of Technology of Carlow.
- I have worked with young children for many years (16 !).
- This study is part of my homework.

WHY IS MY HELP NEEDED ?

- Because you're an expert at being a child.
- I am an adult so I think differently but not better than children!
- I would like to bring a group of expert children together with me to help guide this study.
- This will be called a CRAG – **C**hildren **R**esearch **A**dvisory **G**roup

WHAT IS INVOLVED ?

- Meet in a small friendly group at _____ where we will do fun activities

3 workshops before the Summer holidays
3 workshops after the Summer holidays

- Talk about what is the best way for us to do this study
- Tell me what young children like or don't like, what questions should I ask and what activities or games could I use.
- Help me understand young children's ideas to enable them to have fun learning about Nature.

WHAT HAPPENS TO OUR CRAG WORK ?

- All of the work you do belongs to you . If you do not want your name used with any of your work or ideas, I will respect that.

- I will not take your photograph.

- I hope that our work can then be used to enable fun learning activities for young children

- I also hope to show others that children have their own ideas and that it is very important to listen to them.

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

- No, you absolutely do not have to take part. It is your choice and that is respected.
- If you decide to take part but later want to stop, you are also free to do this. **You can choose at anytime to stop.** Your choice will always be respected.

WHAT IF I HAVE SOME QUESTIONS?

- Questions are always welcome.
- Chat about it with your family, ___and your other teachers.
- They can call me with your questions.
- Learn more about your rights here: <https://www.oco.ie/>

**Thank you both adults and children
alike for taking the time to read
this information booklet together.**

01/05/2019

Dear Parent or Guardian:

My name is Muireann Ranta and I am an ECEC practitioner with over sixteen years' experience working with young children. I am also a Masters by Research student, supervised by Dr. Sheila Long, in the Department of Humanities at the Institute of Technology, Carlow. My research is a child rights-based study exploring young children's perspectives on Nature. Every child in Ireland has a right under the UNCRC, to an education that enables them to develop a respect for the natural environment. This right is articulated under **Article 29 1 (e)** as follows,

1. States Parties agree that the education of the child shall be directed to:

(e) The development of respect for the natural environment.

(UNCRC, 1989).

This project aims to explore young children's own perspectives on Nature which may in turn, contribute in developing an environmental and sustainable development education (ESD) appropriate and meaningful for them. The study hopes to invite two groups of children to take part in this study:

1. **Children's Research Advisory Group, or CRAG** (Lundy and McEvoy, 2011). This is the group that applies to your child. These are children that will be returning to The Trees Montessori in September 2019. Your child has a lot of knowledge on outdoors and Nature as a result of attending preschool for the past year and so they are uniquely positioned to help me design my study and be expert advisors throughout the process
2. **Research participants.** This group will consist of new children who will start in September, who will be the actual research participants. This part will commence in September. (however, your children will not be in this group)

I am writing to request your consent for your child to participate in this study and be part of the first group – the CRAG.

This group will comprise of your child and other young children that will work with me as advisors to develop a study that is meaningful to the younger research participants, who will start in September. This is a key element to researching with children, as these advisors are closer to age and can contribute their expertise and perspectives to the research design, helping to ensure that the methods used are

fun, child friendly and relevant. Their expertise will also be used to inform my thinking. The CRAG members however, will not be research participants, rather their role is to actively advise me. It is my hope that the CRAG will be facilitated to meet for a number of workshop sessions:

May – June 2019 3 workshops
Sept - Dec 2019 3 workshops

These workshops will be play-based informal discussions using interactive group activities, exploring different stages of the research process. All activities will be explained in terms that children can understand. I would also like to invite you to take home a visual booklet for you to read and explore with your child, to further inform them of the project and encourage conversation and related questions. You are very welcome to call me with any questions.

As this is a rights-based research project, it is grounded by deep respect and dignity for all children. For this reason, it is very important to reiterate that participation is voluntary and that you and your child can choose to participate or not and/or withdraw at any time and at any stage. Furthermore, the children will be asked as an ongoing process, if they wish to participate or rather do something else for each activity. Their choice to participate or withdraw will always be respected, however children will not be made feel excluded if you or they do not give permission. Your decision whether or not to consent to your child in participating will not affect the services normally provided to your child by your early years setting nor will their participation in this study lead to the loss of any benefits to which they are otherwise entitled.

The children's ideas will be collected through manual note taking of discussions taking place during each workshop. Confidentiality, anonymity and data safeguarding methods are guided by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (2016). The write up will omit any disclosed data such as child's name or other personal information. Only the research team will have access to information from your child. Photographic images will be used only to capture ideas and activities evolving, no images of your children will be used in the report. All data collected will be stored with password or in a locked drawer in a building at the Institute of Technology Carlow. Data will be used solely for this project and will be respectfully deleted after a five-year period. Furthermore, any work or creations by your children are their property and ownership is respected accordingly.

Please note, there is a limitation in confidentiality should information be disclosed that causes concern for the protection and welfare of the young child. In such an event, I will take the guidance of Children First: National Guidance for the Protection and Welfare of Children (DCYA, 2017) and refer to the designated liaison person in the setting. I am also fully Garda Vetted.

A copy of this research report will be available for adults and a child friendly version will also be produced with your child. The children will also be invited to present their

findings at a child friendly information-sharing or dissemination event at the end of the study towards Spring 2020.

Should you have any questions or desire further information, you may contact me, Muireann Ranta at _____ muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie. Alternatively, you may contact my supervisor, Dr. Sheila Long at _____ or at sheila.long@itcarlow.ie.
Yours Faithfully,

_____,
Muireann Ranta
Institute of Technology, Carlow

Parents/Guardians Informed Consent Slip for CRAG coresearchers

Please indicate if you would/wouldn't like your child to participate as a CRAG co researcher in this project by selecting the statements below, signing your name and your child's name and returning to the Consent Form box at _____.

I have read the information sheet and understand the nature of this research project _____

I have been given the opportunity to ask questions _____

I give permission for my child to participate as a CRAG co researcher in Muireann Ranta's study exploring young children's own perspectives on Nature _____

I do not grant permission for my child to participate as a CRAG co researcher in Muireann Ranta's study exploring young children's own perspectives on Nature _____

Signature of Parent/Guardian

Date

Printed Parent/Guardian Name

Date

Printed Name of Child

Date

Appendix F. Research Information Storybook & Consent Material for Research Participants and Families (September 2019)

Hello. My name is Muireann and this is Hazel and we are researchers. Do you know what a researcher is?

A researcher is someone who looks and listens to people's ideas.

Hazel and I are nature researchers. We like to explore people's ideas about Nature. Do you have ideas about Nature?

We would like to listen to young children's ideas about Nature because we are not children. Do you know what Hazel is?

We will be coming to your preschool in a couple of weeks with some activities about Nature for you to try, and if you would like, you can share some of your ideas with us. Would you like to take part in those activities and share your ideas?

If you would like to try an activity and you don't like it or you would rather do something else, that is ok. You can stop whenever you like. Or if you want to watch first and see what Hazel and I are doing and then come and join in, that's ok too. It will be your choice and Hazel and I will always listen to what you choose.

Thank you for taking the time to read our little book.

23/09/2019

Dear Parent or Guardian:

My name is Muireann Ranta and I am an ECEC practitioner with over sixteen years' experience working with young children. I am also a Masters by Research student, supervised by Dr. Sheila Long, in the Department of Humanities at the Institute of Technology, Carlow. My research is a child rights-based study exploring young children's perspectives on Nature. Every child in Ireland has a right under the UNCRC, to an education that enables them to develop a respect for the natural environment. This right is articulated under **Article 29 1 (e)** as follows,

1. States Parties agree that the education of the child shall be directed to:

(e) The development of respect for the natural environment.

(UNCRC, 1989).

This project commenced in May this year at _____ and aims to explore young children's own perspectives on Nature which may in turn, contribute in developing environmental and sustainable development education (ESD) approaches appropriate and meaningful for them. The study hopes to invite two groups of children to take part in this study:

1. **Children's Research Advisory Group, or CRAG** (Lundy and McEvoy, 2011). This is an advisory group that was established with me in May during Phase 1 of the project. They have a lot of knowledge on outdoors and Nature as a result of attending preschool for the past year and are uniquely positioned to help me develop my study and ensure that it is meaningful to the younger participants. They will be expert advisors and coresearchers throughout the process. This group does not apply to your child.
2. **Research participants.** This group will consist of new children who have started in September, who will be the actual research participants. They would work with me in Phase 2 (September-December).

I am writing to request your consent for your child to participate in this study and be part of the second group – the Research Participants.

This group would comprise of your child and other young children who will be invited to take part in some fun, nature related activities developed on the advice of the older group of children (The CRAG). The study consists of initially getting to know your child, forming a trusting relationship and better understanding of their individual interests and personalities. The research activities, aligned with Aistear and led by those preferred interests, are intended to give the children the opportunity to explore their own ideas and perspectives of Nature. An example of activities, may include exploring natural materials such as sand/water, planting seeds, looking at animals/interests, all subject to preference. The research activity sessions will last no more than one hour and will take place weekly over a 3-month period and will be explained in terms that your child can understand. I have also attached a story booklet for you to use with your child, to further inform them of the ideas behind the

project and to facilitate conversation and related questions. You are very welcome to call me with any questions.

As this is a rights-based research project, it is grounded by deep respect and dignity for all children. For this reason, it is very important to reiterate that participation is voluntary and that you and your child can choose to participate or not and/or withdraw at any time and at any stage. Furthermore, the children will be asked as an ongoing process, if they wish to participate or rather do something else for each activity. Their choice to participate or withdraw will always be respected, however children will not be made feel excluded if you or they do not give permission. Your decision whether or not to consent to your child in participating will not affect the services normally provided to your child by your early years setting nor will their participation in this study lead to the loss of any benefits to which they are otherwise entitled.

The children's ideas will be collected through manual note taking and audio recording taking place during each workshop. Audio recordings will be manually transcribed and recordings subsequently deleted from audio device. Confidentiality, anonymity and data safeguarding methods are guided by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679 (2016). The write up will omit any disclosed data such as child's name or other personal information. Only the research team will have access to information from your child. Photographic images will be used only to capture ideas and activities evolving, no images of your children will be used in the report. All data collected will be stored on a password protected computer or stored in a locked drawer in a building at the Institute of Technology Carlow. Data will be used solely for this project and will be respectfully deleted after a five-year period. Furthermore, any work or creations by your children are their property and ownership is respected accordingly.

Please note, there is a limitation in confidentiality should information be disclosed that causes concern for the protection and welfare of the young child. In such an event, I will take the guidance of Children First: National Guidance for the Protection and Welfare of Children (DCYA, 2017) and refer to the designated liaison person in the setting. I am also fully Garda Vetted.

A copy of this research report will be available for adults and a child friendly version will also be produced with the CRAG alongside a child friendly information-sharing or dissemination event of the research findings at the end of the study towards Spring 2020.

Should you have any questions or desire further information, you may contact me, Muireann Ranta at _____ or muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie. Alternatively, you may contact my supervisor, Dr. Sheila Long at,

Department of Humanities,
Institute of Technology, Carlow,
Kilkenny Road,
Carlow.
Sheila.Long@itcarlow.ie
059 xxx

Yours Faithfully,

_____,
Muireann Ranta
Institute of Technology, Carlow

Parents/Guardians Informed Consent Slip for Research Participants

Please indicate if you would/wouldn't like your child to participate as research participant in this project by selecting the statements below, signing your name and your child's name and returning to the Consent Form box at _____.

I have read the information sheet and understand the nature of this research project_____

I have been given the opportunity to ask questions _____

I give permission for my child to participate as a research participant in Muireann Ranta's study exploring young children's own perspectives on Nature _____

I do not grant permission for my child to participate as a research participant in Muireann Ranta's study exploring young children's own perspectives on Nature_____

Signature of Parent/Guardian

Date

Printed Parent/Guardian Name

Date

Printed Name of Child

Date

Appendix G. Research Update Information Letter for CRAG members and families (September 2019)

September 26/9/2019.

Dear Crag members and families,

This is a brief note to firstly say a big Thank you for the fantastic advice and expertise I received from your children, who took part as advisors, as CRAG members in our research project. They have been hugely informative for the design of phase 2!! I would never have thought of such ideas and perspectives and I am super excited to start back at _____ in October and get going again!

Just to keep you updated, Phase 2 of the project now involves 2 groups of children, as follows,

RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

This is a group of younger children who have started at _____ in September 2019. They will have the opportunity to participate in the fun activities that the older children (your children, the CRAG members) have helped design. Such activities are envisaged to help the younger children explore their own ideas and perspectives about Nature and to share these with me.

Children Research Advisory Group - CRAG CORESEARCHERS

This is the group to which your children belong. It is made up of slighter older children in the setting (preschoolers that returned to _____ in Sept 2019). As they are closer in age with the research participants, they are better informed to advise me on the design of the project and continue to help me better understand ideas and perspectives that evolve. In Phase 2, The CRAG members will meet in similar workshop sessions as Phase 1 with me (1 hour approx) and take part in fun activities that will enable them to form ideas for this advisory role. **As is Phase 1, they can chose to take part and/or withdraw from the sessions, at any given time.** Sessions are scheduled as follows;

Sept – Dec 3 workshops

Spring 2020 Final project presentation

As the study progresses in Phase 2 I will be maintaining a blog

(<https://muireannranta.wixsite.com/article291eandme>) to keep you informed as to what we are getting up to. There will be no images of your children nor any of their data shared in this blog. In Phase 1 the CRAG members shared many experiences and ideas about Nature that happened with family members and at home. This was so much fun and made the discussions very meaningful for each child. I would like to suggest that when discussing the study with your young child, if they have a particular idea or resource, for example, something you have found on a family outing sea shells, pine cones etc, seeds/bulbs from your garden, material we can recycle or repurpose etc, that they would like to include in our project, please let me know and we can look at how to incorporate it into our activities. After all this is a study exploring their perspectives and I welcome all aspects of how we can empower them as coresearchers. A key part of developing education for sustainability with young children is working with families and communities to develop the young child's sense of identity as a contributing local and global citizen, that they too have important ideas to share in developing changes in our everyday lives that can have a positive impact for climate action and our planet.

The 7 R's (**reduce, recycle, reuse, respect, refuse, rethink and repair**) play a big role in our thinking as we plan activities over phase 2 and both the CRAG members and the research participants will be exploring these concepts. It would be great to hear from you how they discuss this knowledge when they are at home and how they might develop them in ways that are authentic to their own lives.

Should you have any other questions or comments relating to Phase 2, please do not hesitate in contacting me on _____ or muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie,

Looking forward to getting back into Nature and exploring lots more great ideas with your children.

Appendix H: Recruitment Letter for Adult Participants

01/05/2019

Dear ECEC Practitioner:

My name is Muireann Ranta and I am an ECEC practitioner with over sixteen years' experience working with young children. I am also a Masters by Research student, supervised by Dr. Sheila Long, in the Department of Humanities at the Institute of Technology, Carlow. My research is a child rights-based study exploring young children's perspectives on Nature. Every child in Ireland has a right under the UNCRC, to an education that enables them to develop a respect for the natural environment. This right is articulated under **Article 29 1 (e)** as follows,

1. States Parties agree that the education of the child shall be directed to:
(e) The development of respect for the natural environment.

(UNCRC, 1989).

As you may already know, _____ is interested in being involved in this study, which will take place over two phases, phase one (May-June 2019) and phase two (September – December 2019). For both phases, I will be working with two different groups of children in workshop sessions, that will take approximately one hour.

Phase 1: Support Role

In the first part of the research, I hope to carry out hands-on activities about and in nature with the children. As my knowledge of the children will be very limited, your role in this phase as their primary care givers would mean being present in the area of research activity should an occasion arise for me to call on your support in terms of emotional or practical needs of any of the children. The research activity itself, set up, process, clean-up will be solely my responsibility.

It is very important for me to assure you that my presence as a researcher will not impact too greatly on daily routines and practices and that I will at all times be very mindful and respectful of your roles as ECEC practitioners and the children's primary care givers. While building trusting relationships with the children is integral to supporting this project, it will at all times be in a respectful partnership with the other adults in the setting.

Phase 2: Interview

Towards the end of phase 2, I would like to invite you to take part in an interview, sometime in December. The purpose of these interviews is to explore with you, as ECEC practitioners what you have learned about Nature from the young children and your views on the impact of the research project on your understanding of the children's participation, learning and development.

The duration of the interview will be no more than one hour arranged at a mutually convenient time and which will not impact on routines or ratios. Your participation in this interview is voluntary and you can choose to participate or not and/or withdraw at any time and at any stage. Your choice to participate or withdraw will always be respected and you will not be made feel excluded if you do not give permission.

Furthermore, your decision whether or not to participate in this interview will not affect your normal every day routines nor will your participation in this study lead to the loss of any benefits which your early years setting is otherwise entitled. In order to keep the interview process non-invasive, an audio recorder will be used. Confidentiality, anonymity and data safeguarding methods are guided by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (2016). Recordings will be transcribed using Microsoft Word by myself and will be stored electronically protected with password. The write up will omit any disclosed data such as names or other personal information. Recordings will then be deleted from recording device. Only the research team (myself, the CRAG and my supervisor) will have access to data from the semi structured interviews. All data collected will be used solely for this project and will be deleted after a five-year period

While your anonymity and confidentiality are important to me throughout the study, there is a limitation on confidentiality should information be disclosed that causes concern for the protection and welfare of the young child. In such an event, I will speak with you first and will take the guidance of Children First: National Guidance for the Protection and Welfare of Children (DCYA, 2017) and refer to the designated liaison person in the setting. I am also fully Garda Vetted.

Should you have any questions or desire further information or like to meet in person, you may contact me, Muireann Ranta at _____ or muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie. Alternatively, you may contact my supervisor, Dr. Sheila Long at _____ or at sheila.long@itcarlow.ie.

Yours Faithfully,

Muireann Ranta
Institute of Technology, Carlow

Informed Consent Slip for ECEC practitioners

Please indicate whether you would or would not like to participate in this semi structured interview by selecting one of the statements below, signing your name and return to the researcher. You should sign both copies and retain one for your own records.

_____ I wish to participate in the semi structured interview with Muireann Ranta's study exploring young children's own perspectives on Nature

_____ I do wish to participate in the semi structured interview with Muireann Ranta's study exploring young children's own perspectives on Nature

Signature of ECEC practitioner

Date

Printed Name of ECEC practitioner

Date

Appendix I: Recruitment Letter for Identified Listener

01/05/2019

Dear _____,

My name is Muireann Ranta and I am a Masters by Research student, at the Humanities Department of the Institute of Technology, Carlow, and a recipient of the President's Fellowship award. I am supervised by both Dr. Sheila Long and Dr Niamh McCrea. My research is a child rights-based participatory study that focuses on children's lived experiences of nature, based in Carlow. This project aims to explore with young children their own perspectives, and elicit their voice about learning in, through and for Nature, which may in turn, shed light on participatory practices and their education rights, while also contributing to the knowledge of environmental and sustainable development education (ESD) appropriate and meaningful for young children in ECEC settings.

As a child rights-based study, the UNCRC is used to guide the framing of the question, the methods, ethics and entire research process. I am following an approach advanced by Lundy and McEvoy (2011) and incorporating methods from the Mosaic approach (Clarke and Moss, 2005), appropriate to ECEC contexts, and in line with the children's age and maturity and interests. I am working with both a children's advisory group (CRAG) and a group of child participants, and the field work will begin in September, 2019. Unique to a child rights-based approach is the focus on the relationship between rights holder (the child) and duty-bearer (the adult, or state actor and Government). To this end, and drawing on the Lundy model of participation (Lundy, 2007), both audience and influence elements of the principle of participation are particularly important in this project. For that reason, I am contacting you about the study, as the local Department of Education inspector for this locality, to become involved in this study, not as a participant, but as an identified listener, to ensure that the children's voices are heard, respected and acted upon at local and national level.

As an identified listener, I would like to give you the opportunity to hear the children's views as they evolve, whatever they may be. To facilitate this process, you can keep up to date with the project by accessing my website and blog, which I am using as an information point (<https://muireannranta.wixsite.com/article291eandme>). I would also like to invite you to a child-friendly dissemination event, which I am scheduling for Spring 2020, when I have finished with my data collection and have findings to

present to the children, their parents and educators. I hope to also present you with a copy of the report.

I do hope you would be interested in engaging with this project at a level you feel comfortable with. I would like to invite you to provide me with a photograph and a short narrative about yourself for the children, to enable me to introduce you to the children during the process of the research, so that they become familiar with you as an adult decision maker who will attend their event. This can be shared in person, or on the website if you are comfortable. Although I am not asking you to take part in the actual research as a participant, if you would like to see any of the informed consent materials, I can forward them to you.

If you have any questions or would like further information on the research design, please don't hesitate to contact me, by phone at _____or by email muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie.

I look forward to hearing from you soon.

Yours Faithfully,

Muireann Ranta
Institute of Technology, Carlow

Appendix J: Original Overview of Research Plan & Proposed Phase Content (April 2019)

1. Framing the research April and May 2019

2. Conducting: June-Sept (or Sept – Dec) 2019 depending on summer holidays

3. Disseminating 2020

Appendix K: Field Reflective Notes and CRAG Feedback from Workshop 1 Workshop 1 (The Icebreaker) Rationale.

Workshop 1 – Icebreaker May 15th

Bearing in mind that relationships have yet to be formed and an understanding of local context practices and principles are minimal for the adult researcher, emphasis shall be placed on the emotional support for the young CRAG members. The workshop will take place in the vicinity of the ECEC practitioners and will involve an initial icebreaker/ get to know one another informal chat, where children are invited to ask questions, share ideas or experiences they have on the topic. This is intended to take place outdoors to facilitate access to natural materials or elements that may support the young child to form ideas or views. The rationale for this approach is to promote child initiated perspectives with minimal direction or leading from the adult researcher and to inform the same of authentic own interests of the individuals and/ or group.

As a follow up, the workshop will also involve a discussion as to what the research topic is, what the role of a CRAG member might entail, while encouraging input from the children themselves, as to how that role can be defined as to being meaningful to them. They shall also be introduced to Hazel, a soft toy hedgehog prop, which may again invite opportunity for ideas or views to form.

Direction from CRAG members from Workshop 1 (The Icebreaker May 15th) and Informal/Hang out Session (May 24th)

CRAG members voiced following ideas in relation to initial Research Topic

- Do work
- Look at work
- Be with friends
- Go back to big garden
- Buckets are cute
- Likes bikes, planting, spiders, unicorns, drawing, animals, flowers, sticks
- Food

Workshop 2 & 3 will look at research methods and further aspects of research question. Given the local context, lay out of facilities (1 room and 1 outdoor area) and group size (18 approx), along with age and wishes of the young CRAG members to remain with their friends and move back and forth from a variation of activities, the next workshop will incorporate these elements to respect their own perspectives.

In consideration of an overall formation of CRAG identity, the adult researcher will work with CRAG members while other ECEC practitioners work with other children from setting.

The intention is to offer children a number of proposed research methods that they have expressed an interest in,

Planting (seeds, compost)

Insects (Bug book and exploration)

Animals (Photographs of native Birds and Butterflies)

Buckets (collection of recycled large gardening pots of varied colours, to promote their own choice)

Flowers (photographs of common native Spring/Summer flowers)

Drawing (Materials, colours, pencils, paper)

while also interacting with peers, ECEC practitioners and familiar surroundings in respect of their expressed wishes and the flow of contextual practices and how they engage with learning.

As this is the framing stage of the research process and it is the CRAG members supported by the adult researcher to do this in an intellectual honest and respectful manner, the above reflections and considerations have been fed back into the design of Workshop 2 – Exploring Research Methods See Figure 1 for visual summary.

Figure 1. Framing of CRAG Workshop 2 – Research Methods

Appendix L: Reflexive Fieldnotes and CRAG guidance from Workshop 2 – Research Methods (May 28th)

Background

All the children from the setting were invited to explore some of the activities in the research methods toolkit,

Planting (seeds, compost)

Insects Bug book and exploration)

Animals (Photographs of native Birds and Butterflies)

Buckets (collection of recycled large gardening pots of varied colours, to promote their own choice)

Flowers (photographs of common native Spring/Summer flowers)

While the children came at various stages to engage, attention was given for the most part to the digging/ filling of pots with compost using buckets and shovels. CRAG members spoke briefly as to what other seeds they could grow (sweetcorn, berries) and making lots of pots to take home to their family members. The majority knew a seed needed dirt and water to grow, some spoke about planting seeds with family members, others were more interested in putting seeds into dirt, covering seeds with dirt. Extra resources were left after the session in the sandpit to facilitate this interest.

Limited ideas discussion **arose due to the large number of children. It was apparent that the CRAG members had ideas to share but eliciting these due to facilitating the large number proved difficult and stronger voices dominated?**

The visual images of native flowers and birds provoked interest and conversation although being a windy day and number of them were not easily accessible for the children.

CRAG members voiced following ideas during session

- I like planting seeds that you can eat, like sweetcorn and berries
- Do that bird noise again, I like that, sounds like a ghost
- I want to use the shovel
- Look at this spider. How many eyes does the spider have
- I want to make one for my Mammy, one for my Daddy.

Framing Workshop 3 – Research Methods

While the CRAG members had an opportunity to engage with nature based activities, discussion and their ideas to Research design and question were limited. With feedback from the children, contextual understanding is developing as is an understanding of group dynamics and interests, Workshop 3 will be framed as follows,

2 Small group (3 children) workshops (over 2 days June 12th & June 18th)

A participant appropriate story using contextual language and interest to develop further understanding of research question and design

A group discussion as to research design

Junk Art (recycled card, playdough, paint, colours, glue, crepe paper, images from magazines, scissors) will be offered as an opportunity to create a research design of their own to elicit experiences and perspectives.

Figure 1. How Workshop 3 is framed.

Appendix M: Reflexive Fieldnotes and CRAG guidance from Workshop 3 – Research Methods (2 sessions June 12th & June 21st)

Background

Workshop 3 – Research Methods

With feedback from the children, contextual understanding is developing as is an understanding of group dynamics and interests on the part of the adult researcher, Workshop 3 will be framed as follows,

2 Small group (3 children) workshops (over 2 days June 12th & June 21st)

A participant appropriate story using contextual language and interest to develop further understanding of research question and design (See Appendix 19) and explore story telling as a method.

Storytelling. Aside from using the story to explore understanding of research question with the CRAG members, the nature of the story telling session also offered insight to an environment that promoted open discussion, dialogue, a sharing of ideas that was evidently enjoyed by the group. **It equally gave in the moment opportunity to change the research agenda from adult to child initiated discussion topics and emanated real life moments of Article 12, expressing views, being listened too, having those views influence the research space. How the CRAG used the original story to form their own ideas in an organic flow of dialogue was remarkable and the enjoyment (laughter and excitement) was apparent. Notably not all ideas were fully understood by me but my response in giving the space over to this dialogue was huge learning on my part.**

A group discussion as to research design

Junk Art (recycled card, playdough, paint, colours, glue, crepe paper, images from magazines, scissors) will be offered as an opportunity to create a research design of their own to elicit individual experiences and perspectives.

The CRAG members were told the story with the assistance of Hazel the Hedgehog, with particular interest as to who's turn it was to hold her rather than story itself. Once set up for junk art activity, engaging with all the different colour paints and paint itself showed to a method, the children enjoyed and were **confident** to engage with. Participatory rights were emphasised through, choice of participation or not and for how long (one child did two), autonomy and agency through freedom of colour and paintbrush choice and freedom of expression of ideas as to what children like to do when they are outdoors, decision as to what would go into each design and overall ownership of design. Ideas as follows formed as the CRAG members engaged with their **creations**. (Crag member's own word).

Expressed Views

I am putting my glasses in the garden

Playdough in the garden

Sand pit for making castles and magic potions and for digging

We need flowers and a lion

A bench for sitting, eating, relaxing .

Water for to make a sea for sharks and fishes. They wont be in this garden though.

Waterhose for to water the plants

Lots of colours like blue purple orange

Definitely bikes.

Growing flowers and gardening

I love doing this. I am making it really purple. I am putting sellotape in the garden.

I have grass and the sun.

I have white clouds because you have different weather. And a sesaw.

I like to run around and play football.

I like playing.

There is a place for magic potions.

I am putting a MacDonalds in the garden.

I find easter eggs in the garden. And rocks. And I throw the rocks into the water.

There are birdies and cows and we have trees. I am painting a tree.

Here is a puddle and a field and the grass and all this space for playing soccer and going on my bike that is blue.

Children like building things in the garden. Like queen/king castles and my seesaw.

The expressed views were categorised broadly into two main themes, first in purple, ideas expressed by the CRAG members as to what children like to do outdoors and secondly in yellow, ideas that have a Nature based theme. Both sets of views helping to inform the adult researcher on suitable research methods for data collection in September.

Second part to this workshop will provide children with further open ended art materials and magazine cuttings of initial ideas expressed in a further capacity building strategy to engage in an exploration of young children's own perspectives and lived experiences of Nature meaningful to the group and how the study is best designed using their expertise input in a participant appropriate manner.

Research Methods

From an analysis of views and activities over the duration of the 3 Workshops, the CRAG members have expressed a preference for research methods, that are **active, hands on, sensorial, free moving, explorative, creative with an opportunity to use a range of tools, play and new information (intergenerational dialogue)**. Specific to Nature, they have expressed a preference to engage with sand, water, muck, rocks, gardening, insects, space,

flowers, birds, animals, trees, seeds, planting for food produce, weather elements, free movement.

Going forward in preparation for Data Collection in Phase 2 (September - December), the proposed research method will incorporate aspects of the Mosaic Approach (Clark and Moss) to include a range of play based child conferencing sessions whereby the participants will be invited to engage in a portfolio of activities (as advised and will continue to be advised in Phase 2 by the CRAG members). Data will be collected from the narrative discussions that take place during the engagement and process of these specified activities, through audio recording and note taking.

Portfolio of Suggested Activities (Subject to change and more detail pending input from CRAG)

Sand & Water play (explorative, active, free moving, creative) – (access to natural materials, stones, water, sand, grass, muck, wood)

Insect Hunt (explorative, sensorial, active, use of tools, intergenerational learning, how to explore and handle tiny creatures) - (access to natural resources, insects, grass, muck, wood) – Place based- what is in our garden.

Planting & Gardening (active, hands on, explorative, use of tools, new information) – (access to natural materials, intergenerational learning, what are flowers and trees for) – Place based – what is in our garden.

Outdoor Creative art (explorative, active, sensorial, free movement, creative) (access to natural materials, intergenerational learning, play dough from clay, paint from clay, water, grass, flower colouring).

Construction (explorative, creative, free movement, use of tools) – (access to thought on Reuse, Recycle)

Use of Space (free movement, explorative, sensorial, use of tools) – (access to free open air space, different terrains). Place Based, what can I do in my garden.

Exploration of Weather elements (explorative, sensorial, intergenerational learning) – (access to natural resources, use of alternative energies)

CRAG Members – Evolving Capacities

An initial reflection on workshop 3 was the level of **confidence** shown in both small groups as to the aim of the workshop in providing an insight into the topic (how the study can be designed to help explore children's own perspectives of Nature). In this particular activity including the feedback from previous workshops and relationship forming sessions, **time, space and flexibility** had been key elements in supporting the environment most effective for **evolving the capacities** of this particular group.

Secondly, the views expressed by the CRAG members have drawn out key attributes to an environment that is engaging and meaningful for young children to learn in Nature. Offering their own initiative and interpretation underlines a capacity to explore the multi-faceted ways

young children engage with Nature and significantly in terms of research question, **children’s own perspectives**, moving from the traditional imposing adult assumed explanations and understandings of the same.

What needs to be remarked at this stage, is the possible blurred line between self and other given the closeness of age between CRAG member and research participant, the cognitive development of this particular age range (3-4 years) and the setup of the local context (both groups are together). However, it is the role of the adult researcher to continue to support both groups and develop capacity building strategies that respect this sensitive consideration. At this stage, it is thought that both groups will share the same outdoor time and space but CRAG members will be involved in analysis and interpretation of data collection (adult researcher with research participants only) in separate activities. **However this requires more consideration and may not be respectful to the local culture.**

Outcome of Workshop 3.

Appendix N: Story used with CRAG members to explore research understanding and evaluate story telling as research method.

Olive Owl stood in the garden of Primrose Preschool scratching her head.....
HMMMMM, she said, HMMMMMMMM.

OOOoooo OOOOoooo Good morning Olive, said Patsy Pigeon the local Postman, you look a bit puzzled.

I am puzzled said Olive. There are lots of new children coming to the preschool in September and I would like to make this garden into a place where they can enjoy learning about Nature.

OOOOoooo OOOOooooo that sounds like fun said Patsy but why are you puzzled ?

Because, I don't know what children might like says Olive because I am all grown up.

Ooooo OOOooooo says Patsy and he starts scratching his head too.

Frankie Fox arrives on his bike with his Daddy Fredrico and his baby twin sisters Florie and Feadh.

Good morning Olive, Good morning Patsy says Frankie, what are you doing?

Good morning everybody says Olive, we are trying to think how we can make this garden into a fun place to learn for Florie and Feadh and all the other little children starting here in September but we have no idea what little children think about Nature.

HMMMMMM says Fredrico, Frankies Daddy and he starts scratching his head too.

Well says Frankie, Why don't you just ask them ?

What do you mean Frankie? asks Fredrico .

Well says Frankie, I am a child, Rory Rabbits a child, Sahid Squirrel is a child , Hazel Hedgehog is a child and Bartla Badger is a child and his little brother will be starting in September too.

Why don't you just ask us, what we think the new children might like and we can help make the garden into a fun place for them and us to learn about Nature? And in September we can see if they liked our ideas or if they had other ones.

Frankie, Frankie..... Florie and Feadh start clapping their hands and smile at their big brother.

OOOOoooo OOOOoooo says Patsy. That's a terrific idea Frankie.

Yes says Olive, Let's go do that Frankie, lets go find the other children and ask them their ideas about what the new children might like to do in the garden.

Sample Questions

What do you think the children's ideas might be ?

What do you think other children's ideas might be ?

How can we see other children's ideas ? How can we understand what they like or don't like about Nature ?

What questions would we ask ? What questions would you like to ask ? What questions would you find interesting ?

How can we see what other children's ideas might be ?

If they drew a picture of their ideas ?

If they took photographs of ideas ?

If they walked around the garden to show their ideas ?

If they looked at books or photographs for ideas ?

If they made their ideas? How could they make their ideas?

If they do their ideas? How can they do their ideas?

Who will listen to their ideas?

What will we do when we hear their ideas?

What will we do with with those ideas ?

Appendix O: CRAG members and families' information newsletter for phase 2

Dear Crag members and families,

This is a brief note to firstly say a big Thank you for the fantastic advice and expertise I received from the CRAG members that has being hugely informative for the design of the next phase of our research project. I would never have thought of such ideas and perspectives and I am so excited to start back at _____ in October and get going again! Just to keep you updated, Phase 2 of the project involves 2 groups of children, as follows,

RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

This is a group of younger children who have started at The Trees in September 2019. They will have the opportunity to participate in the fun activities that the older children (CRAG CORESEARCHERS) have helped design. Such activities are envisaged to help the younger children explore their own ideas and perspectives about Nature and to share these with me.

Children Research Advisory Group - CRAG CORESEARCHERS

This is your group made up of slighter older children in the setting (preschoolers that returned to _____ in Sept 2019). As they are closer in age with the research participants, they are better informed to advise me on the design of the project and continue to help me better understand ideas and perspectives that evolve. In Phase 2, The CRAG will meet in similar workshop sessions as Phase 1 with me (1 hour approx) and take part in fun activities that will enable them to form ideas for this advisory role. **As is Phase 1, they can chose to take part and/or withdraw from the sessions, at any given time.** Sessions are scheduled as follows;

Sept – Dec 3 information and analysis workshops

Spring 2020 Final project presentation

As the study progresses in Phase 2 I will be maintaining a blog (<https://muireannranta.wixsite.com/article291eandme>) to keep you informed as to what we are getting up to. In Phase 1 the CRAG members shared many experiences and ideas about Nature that happened with family members and at home. This was so much fun and made the discussions very meaningful for each child. I would like to suggest that when discussing the study with your young child, if a particular idea or resource arises that they would like to include in our project, please let me know and I will endeavour to incorporate it. After all this is a study exploring their perspectives and I welcome all aspects of how we can empower them in their agency as coresearchers. A key pinning of ESD (education for sustainability development) is working with families and communities and to develop the young child's sense of contributing global citizen!

The 7 R's (**reduce, recycle, reuse, respect, refuse, rethink and repair**) play a big role in our thinking as we consider activities related to different aspects of ESD and over phase 2, both the CRAG members and the research participants will be exploring these concepts. I would like to invite you to also consider the 7 R's with your young child at home to develop ideas authentic to their own lives. Should you have any other questions or comments relating to Phase 2, please do not hesitate in contacting me on _____ or muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie,

Looking forward to getting back into Nature and exploring lots more great ideas with your children.

Appendix P: Email to CRAG members and families for further informed consent.

Dear Families:

I hope that you are all staying safe and managing as best you can during this worrying time for us all. I am very lucky to have the opportunity to work from home and to listen to the children's wonderful stories and ideas that evolved during the last two research phases. Their Nature Book that developed during the project and is a compilation of their own pictures, photographs and stories is really taken shape and subject to their approval of the final draft, I hope to organise a launch event to celebrate their work at a later date.

Further to this, I am also writing to ask for consent from you and the children to use their data within my own final research write up. Originally, when consent was sought, your children were members of the CRAG (Children Research Advisory Group), specifically recruited in an expert advisory role to develop fun and creative activities with younger children and to inform my thinking in data analysis. Data was only being collected from the younger children. However, as the project evolved, the CRAG members developed their own role as field assistants and enjoyed their workshops so much, that I believe that this child driven aspect and how they made their research participation their own, to be particularly contributing in supporting further research in Early Childhood.

For this purpose, in keeping with the ethical guidelines of IT Carlow Research Ethics Committee and due to the exceptional Covid 19 circumstances, I am sending you this email to inform you of this new development in the research and to ask for you and your child's permission to use their data and how they defined their role as field assistants during both the data collection and data analysis workshops. I have also made a video for your children to further inform them of this idea, if they have any further questions, please feel free to contact me at details below.

To reiterate, confidentiality, anonymity and data safeguarding methods are guided by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679 (2016). The write up will omit any disclosed data such as child's name or other personal information. Only the research team will have access to information from your child. Photographic images will be used only to capture ideas and activities evolving, no images of your children will be used in the report. All data collected will be stored on a password protected computer or stored in a locked drawer in a building at the Institute of Technology Carlow. Data will be used solely for this project and will be respectfully deleted after a five-year period. Furthermore, any work or creations by your children are their property and ownership is respected accordingly. Should you or the children have any questions or desire further information, you may contact me, Muireann Ranta at ____ or muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie.

Wishing you and your families strength during these very difficult times,

Yours Faithfully,

Muireann Ranta
Institute of Technology, Carlow

Parents/Guardians Informed Consent Email Reply for use of data from CRAG members

Please indicate if you would/wouldn't like your child's data as a CRAG member to be used in the final report of this study by selecting the statements below, (Copy and Paste) and replying by email to _____

Child's name:

I have read the information sheet and understand the nature of this research project

I and my child have been given the opportunity to ask questions

I and my child give permission for their data as a CRAG member to be used in the final write up of Muireann Ranta's study exploring young children's own perspectives on Nature

I and my child do not grant permission for their data as a CRAG member to be used in the final write up of Muireann Ranta's study exploring young children's own perspectives on Nature

Appendix Q. Information Blurb on PAR study- How can we hear your voices?

FROM THE GROUND UP
CPD OPPORTUNITY FOR ECEC PRACTITIONERS

Recruitment for ECEC practitioners is taking place for part 2 of the child rights based participatory project 'Can we see our voices?' To date, the project has explored directly with young children their own contributions on the transformative change needed in education policy, to bring about effective education for sustainable development.

Do you want to create a more sustainable setting?

Knowing where to start with sustainability can be daunting in itself. By combining views directly from children and ECEC practitioners, now is our chance to contribute directly from the sector for the development of sustainable practice which works for us.

6 (one hour) online workshops every 3 weeks from March to June 2022

Using a participatory action research (PAR) approach, these free CPD sessions will create a space for professional reflection and collaboration on the interrelated role of ECEC practitioners for the fuller realisation of early childhood rights.

For more information, please contact me at (089) 4506256 / muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie

 enhancing professional practice

Appendix R. Informed Consent Material

14/03/22

Information Letter to gatekeeper/participants

Dear Early Childhood Education and Care practitioner,

My name is Muireann Ranta and I am also an ECEC practitioner and PhD candidate supervised by Dr. Niamh McCrea and Dr. Lilian Byrne at the Institute of Technology in Carlow. My research is based on a child rights-based participatory study exploring young children's perspectives on Nature which was carried out in an early year setting in South East Leinster as part of a Masters by Research program in 2019.

As part of this approach, I am now looking to engage with the pedagogical skillset of ECEC practitioners in their role as duty bearers to further support the children's perspectives being elicited under their education and participatory rights. In doing so it is my intention to contribute directly from the sector as to how a rights based approach to education for climate action could be promoted for early childhood. Notably resources of which have been limited in contrast to other educational sectors to date. This will be done as a participatory action research approach using a secure online video conference platform. The project will commence in March 2022 – June 2022 and will consist of one-hour long focus group sessions per month (6 sessions in total), as follows;

Thursday March 24th

Thursday April 7th

Thursday April 28th

Thursday May 19th

Thursday June 9th

Thursday June 30th

The initial session will start with an introduction of the study this far and getting to know one another. Concentrating specifically on aspects of early childhood

pedagogy such as relational, slow, listening, preceding sessions will look at understanding the local cultural context where each participating practitioner works in developing a rights based sustainability project that would promote authentic child participation. Opportunity will also be given for reflection and dialogue engaging as a community of practice in considering both barriers and opportunities in developing such an approach.

As this is a rights-based research project, it is grounded by deep respect and dignity for all humans. For this reason, it is very important to reiterate that participation is voluntary and that you can choose to participate or not and/or withdraw at any time and at any stage. Your contributions will be collected through manual note taking and video audio recording taking place during each research session using Microsoft Teams. Video recordings will be manually transcribed and recordings subsequently deleted from audio device. Confidentiality, anonymity and data safeguarding methods are guided by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679 (2016). All participants will have access to a secure shared drive in order to facilitate ongoing reflections during the study. Information on this share drive will be secured and omit any disclosed data such as names or other personal information. Each participant will be informed of an agreed protocol for using this shared drive. Equally the final report will also omit any disclosed data. Only the research team will have access to information. Photographic images will be used only to capture ideas and activities evolving, no images of children in your settings will be used in the report. All data collected will be stored on password protected files. Data will be used solely for this project and will be respectfully deleted after a five-year period. Furthermore, any work or creations by children from your setting are their property and ownership is respected accordingly.

Please note, there is a limitation in confidentiality should information be disclosed that causes concern for the protection and welfare of the young child. In such an event, I will take the guidance of Children First: National Guidance for the Protection and Welfare of Children (DCYA, 2017) and refer to the designated liaison person in the setting. I am also Garda vetted.

A copy of this research report will be available for adults and a child friendly version at the end of the study towards Spring 2023.

Should you have any questions or desire further information, you may contact me, Muireann Ranta at (089) 4506256 or muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie.

Yours Faithfully,

M.RANTA

Please read the checklist below before signing and giving your consent to participate in this study.

- I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my participation, in which case the material will be deleted.
- I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
- I agree that my participation will be audio-recorded using an online video conferencing platform (Microsoft Teams).
- I understand should I choose to use the shared drive set up for the project that I must adhere to the attached shared drive protocol.
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
- I understand that in circumstances where the researcher strongly believes there is a serious risk of harm/danger to myself or others (self-harm, physical or emotional abuse, or suicidal intent) then confidentiality will have to be broken.
- I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my participation which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.
- I understand that disguised extracts from my participation may be quoted in the researcher's dissertation.

- I understand that signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be kept in a safe and secure place and only the researcher or her supervisor will have access to them.
- I understand that a transcript of my participation in which all identifying information has been removed will be retained for the relevant period.
- I understand that under freedom of information legislation I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information

The above has been explained to me clearly and I have been given the opportunity to ask questions. I am satisfied I am fully informed, and I agree to participate. I have received a copy of this form which includes all necessary contact details should I require them.

(Please tick accordingly:)

_____ I wish to take part in Muireann Ranta's participatory action research project entitled 'How can we see your voices' as part of a PhD study.

_____ I do not wish to take part in Muireann Ranta's participatory action research project entitled 'How can we see your voices' as part of a PhD study.

Printed Name of Participant

Date

Signature of Participant

Date

Appendix S: Protocol for Shared Drive

Protocol for Shared Drive

Dear Early Childhood Education and Care practitioner,

A folder entitled '**reflections**' will be set up on a secure shared drive (Microsoft Teams) that only participants and researcher will have access to. The organisation of this folder will be decided upon with participants with anonymity of data assured. Pseudonyms will be used and data safeguarding procedures as guided by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (2016), and the Institute of Technology Carlow's Ethics in Research Policy (2021). The purpose of this folder is to offer participants an additional opportunity to add reflective notes to the study as it progresses in their own time. Every participant has the right to choose not to use this space and/or withdraw from using this space at any stage of the research process.

Before uploading reflections, please adhere to the following checklist,

- 1. All personal information has been omitted.**
- 2. All identifiable information of your ECEC setting has been omitted.**
- 3. No images of any persons are included.**
- 4. Assent from children has been attained for any images taken of their work and will be accredited accordingly under their property rights.**

Should you have any questions or desire further information, you may contact me, Muireann Ranta at _____ or muireann.ranta@itcarlow.ie. Alternatively, you may contact my supervisor, Dr. Niamh McCrea at,

Department of Humanities,
Institute of Technology, Carlow,
Kilkenny Road,

Carlow.
Niamh.McCrea@itcarlow.ie
059 xxx

Yours Faithfully,

Appendix T: Suggested Outline of content for ESD module.

Module Title:

Transformative Child Rights Approach for Education for Sustainability in Early Childhood (NFQ Level 8)

Module Aim:

This module is an outcome of a PhD study that collaborated with young children and ECEC practitioners to contribute to the development of child rights-based education for sustainable development for early childhood education and care (ECEC) under Article 29 1 (e). Article 29 1 (e) is an education right for all children to develop a respect for the natural environment under the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). It aims to develop students' understanding of effective learning for sustainability and child rights participatory approaches in early childhood practice.

Module Content:

As recommended by research participants, the module begins with an introduction of climate change and what the planetary crisis is happening. This includes an analysis of human behaviour and the effects of them on global warming, biodiversity loss, population displacement, water/food scarcity and sanitation and other impacts. Climate injustice and how certain groups of people are more at risk from climate change will be explored. This will lead to analyzing how sustainability itself is an evolving concept and the multiple pillars of sustainability (ecological, economical, social and cultural and political). We will also explore alternative, pro environmental human behaviours and what changes need to be made on a global, local and personal level to combat the crisis.

Connecting with Nature and extending these connections to develop sustainability thinking to develop a rights-based participatory approach with the young participants was another research finding. In addition, the ECEC practitioner participants also recommended the opportunity for students to develop their own 'sense of wonderment' of Nature as means to effectively support taking care of the planet in practice. To that end, the module will explore this aspect by providing learners to be in Nature (using the outdoor campus spaces/local outdoor amenities such as forests, rivers/beaches, mountains etc) and through the use of technology and the digital world.

As the module is underpinned by children's rights, time will be dedicated to understanding the Convention itself, corresponding general comments and the overall reporting cycle for Convention members. Emphasis will be placed on participatory rights, child participation and as with the PhD findings, the role of ongoing reflexivity to ensure authentic rights-based approaches in everyday practice. This section will also include an analysis of pedagogy synergies between ECEC and ESD found in the research to further support a rights based approach.

The final part of the module involves a reflection of the concepts of ‘funds of knowledge’, ‘authentic learner participation’ and respect for local context to develop authentic rights-based participatory approaches. We will also look at ESD projects in ECEC for students to build their own portfolio of learning resources and activities.

Learning Outcomes:

On successful completion of this module, the learner should be able to: explain, analyse, reflect, create, synthesis

LO1: Reflect on why the planetary crisis is happening and the impact of human behaviours.

LO2: Explain why the triple planetary crisis is a child rights crisis and the role of the UNCRC in advocating for climate justice.

LO3: Analyse sustainability as an evolving concept and the multiple pillars of education for sustainability.

LO4: Reflect on the pedagogical advantages in ECEC for the uptake of learning for sustainability and exploring in detail the likes of slow, relational, listening, and reflective pedagogies to support a child rights-based approach.

LO5: Create child-initiated project-based learning approaches for sustainability and their relevance to authentic learning for sustainability for young children.

LO6: Synthesize the concept of authentic learner participation and how it applies to a rights-based ESD approach in early childhood.

Teaching and Learning Strategies.

Using a transformative learning approach the module is designed to make changes in both thought and practice to support a child rights-based ESD approach. Reflective learning plays a central role in the delivery of this module where the learner is presented with content that is aimed to challenge and develop critical analysis of early childhood practice. Students will engage in a variety of teaching and learning methods, problem-solving and critical thinking exercises, case studies, class discussions, written and hands-on tasks and Nature-based outdoor activities. Active participation will be encouraged to develop analytical and communication skills required throughout all areas of Higher Education. The module will be supported with online learning materials through Blackboard and Microsoft Teams, and students will be expected to engage in self-directed learning to develop autonomous learning and work practices.

Essential Reading List

Davis, J. M. (Ed.). (2015). *Young children and the environment: Early education for sustainability* (Second edition). Cambridge University Press.

United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC). (1989). *Convention on The Rights of the Child*. Geneva: UN General Assembly

United Nations Childrens Fund (UNICEF). (2021). *The Climate Crisis is a Child Right’s Crisis: Introducing the Children’s Climate Risk Index*. New York: United Nations Children’s Fund.

